

UP2030

Urban Planning and design ready for 2030

D4.2 – UP2030 Implementation plan for the pilot cities 2

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About UP2030:

UP2030 is dedicated to aiding cities in achieving climate neutrality through enhanced urban planning and design. The project introduces the innovative 5UP approach to support city stakeholders and local authorities in integrating climate-neutral strategies into their everyday actions and long-term planning. Focused on promoting spatial justice and inclusive participation, UP2030 empowers communities and local governments to become agents of change, driving socio-technical transitions that enhance urban liveability and sustainability. The project's strategy aims to produce actionable insights and scalable solutions for urban environments, prioritizing resilience, equity, and sustainable urban development.

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Abstract	Updates the plans that cities have created for the implementation of UP2030 activities in the first year of the project. Gives an overview of the steps that will guide the process and the key insights that were identified from each city’s work planning. Ways of working with cities and liaisons, other WPs and project partners and key milestones guiding the project have also been compiled.			

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Executive summary

UP2030's objective is to leverage innovation, holistic urban planning, and design approaches to support cities in driving the socio-technical transitions required to meet their climate neutrality targets in an inclusive manner with their stakeholders, thereby building capacity to develop systemic approaches to achieving climate goals through their day-to-day activities. The '**Pilot Implementation Plan**' is the primary step to define the processes that cities will follow to operationalize the UP2030 approach in their respective contexts.

The first version of the Pilot Implementation Plan was submitted in M3 (March 2023), including (i) a '*City Storyline*' as a narrative tool to streamline the scope of each pilot and (ii) a '*Workplan*' which is a planning tool to understand common project milestones, city specific factors and timelines that are important for UP2030 implementation on a local level. The Plan provided clear directions for the pilot cities and paved the way for the project activities implemented during the first year of the project.

The current report presents an updated version of the Plan, highlighting the achievements and the changes in the storylines originally developed, as well as the solutions selected so far to support the needs identified by the cities. Compared to its previous version, this report includes a specific section on the progress in each pilot city, as well as the description of the Task Forces developed to support the coordination of project activities.

The Pilot Implementation Plan continues to be an essential foundation to better coordinate exchanges and support for the cities from other work packages (WPs) in UP2030, as well as identify key insights on opportunities, similarities, and potential risks to be mitigated in the cities. The implementation roadmap will continue to be updated regularly to track cities' progress and ensure that all activities implemented in UP2030 are consistent with the general objectives and timeline of the project.

Content alignment with other UP2030 deliverables

The UP2030 project fosters exchange and cooperation among partners and deliverables beyond the WPs structure. The implementation of activities in the pilots is achieved through the close collaboration and alignment with various tasks spread across the UP2030 project WPs, namely:

- WP2 – UP-DATING (led by UIC)– Understanding cities' and stakeholders' needs for upgrading, and co-designing visions of urban transformations.
- WP3 – UP-SKILLING (led by TUD) - Empowering the city's stakeholder ecosystem to codevelop urban planning and design enabled transformation pathways.
- WP4 – UP-GRADING (led by RCities) - Piloting and demonstrating. (WP responsible for this document)
- WP5 – UP-SCALING (led by ICLEI) - Implementation and mainstreaming through renewed policy development and decision-making.

Task 2.1 (Project Vision Consensus), led by the project coordinator, Fraunhofer, is responsible for aligning expectations and activities across WPs. T2.1 is also critical for building shared scientific and process understanding across the project partners. This applies also for the activities specific to T4.1 (Pilots coordination & implementation of solutions & processes). As a result, the current document has been developed in alignment with partners from WP2, WP3, WP4. The following table lists the deliverables and milestones that were input for this present document and the upcoming ones that could benefit from the content here presented.

Table 1 - Input from other deliverables and milestones

Input from	Contributes to
<p>D2.1 – The 5UP approach and its contextualization in the project cities</p> <p>D4.1 – UP2030 Pilot Implementation plan for the Pilot Cities 1</p> <p>D4.3 – Sustained engagement strategy of Learning & Action Alliances to promote the neutrality vision in the UP2030 pilots</p>	<p>D3.2 – Transformative pathways roadmaps: strategic integration of solutions and interoperability 2</p> <p>D3.4 – Bundle of digital twin tools for net zero decision-making 1</p> <p>D3.6 – Digital planning and design tools for climate neutral cities 1</p> <p>D3.8 – Tools and approaches for promoting inclusive participation and spatial justice 1</p> <p>D6.6 – Neutrality Story Maps for the pilot cities 1</p>
<p>M4 – Cities have set up their LAA</p> <p>M5 – Cities run first workshop on needs</p>	<p>M6 – Cities run second workshop on vision</p> <p>M10 – Cities run third workshop on action</p>

The Implementation roadmap targets primarily the cities in the implementation of UP2030’s approach and tools in the pilot areas; it serves as a guide to connect the Analysis and Vision phase towards the Action phase. The document is also useful for consortium partners (including liaison partners) to ensure that all activities carried out in WPs and task forces are aligned and consistent. In particular, the cities’ storylines incorporate the narrative of each pilot, providing an overview of all activities implemented and the progresses achieved.

As narrative tools, the storyline will be further updated by the end of 2024 to keep track of the project development in the pilot cities. A final storyline could be published and disseminated to demonstrate the success of UP2030’s approach.

Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
AQUATEC	AQUATEC Proyectos Para El Sector Del Agua Sa
CCC	Climate City Contract
D	Deliverable
DCAP	District Climate Action Plan
(EU) Mission	EU Mission: Climate-neutral and Smart Cities
GGGI	Global Green Growth Institute
GUNAM	ODTU – GUNAM - Centre for Solar Energy Research and Applications
ICA	I-Catalist
LAA	Learning Action Alliance
LINKS	Fondazione LINKS - Leading Innovation & Knowledge for Society
LNEC	Laboratorio Nacional de Engenharia Civil
MDAT	Major Development Agency Thessaloniki
METU	Middle East Technical University
MfC	Mapping for Change
NBS	Nature-Based Solutions
RCities	Resilient Cities Network
TUD	Technical University Delft
UDCW	Urban Design Climate Workshop
UIC	Universitat Internacional de Catalunya
UPV	Valencia Polytechnic University
VM	Vesela Motika
WP(s)	Work Package(s)

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

The Deliverable 4.2 ‘UP2030 Pilot Implementation Plan for Pilot Cities 2’, updates the plan of activities that cities have started implementing within UP2030 in the first year of the project. This report consists of the overall methodology that guides the project, the processes that cities undertook to plan out their actions and solution selection and implementation, and the key insights that were identified as a result. It also provides more insights into how cities are working together with City Liaisons and other partners from the various WPs in UP2030. Furthermore, the report provides an update on the progresses city by city and presents an updated version of the story lines in the Annex.

1.2 Document Structure

The document is organised as follows:

- ❖ Section 1 – Introduction: description of the purpose and scope of the document and its structure
- ❖ Section 2 – Methodology: Objectives, process of working and coordination within the project consortium
- ❖ Section 3 – Key Insights and progress in Pilot Cities: Observations from analysis of cities’ storylines and tools selection
- ❖ Section 4 – Conclusion and next steps: Key takeaways and expected next iteration of this report

The update version of the cities’ Storyline is included in the Annex section.

2 Methodology

2.1 Objectives

By leveraging innovative and holistic urban planning and design approaches, UP2030's overall objective is to support cities in driving the socio-technical transitions required to meet their climate neutrality targets, helping city stakeholders and local authorities put neutrality and resilience on the map of their communities in day-to-day actions and strategic decisions. The objectives will be achieved by developing and applying an innovative methodology (5UP-approach) that cities can adopt to meaningfully engage with the EU Mission Climate-neutral and Smart Cities. This methodology comprises the backbone of UP2030 by (i) updating cities' vision through consistent policy development, (ii) upskilling in state-of-the-art approaches, (iii) prototyping upgrades, and ultimately (iv) upscaling city-wide neutrality actions. This will be achieved through the co-development and implementation of science-based – yet practical - tools, and methods which will guide cities to deliver across the values of equity, resilience, neutrality, and sustainability within specific pilot projects in their cities.

To operationalize this 5-UP approach and to set up a coordination flow of actions in the cities, each city developed a 'Pilot Implementation Plan'. The initial version (see Deliverable 4.1) consisted of a City Storyline and a Workplan as their first step. The current version includes an update of the cities' storylines and a reference to the timelines currently developed in the processes of engagement, visioning, and implementation of solutions. The implementation plan helps identify the specific activities and timeframes for the development of the pilots, while also providing the necessary background and baseline information that is needed to ensure that all partners across the project are aware of. The implementation plans reflect both the common activities that are part of the project's overarching implementation methodology and the specific steps each city needs to take based on their stakeholders' timelines and capabilities.

2.2 Working together with cities and liaisons

The UP2030 consortium comprises of 8 EU cities (Budapest, Granollers, Lisbon, Milan, Muenster, Rotterdam, Thessaloniki, Zagreb; including MDAT, E-Nova as the operational arms of Thessaloniki & Lisbon respectively), 1 associated country city (Istanbul) and 1 transitional arrangement city (Belfast). Rio de Janeiro also participates in the project as an "observer city". Considering that Rio de Janeiro does not receive financial resources from UP2030, a lighter engagement process has been agreed where the city focuses on implementation and looks to capitalize on the technical expertise available in the project. Hence, this city has not followed the process laid out in sections 2.2.2 and 2.3 and will not prepare the same documentation.

2.2.1 Coordination between Cities and Liaisons

In UP2030, each pilot's activities are led by the city team in collaboration with its City Liaison. The liaisons are Research and Innovation partners of the project from the same country as the pilot city, for logistical and language reasons, who help the cities engage more efficiently and deeply with the project through direct support. The liaison is the main point of contact of the project with the cities. They manage the process with the city and together review information and formulate implementation and action plans. The liaison coordinates with WP4 partners to provide updates and present needs that will be communicated to the other WPs.

Table 2 - Partners working together with cities as City Liaisons

City Name	City Liaison
Belfast	MfC
Budapest	GGGI
Granollers	AQUATEC
Istanbul	GUNAM/ METU
Lisbon	LNEC
Milan	LINKS
Muenster	Fraunhofer
Rio de Janeiro	TUD
Rotterdam	RCities
Thessaloniki	MDAT
Zagreb	VM

2.2.2 Implementation Methodology

All cities follow a common implementation process that consists of phases organized as per the Implementation methodology for the Learning Action Alliances (LAAs), as described in Milestone 4 (Cities have set-up LAAs). These LAAs are living labs consisting of diverse stakeholders from each city who together go through the various steps of the project as defined in the Implementation methodology for LAAs in the Grant Agreement (Figure 1).

Figure 1 - Implementation methodology at the pilot environments run through participation activities (adaptation of Design Thinking steps)¹

- **Step 1: Analysis:** “empathize”² to create each pilot case profile. This step supports the identification of needs, baseline conditions, and barriers for the city and its stakeholders.

¹ IDEOU – What is design thinking?

² “Empathise” looks into understanding people/agents deeper (understand the way they do things and why, their physical and emotional needs, how they think about the world, and what is meaningful to them). This can refer to city employees through to specific citizen groups that interventions will target.

- **Step 2: Vision:** ideate and think in systems, also tap into the creative abilities of participants that typically get overlooked to generate the vision through workshops. Link the vision to metrics and identify high-impact factor actions. Preparation of the roadmap implementation is needed to move to Step 3.
- **Step 3: Action:** Implement roadmaps to prototype pilot solutions, including designs of physical interventions, digital tools, products, and new policies.
- **Step 4: Evaluate:** Explore success through validation of metrics and based on new knowledge, examine opportunities for further upscale.

Each step consists of a key **workshop** that will be planned to engage stakeholders, gather feedback, and foster innovation. Further activities such as desk research, surveys, and consultations may be planned as per the city's needs. The purpose of these activities is to meaningfully engage stakeholders and communities in the planning and design of the pilot with the objective of contributing to the city's vision on becoming climate neutral (to be developed within T2.4 Co-designing pilot shared visions and adaptive pathways for transformation). The objective of this process is to embed new urban design tools and methods in everyday practice, ensuring the neutrality vision is an equitable one that engages the unusual suspects and ensuring that this way of working is mainstreamed in policy and governance of the city.

2.3 [Alignment with other WPs](#)

2.3.1 [Coordination within UP2030 consortium:](#)

UP2030 is a complex and ambitious project, with many different partners and cities involved and working together. The project has a total number of 10 pilot cities, each one with a different context, conditions and starting points; this makes it difficult to set up processes and activities that work for all and are sufficiently specific at the same time. Furthermore, many WPs activities integrate and complement each other, requiring constant communication, alignment and sharing.

For the delivery of the Analysis workshop in each pilot city, the different WPs have worked in an integrated manner (as represented in [Figure 5](#) in the Annex):

1. WP4 through Task 4.1 (Pilots coordination & implementation of solutions & processes; led by RCities) provides the base information on each pilot's case profile through the city storyline and Work Plan.
2. WP4 through Task 4.2 (Learning and Action Alliances' setup and activities; led by ICA) provides the methodology for mapping stakeholders that need to be engaged through the LAA and provides the guidelines on setting up the LAAs in each city.
3. The City Liaison and City lead the organization of the workshops in their city.
4. WP2 through Task 2.3 (City & stakeholder engagement for the identification of needs for upgrading, barriers and drivers of change; led by MfC) develops the stakeholder engagement methods that the workshops will follow at each stage. These methods will be customized per city by the Liaison.
5. WP2 through Task 2.2 (Benchmarking against the state of the art in urban planning and design; led by UIC), develops the State-of-the-Art concepts and approaches in planning and design according to the 5UP approach to be applied in the pilot cities.
6. WP3 provides tools and methods to be tested as necessary.

Pilot cities and liaison partners are currently working together with consortium partners to align the visioning process and the second workshop on "Vision" (Step 2 of the abovementioned process in Section

2.2.2). This series of workshops are scheduled for the first months of 2024, and it is coordinated by TSPA and supported by the Engagement Task Force. The first steps of this process are expected to be completed in February 2024, when all cities will frame the “Pilot Vision Definition”. The upcoming steps are expected to be completed by April 2024 with the validation of the Adaptive Pathways. [Figure 6](#) (see Annex) presents the timeline and the steps of the visioning process.

Framing a vision is crucial to set clear, aspirational goals that guide urban planning and design, and to justify set of goals and actions. In this perspective, the creation of a solid vision, aligned with the aspirations of local stakeholders, will provide legitimacy to the tools and solutions that will be implemented in the pilot cities. The updated version of the City Storylines includes the visioning process for each of the 10 pilot cities.

2.3.2 Task Forces:

To ensure a more effective collaboration within the consortium (and especially in supporting pilot cities), a series of Task Forces have been created during year 2023. These Task Forces create synergies between WPs and allow consortium partners to work together in smaller, more integrated groups. This approach has proven to be beneficial as it has allowed the consortium to advance the work and better support the cities in planning their activities. UP2030 currently counts five active Task Forces:

- ❖ Engagement and Vision
- ❖ Benchmarking, KPIs and monitoring
- ❖ Implementation roadmap and solutions
- ❖ Dissemination, exploitation & the Mission
- ❖ Strategic Learning and Legacy

Table 3 - Ongoing Task Forces in UP2030

Task Force	Leading partner	Supporting Partners	Role
Engagement & Vision	RCities	MfC, UIC, ICA, TSPA	It brings together all activities to cities and stakeholder engagement, LAAs within UP2030
Benchmarking, KPIs & Monitoring	Fraunhofer	RCities, UIC, UPV, Adelphi, TUD, DRAXIS	Activities that are related to the cities’ needs and KPIs and monitoring. It lays the ground with the understanding of the cities and provides tools for governance and benchmarking to then support the KPIs and monitoring of the pilots
Implementation roadmap and solutions	TUD	R-Cities, Fraunhofer,	Define cities’ implementation plan, storylines, work plans, bundle of tools and service platform

		DRAXIS, Deltares, METU	
Dissemination, Exploitation & the Mission	DreVen	ISOCARP, UCCRN, ICLEI	Communication, dissemination, exploitation of the project; synergies with the project’s Cluster and the EU Mission
Strategic Learning & Legacy	ICLEI	Adelphi, RCities, TUD, UIC, GGG	Knowledge exchange, community of practices, city twinning, recommendations, lesson learned and legacy of UP2030

The Task Force on Implementation Roadmap and Solutions is responsible for supporting cities in shaping the implementation process within their pilot area. Besides defining the implementation roadmap (cities’ storylines), this TF coordinates the pilot cities in the selection and implementation of the tools provided by the consortium partners.

As WP leader, TUD leads the task force and the selection of the tools (TUD also prepared the database with all tools and solutions offered to cities by consortium partners). The cities have been assisted by the liaison partners in preselecting suitable tools for their pilot areas, based on the identified needs and the ambition within the pilots. Most of the cities preselected the tools in September-October 2023. To facilitate the process, the Task Force has classified the tools in four thematic categories and identified four working groups:

- *Neutral Cities* (Led by METU): tools that refer to climate-neutrality and net-zero agenda, such as accounting of carbon emissions and energy performances.
- *Adaptive Cities* (led by Deltares): tools that support climate adaptation, NBS and ecosystem services assessment.
- *Inclusive Cities* (led by TUD): tools that promote participation, engagement and inclusion of local communities and stakeholders.
- *Smart Cities* (led by DRAXIS): tools that require complex data collection and visualization, including digital twins.

The working groups leaders are responsible to identify partners to create each working group, produce a value proposition for their respecting group, coordinate internally the distribution of resources among partners.

2.3.3 Pilot Implementation Plans:

For the process of setting up the Pilot Implementation Plan, RCities developed templates to capture each city’s objective and expected outcomes through the UP2030 project, and the projected activities to be carried out in order to achieve them. The City Storyline is a living document that has been created as a ‘narrative building tool’ for cities to develop their pilot case scope further. The city storyline will be periodically updated and used as a database for other WPs to understand the framework, needs, and context specific characteristics of the pilot, in order to better customize the approaches, tools, and

methods developed throughout the project. As a result, the story lines give and receive feedback from Task 2.3 (in Q1-Q2 of the project) and Task T2.4 (in Q3-Q4 of the project). RCities developed a template with guiding questions exploring the following aspects:

- Historic influences on the pilot site.
- Spatial characteristics of the neighbourhood with reflections on UP2030 urban design approaches of compact, connected and net-zero city.
- Social characteristics of the neighbourhood with reflections on UP2030 principles of participation, social, and spatial justice.
- Challenges and opportunities for exploration Current policies and programs taken by the city in the pilot site.
- Preliminary assessment of objectives, needs, and aspirations through the UP2030 project.
- Preliminary understanding of important stakeholders in the neighbourhood and city to be engaged.

Each city has opted to present the above information in a semi-structured manner that fits its narrative and the current stage of work. Hence, differentiations among story lines can be expected. Cities expressed that the storyline has been useful to compile their approach and the factors influencing it and as a tool to streamline the focus on UP2030 activities in their context.

The first versions of the city storylines were developed in March 2023 (M3) of the project and included in the Deliverable 4.1. The updated version of each city’s storyline is included in the Annex of this document.

Figure 2 - Example city storyline using the case of Rotterdam BoTu neighborhood

With the broader goals set through the city storyline, a Workplan template was initially created to capture the implementation of each city’s UP2030 activities. However, compared to the previous deliverable, this

document does not include an updated version of the city work plan, as pilots are not building (and following) the timeline for the visioning process.

Figure 3 presents the initial timeline of activities as indicated in the Grant Agreement. It includes the general activities that are common across all cities and is further developed to include city specific activities and milestones that are important for the project. Nonetheless, the project evolution and the reality in the cities might mean that certain phases are rolled out earlier or later. These variations in timeline are a direct result of the influencing factors identified to have an impact on the cities’ activities. The influences have been captured in Section 3, together with key insights.

All Cities follow common activities over the course of the UP2030 timeline. The 4 key workshops with the city’s LAAs are the highlights in this timeline. The first workshop focuses on the needs/analysis stage, the second is on visioning, the third is on action and the fourth is on upscaling. As mentioned in section 2.2.2, these milestones are based on the implementation methodology of the project.

Figure 4 presents the updated timeline for milestones and deliverables planned in the pilot cities. The main differences are related to the setup of the LAAs, which requires a more continuous process, and the series of workshops on “Vision” which will take place between December 2023 and February 2024. In addition, the implementation roadmap process has been supported by a phase of “pre-selection of tools”, where cities have expressed interests in the application of specific solutions and tools. This activity has been done taking into account the initial needs assessment and in accordance with the visioning process.

Figure 3 – Initial timeline of milestone and deliverable planned (March 2023)

Figure 4 - Updated timeline of milestone and deliverable planned (December 2023)

3 Key Insights and progress in Pilot Cities

3.1 Key insights from the Implementation Plans

Through the analysis of the updated City Storyline and the process of tools selection, common threads among cities have been identified, both in terms of risks that might impact the timely implementation of the project and in terms of opportunities that can further enhance the outcomes of the project.

The first version of the implementation plan highlighted the impact that **political changes** (such as local or national elections) could have on the project's timeline, as well as turnover in staff and delays in the **recruitment of people** that will manage the project internally. Furthermore, it emerged clearly that cities need time to **engage their internal stakeholders** and communicate about the objectives and purpose of the UP2030 project before being able to reach out and include more external partners and local communities. During the process, it was also recognized that each city can provide **lessons learned** for the other cities involved in UP2030, becoming front-runners for specific processes within UP2030. Another important element considered was that all cities were actively identifying **additional steps to be taken beyond UP2030** planned activities, and particularly with the Mission on Climate Natural and Smart Cities.

These insights have been confirmed and become even more clear during 2023. Having strong **political support** and commitment is important to help advance the planned activities. For instance, Thessaloniki aims to directly target elected officials to ensure their support in UP2030. Budapest's progress was dependent on the launch of the call for application for Healthy Streets, which was only announced at the end of November 2023.

Regarding the engagement activities, the LAA plays an important role in steering the project in the pilot cities, hence the cities want to ensure that the process and selection of stakeholders is as inclusive as possible. However, stakeholder engagement requires time, effort and it does not necessarily follow a linear process. In fact, most of the cities have complemented the first series of UP2030 workshops with additional focus groups, interviews, and surveys to collect additional feedback and activate more stakeholders. As a result, most of the cities have decided to set up the **LAA initially as internal working group** (within the municipality, connecting different departments); the ambition is to expand the LAA to external stakeholders as the project continues in 2024 and 2025. The liaison partners are working proactively in supporting the cities, both in planning activities (such as workshops) but also in the roadmap developments for engagement, visioning, and tools selections.

For what concerns the tools selection, the cities expressed preferences and interest for specific applications. The heterogeneity between pilot areas has allowed for a relative **variety in the tools selected**, as indicated in the working groups identified under the Task Force on Implementation. This has allowed the activation of several technical partners within the consortium. Nevertheless, this matchmaking process was not easy and required several interactions. In some cases, cities wanted to avoid duplications of tools already in place within the municipality but could not have an overview of the tools in use. In other cases, tools providers were able to understand cities' needs (based on the initial needs assessment and the City Storyline) but requested additional information to evaluate how the tools could be customized. A series of bilateral meetings between each city (with liaison partner) and tool provider was useful to better understand the functionality of the tools and align the timelines between cities and tool providers.

In this context, it is important that the project consortium offers regular opportunities for exchange between cities and **peer-to-peer learning**: these activities include both periodic online meetings with pilot cities and events such as the city twinning "knowledge exchange" event (planned for summer 2024). Since the beginning of the project, an effort has also been made to maximize synergies and foster opportunities for collaboration beyond UP2030. The clear **connection with the Mission on Climate-Neutral and Smart**

Cities has allowed us to develop synergies and further opportunities for collaboration. As some of the cities are also Mission’s cities (112 cities selected to participate in the EU Mission for 100 climate-neutral and smart cities by 2030), some project activities were aligned with the development of the Climate City Contract (CCC). In particular, Thessaloniki aims to develop a District Climate Action Plan (DCAP) in the pilot area, integrating the recommendations included in the CCC at the local level.

The City Storylines has been useful for cities to further mature the scope and narrative of the pilot project that is critical in ensuring that all activities align with the scope and contribute to the overall objectives identified. The Storylines will remain the document where to capture all activities, progresses and insights developed by cities to make their district better connected, resilient and carbon-efficient.

Table 4 - Overview of pilot cities and pre-selection of tools

City Name	Pilot Area(s)	Objective(s)	Tools preselected
Belfast	Linen Quarter District	Creating the first Net-Zero district through tree planting, green infrastructure and play	Urban Design manual for Child and Youth Friendly Cities (<i>Design Clips</i>); Community Maps (<i>MfC</i>)
Budapest	City districts participating in the Call for application	Develop healthy neighbourhoods for climate neutrality, applying the Healthy Street approach	Citizens Voice (<i>TUD</i>); Community Maps (<i>MfC</i>)
Granollers	Sector 129-La Bòbila (around the railway Station)	Develop a new district balancing urban growth and climate resilience	RESCUUE Resilience strategies database and assessment (<i>AQUATEC+LNEC</i>) Data driven geospatial analysis and parametric design (<i>TSPA</i>);
Istanbul	Kadıköy district	Initiate positive energy neighbourhoods using advance computational methods for decision making	UBTEM Urban Building/Transport Energy Model (<i>METU & ODTÜ-GÜNAM</i>)
Lisbon	Parish of Alvalade	Redesign a best neighbourhood fostering synergies of adaptation and mitigation	Water management tools (<i>LNEC</i>); Air quality monitoring and forecast (<i>LINKS</i>) Ecosystem service assessment (<i>LINKS</i>)
Milan	Scalo Porta Romana	Accelerating the transition to carbon neutrality of urban regeneration areas	<i>Ecosystem service Assessment</i> (<i>LINKS</i>); City Resilience Framework & Index (<i>RCities</i>)
Muenster	Überwasser/Frauenstraße district	Shaping climate neutral and resilient compact neighborhoods	Climate Proofing (<i>BURO HAPPOLD</i>)

Rio de Janeiro	Morro de São Carlos favela	Support just transition challenge in informal settlements	UDCW Simulation Toolkit (<i>UCCRN</i>); CRCTool Climate-resilient City Tool (<i>DELTA</i> RES)
Rotterdam	BoTu district	Create a framework of BoTu approach for upscaling in other city's districts	Citizens Voice (<i>TUD</i>); Community Maps (<i>MfC</i>);
Thessaloniki	Dioikitirio district	Develop a District Climate Action Plan (DCAP)	UDCW Simulation Toolkit (<i>UCCRN</i>); UBTEM Urban Building/Transport Energy Model (<i>METU & ODTÜ-GÜNAM</i>); Spatial Justice Benchmarking (<i>TUD</i>)
Zagreb	Sesvete district (school) and Maksimir district (zoo)	Modular indoor farms to support circular economy and low-carbon urban food systems	Carbon budgeting management tool (<i>UCAM</i>); Circular buildings tool (<i>ETH</i>); Resilience assessment framework (<i>LNEC</i>); Air quality Monitoring (<i>LINKS</i>)

3.2 Belfast

Belfast's vision under UP2030 is to develop a framework that sets up a pathway to be net zero at the neighbourhood level, inspiring and guiding communities, businesses and policy makers on how to best achieve this. The framework will be tested in the pilot area of Linen Quarter district, which has been identified to become the first sustainable and net zero business district in Northern Ireland.

The LAA was kicked-off in April 2023 and began with an extensive stakeholder mapping, including several categories, from government to academic institutions. In the initial phase of needs assessment, the city of Belfast was clear in identifying the need to set a baseline for the area (in terms of emissions, air quality and behavioural attitudes such as car use), but also to engage youth and children's groups in the planning of regeneration projects. At the same time, Belfast City Council identified three key thematic areas to reduce emissions in the city and promote climate projects: green infrastructure, active travel, and retrofitting buildings. The first engagement workshop (held in August 2023) centred around these three themes, engaging local government officials, policymakers, academics, and representatives from citizen groups. As a follow-up, the Belfast team and liaison partner Mapping for Change (MfC) implemented additional engagement activities to extract more needs and barriers from different stakeholders' groups.

Regarding the implementation roadmap, the city of Belfast has preselected a series of tools provided by the consortium. The criteria that led the selection process were (i) supporting Belfast's UP2030 project delivery, (ii) minimal duplication with other ongoing Council's projects and tools, (iii) resource requirement, diversity of functions and stage of development of the tools, (iv) appropriateness to Belfast

and encompassed communities. The municipality expressed particular interest for the engagement tool Urban Design manual for Child and Youth Friendly Cities, provided by Design Clips; the tools support small-scale design interventions to enhance the public realm's spatial quality, particularly for children and young people. Additional tools considered are the Ecosystem Services Assessment and the Equal Services & Facilities Assessment (Links Foundation) to quantify benefits and support decision making. In addition, the city expressed interest in training and capacity building for municipal staff during the project. The City of Belfast has agreed to start collaborating with Design Clips on the urban design manual to support engagement activities and ensure the involvement of children and youth from the beginning. As MfC is the liaison partner, the city plans to use their Community Maps tools within UP2030. The city of Belfast is open to receive additional support from other consortium partners and test additional tools in future (preliminary interest was given to the Green Economy Model tool, the Resilience Model Maturity tool, and the UDCW Simulation Toolkit).

The municipality is currently revising the timeline of activities for the co-visioning process. An important aspect to consider in the upcoming years of the project is how the framework can be utilized in other neighbourhoods, supporting the upscaling phase of the project.

3.3 Budapest

In order to serve the objective to increase access to a healthy environment, Budapest leadership committed itself to introducing the Healthy Streets approach (developed by Lucy Saunders³). Budapest included the Healthy Streets program in its Integrated Development Strategy adopted by the City Council in April 2021. Beside promoting the practical application of the Healthy Street approach by planning professionals, the city is facilitating streets upgrades through a tendering process supported by the EU, enabling districts to apply and receive funding for implementation. Within UP2030, Budapest aims to encourage urban development professionals to apply extensively the Healthy Street approach and promote public health perspective in the public discourse.

The call for application has been launched on 28th November 2023, therefore the districts that will participate in this initiative are not known yet. Nevertheless, the municipality has already organized five workshops and training events for the districts and another side event to present the details of the Design Checklist, highlighting main objectives, methodology, logic of interventions and details of design principles. In February 2023, the Municipality of Budapest requested the districts to submit their indicative projects for preliminary assessment and consultation purposes to facilitate the design process. Different departments of the City Hall are cooperating in the preparation and the implementation of the support framework for Healthy Streets. In particular, the municipality is working closely with the Budapest Transport Centre), responsible for transport strategy and operation of transportation. The LAA process kicked off in April 2023 and includes various municipal departments. The core group participated in the first UP2030 workshop. The objective is to extend the LAA in future with more stakeholders to promote wider upscaling within the city.

The evolution framework of the Healthy Streets proposal will be carried on in collaboration with local communities, thus their engagement in the process is recognized as crucial and it was recognized as underdeveloped in the needs assessment phase. For this reason, the municipality has selected tools to enhance the engagement of local communities in the selected districts and involve other stakeholders from the wider community and civil society. To this end, the primary tools identified are Community Maps

³ [Healthy Streets.com](https://www.healthystreets.com)

(provided by MfC) and Citizen Voice (by TUD). As far as actual spatial design for healthy streets, Budapest will collaborate with Design Clips to promote youth and children inclusive design. These tools will help the municipality in creating public awareness and increasing participation, as well activating and engaging local communities in the applying districts.

As part of the visioning process, the city will go through a series of activities in the coming weeks to define engagement strategies that will be embedded in the Healthy Streets programme, enriching it with goals for a resilient, equitable and carbon neutral future.

3.4 Granollers

Granollers pilot area is located in La Bòbila, the neighbourhood around the central station. Despite existing planning regulations (including a masterplan), the area is still largely vacant and to be developed. The Strategic Plan of Granollers 2030 indicates the criteria to transform the area into a liveable neighbourhood, resilient to climate change. The new planned metropolitan development will integrate tertiary uses with public facilities and open spaces together with a new mobility system. Within UP2030, the municipality aims to find a balance between urban growth and climate resilience in a new district development. This includes (a) design for a carbon-neutral, liveable and resilient neighbourhood; and (b) develop a proposal to connect the urban green, balancing blue/green infrastructure; and including measure to ensure equity and prevent gentrification. The objective is to reach a consensus on setting the guidelines for the future development of the area together will all stakeholders involved (citizens, public authorities and services, suppliers, organizations, etc.).

Since February 2023, Granollers has carried out two workshops, one with internal and one with external stakeholders, as well as a series of in-depth interviews and questionnaires. This process highlighted the need for a systemic approach to align plans and projects, as well as coordination across disciplines and departments; it was also acknowledged that the public sector lacks resources to drive this collaboration and that internal knowledge could be developed further, particularly in the understanding of climate neutrality and just transition concepts. Moreover, technical needs emerged regarding data management, sharing, and cross-analysis, requiring investment in IT solutions and staff understanding of effective data usage.

The LAA was kicked-off in April 2023, and the municipality plans to expand it, as it is supporting knowledge exchange and co-creation, promoting communication, coordination, and dialogue among stakeholders. Regarding the implementation roadmap, Granollers municipality is interested in the application of tools which support the development and visualization of multiple scenarios in order to explore alternative design options and potential adjustments to the original masterplan of the area. Considering the early stage of the project (most of the area is not developed yet) and that the municipality needs to complete additional spatial analysis, the most suitable tool is the Data driven geospatial analysis and parametric design (provided by TSPA). The objective is to support local decision-makers with design-oriented evaluations, by visualizing multiple options with different parameters (i.e., variation in density, orientation, green areas etc.). The tool could also support a wider engagement process, where different stakeholders can test different scenarios. In addition, AQUATEC will support Granollers as liaison partners and will make use of the RESCCUE platform to assess different climate adaptation measures based on the hazards faced by the city and then perform a cost-benefits analysis.

Both tools will be tested in the first months of 2024 and will reflect the outcomes of the second UP2030 workshop on Vision. The results will shape the phase of Action and the adaptive pathway definition. After the successful application of these two tools, the municipality will explore the use of additional technical tools. In parallel, Granollers is planning additional engagement activities (including a Local Info Day) to achieve a greater consensus on the future development of La Bòbila neighbourhood.

3.5 Istanbul

The city of Istanbul has been experiencing significant population growth and rapid urbanization in the last decades. This has led to a significant increase in carbon emissions and energy consumption. Istanbul Climate Change Action Plan (ICCAP) has been preparing to develop strategies and plans against climate change and to reduce GHG emissions. Nevertheless, the municipality needs to deploy more advanced analytical tools to support climate mitigation and the transition towards a net-zero city. In the context of UP2030, the city aims to improve decision making to advance its planning agenda and to initiate positive energy neighbourhoods by making use of advanced computational methods (such as digital energy twins and artificial intelligence). The interventions that will be deployed in the pilot area aim to the decarbonization of building and transport system (by integrating photovoltaic systems in building and public spaces and promoting 100% renewables fed e-scooters); moreover, the interventions will measure social benefits to reduce energy poverty and extreme heat-related health risks.

Given the city's size, the Istanbul team decided to scale down the project in a pilot district (Kadikoy). The LAA was set up accordingly, and a stakeholder engagement process was activated, including residents and local community (especially women and youth), and local businesses. As part of the LAA process, Istanbul is currently preparing a large survey aiming to collect responses from 150 residents on urban climate change, micro-mobility, and solar panels in buildings. The results of the survey will be utilized to help inform the visioning process.

The first workshop on needs (held in May 2023) emphasized some barriers to change, including regulatory constraints, financial constraints, as well as limitations due to the specific context of Istanbul (i.e., unique topography which makes the development of micro mobility solutions more difficult, lack of integrated public transport and dense car population). The proposed solutions include raising public awareness, improving legislations and obligations, offering financial incentives and integrate urban transformation with renewable energy applications and micro-mobility solutions.

Working together with METU and the liaison partner GUNAM, Istanbul team has started a data collection process related to buildings (GIS data, coordinates, number of dwellings, residents, etc.), natural gas consumptions, and e-scooter (i.e., route and time). Moreover, a 3D energy modelling was created to calculate energy consumptions levels, the potential application of solar panels and planning the deployment of charging stations in the area.

Given the strong and ongoing collaboration with METU and GUNAM, the tool selection process was relatively straightforward. Significant progress has already been made in working with the UBEM/UBTEM. In fact, the tool has already been successfully tested to assess and model energy consumption patterns within the city. Istanbul's engagement with this tool reflects the city's commitment to data-driven decision-making and its dedication to understanding and addressing energy consumption challenges comprehensively. By utilizing the UBEM/UBTEM tool, Istanbul has taken a significant step towards achieving its sustainability goals, particularly in the context of the decarbonization of buildings and transport systems.

Furthermore, the city has expressed interests in other tools that support analysis of consumptions data, performances of buildings, locations for renewable energy and development of business models. These tools include the BIM module & Building LCA assessment module (CIRCE), the Data Driven Geospatial Analysis and Parametric Design (TSPA) and Urban Heat Island Risk analysis (LINKS). Ultimately, the goal of the city is to achieve carbon-neutrality targets by integrating buildings, mobility and renewable energy in a comprehensive way.

3.6 Lisbon

The city of Lisbon is trying to improve the provision of high-quality multi-functional public spaces, promote healthier lifestyles, and support its climate neutrality targets. Over the last 10 years, the city completed several interventions (including new green infrastructure, horticultural parks, tree plantings and improvement of existing public spaces). One key challenge the city is facing is how to measure the benefits of these activities and maximise impact to further accelerate the introduction of new green and blue infrastructure at the neighbourhood level. Within UP2030 project, the city of Lisbon aims to improve its digital decision-support platform around the level of effort and impact of its climate neutrality and adaptation actions. The approach is tested and validated in the district of Alvalade, an area of more than 30,000 inhabitants and characterized by significant climate vulnerabilities and social inequalities. The planned interventions will be focused on the various social facilities located within the parish, promoting climate-neutrality and adaptation, taking multiple impacts into account (social, economic, political, environmental, technological and heritage).

During the first year of UP2030, the Lisbon team has identified the public facilities in the parish as key locations where to start testing the planned interventions. At the same time, the team has identified local facilitators (such as teachers and sports instructors) and started engagement activities to reinforce stakeholder engagement and commitment. The LAA was launched in April 2023 with a stakeholder mapping and the engagement process is advancing; several key local actors and areas emerged, including the Sao Miguel Rugby Club, the Corechêus Library and Elementary School, and the Alvalade Norte Market. The first UP2030 workshop was held at the end of May 2023 and focused on the topic of climate-neutral neighbourhood, climate resilience and social inclusion. A clear outcome was the need of more and better data measures to support decision-making and complement historical data. Other issues that emerged referred to citizens participation, awareness, and climate-related communication. Beside the workshop, the city implemented additional activities (such as technical visits to the pilot areas of São Miguel Rugby Club and Biblioteca dos Coruchêus). Following the General Assembly (hosted in Lisbon), the liaison partner LNEC organized 4-in person working sessions with different departments of the municipality of Lisbon, from Environment, Climate Change & Energy, to Architecture, Transport and Water.

Regarding the tools' implementation process, Lisbon has expressed primary interest for tools that allow the measurement of variables and KPIs in real time, as well as tools that support decision-making. In this perspective, the Air quality monitoring and forecasting and the ecosystem service assessment (provided by LINKS) were considered. Thanks to the close collaboration with LNEC as liaison partner, the city of Lisbon has also the opportunity to address water-related challenges. In particular, the city has started exploring the application of tools for circularity in the urban water cycle. These include tools for measurement, water-smartness assessment, reclaimed water quality model in distribution systems and risk assessment tool for urban non-potable water reuse.

In terms of next steps, the team in Lisbon is working to create synergies between various streams of work underway in the municipality (Lisbon is also part of the Mission on climate-neutral and smart cities). The team intends to conduct additional interviews with local "ambassadors", develop a catalogue of fit-for-

purpose” solutions, and monitor the progresses in the pilot areas. The ambition is to ensure the involvement of local communities in the process of transformation of the parish and establish good practices for replication, guaranteeing the local identity of the area.

3.7 Milan

The City of Milan has committed to reducing its CO₂ emissions by 45% by 2030 and becoming carbon neutral by 2050. The key challenge for Milan is now how to apply these high-level commitments at the neighbourhood scale and upcoming regeneration projects. One of the major challenges that the city has been facing is the regeneration of several abandoned areas, including decommissioned railyards. Within UP2030 project, the municipality aims to accelerate the transition to carbon neutrality of urban regeneration areas. The pilot area identified is the Scalo Porta Romana, a large, abandoned railway (except for the passenger railroad), which has taken on the role of a barrier, reinforcing the distance between northern and southern neighbourhoods and constituting an element of fracture in the design of the city. This railyard has an important opportunity of transformation in view of the 2026 Winter Olympic Games. The ambition of UP2030 in Milan is to shape the design of the area, supporting climate-neutrality but also integrating resilience and ensuring a just transition. The approach tested in Scalo Romana is extendable to other abandoned railyards and regeneration areas.

The city has committed that the regeneration shall align with the goals of the European Green Deal and the Italian Recovery and Resilience Plan in particular: (1) decarbonisation of the building stock, (2) creation of a resilient community, (3) circular economy, (4) nature-based solutions. Through UP2030, the city will develop and apply quantitative and qualitative metrics to inform the intervention’s plan and design to ensure that it meets its objectives. These will reflect socioeconomic, demographic characteristics of beneficiaries, as well as adaptation and mitigation metrics. Nevertheless, the city emphasized the need to improve the capacity to design green areas in urban regeneration projects to provide more ecosystem services, enhancing citizens’ quality of life. Moreover, the municipality should become more aware about the environmental, social and economic impacts of its adaptation and mitigation measures indicated in the municipal “Air and Climate Plan”.

The municipality of Milan held the first workshop on gap and needs analysis in June 2023 bringing together different city departments (urban regeneration, welfare and health, energy and climate, urban resilience, green and environment). Two additional workshops and other internal meetings took place during summer to align different departments and groups on the planned activities. The LAA was set up in April 2023 within the City Hall, however the goal is to reach out to priority external stakeholders after the second workshop on Visions.

Regarding the implementation roadmap, Milan’s team believes that UP2030 can support them in adopting new approaches in decision-making regarding green areas and develop evaluation systems of the measures and projects implemented within the city. The city plans to make use of the Ecosystem Service Assessment tool (provided by LINKS, which is also Milan’s liaison partner); the objective is to improve the design and management of urban green areas, increasing awareness about the environmental, social and economic associated benefits. Moreover, the city is willing to test for the first time the multi-dimensional analysis of the City Resilience Framework (RCities) tool at a neighbourhood scale; the ambition is to develop a robust evaluation system that can be replicated in other regeneration projects in the city.

In terms of next steps, the city of Milan will identify other suitable tools provided by construction partners (such as the MIRA Digital Twins Platform, water management-related tools, and air quality monitoring and forecast). In addition, the municipality will identify other suitable replication area (i.e., Scalo Farini). The

visioning process will continue with the second workshops and will be the foundation to start the implementation phase.

3.8 Muenster

The city of Muenster is currently undergoing the revision of the goals and measures established in the INSEK Muenster 2030 (Integrated urban development concept) for the urban development of the city centre. The plan was originally developed in 2008, it has been revised in the years and politically approved in March 2023. The review of the initial plan was necessary to better answer to ongoing challenges and trends, including the need to increase climate-adaptation within the city centre and strengthen the existing blue-green infrastructure. The UP2030 project represents an opportunity for the city to shape climate-neutral, resilient and compact neighbourhoods, creating a roadmap that show how achieve these objectives. The area of Überwasser/Frauenstraße has been selected as pilot district, considering that both the buildings and the design of the street space offer a lot of potential, but also the need for various climate adaptation and climate protection measures.

In 2023, Muenster's team implemented the first workshop on needs analysis (May 2023), a series of interviews with stakeholders from the pilot area and organized a Climate Week in October. The LAA was set up, including the Planning department, the Office for Mobility and Civil Engineering; different institutions and individuals will be added to the working group depending on the topic.

The city of Muenster emphasized the need for a holistic view of climate protection and adaptation measures in the context of urban development processes, as well as the need to develop participatory strategies to promote public acceptance and co-design by citizens. In 2024, the city is planning to organize a series of Climate Trainings (KlimaTraining) at the neighbourhood scale; the ambition is to enable participants not only to change their lifestyle and behaviours but also motivate them to take sustainable initiatives (i.e., urban gardening, green facades, use of renewable energy etc.). Nevertheless, the city is currently facing barriers that can hamper to successful realization of these initiatives. The municipality has limited resources available, there are communication gaps between departments and office, collaboration needs to be reinforced, and there is no overview of the tools currently used by the municipality. UP2030 can support the city of Muenster by providing a systemic method to integrate synergies between adaptation and mitigation, facilitating replication in other neighbourhoods. In addition, the project should support the city in enabling the involvement of citizens, contributing to raining public acceptance of measures among residents.

In terms of tools selection and implementation roadmap, the city has started the collaboration with Buro Happold on the use of the Climate proofing tool; it will assist the municipality with a quick assessment of urban development projects and their impacts and potentials on both climate mitigation and adaptation. The tool is expected to provide high-level recommendations to the municipality. In parallel, the city will continue engagement activities (such as the KlimaTraining) and the development of the UP2030 visioning process in the first months of 2024.

3.9 Rotterdam

The city of Rotterdam has invested in the Resilient BoTu 2028 program to make the neighbourhoods of Bospolder and Tussendijk the first resilient district of Rotterdam in 2028. Following an unconventional yet holistic approach, the focus of the programme is laid on using physical challenges such as the energy transition and climate adaptation as a lever to strengthen social resilience. BoTu invests in its people as its primary asset, improving their life and capacities. One of the main action points was to develop an

integral and sustainable neighbourhood approach, creating room for new forms of collaboration between municipalities, partners and local communities. Within the framework of UP2030, the city of Rotterdam aims to build a framework or blueprint to replicate BoTu's district-first approach to other neighbourhoods within Rotterdam and the Netherlands. The framework will include elements such as documenting initiatives and harvesting of results, methodologies used, policy recommendations, indicators and measures developed.

Throughout 2023, the Rotterdam team has implemented a series of engagement activities both within the municipality and in BoTu area. Following the two workshops on Needs (May 2023), Rotterdam continued to engage with key stakeholders to better frame their objectives for the UP2030 project, including the organization of a reflection workshop in June 2023. In the following months, Rotterdam has been meeting regularly with local actors, often through 1-1 meetings in BoTu, to build an alliance of involved stakeholders, in line with the city's strategy around Asset Based Community Development (ABCD). The LAA was established in April 2023 but will be further established in the form of working groups consisting of community groups, policymakers, external stakeholder etc. with the purpose of critically analysing the program and building the framework/blueprint together. Furthermore, a conference on social resilience took place in BoTu in June 2023 and the municipality is working on open call processes for community-led local development (CLLD).

Given the level of maturity of the BoTu program (the program has already started since 2019), the focus of the municipality is primarily on upscaling, by leveraging the lessons learned so far and making these actionable for other neighbourhoods of the city. In regards of the implementation roadmap, the city is willing to refine engagement activities by making use of the Citizen Voice tool (provided by TUD) and Community Maps (by MfC). The Rotterdam team expressed interest also in the Resilience Assessment Framework (LNEC), in storytelling methods for participatory exchange, as well as training for capacity building of municipal staff. In 2024, Rotterdam plans to continue the coalition-building learning process with external stakeholders, knowledge dissemination, and the expansion of activities in BoTu (including webinars, seminars and workshops).

3.10 Thessaloniki

Over the past three decades, Thessaloniki has been experiencing shrinking population in the urban fabrics of the city centre, as well as suburban and urban sprawl dynamics. Despite the touristic vocation of the centre, the city faces several challenges related to habitability (such as the lack of affordable housing but also an increasing stock of abandoned buildings), decline of economy activities and sustainability. In this context, the participation of Thessaloniki in the EU Mission on "100 climate-neutral and smart cities by 2030" represents an opportunity for needed transformations at the city level.

The goal within UP2030 project is to support the municipality in advancing the net-zero transition by developing a DCAP in the district of "Dioikitirio". The area faces key challenges both at the spatial and socio-economic level: urban shrinkage of residence and economic activities, increasing stock of vacant buildings, decline of economy activities in favor of short-term tourism rents, reducing the neighbourhood cohesion. Transforming Dioikitirio into a green and thriving district means promoting greening strategies and implementing local sustainable practices, as well as promoting better quality of life for residents and prioritizing their well-being.

As part of UP2030 activities, the cities conducted an initial stakeholder mapping and set up the LAA in April 2023. The municipality held additional five internal meetings to further map the stakeholders to be engaged in the pilot area (specific attention is given to elderly people and parents). The workshop on needs

analysis took place in May 2023 and highlighted the need for more specific climate indicators, comprehensive data on emissions and sources, vacant building stock, green space, public perceptions of net zero, and demographic change. This challenge is also closely related to the implementation of the CCC developed within the Mission project Net Zero Cities.

The upcoming activities planned by the Thessaloniki team include further processing of the data for mapping the area and initiating the development of the DCAP. This will be done by scaling down the CCC recommendations and creating a list of short-term and local action. In addition, the municipality will continue to involve policy offers and political elected staff, as well as continue the engagement with external stakeholders. The implementation roadmap and the visioning process will align to the development of the DCAP.

For what concerns the tool selection, Thessaloniki has expressed interest for three typologies of tools. At this stage, Thessaloniki wants to strengthen its climate action related data management capabilities (collaboration with Smart Cities WG), model energy efficiency (METU) and assess heat risk (UCCRN) in the pilot area. The analysis will be carried out through a lens of spatial justice (TUD).

3.11 Zagreb

In recent years, the city of Zagreb has focused on projects to develop productive green infrastructure for urban regeneration of former industrial areas, and particularly the former Sljeme factory in Sesvete. The successful implementation of these projects includes the development of a modular urban farm with NBS, solar solutions, green walls, green roofs and aquaponic elements. Within UP2030, the city aims to build on the acquired knowledge and experience and improve activities that will support climate-neutrality and sustainable urban development. The original goal was to focus on the same location in Sesvete, but after a phase of data collection it was decided to include two additional pilot areas: a school in the city district of Sesvete and the zoo in the city district of Maksimir.

In the first year of UP2030, the municipality has already achieved some important results. Regarding the school “Luka Sesvete”, a detailed plan of the project activities was agreed (including green walls, a green showroom indoor and an urban forest outdoor); the school curriculum is integrated with project activities; and the infrastructure for green walls and green showroom was installed. Nevertheless, the school presents some technical and governance limitations (i.e., it cannot be open to the public 24/7). For this reason, Zagreb team decided to include the zoo in the project, to maximize the impact of the project and overcome obstacles in the implementation (the city of Zagreb is founder of the zoo, therefore it operates in accordance with city policies and budget). The declared objective of the project is raising awareness and increasing the education of children, which are the key target group of the project. Although the key stakeholders to be included in the LAAs were defined from the beginning, the response and willingness to participate is still relatively poor. More tailored engagement activities might be required to overcome this barrier.

In terms of activities implemented so far, the municipality hosted the first UP2030 workshop and carried out 30 additional interviews with selected stakeholders. The main challenges emerged are related to the involvement of stakeholders and how to ensure their commitment in the project. In the upcoming months, Zagreb’s team plans to continue the activities both in the school and the zoo, including the participation in the agricultural fair CROAGRO. Regarding the implementation roadmap, the city is interested in tools to increase awareness within the general public, supporting creative solutions and better implementation. The tools selected so far are measuring and assessment tools (such as carbon budgeting, air quality monitoring, resilience assessment framework), as well as tools to support capacity

building within the municipality. There is still lack of definition in the scope of tool selection and implementation. As such, the Zagreb team will deepen the collaboration with tools providers and work in parallel with the visioning roadmap (including the second UP2030 workshop on visioning).

3.12 Rio de Janeiro (observer city)

As observer city, Rio de Janeiro is not following the same process as the other pilot cities. Rio de Janeiro's focus is specifically on how their funding received by the Interamerican Bank of Development ensures that it meets the adaptation and climate neutrality objectives set out. In this sense, this city plays a role in exploring UP2030 approach under critical urbanization and equity challenges, and as front-runner city in aligning with financing instruments.

Beside implementing some local engagement activities and creating synergies within the municipality, the Rio de Janeiro's team is currently exploring the collaboration with the consortium partners UCCRN and Deltares for the assessment of flood and heat risk.

4 Conclusions and next steps

The current document provides the updated version of the “Pilot Implementation Plan”, previously submitted in March 2023. Compared to the previous version, the document includes the new version of the City Storyline and the state of advancement in each pilot city. This plan also provides contextual information for project partners to deliver customized input and support to the cities. In addition to the common project milestones, the Pilot Implementation Plan uncovers the actions that need to be taken in the cities to achieve the objectives of the project, the risks of implementation and the strategies to mitigate the risks.

Several common factors such as local elections, hiring of project staff and limitations on available time to meaningfully engage local stakeholders for setting up the LAAs have been identified. Cities are also aligning with other activities and milestones that can support the UP2030 timeline in their local settings. For instance, alignment with the Mission on Climate Neutral and Smart Cities is also considered. A key takeaway has been identifying front-runner cities among the pilots that can test certain approaches and then transfer the lessons to other cities, i.e., use an agile implementation approach with short learning cycles. This also reinforces the matching making and collective learning approach of UP2030.

Given the current state of the project, it is critical that the Implementation roadmap of each city is supported by a solid visioning process (Task 2.4 Co-designing pilot shared visions and adaptive pathways for transformation), to ensure legitimacy of the solutions proposed and to adequately connect the phased of “Analysis” and “Vision” with the phase of “Action”. Pilot cities are currently refining their visioning process. For this reason, the original city work plans developed are not included in this deliverable.

5 References

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6 Annex 1

Figure 5 – Alignment between WPs for the design and delivery of the Analysis workshop in Pilot Cities

Process

General UP2030 visioning process, outlining key milestones.

Figure 6 - Visioning process to be followed by all pilot cities

Belfast – Belfast Net Zero Neighbourhoods– City Storyline

Context and background of Belfast’s pilot case	1
History	1
Social characteristics of the neighbourhood.....	4
Challenges and opportunities	5
Current approach and actions	7
Needs and aspirations	9
People, Partners, Organisations and more	11
Activities undertaken as part of UP2030	12
Setting up of Learning Action Alliance	12
An extensive needs analysis process	12
Working together with tools and services	14
Co-visioning phase	15

Context and background of Belfast’s pilot case

History

Belfast’s history of sectarian conflict has helped shaped the city and the attitudes of those who live there. While the conflict is now in the past, sectarian divide still exist with several single identity communities around the city centre. Fragmented policy and governance is also an issue along with the fact that Belfast City Council does not have statutory powers for regeneration, transport or infrastructure delivery. Belfast City Council serves a population of approximately 330,000 people and is responsible for a range of power and services including land use planning, community planning, off-street car parking and some responsibilities for economic, physical and social regeneration. We also provide key public services such as bin collections, burials and cleansing.

In 2019 and 2020 Belfast established a Belfast Resilience and Sustainability Board and a Belfast Climate Commission to support climate planning in Belfast, linking to cities across the UK, EU and around the world

through the Resilient Cities Network and Place Based Climate Action Network. In December 2020, Belfast launched the Belfast Resilience Strategy alongside the Belfast Net Zero Carbon Roadmap and the Belfast One Million Trees programme. Together these form the foundations for the city's ambitions to achieve carbon neutrality (66% by 2025, 80% reduction by 2030 and 100% by 2050). A Belfast Local Area Energy Plan, Electric Vehicle Infrastructure Strategy and Retrofit Programme are currently in development, with a Belfast Retrofit Hub having been established in September 2022. The city has also put liveability in its core through the multi-partner strategy 'A Bolder Vision for Belfast' which aims to create sustainable and mixed-use neighbourhoods in the city centre through the redevelopment of brownfield sites. Belfast's vision is to create a people-focused environment with playful streets and spaces for children and families to live and thrive. The city has been working in aligning play, climate neutrality, tree planting and green infrastructure by developing the award-winning Urban Childhood Report and has been testing these new approaches in the design and implementation of a new city centre multi-functional park and in the Cathedral Gardens. However, the municipality needs to elevate and embed these learning and work across council departments and with city stakeholders in more areas and projects across the city.

(Cathedral Gardens Belfast, 2021)

Through UP2030, Belfast seeks to create a toolkit that will be applied in all its regeneration projects that integrates tree planting, green infrastructure, play and co-design with young people. The framework will

be tested in the Linen Quarter district and around the Barrack Street area, which has been identified of becoming the first sustainable and net zero business district in Northern Ireland. Lessons learned from this pilot will be useful to identify opportunities in other neighbourhoods and upscale the concept of net-zero districts across the city. Furthermore, the municipality aims to address the fragmentation in terms of governance and delivery, embedding this project in the upcoming update of Belfast's Community Plan 'The Belfast Agenda'. Finance and resources are required to achieve net zero.

(Belfast City Centre)

Social characteristics of the neighbourhood

(Linen Quarter)

The pilot will take place within the Linen Quarter and around Barrack Street area, which have a rich history, a diversity of active residents and businesses, initiatives and network activities that are involved across the neighbourhoods. While the city centre has a relatively low population due to historical factors, the Linen Quarter area includes the residential areas of Sandy Row, Donegall Pass and The Markets with a population of roughly of 9,000, while the Barrack Street area has a population of around 500.

The area is located within Belfast city centre and has a holistic mix of land uses that includes, residential, commercial, tourism, a large transport hub and a thriving hospitality industry. In terms of the residential composition, there are apartments that tend of house newer residents, singles, and ethnic minorities. Recently, there have been a number of new Purpose-Built Managed Student Apartments in the area to cater for the ever-growing student population within the city centre. Traditionally the pilot is characterised by low-density housing from single identity communities, which means majority Catholic or Protestant.

The area is undergoing significant change with several major regeneration projects underway. The new [Belfast Transport Hub](#) is under construction and will be the main public transport hub within the city. The area has also seen significant investment in a sustainable travel infrastructure during the COVID 19 pandemic. A new route for Belfast's Rapid Transport System (Glider) is proposed to run through the area, with work ongoing to facilitate this. The Linen Quarter Business Improvement District (BID) has recently been successful in its re-ballot and has now expanded to cover more of the of the Linen Quarter area that will be involved in the pilot.

The area faces several challenges in terms of social segregation that is reinforced by road infrastructure and extensive hard landscaping in the public realm. There are few accessible, public green spaces in the area and the access to the river Lagan is mainly through an office park onto a public footpath. However, the river does not have access points in this area for recreation such as swimming or rowing. These are compact urban communities that are relatively and walkable and contain some cycle lanes and quiet streets that could be further improved and linked together to better connect to the city centre, services and amenities. Given the proximity to the city and challenges around traffic and car parking, people tend to travel by foot for very short local trips, however, there is anecdotal evidence that people will use cars to travel short distances due to the lack of services such as large grocery shops within the vicinity. This is also exacerbated by the legacy of the conflict and division between communities.

[Challenges and opportunities](#)

The City Council has been working in aligning play, climate neutrality, tree planting and green infrastructure by developing the award-winning [Urban Childhood Report](#) and has been testing these new approaches in the design and implementation of a new city centre multi-functional park and in the Cathedral Gardens.

(Cathedral Gardens designed by children for children)

Through UP2030, Belfast seeks to create a framework that will be applied in all its regeneration projects that integrates tree planting, green infrastructure, play and co-design with young people under the banner of reaching net zero at the neighbourhood level. The framework and neighbourhood approach developed from this pilot will be used to in other neighbourhoods and help us to integrate and upscale the concept of net-zero districts across the city.

In Belfast we have developed a [Net Zero Carbon Roadmap](#) which analyses the Scope 1 and 2 emissions in the city. That report found that buildings and transport are our two biggest sources of emissions. We have adopted city targets from that report – 66% reduction by 2025, 80% by 2030 and 100% by 2050. These align with the Northern Ireland legal obligation to be net zero by 2050 – linking to the Climate Act, Energy Strategy and other relevant regional plans. There is a gap at neighbourhood level in terms of understating the issues around becoming a net zero area and this initiative will go a long way to help us engage with communities of interest and place in developing neighbourhood net zero plans. We will also link to our new Belfast Retrofit Hub which aims to create neighbourhood pathfinder projects. The Bolder Vision Strategy and wider regeneration programme are key to making the transition to net zero a reality and the UP2030 project will help to embed net zero in those programmes.

The area has issues with homelessness and drug abuse as well as transport poverty. Sectarianism continues to be an issue within the city as a whole and there are a number of single identity communities within the area although the city centre is seen as a neutral space and a space for everyone.

Potential projects to link to include Linenquarter Business Improvement District ambition to be a Sustainable District, the UPSURGE project, Grey to Green initiative, Vacant to Vibrant initiative, Belfast Retrofit Hub, Belfast One Million Trees Programme, Belfast Transport Hub etc.

Current approach and actions

There are several key strategies that are currently being implemented within Belfast and the pilot area:

[Belfast Agenda](#) - Following an extensive period of engagement and consultation, we published our city's first community plan in November 2017, the Belfast Agenda. The Belfast Agenda was created by a partnership of key city partners, residents and community organisations. It set out our joint vision and long-term ambitions for Belfast's future, as well as outlining our priorities for action over the next four years.

[Belfast City Centre Regeneration and Investment Strategy](#) - The City Centre Strategy sets out the context for developing the city centre and outlines our aspirations for the continued growth and regeneration of the city core and its surrounding areas. The Strategy is based on the following core principles:

- Increase the Employment Population
- Increase the Residential Population
- Manage the Retail Offer
- Maximise the Tourism Opportunity
- Create Regional Learning and Innovation Centres
- Create a Green, Walkable, Cyclable Centre
- Connect to the City Around

- Shared Space and social impact

[Belfast Resilience Strategy](#) - Belfast launched its Resilience Strategy, the city's first climate plan in December 2020. It sets out 30 transformational programmes to transition Belfast to an inclusive, zero-emissions, climate-resilient economy within a generation.

The strategy comprises three elements:

- Resilience Assessment – a review of how resilient we currently are and what the main threats are to the city
- Ambitions Document – our resilience aspirations and a vision of what and where we want to be as a city
- Delivery Plan – how we plan to achieve this.

The Belfast Resilience Strategy is essentially a framework to safeguard Belfast against situations that could threaten its safety and stability over coming years and help us deliver our Belfast Agenda priorities.

[Belfast Net Zero Carbon Roadmap](#) - Net-Zero Carbon Roadmap for Belfast was launched along with the Resilience Strategy in December 2020. We developed this as a Belfast Climate Commission partner through the Place Based Climate Action Network (PCAN). The roadmap identifies transport, buildings and industry as key sectors to decarbonise. Work is now underway with city partners to develop a Carbon Action Plan.

[Belfast Urban Childhood Framework](#) - With 35% of Belfast's population aged 25 or under, Belfast City Council recognised the need to design for the youngest in the population and place them at the heart of city planning. With support from the Resilient Cities Network (R-Cities), and working closely with Belfast City Council, Arup developed a framework and design strategy that creates a more healthy, inclusive and child-friendly city centre in Belfast.

[Bolder Vision](#) - A Bolder Vision is an ambitious blueprint to explore a shared approach to creating a more attractive, accessible, safe and vibrant city. Developed jointly by Belfast City Council, the Department for Communities and the Department for Infrastructure, the vision is built on four Visioning Principles:

- 1. Creating a healthy, shared, vibrant and sustainable environment that promotes wellbeing for all, inclusive growth and innovation.
- 2. Fundamentally changing the centre of Belfast to prioritise integrated walking, cycling and public transport and end the dominance of the car
- 3. Providing lively, safe and green streets linking inclusive shared spaces to promote resilience and enhance our built heritage
- 4. Removing severance and barriers to movement between the centre of Belfast and the surrounding communities to improve access for all.

[Carbon Budget for Northern Ireland](#) – The Department for Agriculture, Environment and Rural Affairs through the Climate Change Committee (CCC) have published its advice for the first three Carbon Budgets for Northern Ireland, the first of which will cover the period 2023 – 2027.

A carbon budget is the maximum amount of greenhouse gases that can be emitted in a given period. The CCC advice is that the Carbon Budget for Northern Ireland from 2023-2027 is set at levels that have an average reduction of 33% on 1990 levels over the carbon reduction period. The Committee also advises that interim targets for 2030 and 2040 should be set at reductions of 48% and 77% respectively.

A number of regeneration projects in the area that are taking place or about to take place such as the South West Quarter revitalisation scheme and the Grey to Green projects which will look to increase green infrastructure to the area. The [Linen Quarter Business Improvement District](#) (BID) have identified several projects that they are looking to implement within the pilot area and will be a key stakeholder in the pilot.

[Needs and aspirations](#)

The pilot has the follow visions:

Vision 1

- To develop a framework that sets out a pathway to be net zero at a neighbourhood level, inspiring and guiding communities, businesses, and policymakers as to how best to achieve this.

- The framework will be tested in the Linen Quarter district, which has been identified of becoming the first sustainable and net zero business district in Northern Ireland.

Vision 2

- Embed the UP2030 framework in programmes across the city.
- Identify opportunities in other neighbourhoods and upscale the concept of net-zero districts across the city.

Vision 3

- A coordinated approach to reaching Net Zero at the neighbourhood level.
- This will be achieved by addressing the fragmentation in terms of governance and delivery that currently exists by involving key stakeholders in the project to ensure their buy in.

The following needs have been identified which it is hoped that the pilot can address:

Need 1

Set a baseline for the area in terms of air quality, emissions, car use, attitudes.

Air quality readings and other baseline figures pre and post project to understand how the project has had a positive impact on air quality and other factors.

Need 2

Identify meaningful interventions for the area.

Impactful projects to be delivered which can be replicated in other areas of the city.

Need 3

Engage youth and children in the planning of regeneration projects.

Series of workshops with children and youth groups to encourage their input into the project.

(Stakeholder engagement with children on the design of Cathedral Gardens)

People, Partners, Organisations and more

Belfast City Council has a good relationship having worked closely with several key stakeholders in the pilot area and in the wider city context. Among the key stakeholders are:

- Politicians
- Department for Communities
- Department for Infrastructure
- Translink – Public Transport Provider
- Linen Quarter Business Improvement District
- Belfast Chamber of Commerce
- Queen’s University
- Ulster University

- Children and Youth Groups
- Local communities
- Belfast Resilience and Sustainability Board/Climate Commission
- Belfast City Council Departments

Activities undertaken as part of UP2030

Setting up of Learning Action Alliance

The Learning and Action Alliance (LAA) of Belfast was kicked off in April 2023 and began with an extensive stakeholder mapping, conducted with the support of Liaison partners Mapping for Change. Belfast, in contrast to most other UP2030 cities, could already count on a long tradition of community participation and involvement, which aided in this phase of engagement. Belfast has divided stakeholders around several categories, from government to academic institutions, aligning project partners and city partners.

- [UP2030 Stakeholder list and matrix Belfast Final.xlsx](#)

After the series of workshops around needs, Belfast carried out further thematic workshops to dig deeper into the 3 main themes that had emerged: Retrofit, Greening and Transport. One of the key take-aways of the first phase of the LAA in Belfast is that there is an urgent need to match this (and other) engagement processes with concrete results for locals, though at a time in which there is little to no funding available for urban climate initiatives from the central government. Additionally, there is perhaps a need to refine the messaging, making sure that the social and economic dimensions are well embedded in climate actions.

Currently, Belfast is aiming to better understand the citizens' and stakeholders', including businesses' understanding and knowledge around net zero in the different pilot areas it has selected, and planning further engagement towards the Visioning phase.

At the General Assembly, Belfast reported that the core LAA would be composed of the different pilot neighborhood representatives, in addition to representatives from the Queens Community & Place team key stakeholder group Belfast seeks to engage is the youth and children and city partners.

An extensive needs analysis process

At the start of the engagement process, Belfast City Council (BCC) identified three key thematic areas for concentration: green infrastructure, active travel, and retrofitting buildings. These were chosen as they were identified as main sources of emissions and to align with the existing knowledge and expertise within the BCC team, as well as plans and ongoing activities from climate projects in the city.

The initial workshop centred around these three themes, engaging local government officials, policymakers, academics, and representatives from citizen groups. They were divided into the three thematic groups to complete a fuzzy cognitive mapping exercise. As a follow-up to the first workshop, the Belfast team, along with their liaison MfC, implemented additional activities to extract more detailed needs and barriers. The team utilized existing professional and industry networks, bringing together stakeholders under the UP2030 umbrella.

The primary needs and barriers identified were related to the complex and fragmented nature of local governance and community organizing, shaped by the legacy of sectarian conflict in modern Belfast. This community fracturing was not only addressed within the workshop but has also been a key consideration in planning and designing Belfast's engagement approach. Collaboration and partnership working have been fundamental to how Belfast plans to achieve its pilot aims.

During the initial workshop, participants discussed the challenges faced by BCC, highlighting their limited decision-making power over local infrastructure and housing. This is further complicated by agencies responsible for these services lacking clarity on the scope of their own power and responsibilities. Closing governance gaps within BCC and other local and national agencies therefore emerged as a major need. Retrofit groups particularly emphasized the necessity for better alignment and simplification of policy and regulation, such as fire regulations and building control, to streamline and accelerate retrofitting efforts. Currently, retrofitting schemes are not tailored to suit all buildings uses and so BCC has recognised the need to deliver targeted schemes for all building types and tenure mixes. The expansion of schemes needs support from education, upskilling, and improved employment opportunities, as Belfast currently lacks the workforce for large-scale implementation of proposed ideas.

Education and upskilling were also identified as key needs in the green infrastructure thematic area. Long-term maintenance provision is a barrier to creating new green spaces due to current cost-effective options lacking quality service and utilisation of local workers. Therefore, community buy-in and ownership will be crucial, especially since much of the current provision of green space is owned and controlled by private entities. Improved cross-sector communication and collaboration in the area of green infrastructure are needed to identify new site locations and strike a balance between conflicting land use interests in premium city centre areas.

In the active travel engagement activities, the lack of supportive infrastructure was identified as the main challenge. Large road junctions in the pilot area discourage pedestrians and cyclists, despite available resources such as cycle lanes and route maps. To overcome this, Belfast needs to promote existing resources while investing in and renewing infrastructure to encourage more active travel.

Traversing all thematic discussions on needs and barriers was the issue of financing. There is an over prioritization of large-scale and expensive interventions that receive initial funding but lack revenue, limiting their long-term viability. Focusing on smaller-scale opportunities may instead provide sustainable, cumulative, and marginal change. Public-private collaboration on the provision of new green spaces may reveal new funding opportunities.

Taking an individual view of financing, the use of monetary incentives was repeatedly discussed to encourage wider participation in proposed interventions. Public awareness of the cost benefit and potential savings available through participation in green initiatives also needs improvement.

To quantify these savings, Belfast requires more data to evidence the benefits of their interventions. Data collection has often focused on specific project aims, limiting the usefulness of available datasets. This limits opportunities to secure future funding and communicate with the public on their personal priorities and needs.

BCC continues to work diligently on stakeholder engagement, positioning themselves as leaders in local climate activities. They have carried out extensive stakeholder mapping to explore how local public and private sector activities can be aligned.

As young people are key stakeholders for BCC in UP2030, future planned engagement activities will focus on capturing their insights and encouraging their involvement, especially in harder-to-reach communities. For example, the Translink Youth Forum, set up to give young people a voice in the ongoing establishment of a new transport hub, will be engaged in a series of workshops. Further sessions will be held with other youth groups, supported by tools provided by UP2030 partners.

The interpretation of 'carbon-neutral city' in BCC has been expansive, incorporating elements like climate resilience and circularity. Looking forward, more clarity will be needed to outline the scope of climate neutrality, focusing on the broad efforts of BCC towards more targeted goals.

Further reading:

[Stakeholder Engagement Workshops - Reports](#)

[1st Engagement Review - Belfast.docx](#)

Working together with tools and services

As part of the UP2030 project, several tools and services are being offered to the cities by the technical partners. These tools play an important role in how the pilot project evolves and influences the results of the city's participation in the UP2030 project and beyond. Cities were hence encouraged to reflect on the purpose of using these tools in their process and create principles to guide the pre-selection process. For Belfast, tools are an opportunity to enrich the project with a focused approach to challenges through expertise and innovation.

Consistently the initial needs assessment phase, Belfast has defined some thematic areas for tool integration:

- Sustainable transport, green infrastructure, active mobility, and building retrofit. These are key areas where to reduce carbon emission locally, prioritizing small-scale, distributed interventions.
- Need for more data, information and better synergies between departments. Having clear baseline information and assessment tools is essential to monitor the success of the transition towards net-zero districts in the city.

The city of Belfast has preselected a series of tools provided by the consortium partners. The criteria that led the selection process were (i) supporting Belfast's UP2030 project delivery, (ii) minimal duplication with other ongoing Council's projects and tools, (iii) resource requirement, diversity of functions and stage

of development of the tools, (iv) appropriateness to Belfast and encompassed communities. The municipality expressed particular interest for the engagement tool Urban Design manual for Child and Youth Friendly Cities, provided by Design Clips; the tool supports small-scale design interventions to enhance the public realm's spatial quality, particularly for children and young people. Additional tools considered are the Ecosystem Services Assessment and the Equal Services & Facilities Assessment (Links Foundation) to quantify benefits and support decision making. Since tools implementation also requires capability and resources within the city teams, the city of Belfast expressed interest in training opportunities to leverage for broader learning goals and capacity building of the city team engaged in the project.

The city of Belfast has agreed to start working with Design Clips on the Urban Design Manual for Child and Youth Friendly Cities. The tool supports the design of small-scale interventions to enhance the public realm's spatial quality, particularly for children and young people. The intention is to conduct meaningful engagement with young people in the community, and to co-design solutions to some of their current challenges. This decision is consistent with the place-based approach that the city wants to follow and supports the production of a framework for replication in other districts of the city. The city has already started the collaboration with Design Clips and the implementation of the tools will take place in the first months of 2024. As Mapping for Change is the liaison partner, the city plans to use and integrate their Community Maps tool within UP2030.

The city of Belfast is open to receive additional support from other consortium partners and test additional tools in future (preliminary interest was given to the Green Economy Model tool, the Resilience Model Maturity tool, and the UDCW Simulation Toolkit). During the General Assembly in November 2023, the city had an opportunity to interact with the tool providers in order to further streamline the selection and explore which tool would be best suited to begin working with. As part of the process undertaken by the Implementation Taskforce, cities will first make a final selection of the tools, in alignment with the Visioning process, and thereafter build “implementation pathways” that map how a tool or selection of tools will be integrated in the pilot’s process in UP2030.

Co-visioning phase

The co-visioning phase is anchored on a needs assessment conducted under T2.3 and objectives previously identified within UP2030. This information provided a foundation for identifying specific needs and goals for Linen Quarter transformation and were used to tailor the methodology for co-designing of a shared vision, specific Linen Quarter context. The detailed steps for the co-visioning process with recommendations tailored to Belfast context have been developed by the technical partners and are currently being evaluated by Belfast team. Co-design is an approach at the core of the UP2030 process, therefore cities and their stakeholders' input in designing a co-visioning process enables to develop a more specific and contextualised approach to engagement.

Belfast is currently evaluating the feasibility of the proposal and creating a timeline for the next engagement steps to be taken under the co-visioning phases.

Belfast

[update the process diagram once it's finalised by the city: [Guide to Co-visioning. Visioning Roadmap](#)]

As part of the preparatory activities that sets the base for the co-visioning (Milestone 1 – Validate Pilot Objectives), Belfast is currently in the milestone of validating and refining identified key objectives. During the first year of the project, the understanding of objectives and needs has evolved and therefore the revision of objectives plays an important role for the upcoming engagement activities. The activity was started during the General Assembly meeting in Lisbon in 2023, where representative of the city, supported by liaison team, reflected on how well the identified objectives aligned with the pilot context.

The activity will help to identify which aspirations are most relevant to the short-, medium- or long-term goals and to validate their relevance by aiming to contextualise goals and break it into more operative objectives that can support implementation actions for transforming Linen Quarter. (Full document with objectives validation can be found [here](#)).

In the coming weeks and months, the city will engage in a series of activities to define a vision for a resilient, carbon-neutral, and just future for Belfast’s pilot. It will also identify concrete actions and barriers in light of defining adaptation pathways towards becoming the first Net-Zero Business District in Northern Ireland

Budapest– Measuring Healthy Streets© – City Storyline

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Context and background of the Budapest pilot

History

In order to implement the objective to increase access to healthy environment, Budapest leadership committed itself to introduce Healthy Streets® approach developed by Lucy Saunders in London. Budapest included Healthy Streets® in its Integrated Development Strategy adopted by the City Council in April, 2021.

In order to upscale the Healthy Streets approach Budapest adapts two methods: 1) achieving application and adaptation of Healthy Streets method in practice by urban development professionals, 2) the city is facilitating street upgrades through a tendering process supported by the EU, enabling districts to apply for and receive funding.

The Healthy Streets Budapest call for application

Under the programming of EU structural and cohesion funds in the 2021-2027 programming period, Budapest dedicated EUR 69 million in the Territorial Operational Programme Plus for a call for application for districts. Districts will be able to apply with individual projects designed & based on the principles of Healthy Streets®.

The Municipality of Budapest transformed the [Healthy Streets Design Check](#) adapted to the local features, with special focus on local challenges as traffic patterns, design standards, climate change impacts as precipitation patterns and heatwaves.

BUDAPEST

Egészséges Utcák értékelési rendszer

[Kezdőlap](#)
[Bevezető](#)
[Projekt](#)
[Portfólió](#)
[Eredmények](#)
[Hogyan értékelünk](#)
[Budapest belvárosi és központi](#)
[Csapadékvíz vizsztatás](#)
[Jóga](#)
[Hogyan jön létre a pontszám](#)

All projects must meet selection criteria defined in the call for application. All submitted applications should be in line with the Healthy Streets® approach assessed by the funding Managing Authority and City Hall experts (1st evaluation of feasibility document by City of Budapest – City Hall experts, Budapest Transport Center – BKK, Gov’t Jury for Cycling - KPT, Gov’t Jury for Green Infrastructure – ZIT; 2nd evaluation of applications and selection of winner by the Managing Authority and City Hall). The project proposals will be ranked based on the difference between current and designed street plans’ scores. The evaluation will follow the Healthy Streets Design Checklist, which is also available for the applicants since September 2022.

During the summer of 2022, an extensive testing phase was carried out with the involvement of the professional urban design company of the city (Budapest Urban Development Company Ltd.) and NGOs. All feedbacks were evaluated and the Design Check was adjusted accordingly.

Examples for test results of Healthy Streets incremental scores (as is and to be design version) for Csengery Str. (6th district): currently 19 points will be increased to 66 points.

	Meglévő állapot pontszám	Tervezett állapot pontszám
Egészséges Utcák pontszám	19	66
Mindenki otthon érzi magát	19	61
Könnyű átkelni az úttesten	33	72
Vannak árnyékos és védett helyek	0	67
Van hol megállni és megpihenni	0	40
Nincs túl nagy zaj	33	89
Az emberek szívesen sétálnak és kerékpároznak	19	61
Az emberek biztonságban érzik magukat	22	64
Van mit látni és csinálni	0	58
Az emberek jól érzik magukat	19	61
Tiszta a levegő	50	83

Within the EU funds framework, additional points can be earned for other project elements or approaches not fitting into the Healthy Streets® methodology: developing of community spaces on street openings, developing of other public assets as public transport stops and public toilets, cost-benefit ratio of the project (unit cost per user, unit cost per area), project contributes to core objectives of the integrated development plan (supports brown field development, green-blue infrastructure target area), project based on community design or public poll, participation of NGOs and local communities, supporting energy efficiency and application of renewables.

Spatial and social characteristics of the neighbourhood

Individual locations will be scattered around the city, therefore in this City Storyline it is not possible to introduce individual sites. The call for application is prepared in cooperation with the Managing Authority in charge, call for application has been published on 28th November 2023.

Some examples for the test projects:

Újhelyi str. (10th district – implemented):

Csengery Str. (6th district – planned design):

Current approach and actions related to the call for application

The application process has just recently been launched on 28th November 2023 and the Municipality has not received any information on yet on the actual proposed projects of the districts.

The Municipality of Budapest has already organised five workshops and training events for the districts and another side event to present the detailed Design Checklist with experts involving Lucy Saunders online. The events highlighted the main objectives of the methodology, intervention logic of the call, details of design principles.

In February 2023, the Municipality of Budapest requested the districts to submit their indicative projects for preliminary assessment and consultation purposes to facilitate the design process. Following the submission in 2023 Q2, the City Hall has launched consultation events with site visits and expert consultations to the district to assist project development.

HS applications timeline:

People, Partners, Organisations and more

Different departments of the City Hall are cooperating in the preparation and the implementation of the support framework for Healthy Streets.

The Municipality is working closely on the implementation with Budapest Transport Centre (BKK), responsible for transport strategy and operation of transportation. BKK will take part in the evaluation process focusing on transport infrastructure design eligibility. The Budapest Urban Development Company Ltd. assisted already the adaptation of the Design Check tool to Budapest in cooperation with Lucy Saunders.

The districts are also involved in the process as their future applications should be in line with the concept.

[Járókelő](#) NGO was the first organisation promoting Healthy Streets concept back in 2018 and they still [take an active part](#) not only in communication and providing feedback about the Design Check – as mentioned above – but in assisting community involvement in individual project preparation.

Upscaling the Healthy Streets methodology

The slow progress of Healthy Streets call for application's launch and the risk of further delay made the city rethink its goals under UP2030 project, yet keeping the overarching objective of the promotion and

upscaling of Healthy Streets. Besides the financially incentivised call for application, further application opportunities emerged for the Healthy Streets approach. During the consultations with potential applicants, districts have already started to use Healthy Streets methodology, some even beyond the scope of the call for application. To widen the use of HS approach – developed for the call for application, the Healthy Streets Design Check – , Budapest will set up an extended LAA, invite more stakeholders in the discourse and build a knowledge centre around it and start the co-visioning process for upscaling the methodology with different stakeholders and the involvement of local citizens. The city’s defined objectives for upscaling and achieving urban development professionals to adopt and apply the methodology in practice in urban space development (which is our **overarching objective**):

- Create a professional discourse, and the establishment of Healthy Streets knowledge centre and active dissemination of the methodology via setting up a dedicated Learning Action Alliance (LAA)
- Enhance Budapest citizens' public discourse on public health of their streets and public spaces, awareness raising and building public expectations.
- Testing community mapping instruments in line with the Healthy Street approach to gather public opinion, define potential projects and development targets, and raise awareness.
- Create guides and standards for the subsidiaries, districts and the planners involved.
- Involvement of market players who are (financially) interested and can be the drivers of change.
- Supporting the involvement of local citizens through the districts in the planning and implementation.

Activities undertaken as part of UP2030

Setting up of Learning Action Alliance

In Budapest, the LAA process was officially kicked off in April 2023 with a stakeholder mapping conducted by City Liaison partners Global Green Growth Institute (GGGI).

- [UP2030 Stakeholder list and matrix Budapest \(1\).xlsx](#)

Since the beginning, the UP2030 project has been envisioned to support the execution of the Healthy Streets Program in Budapest. In the first months, the LAA process stayed internal to city stakeholders to better define how such support could materialize. In the lead-up to the General Assembly of 13-15 November, Budapest became increasingly clear that it wanted to create an LAA to truly enhance citizens’ and local stakeholders’ involvement in the creation of Healthy Streets applications from district municipalities in Budapest (existing 67M euro program). While this program already offers a tangible opportunity to enhance local awareness and action around Healthy Streets, Budapest City aims for the UP2030 LAA process to ignite a wider movement of sustainable urban design for the planning and redesign of each street in the city and beyond.

At the moment, the “core” LAA consists of various departments from City Hall (Climate & Environment, Urban Planning, Citizen Engagement, IT Development) and Budapest Transport Center (BKK) and Budapest Urban Planning Ltd. (BFVT)

One of Budapest’s objectives is to expand and establish a dedicated LAA centered around Healthy Streets - Budapest methodology to involve more stakeholders (NGO’s municipalities, private sector entities, academia, etc.).

Further questions the city will explore and steps it will take:

1. New stakeholder analysis and mapping based on our redefined objectives.
2. Definition of goals, expectations and level/type of involvement of different stakeholders.
3. Allocating stakeholders into different groups ("core", "extended", any other if needed) based on their contribution to the objectives (type of LAA involvement).
4. Plan engagement roadmap with different groups of stakeholders.
5. Plan and organise "engagements" according to different groups of stakeholders, integrating with visioning tasks where appropriate.
6. Organise kick-off meeting with extended LAA and plan other engagement events.

An extensive needs analysis process

The needs analysis process in Budapest involved identifying key needs and barriers through a workshop with relevant stakeholders in city administration. The findings emphasised the necessity for improved coordination and communication within city projects and the municipality. To address these issues, a high-level coordinative body or platform is needed to maximise the impacts of climate action projects.

Participants also highlighted variations in digital literacy across municipal departments. Addressing the needs for enhanced digital literacy and cross-departmental collaboration could be achieved through the development of a common data strategy spanning the entire municipality. This strategy could also encompass the need for an implementation and monitoring system with shared KPIs. High-level coordination could further fulfil the city's requirements for shared communication channels to educate residents and foster community ownership of projects.

Community building was recognised as underdeveloped, with workshop participants calling for formal mechanisms for engagement, inclusion, and capacity building. Facilitating these efforts requires the development of functioning legal frameworks to enable collaboration between city hall, districts, and industries - for instance through increased involvement of local SMEs in city projects.

Broad needs identified also include increased funding, especially for innovation, which could be sourced from new funding channels and revenue recovery.

However, further insights are necessary to understand the city's needs and barriers in more detail. The alignment of the city's interests with UP2030 goals, like 'net-zero, resilient, just transition,' needs clarification. The perceived shortage of technical input from municipal staff indicates a need for more active involvement and expertise from these stakeholders in planning and implementation.

The unique structure of Budapest's pilot project presents challenges for widening engagement at this stage, although, through a review of their engagement approach, city has recognised the need to include a more representative range of perspectives. In the next steps, the city plans to define follow-up engagement activities to ensure broader stakeholder involvement and comprehensive, contextualised needs. As the city aims to organize a funding call for districts within the Healthy Cities Initiative in April 2024, UP2030 can assist in shaping the funding call elements.

Therefore, engagement will not initially widen through direct activities between the city municipality and residents or community groups. Instead, additional engagement will occur with municipal staff, trained and rewarded for emphasizing community engagement in their Healthy Streets tender bids. The draft of the funding call specifies a mandatory requirement of community planning and engagement and allows a

proportion of the budget for this. Potentially, capacity building sessions will be held for the districts on how to engage communities in the co-design which could include surveys, focus groups and meetings.

Direct community engagement will commence in the later stages of the project, around autumn 2024, following the successful award of tenders, potentially through surveys and focus groups.

Further reading:

- [Final UP2030 - 1st workshop reporting Budapest.docx](#)
- [Challenges and barriers identified.xlsx](#)
- [Budapest 1st review.docx](#)

Engagement activities so far

- So far only the initial ('core') LAA has participated in the first workshop and planning of the Healthy Streets application ToR.
- During the past months Budapest has held several workshops (5) with potential applicants (district municipalities and professionals) on Budapest call for application and general methodology.
- Budapest also holds in person site visits and consultations with interested municipalities about project ideas.
- A dedicated email address is set up and in operation for district inquiries, project team is formed in the city hall (up2030@budapest.hu).

Districts have shown a great interest in obtaining funding through the call for application. The evaluation framework of the Healthy Streets proposal requires the definition of project content to be carried out in collaboration with the local community, such as preliminary needs assessment, public idea submissions, audience voting in competitions, and participatory planning. A partnership plan is required to be prepared by municipalities that includes the project's most important elements related to involvement of civic society. Based on several discussions there are differences between experiences and knowledge of municipalities in involving local citizens – some have experience and can carry out participatory planning involving local citizens, whereas others indicated that they need support from Budapest in this area.

Working together with tools and services

As part of the UP2030 project, several tools and services are being offered to the cities by the technical partners. These tools play an important role in how the pilot project evolves and influences the final results of the city's participation in the UP2030 project and beyond. Cities were hence encouraged to reflect on the purpose of using these tools in their process and create principles to guide the pre-selection process.

The evaluation framework of the Healthy Streets proposal sets out that project content must be carried out in collaboration with the local community. For this purpose, it is essential that stakeholder involvement by the municipality is as comprehensive as possible. Hence Budapest has pre-selected tools to:

- Enhance the stakeholder engagement of proposing districts with local communities – mainly carried out by districts

- Involve other stakeholders from the wider community and civil society (e.g. alliance of pedestrians or for people with disability etc.) to participate in HS proposals – jointly carried out by city hall and districts

Since tools implementation also requires capability and resources within the city teams, there is an opportunity to leverage broader learning goals and capacity building of the city team engaged in the project.

With an extensive inventory of tools to choose from, it was important to deploy a clear process to ensure an informed pre-selection process. Budapest followed a step-by-step approach as follows:

1. Internal workshop with city liaison (GGGI) to define objectives and gaps.
2. The tools were first evaluated by the core LAA team members. A shortlist was prepared based on core LAA team feedback.
3. It became clear from the beginning that the Healthy Street initiative supports just and inclusive transition through redesign of public spaces. In addition, UP2030 and Healthy Streets call for application processes had to be aligned. These factors lead the city to prioritize the focus on participatory tools.
4. Call with the TF Implementation and technical partner (September 2023), where the city team discussed the preselected tools that focus on stakeholder engagement activities in the framework of Healthy Streets applications.

Based on the redefined objectives, a further refinement of the preselected tools occurred. The city of Budapest decided to focus on tools that support (i) HS call for application implementation and (ii) HS methodology upscaling:

- HS applications will be planned and implemented by local municipalities assisted by UP2030 participatory tools (i)
- Creation of 'LAA' for Budapest Healthy Streets to disseminate the methodology, creation of discourse, and the establishment of Healthy Streets knowledge center, active dissemination of methodology (ii)
- Enhance Budapest citizens' public discourse on public health of their streets and public spaces, awareness raising and building public expectations (ii)
- Testing community mapping instruments in line with the Healthy Street approach to gather public opinion, define potential projects and development targets, and raise awareness. (i) (ii)

During the General Assembly in November 2023, the city had an opportunity to interact with the tool providers in order to further streamline the selection and explore which tool would be best suited to begin working with. As part of the process undertaken by the Implementation Taskforce, cities will first make a final selection of the tools, in alignment with the Visioning process, and thereafter build “implementation pathways” that map how a tool or selection of tools will be integrated in the pilot’s process in UP2030.

The city and liaison will hold further discussions with the tool owners in December 2023, to understand their applicability, implementation needs, expected outcomes, based on which the city will make a final selection during the visioning process. The following tools were preselected:

- LAA - ICATALIST
- Community Mapping – MfC
- Citizen Voice (and optionally Spatail Justice Benchmarking) - TU Delft
- Storytelling for Participatory Exchange - ISOCARP
- Urban Design Manual for Child and Youth Friendly Cities - Design Clips
- Transformative Governance Instruments - Adelphi

Visioning phase

The foundations for the co-visioning phase were laid through a series of preparatory actions. These included a detailed identification of the existing barriers and needs of applying districts, and the articulation of specific objectives that had been outlined previously. These elements were analysed in order to tailor the methodology that would guide the co-design of the shared vision for Budapest's Healthy Streets programme. The details of the co-visioning and the tailored recommendation for adapting the process have been developed by the technical partners and are currently being evaluated by the Lisbon liaisons and the project team in order to provide a more specific and contextualised approach.

The co-visioning phase is anchored on a needs assessment conducted under T2.3 and previously identified objectives. This information provided a foundation for identifying specific needs and goals for Healthy Streets programme as a pilot project within UP2030. These elements were used to tailor a methodology to guide the co-design of a shared vision for the pilot. The detailed steps of the co-visioning with recommendations tailored to the context have been developed by the technical partners and are currently being evaluated by Budapest's team. Co-design approach is a core to UP2030 process, therefore cities and its stakeholders input for designing co-visioning process enables to develop a more specific and contextualised approach to engagement.

City is currently evaluating the feasibility of the proposal and indicating the timeline for the next steps to be taken under the co-visioning phases.

[the process diagram will be updated once the city has finalised its stakeholder mapping and engagement roadmap with LAA]

Budapest

As part of the preparatory activities, the city has started to validate and refine the identified key objectives. During the first year of the project, the understanding of goals and needs has evolved and therefore the revision of the aspirations plays an important role for the upcoming engagement activities in co-designing the vision. With a support of the city’s liaisons the goal is to first validate the objectives and identify, whether the objective is most relevant to the short term, medium term, or long-term goals.

Our list of objectives defined in November:

Overarching upscaling vision

Healthy Streets	#	Célok	Objectives	New objective?	ST (0-1 year)	MT (1-5 years)	LT (5+ years)
UPSCALE METHODOLOGY	1	Egészséges Utcák szempontrendszerét ismerje és alkalmazza a szakma (építészek, tervezők, várostervezők) a közterületeket érintő város- és ingatlanfejlesztési gyakorlatban.	Urban development professionals (architects, designers, urban planners, engineers) learn and apply extensively Budapest's Healthy Street approach in practice in public space development projects.	New		X	
	2	A Budapesti Egészséges Utcák szövetségének „LAA” létrehozása a módszertan terjesztéséhez és adaptálásához, professzionális diszkurzus megteremtéséhez, tudásközpont létrehozásához, módszertan aktív terjesztéséhez.	Creation of 'LAA' for Budapest Healthy Streets to disseminate and adapt the methodology, creation of professional discourse, the establishment of Healthy Streets knowledge center, and active dissemination of the methodology.	New	X		
	3	Budapestiek beszéljenek, gondolkodjanak arról, hogy az utcájuk, lakóhelyük mennyire „egészséges”, alakuljon ki ezzel kapcsolatos elvárás a budapestiekben.	Enhance Budapest citizens' public discourse on the public health of their streets and public spaces, awareness raising and building public expectations.	New		X	
	4	Az Egészséges Utcákkal kapcsolatos közösségi térképezési eszközök tesztelése közvélemény-kutatáshoz, lehetséges projektek és fejlesztési célok meghatározásához, valamint a tudatosság növelése érdekében.	Testing community mapping instruments in line with the Healthy Street approach to gather public opinion, define potential projects and development targets, and raise awareness.	New	X		
	5	Készítsünk útmutatókat, szabványokat a saját cégeinknek, kerületeknek és érintett tervezőknek.	Create guides and standards for our own companies, districts and the planners involved.	New		X	
	6	Piaci és egyéb szereplők bevonása, akik (anyagilag is) érdekeltek és változás a motorjai lehetnek.	Involvement of market players who are (financially) interested and can be the drivers of change.	New	X		
FUNDING APPLICATION	7	Társadalmasítás támogatása a kerületeken keresztül (helyi lakosok bevonása) a tervezésbe és megvalósításba.	Supporting the involvement of local citizens through the districts in the planning and implementation.	-	X		
	8	Egészséges Utcák pályázat megvalósítása, nyertes projektek implementációja.	Implement Healthy Streets projects across Budapest (winning proposals).	-		X	

Additionally, during the General Assembly meeting in Lisbon, in 2023 city's representatives with a support of liaison, has done a reflection on the alignment between the identified objectives and the pilot context. This exercise helped to specify goals that been identified in the first months of the project and see how they align with project pillars. The workshop results can be found [here](#). The activity helped to identify how certain objectives can be translated into preliminary actions and how UP2030 can support the city and the ongoing programme. (e.g. Objective: Enhance Budapest citizens' public discourse on public health of their streets and public spaces, awareness raising and building public expectations. Suggestion: Involve local citizens by using suggested tools from technical partners, such as Citizens Voice tool & Urban Youth tool)

In the coming weeks, the city will go through a series of activities to define engagement strategies that will be embedded in the Healthy Streets programme, enriching it with goals for a resilient, equitable and carbon neutral future.

Granollers city – Granollers – Granollers Storyline

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Context and background of the Granollers Pilot

Granollers city with a population of 61.983 inhabitants in 2022, is located in the Besòs river basin (Congost river sub-basin), in the metropolitan region of Barcelona.

Granollers' economy is based on industrial and commercial sectors but it conserves agricultural lands and an agroforestry landscape. Granollers is the main city of the Vallès Oriental County.

Granollers, as a pilot city, will focus its interventions in sector 129-La Bòbila around the Rail Station towards creating a low carbon district.

Through the proposed work of UP2030, Granollers and its stakeholders will co-create visions and roadmaps to advance the city's mitigation agenda and deliver on justice, resilience and sustainability. In this context, the city will identify effective measures towards reducing its greenhouse gas emissions, then review the human and financial resources to be committed

toward implementation, before proceeding to deployment both during and after the project’s completion.

History

Granollers case study is focused on La Bòbila sector, a neighbourhood pending to be developed. One of the historic causes because this sector has not been developed yet is the presence of the infrastructural barrier: the railway tracks and station for passengers and goods.

<p>Aerial view of Granollers. La Bòbila sector circled in yellow, 1956</p>	<p>Aerial view of Granollers, La Bòbila sector circled in yellow, 2022</p>

The Metropolitan Territorial Plan of Barcelona (PTMB, 2010) presents Granollers as an urban area with strong structural relation with Barcelona, in terms of labour market, public facilities, services and nodes of transport network. Granollers has already started working towards climate neutrality through its commitment to the Covenant of Mayors. The city is also developing Low Emission Zones, safe and healthy school environments and other actions that facilitate traffic calming and the recovery of the pedestrian public spaces. The **Strategic Plan of Granollers by 2030** develops the criteria to transform the area around Granollers Centre railway station into a liveable neighbourhood, resilient to climate change. The planned new metropolitan development around the railway station, will integrate tertiary uses with public facilities and open spaces together with a new mobility system.

<p>Scope of Granollers' pilot case: developable sector 129-La Bòbila (<i>Urban Master Plan, 2012</i>)</p>	<p>Granollers Centre railway station area (circled in blue); discontinuous developable sector 129-La Bòbila (in yellow); freight railway station pending to be moved out of Granollers municipality (in red)</p>

Spatial characteristics of the neighbourhood

La Bòbila sector is an area which is pending to be developed, just behind the existing the central and the freight railway station, located between the dense urban area (at West) and a small mountain range (at East). The sector pending to be developed behind this front plane is called urban sector 129-La Bòbila. Surrounding this sector there are also rural spaces, forests, roads and other Granollers' neighbourhoods well consolidated (Font Verda, Tres Torres and Sant Miquel).

N-S view of the urbanizable sector 129-La Bòbila.

Social characteristics of Granollers

Regarding demography data in Granollers we can remark that population density is 4.168,3 inhabitants per square km with gender parity. Regarding education data, 56,4% of inhabitants is over secondary education.

Granollers has several thematic groups of organized civil society, which are expected to collaborate in the UP2030 project as stakeholders through the participation in the workshops.

W-E view of the urbanizable sector 129-La Bòbila.

Challenges and opportunities

Granollers would like to achieve, through UP2030 project, the definition of a strategy to implement a neighborhood intervention of developable sector 129-La Bòbila, to achieve the urban prosperity of this new area at the same time it gets a better adaptation to climate change effects putting people at center and leaving nobody behind. As a result of the development of the pilot case, it is also expected the upgrading of municipal skills in the creation of climate neutral neighborhoods, that can be replicated in other areas in the existing intermunicipal urban continuum of Granollers.

Proposed activities to be done after the project will be:

- . Development of other climate-neutral neighborhoods in the city by 2030, addressing the challenges of climate change and resilience, therefore addressing SDGs 11 and SDGs 13.
- . Creation of a citizen laboratory to urban development for prosperity (CityLab for u-prosperity): a space to facilitate the participatory processes that accompany specific projects or policies to turn them into spaces for co-design, co-management and the production of policies and knowledge.
- . Implementation of tender processes/calls for urban innovation projects with the aim of providing financial and technical support for the implementation of projects that respond to the urban challenges, and that have a real impact on people's quality of life, based on the great global challenges (fair and inclusive digital transition, urban sustainability, etc.). Selected projects must represent a high impact in terms of measurable indicators and promoted from the bottom up. Projects must be executable on time, scalable and sustainable.

The challenges expected to achieve within UP2030 in Granollers are:

- Climate neutrality in neighbourhoods
- Connection with the rest of the city neighbourhoods within green axis
- Remove infrastructural barriers, specially railway of La Bòbila sector or at least provide permeability in order to connect the new sector with the rest of the consolidated city
- Provide new developed sectors within equipment's such as healthcare, education, sports, welfare, etc.

Current approach and actions

Roadmap for climate neutrality in development or renovation of city areas:

To date Granollers has already begun the process to adapt to new commitments of the **Covenant of Mayors** by 2030 and 2050 (to achieve at a municipal scale the 55% reduction in GHG emissions and the climate neutrality, respectively). Within the framework of the Spanish Urban Agency, city councils must launch its own action plans to meet the challenges of cities. In the case of Granollers

it will be conveyed through the Municipal Strategic Plan by 2030, which will define the city's missions and the projects to meet its challenges.

Some of these initiatives that are on track of the main city challenges are: the implementation of several **projects on energy efficiency and renewable energies in public buildings and facilities**; the municipal master plan to create a **Low Emission Zone (ZBE)** where the circulation of the most polluting vehicles is restricted, and its integration in the Barcelona' ZBE of more than 95 km² of surface. The **Safe and Healthy School Environments** project has been launched within the course 2021-2022, with the aim of protecting the children by improving safety and reducing pollution around the schools. The actions respond to the traffic calming strategy and the recovery of the pedestrian public space to implement the future ZBE.

Also the **re-naturalization project** to multiply the urban green infrastructure of Granollers, applying the superblock methodology (**CoCoNat25 project, 2021**); the participatory process to co-create the **Municipal Strategic Plan** up to 2030 (2021-2022); the development of a renovation and energy service to face energy poverty, integrated in the **Municipal Housing Office (2022)**; the study to localization, evaluation and adaptation of **school environments in climatic refuge spaces**, the prioritization index of school environments in Granollers and a methodological guide for its calculation (Barcelona Provincial Council and ISGlobal); the **Map of the city's heat island** and the **software of the Local Climate Zones** developed by the Cartographic and Geological Institute of Catalonia, which allows to city council to assess the impacts of changes in urbanization models and on the roofs of the buildings of the city; the networking and co-creation of transformative projects, through participation in **international projects such as THERMOS H2020** to map annual energy and water consumption data and to make heat network planning faster, more efficient, and more cost effective with an open-source software; **INTERLACE-H2020** to restore, rehabilitate and connect nature, places and people, or **EYES** and **CLIMATUBERS-Erasmus⁺** to involve local communities in learning about the effects of climate change in the city and, by at the same time, imagine and engage in the co-creation of possible solutions, (<https://www.granollers.cat/ajuntament/projectes-europeus>).

Previous experience in projects on the challenges is the implementation of 5 strategies for territorial and landscape integration in the development of planning of an industrial sector in Granollers, consisting in adding to the rules of **Urban Master Plan** several criteria to agricultural landscape protection, considering road matrix, proposing trees plantations for natural shielding, defining social uses for the area.

Actions within master plan of Granollers

Areas of transformation to new technologies, residential sector of "La Bòbila" (S-129) it is proposed, on the one hand, due to the need to overcome the railway barrier and the urban scar it currently causes, promoting new transversal routes and strengthening the north-south axis, extension from Muntanya promenade; and on the other hand to take advantage of the strategic

position of this site, next to the train station and the link with the South roundabout. This proper location factor must be used to create a residential area with an important presence of services and offices, as well as the essential provision of a large car park. The proposal will include a large part of the criteria provided in the preliminary urban planning study for the area around the railway line, drawn up in March 2002. According to the forecasts made, it could accommodate around 1500 homes, and a roof surface of services and new technologies (TIC) of around 20.000 m². On the other hand, it would mean obtaining about 10 Ha of open spaces that would be located on the ridge line of the eastern mountain range, in order to give it continuity and preserve its landscape values.

Free spaces: The treatment of free spaces must go in two directions. On the one hand continue with the successful creation of urban parks arranged mainly along the stream or on the ridges, and on the other hand the small free spaces, more detailed, distributed throughout the city and closer to housing. The latter, which are largely obtained from the sale of action units on urban land, must be strategically placed on the main pedestrian routes.

Parks on the Llevant mount, there are two large pieces of open space joined by the green itinerary of the Llevant mount. This is the park on the ridge of the La Bòbila sector, between the southern roundabout and the hotel on the La Roca road; and on the other hand, the Font Verda parks and the new park on the hill of Torre del Pinós.

Transformation of the east area of the railway station, La Bòbila, into residential and tertiary to improve the connectivity of the urban area between the railway and La Roca del Vallès. Within La Bòbila sector is planned to build educational equipment such as a nursery school and a primary school.

Regarding connections with intermunicipal roads with internal streets it is planned to connect from south to north with Muntanya promenade across new sector La Bòbila. One of the barriers to solve is railways pass, specially for East-Weast connection, the possible solution planned is an underpass.

For public services such as parking areas, there is planned an intermodal area for public transport and parking area on the edge of new sector la Bòbila (between Josep Umbert and Santa Quitèria streets). Also is planned a new parking area next to the railways in La Bòbila area.

Planned solutions for pedestrians within new sector are the construction of passes over the railways and roads.

Railway coverage project:

Railways coverage, 356 meters along during 2023, between Josep Umbert and Agustí Vinyamata streets. This project is done for the integration of the network railway in Granollers. This step is the first to succeed towards the coverage of the train tracks became a reality, which at the same time is a historical vindication of the city.

Thus, it is planned to cover 356 meters of track, and join, with a green promenade, of the Font Verda neighbourhood and the Torras Villa park and it also will be a connection of La Bòbila sector within the consolidated city. With this, the city will have of a new area of public space and green area of more than 8.000 square meters.

In addition, it is expected that in two years it will also be a reality the transfer of the current station of goods in La Llagosta.

N-S view of the project to cover the train tracks between Josep Umbert and Agustí Vinyamata streets

CoCoNat2025 project

CONNECTA CONGOST NATURA 2025 (CoCoNat25) project promotes more sustainable and healthy ways of life and behaviour. The super blocks project favours the most sustainable means of transport by avoiding impacts on the environment (reduction of energy consumption, CO2 emissions, environmental pollution, noise, etc.) and promoting local commerce which, with the implementation of the super blocks, is always increased.

The project also strengthens and expands the Green Infrastructure System throughout the city, guaranteeing an equitable distribution of urban greenery (parks, tree-lined walks, orchards) that promotes leisure activities close to nature in contact with nature, generating well-being and improving the quality of life for all citizens.

Green infrastructure is expected that with UP2030 project helps to connect consolidated city towards new sector development, La Bòbila, by giving continuity to the super blocks established in the CoCoNat project as its represented in the following pictures:

Urban renewal of Sant Esteve Avenue project (Next Generation Funds):

Within framework of Next Generation Granollers is preparing urban renewal of Sant Esteve Avenue. The project, among other actions, plans to reduce the space of the motorized vehicle in favour of other more sustainable modes of transport, such as walking and cycling. It is also planned to add urban green space to improve the quality of the city. Avinguda Sant Esteve is located next to the Bòbila sector, linking this sector with the center of the city of Granollers.

Improvements in the signalling of cycling itineraries:

Other planned projects that constitute an improvement in the connectivity of the new sector are the signalling of itineraries for pedestrians and bicycles that communicate with other neighbourhoods of the city and neighbouring municipalities such as the municipality of Vilanova del Vallès.

Needs and aspirations

Granollers will focus its interventions in sector 129-La Bòbila around the Rail Station towards those main objectives in this project:

- i) Design of a climate-neutral, liveable and resilient neighbourhood in La Bòbila sector

Key secondary targets:

- ii) Creation of a citizen laboratory focused on the urban transformation of the city
- iii) Definition of the policy recommendations to achieve a climate-neutral, liveable and resilient neighbourhood in La Bòbila sector
- iv) Implementation of cross cutting, climate mitigation/adaptation and spatial justice tools to assess: a. the future urban planning of La Bòbila sector; b. the creation of a public node for the modal interchange, that links and integrates the railway and intercity buses stations

Key targets and challenges in the medium term:

- i) Integration of the policy recommendations in tender processes/calls for urban transformation/renovation projects
- v) Development of other climate-neutral areas in the city by 2030 (urban renovation areas)

- i) Proposal for connect the urban green grid defined by CoCoNat25 and other transformation projects with the system of open spaces of East mountain range, agriculture and fluvial areas, through the green infrastructure of La Bòbila sector.

People, Partners, Organisations and more

Granollers has a rich diversity of organized civil society, different organizations are used to participate in several projects which has been held in the city. In fact, this is going to be the initial point to map stakeholders with UP2030 projects (<https://participa311-granollers.diba.cat/>).

By now it is not possible to engage anybody from the neighbourhood, and it is going to be proposed to engage La Bòbila neighbours. For the beginning the main actors that need to be engaged to reach the approach and outputs for the pilot are the representatives of the City Council; the municipal technicians of main thematic areas involved (urban planning, environment-green infrastructure, mobility, public health, social welfare, participation, culture); the neighbourhood associations around the area (Font Verda, Can Bassa, Sant Miquel and Tres Torres); the representatives of some participatory bodies of the city (as organized civil society¹); local NGOs' or stakeholders identified to face the climate crisis (from other previous and simultaneous EU projects as Climatubers, INTERLACE, CoCoNat25; transport operating companies in Granollers: bus, railway, other; other services and suppliers' companies: electricity, gas, water.

¹ Environmental and Sustainability Advisory Council (CAMS), Health Council, Mobility Council, Granollers Youth Forum (L'Arrel), Urban Advisory Council, Economic and Social Council and the Trade and Tourism Forum, Granollers gender equality table, Children's council.

Activities undertaken as part of UP2030

Setting up of Learning Action Alliance

The Learning and Action Alliance (LAAs) of Granollers was kicked off in April 2023 and began with a stakeholder mapping for the La Bòbila pilot area. To maximize participation, stakeholders were subdivided between internal (City Hall) and external stakeholders.

- [UP2030 Stakeholder list and matrix Granollers.xlsx](#)

To get more in-depth answers following the Needs workshops, Granollers conducted 13 interviews within the city administration between M3 and M6. In this phase, the city also began to establish contact with new stakeholders that were identified by the participants of the first workshop. Finally, the feedback from the 1st workshop was transferred to all participants (old and new), as well as a call-up for the Vision workshop of month 13.

As for the next steps, Granollers seeks to reach out to additional stakeholders, to widen the stakeholder representation and achieve greater consensus. While there is no core group for this LAA, Granollers is seeing high levels of commitment from the stakeholders it has engaged so far. Reflecting this, the city plans to organize a Local Info Day during the Action phase of the project.

An extensive needs analysis process

Granollers implemented its needs workshop in two parts, focusing on internal municipal stakeholders and external city-wide stakeholders. In the first part, attendees emphasised defining needs in urban governance dimensions and adopting a systemic approach that prioritises people in decision-making.

There was a consensus that plans and projects must be aligned through a systemic approach putting people at the centre of decisions. The need for specific aims targeted at the neighbourhood scale was discussed, along with the need for maintenance and management resources to involve all departments in project execution. Coordination across various disciplines and the importance of clear political and technical guidelines were highlighted. The workshop identified the private sector as a potential collaborator, leveraging resources and knowledge for innovation through investment.

However, it was acknowledged that the public sector lacks the resources to drive this collaboration, necessitating checks and balances for public-private partnerships such as clear regulations and oversight through EU funding bodies. Internal knowledge could be developed further, particularly in the understanding of climate neutrality and just transition concepts. Stakeholders called for resources to support upskilling and training staff and mechanisms for peer learning that disseminate effective strategies throughout the municipality.

Technical needs related to data management, sharing, and cross-analysis, requiring investment in IT solutions and staff understanding of effective data usage. Community engagement was recognised as crucial but requiring more investment of time and planning to produce meaningful responses. There could also be an examination of current participatory bodies and communication mechanisms as there is a perception that the community may lack trust in the local government. Stakeholders found that clear planning and execution of projects could help improve the city's public perception.

Beyond the two workshops in Granollers, engagement has refined and validated some insights. 13 additional interviews were conducted and produced more specific needs and barriers. Practical ones include the need for more green spaces that serve multiple purposes as climate shelters, health spaces, and opportunities to enjoy nature. Desired changes to mobility patterns may be induced through

dissuasive integrated parking, access restrictions on private vehicles, along with improvements in pedestrian and bike infrastructure. On a strategic level, topography and infrastructural limitations will pose a challenge for working towards universal accessibility of buildings. Housing is also a sector that needs to be looked at further.

The next stage of Granollers will target mapped stakeholders who were unable to attend the first round of activities. The city's online public participation forum has also been set up with a dedicated UP2030 page which currently hosts updates on the project and the results of engagement so far and holds a lot of potential to be expanded in its use to get responsive active engagement from residents.

Further reading:

- [1stWorkshop external stakeholders 20230606](#)
- [1stWorkshop internal stakeholders 20230329](#)
- [1stWS results internalstakeholders 29032023](#)
- [1st Engagement Review - Granollers.docx](#)

Working together with tools and services

As part of the UP2030 project, several tools and services are being offered to the cities by the technical partners. These tools play an important role in how the pilot project evolves and influences the final results of the city's participation in the UP2030 project and beyond. Cities were hence encouraged to reflect on the purpose of using these tools in their process and create principles to guide the pre-selection process. Granollers sees the opportunity in UP2030 to test and obtain scenarios for the future development of the neighborhood and to select which of these scenarios achieve the three objectives defined for the pilot.

From the kick-off meeting in February 2023 until November 2023, Granollers team evaluated the tools presented by the consortium. The idea was to select tools able to meet different objectives in the pilot area, both regarding mitigation and adaptation. Another aspect considered was the need to deploy a cross-cutting methodology in order to involve civil society in the process. As part of the pre-selection process carried on throughout the year (led by the Implementation Task Force), Granollers has specified the following thematic areas for tools integration:

- Focus on interventions for climate neutrality and resilience (blue/green infrastructure, energy) and social inclusion
- Optimize the use of resources and promote systemic approach

Following the logic above, Granollers expressed interest in the application of tools which support the development and visualization of multiple scenarios in order to explore alternative design options and potential adjustments to the original master plan of the area. Considering the early stage of the project (most of the area is not developed yet) and that the municipality needs to complete additional spatial analysis, the most suitable tool was the Data driven geospatial analysis and parametric design (provided by TSPA). The objective is to support local decision-makers with design-oriented evaluations, by visualizing multiple options with different parameters (i.e., variation in density, orientation, green areas etc.). The exploration of alternative options might lead the municipality to formulate some changes in the original master plan (always in accordance with the existing local regulations). The tool could also support a wider

engagement process, where different stakeholders can test different scenarios. In addition, AQUATEC will support Granollers as liaison partners and will make use of the RESCCUE platform to assess different climate adaptation measures based on the hazards faced by the city and, then, perform a cost-benefits analysis. The Learning Action Alliance in Granollers will remain active and support the engagement process in the city, aiming to achieve a broader consensus among stakeholders around the development of La Bòbila.

During the General Assembly in November 2023, the city had an opportunity to interact with the tool providers in order to further streamline the selection and explore which tool would be best suited to begin working with. Granollers team has decided to incorporate GGI tools (Green Economy Model, and Climate PRIO Tool) to quantify cost-benefits of the implementation of actions in the new sector of La Bòbila. Furthermore, the municipality is currently exploring the opportunity to make use of the as well as Buro Happold’s tool for climate proofing (Quick checks on climate impacts).

The upcoming visioning phase

The co-visioning phase for La Bòbila district's transformation is based on a needs assessment conducted in Task 2.3 and objectives set in the UP2030 initiative. This phase uses the gathered information to pinpoint specific needs and goals tailored to La Bòbila’s unique context and challenges. The methodology for co-designing a shared vision has been customized to the district pilot, drawing on multiple input sources and previous activities the City of Granollers has done both during and prior to the UP2030 process.

The technical partners have developed a detailed co-visioning process, incorporating recommendations specifically for La Bòbila. This process has been evaluated by the city. Co-design, a central approach in UP2030, involves cities and stakeholders in crafting the co-visioning process. This collaboration ensures a more targeted and context-sensitive approach to engagement. The intention is to utilise wide stakeholder engagement approaches co-design methods developed by the technical partners in order to develop a clear vision for the future of the site, and a set of adaptive implementation pathways for Granollers to navigate the UP2030 process and beyond.

Currently, Granollers is honing the details of this process, and shaping it to their specific challenges. The city has established a timeline for the upcoming steps in the co-visioning phases.

Granollers

Granollers’ Co-visioning Timeline: [\[Guide to Co-visioning. Visioning Roadmap\]](#)

Granollers has already completed the first stage of the Co-visioning, by validating and revising their objectives. The objectives were taken from the various processes in the first year of the UP2030 process. These were then shared with the city and its liaison and subsequently refined in the GA co-visioning workshop in Lisbon. Furthermore, the objectives developed in the workshop were validated at the end of November 2023.

The validated objectives for the co-visioning process contribute to the three pillars in a variety of ways, described as follows: The city wants to design La Bòbila to be a net-zero emissions neighbourhood. It intends to implement cross-cutting climate mitigation and spatial justice tools to assess future urban planning. From a resilience perspective, the aim is to balance between grey and blue/green infrastructure. Regarding the just transition, contributing objectives include the creation of a citizen laboratory focused on the urban transformation of the city, maintaining inclusion and equity, and preventing gentrification. Holistically, Granollers wants to define policy recommendations to achieve climate neutrality, resilience, and liveability in La Bòbila, and eventually integrate those policy recommendations in tender processes/calls for urban transformation/renovation projects in the development of the neighbourhood and elsewhere. Development of other climate-neutral areas in the city by 2030 (urban renovation areas); Proposal for connect the urban green grid defined by CoCoNat25 and other transformation projects with the system of open spaces of East Mountain range, agriculture, and fluvial areas through the green infrastructure of La Bòbila sector.

From these objectives, Granollers has also worked on the 'third' stage of the visioning process, which is defining explicit visions along the lines of the UP2030 Pillars of Carbon Neutrality, Resilience, and the Just Transition. In early 2023, the city presented preliminary urban assessments during the first engagement workshop. This will serve as a reference going into the future spatial analysis, which will be a component of the development and design of the Urban Master Plan for the district.

Because one of the key objectives is the eventual development of the Master Plan for the La Bòbila, which is in a sense a vision itself, the city wants to use some pre-selected tools to aid in the co-design process. Specifically, the city intends to utilise a parametric design tool from one of its technical partners (TSPA) to develop the master plan in line with their identified indicators, and to allow for rapid and flexible adjustment. In making use of this type of planning tool, it is hoped that such a rapid iterative design methodology can allow for feedback loops and engagement of stakeholders in the design process. The specifics of how this tool will be leveraged will be determined in the next workshop with key stakeholders.

This next workshop is planned for the 24th of January, where the aforementioned will be worked on alongside the definition of the overarching Pilot Vision. To develop this vision, Granollers plans to make use of the common vision method. The process involved is detailed [here](#).

The output of this process will be translated into a vision page, a collection of the validated objectives, pillar visions, and the overall pilot vision.

Reaching into February and March, the development of adaptive pathways will begin by breaking down the objectives into key actions and identifying associated barriers which could stand in the way of implementation. These will be sequenced together to start building preliminary pathways towards developing their vision and key objectives. With the aid of technical partners, Granollers will then filter the actions against the UP2030 benchmarking framework in March and April to further refine the action sequences. Through May and June the technical partners will apply their expertise to identify gaps and risks in the preliminary adaptive pathways, and refine them into drafts of the adaptive pathway pages. Finally, the city tentatively aims for a June 20th deadline for the completion of their adaptive pathways development.

Istanbul – City Storyline

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Context and background of the Istanbul Pilot

History

Throughout history, Istanbul has hosted a dense population due to its geopolitical location and economic, cultural, and touristic benefits. This intense and rapid urbanization has led to an increase in energy demand in the city. Meeting the increasing energy demand with non-renewable energy has led to a significant increase in carbon emissions and the impact of the city on climate change. Istanbul Climate Change Action Plan (ICCAP) has been prepared to develop strategy plans against climate change. In this context, environmentally friendly strategies have been developed to reduce the city's carbon emissions. In order to reduce energy demand and implement energy efficient strategies, there is still a need for tools that will analyze the needs of Istanbul and plans based on analyzes that will spread to the city scale starting from plot areas.

Spatial characteristics of the neighborhood

Istanbul is the most populous city in Turkey and Europe, with a population of over 15.5 million. Istanbul is the world's 14th largest metropolis, with 16 million inhabitants, which keeps increasing daily. Its population has an average annual growth rate of 1.6% between 2010 and 2020. The population of Istanbul

is expected to increase by 22% to 17.9 million in 2030, by 35% to 19.7 million in 2040 and by 46% to 21.3 million in 2050 compared to 2015.

The area of Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality's responsibility encompasses the entire provincial territory, which spans a total area of 5,343 km².

As it lies between the continents of Asia and Europe, Istanbul is well placed geographically to take advantage of its opportunities in not only shipping and trade areas but also touristic and cultural prospects.

Istanbul has a very high urban density due to the dense population leading to high energy demand. Residential buildings constitute a large portion of the building stock, and most of the residentials have mixed usage, including commercial use (market, office, etc.). 95.7% of the Istanbul residential stock has a concrete frame structure with a brick envelope, which consists of a brick exterior wall covered with interior and exterior cement plaster. Old windows were wooden frames; however, after the TSE825 implementation, the windows became PVC frames with double-glazed windows for energy efficiency.

19.6% of the building stock in Istanbul was built in 1960-1980, 50.2% in 1980-2000, and 17.9% after 2000. Most buildings were constructed before the TS825 standard (which came into force in 2008), which results in poor thermal performance and significant carbon emissions. Increasing temperatures with climate change negatively affect the comfort of building users by increasing IOD, especially in buildings with low thermal performance.

Constructions before TS 825

Low thermal properties of construction materials results in poor energy performance and high CO₂ emissions

In İstanbul, building stock, including houses and commercial and public buildings, constitute 58.8% of İstanbul's 2030 potential to reduce greenhouse gas emissions based on energy efficiency-oriented improvements.

Area	5.343 km ²
Density	2.892 per km ²
Green Space	257.452 ha
Population	15.46 million (2019)
Tourists per year	13,9 million
Life Expectancy	77,8 years
Annual average temp (max)	17,7 °C
Hours of sun per year	2.421
Rainfall per year	820 mm
Total GHG emissions	50,9 MtCO ₂ e (2019)
GHG emissions per capita	3,3 tCO ₂ e/capita (2019)

Significant transportation investments, including the new airport, ring roads, highways, and Bosphorus bridges after the 1970s, sparked city growth to the north, that outgrew its ecological and natural bounds resulting in irreversible changes in the macro form of the city. An unsustainable and constrained transportation system has emerged that cannot meet the city's needs for accessibility and mobility because of rapid and unplanned urbanization.

Approximately 15,800 new vehicles appear on Istanbul's roads each month, representing a year-on-year increase of nearly 80%. This corresponds to 191 cars per 1,000 people in Istanbul as of 2020. Failure to develop and implement policies to reduce private vehicles will significantly increase automobile ownership, that is, 39% between 2020-2040. According to this scenario, the traffic congestion problem will continue increasingly. Accordingly, CO₂ emissions caused by motor vehicles increase, reducing air quality and threatening ecology and human health. The growing population and increased car density create the need for parking resulting in the usability of urban open spaces for different purposes (except for parking).

Social characteristics of the neighborhood

Population density of Istanbul is 2.892 people per square kilometer which is a huge number compared to population density of Turkey (102 people per square kilometer). Over 80% of the population in Istanbul is made up of Turkish people, with various ethnic groups making up the remaining 20%. A significant immigrant population from various cities populates Istanbul. Since 1935, the 25-64 age group which represents the working group, has the largest population in Istanbul. 27.49% of the population of Istanbul is between the ages of 0-19, 64.91% is between the ages of 20-64, and 7.61% is aged 65 and over. Older age groups and those with higher socioeconomic positions are clustered along the coast, while younger people and those with lower socioeconomic status are concentrated in outlying areas.

Learn from challenges and see opportunities

By investing in renewable energy sources like solar, the city can move towards a more sustainable future and help mitigate the effects of climate change. The installation of a PV system in a public area can provide clean energy, reduce reliance on fossil fuels, and help meet the city's energy demands without contributing to carbon emissions. Moreover, a PV system can also serve as a charging station for electric mobility, providing a convenient and sustainable way for people to recharge their electric vehicles. As electric vehicles, such as e-scooter or e-bikes become more popular, providing charging infrastructure will be crucial to promote their adoption and reduce emissions from transportation.

In addition to providing electricity to buildings and reducing the need for traditional energy sources, PV systems can play a significant role in promoting e-mobility, particularly for vulnerable groups such as women and young people. The clean energy generated by PV systems can be used to power electronic devices or charge electric bicycles and scooters, offering reliable and sustainable transportation alternatives. This is particularly beneficial for public buildings like schools, hospitals, and government offices, where energy consumption is high.

By emphasizing the importance of safe and accessible e-mobility options, we can empower vulnerable groups and enhance their mobility, reduce their exposure to air pollution, and contribute to their overall well-being. The integration of PV systems and inclusive e-mobility planning and infrastructure can help create a more equitable society, ensuring that everyone has access to the benefits of clean and sustainable transportation options.

Furthermore, a PV system can also be used as a backup power source in the event of an earthquake, providing electricity for communication and other critical functions. This can be particularly important in Istanbul, as it is located in a region with a high risk of seismic activity. Installing a PV system in a public area can also create job opportunities and stimulate the local economy. The installation, operation, and maintenance of the system require specialized skills and knowledge, providing employment opportunities for the local workforce. Additionally, the project's success can attract more investments and businesses interested in sustainable energy practices, contributing to the city's economic growth.

The installation of a PV system in a public area should be part of a broader and more comprehensive sustainability plan for the city. The system should be integrated into the city's overall infrastructure and serve as part of a larger sustainability initiative. To this end, a digital tool should be developed that uses mobility data to model energy efficiency for buildings. This tool can be used to help plan and design the PV system and integrate it with the city's overall energy infrastructure. The data generated by this tool can also be used to optimize the performance of the PV system and identify areas for improvement.

The pilot region for the implementation of the PV system and digital tool is chosen as Kadıköy, which is a district in Istanbul that is vulnerable to seismic activity and has an old building stock that is in need of energy upgrades. By implementing the UP2030 project in Kadıköy, the city can decarbonize its buildings and transportation systems, effectively integrate PV systems into buildings and public spaces, and link this integration with measures to be taken after a potential earthquake. This would include providing shelter for citizens, meeting their energy needs, and offering fast transportation options like e-scooters and e-bikes that can be charged using the PV system. The implementation of renewable energy in this area can also be utilized to meet the energy needs of residential buildings in the district.

Overall, the implementation of a PV system in a public area in Istanbul can provide numerous benefits for the city, including reducing carbon emissions, providing clean energy, creating job opportunities, and stimulating the local economy. The system should be integrated into the city's overall infrastructure and serve as part of a larger sustainability initiative. Pilot region for the implementation of the PV system and

digital tool is chosen as Kadıköy, where it can provide shelter and energy for citizens after a potential earthquake and help meet the energy needs of residential buildings in the district.

Not only for the Kadıköy region but also with 5 UP approach, the developed solutions (UP-Grading) can be prototyped (UP-Scaling) for other regions in İstanbul because the listed challenges for the Kadıköy area is common in most neighborhoods in İstanbul.

High population density and uncontrolled urban sprawl are the major challenges against increasing climate resilience of the built environment. Since İstanbul's problems are getting more and more complex, we need to start from today building a sustainable future where social, economic, and environmental factors are in balance. İstanbul Metropolitan Municipality (IMM) wants to create a sustainable, self-sufficient, and green city that enables citizens to live in better environmental conditions. The main motivation of our climate works is the high amount of young population in the population density.

As shown in the graphs above, energy consumption and transportation are the main sectors that raise greenhouse gas emissions in the city. While modeling the potential of these two sectors on greenhouse gas emissions and climate change, the project aims to provide a new perspective to the city's decision-

makers and contribute to reducing greenhouse gasses by changing the behavior of the city residents and using technology.

Stationary energy covers energy consumption in buildings (residential and commercial). High and intense population and rapidly increasing energy demand necessitate a trend towards renewable and clean energy in cities. Although energy production in buildings is still highly dependent on fossil fuel (highly natural gas in Istanbul), alternative cleaner and greener technologies are being explored and applied in the city.

This project will help us to evaluate the energy potential of buildings in the pilot region, Kadıköy, and the integration of stationary energy with the mobility/transportation systems. With the project, it will be possible to model the energy potential of the efficient use of the entire energy system of the buildings, photovoltaic integration, facade improvement, user-related behavior improvements, and the transfer of this potential to urban transportation. Environmentally friendly technology solutions will be a part of the mitigation system of greenhouse gas emissions over the city.

Micro mobility is a good and environmentally friendly alternative for transportation options. In Turkey, there is 12.9 million young population between the ages of 15-24, and 2.3 million of them live in Istanbul. That means 15% of the population of İstanbul is young people who prefer using mechanical and electrified bicycles. Although topographical conditions such as sloping and hilly structures of the city can intimidate mechanical bicycle users, the e-bike option is much easier and preferable for them.

In İstanbul, car ownership is very low among women, the young, and low-income groups. Women and girls feel insecure and fearful when using public transportation resulting in a limitation of their everyday movement. Woman's movements are significantly affected by factors like where bus stops are located and how well-lit the streets are. Women, youth, and low-income groups experience inequality in transportation accessibility in urban areas. Reducing this segregation requires increased mobility.

Cycling is both a light, cheap, dynamic, and healthy option for users and a transportation option that should be expanded in cities in terms of climate and environment.

So far, in İstanbul, Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality Plan has been prepared and published. The plan was created to support bicycle transportation, which is one of the sustainable transportation modes in Istanbul and to evaluate the existing bicycle infrastructure to increase the rate of use in the city and identify and develop the problems.

Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality company ISPARK, which has implemented bicycle parks to contribute to the development of environmental awareness, has now implemented the "Smart Bicycle Rental System". The stations where citizens can rent and deliver bicycles are shown on the map below.

Current approach and actions

There are various policies and programs for reducing the effects of climate change and for a sustainable Istanbul that can be listed as

1. Member of Global Covenant of Mayors (GCOM)- CDP
2. Deadline 2020 / C40 Cities Climate Leadership Group
 - the goal of making Istanbul a carbon-neutral and resistant city for 2050
3. İstanbul Climate Change Action Plan (CAP)
4. Sustainable Energy And Climate Action Plan (SECAP)- in progress
5. Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan (SUMP)
6. Waste Management Plan- 2050
7. Green City Action Plan (GCAP)- in progress
8. B40 Balkan Cities Network
9. EU Cities Mission-100 Climate Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030
10. EU Adaptation Mission

Towards energy-efficient İstanbul - Needs and aspirations

Based on spatial and social characteristics of İstanbul, several visions and needs are indicated to decrease the effect of climate change and consider the needs of inclusive groups in society. The visions and necessities of the vision can be listed as follows:

- Vision 1: Decarbonisation of buildings and transport systems and the effective integration of photovoltaic systems into the building and urban public spaces
- Vision 2: Inclusive use of transport, which will target 100% renewables-fed e-bikes deployment (note car ownership/use is male-dominated: it is expected that e-bikes will give improved access to women, youngs)
- Vision 3: Measuring social benefits to reduce energy poverty and overheating-related health risks. Furthermore, the digital technologies embedded in the Urban Building/Transport Energy Model (UBTEM) will provide easy-to-explore, open-access data to citizens for well-informed decision-making for all stakeholders.
- Need 1: Necessitate a trend towards renewable and clean energy in İstanbul
- Need 2: Shifting to micro-mobility, electric vehicles (EV), walking and cycling

- Effective integration between clean energy and transportation

People, Partners, Organisations and more

In parallel with the UP2030 project's scope, Istanbul has a diverse population of engaged citizens, IMM internal stakeholders, district municipalities, non-governmental organizations and technology suppliers to support climate change action plans. Some of them and their roles can be listed as

1. Citizens: Engaged citizens in Istanbul can play a crucial role in supporting climate change action plans by taking individual actions to reduce their carbon footprint, such as using e-micro mobility instead of driving etc.
2. IMM internal stakeholders: The Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality (IMM) is a key partner in developing and implementing climate change action plans. Internal stakeholders within the IMM can play a critical role in driving forward UP2030 action initiatives.
3. District municipalities: District municipalities in Istanbul can work together with the IMM to develop and implement climate change action plans at a local level, tailoring initiatives to meet the specific needs of each community.
4. Non-governmental organizations (NGOs): NGOs can play an important role in advocating for needs in Istanbul as defined in Up2030 and supporting community-led initiatives. They can provide expertise on issues related to climate change, engage with local communities, and help to mobilize resources and support.
5. Technology suppliers: Companies that provide technology solutions related to energy efficiency, renewable energy can play a role in supporting climate change action plans in Istanbul. They can offer products or services that help to reduce emissions or increase resilience to climate impacts.
6. Academia: Istanbul's universities and some Technical universities and research institutions can provide expertise and support for climate change action plans, including conducting research, developing tools and methodologies, and providing training and capacity building for stakeholders.
7. Industry associations: Industry associations can work with companies in Istanbul to promote best practices for reducing emissions and increasing sustainability. They can also engage with policymakers and other stakeholders to advocate for policies that support climate action.
8. Media: The media can play a role in raising awareness about climate change, renewable energy and supporting climate action initiatives in Istanbul. They can highlight successful initiatives, report on climate-related news, and help to mobilize public support for climate action.

Activities undertaken as part of UP2030

Setting up of Learning Action Alliance

In Istanbul, the LAA process began in April with an initial stakeholder mapping conducted by GUNAM, the City Liaison partner.

- [UP2030 Stakeholder list and matrix 1st.xlsx](#)

Given the city's size, it soon became clear that Istanbul needed to scale down the project to a district, and the same was done for the approach to the LAA. Around Workshop 1 on Needs, the city decided to focus stakeholder engagement on the Kadikoy pilot area. As was the case for most other cities, the first workshop showed that a sustained engagement process was needed to further refine the decision on the needs. In this light, additional stakeholder engagement was devised, focusing on several core groups, namely:

- Residents/local community
- Women
- Youth
- Local businesses

As part of the LAA process, Istanbul is currently preparing a large survey aiming to collect responses from 150 residents on urban climate change, micro-mobility, and solar panels in buildings. The results of the survey will be utilized to help inform the visioning process.

An extensive needs analysis process

One workshop was held in Istanbul, bringing together a wide range of stakeholders, including representatives from the local government, businesses, community members, and specialists in the fields of renewable energy, urban planning, and transportation. Together, they investigated the city's path to carbon neutrality and identified important needs, barriers, and opportunities.

The structural and legal limitations on the installation of photovoltaic (PV) panels were found to present a major obstacle, particularly in locations where historical buildings are subject to preservation laws. Broadly, the financial and regulatory environment makes it more difficult to develop renewable energy alternatives in Istanbul. Problems with compliance also inhibit progress since they discourage the uptake of renewable energy. This reluctance is exacerbated by high setup costs, which deter stakeholders, particularly households and small businesses, from investing in sustainable practices.

Istanbul presents a distinct mix of transportation-related barriers due to the city's high vehicle population, scarce parking, and lack of well-integrated public transportation. These elements are worsened by its hilly topography, making it difficult to establish the infrastructure needed for the city's proposed micro-mobility solutions. Data scarcity in relation to behavioural and mobility patterns, energy usage, and the efficacy of current actions is another barrier that impedes the implementation of focused transport strategies in Istanbul.

To address these described barriers, the workshop identified some needs and opportunities for change. For instance, to implement the city's micro mobility solutions, there needs to be close integration between all the city's transport infrastructure. This includes integrating new bike and scooter routes with the current vehicle and parking infrastructure, which needs to be facilitated by more robust data collection and sharing systems.

To accelerate PV and thermal insulation uptake, participants suggested they be integrated into upcoming urban redevelopment projects. This would remove some of the onus of uptake from local residents facing financial and regulatory challenges. Incentives and creative financing schemes may also be used to lower initial installation costs for other residents. It was also suggested that battery systems be installed to maximise the utility of renewable energy sources, reducing the risks of an unstable and inflexible energy supply.

Additionally, the current socioeconomic conditions may be capitalised on to incentivise uptake. There is rising awareness of carbon neutrality in the city which, alongside increasing energy prices, could be capitalised on to draw the public's attention to the long-term benefits of adopting renewable and energy-efficient systems - both financial and environmental. Again, data would be needed to support these efforts, specifically to evidence the potential cost savings for households. Such interventions would require a coordinated communication strategy that promotes community cohesion and action through a shared sense of responsibility.

Overarching all areas of discussion is the need for robust legislation and regulatory frameworks that obtain clear targets to track the city's progress.

Looking forward, the city plans to engage community and youth groups to capture needs from a civic stakeholder perspective. Special attention should be given to topics such as heritage and policy constraints, as they present significant challenges to achieving the set goals. The team aims to use the engagement roadmap planning process (M4) as a tool to define these actions further. They have also designed a survey to capture data on awareness of the city's carbon neutral goals as well as use of e-biked and e-scooters and barriers to uptake for PV systems.

Further reading:

- [V2 UP2030 - reflections and takeaways report - 1st workshop - ISTANBUL .docx](#)
- [1st Engagement Review - Istanbul.docx](#)
- @Istanbul: Other documents you want to link here? No, those two links are enough I think.

Intended next steps:

- The intended next steps for Istanbul's UP2030 project encompass a multifaceted approach to address the identified needs, barriers, and opportunities for sustainable urban development. Key initiatives include engaging with community and youth groups to gain valuable civic stakeholder perspectives, with a particular focus on heritage preservation and policy constraints. The city plans to leverage the engagement roadmap planning process (M4) as a strategic tool to further define and refine these actions. Additionally, Istanbul aims to conduct a comprehensive survey to gather data on the level of awareness among its residents regarding the city's carbon neutrality goals. This survey will also assess the utilization of e-bikes and e-scooters, while exploring the impediments to the widespread adoption of photovoltaic systems. In the pursuit of a more sustainable future, Istanbul recognizes the importance of robust legislation and regulatory frameworks, setting clear targets to monitor and track the city's progress towards carbon neutrality. By strategically combining these efforts, Istanbul is poised to take meaningful steps towards achieving its sustainable urban development objectives.
- In addition, for the establishment of LAA, a communication network based on goals will be established with existing stakeholders and an internal mapping will be created to ensure the healthy progress of this communication network. In this way, participation levels can be defined so that existing stakeholders understand our goals correctly and expectations are met at the

highest level. This approach will be integrated with vision tasks and will ensure that different stakeholder groups meet on the same ground.

Working together with tools and services

As part of the UP2030 project, several tools and services are being offered to the cities by the technical partners. These tools play an important role in how the pilot project evolves and influences the final results of the city's participation in the UP2030 project and beyond. Cities were hence encouraged to reflect on the purpose of using these tools in their process and create principles to guide the pre-selection process.

For Istanbul, tools are opportunities for:

- Modelling and analyzing the existing energy performances of buildings
- Developing business models for aligning produced and consumed electricity in buildings and transportation. Calculating the effects of building retrofit scenarios on building energy performances and being able to evaluate the different retrofit scenarios considering building energy performances
- Climate change impact assessment
- Integration of renewable energy with building and e-mobility
- Achieving the net zero building target by performing real-time energy supply-demand analysis and developing strategies for this
- Developing business models for aligning produced and consumed electricity in buildings and transportation.
- Facilitating decision-making processes and guiding actions toward sustainable urban development.
- Supporting the city's participation in the UP2030 project and achieving carbon neutrality goals.
- Creating a data-driven approach to refine energy and mobility strategies.
- Promoting data exchange and collaboration among stakeholders for informed decision-making.
- Ensuring a holistic approach to urban sustainability by addressing building, transportation, and PV-electricity aspects.

As part of the pre-selection process led by the Implementation Taskforce, Istanbul has defined the following areas of scope / thematic areas for tool integration:

- Decarbonisation of Buildings and Transport Systems
- Renewable Energy-Powered E-Bikes Deployment
- measuring social benefits

Since tools implementation also requires capability and resources within the city teams, the following has also been agreed upon as opportunities to leverage for broader learning goals and capacity building of the city team engaged in the project:

- Measuring/assessment tools (especially for emissions and energy consumptions)
- Circular building tools, energy consumption modelling tools, air quality monitoring

Using the logic above, Istanbul has made the following pre-selection of tools:

- UBEM/UBTEM tool (energy consumption modelling tool) tailored to the context of Istanbul
- MIRA Digital Twins Platform - UBEM/UBTEM can generate digital model of Istanbul
- BIM module & building LCA assessment module
- Data driven geospatial analysis and parametric design
- Urban Heat Island Risk Analysis

During the General Assembly in November 2023, the city had an opportunity to interact with the tool providers in order to further streamline the selection and explore which tool would be best suited to begin working with. As part of the process undertaken by the Implementation Taskforce, cities will first make a final selection of the tools, in alignment with the Visioning process, and thereafter build “implementation pathways” that map how a tool or selection of tools will be integrated in the pilot’s process in UP2030.

In the case of Istanbul, the city has already started working with the UBEM/UBTEM Energy consumption modelling tool, and significant progress has already been made. The tool is tailored to Istanbul’s specific context and has been actively employed to assess and model energy consumption patterns within the city. Istanbul’s engagement with this tool reflects the city’s commitment to data-driven decision-making and its dedication to understanding and addressing energy consumption challenges comprehensively. By utilizing the UBEM/UBTEM tool, Istanbul has taken a significant step towards achieving its sustainability goals, particularly in the context of the decarbonization of buildings and transport systems. This proactive approach sets a promising precedent for the city’s continued efforts to leverage tools effectively within the UP2030 project and underscores its commitment to sustainable urban development.

Co-visioning phase

The co-visioning phase is anchored on a needs assessment conducted under T2.3 and previously identified objectives. This information provided a foundation for identifying specific needs and goals for Kadikoy district’s transformation. These elements were analysed to tailor a methodology to guide the co-design of a shared vision for the pilot. The detailed steps of the co-visioning with recommendations tailored to the context have been developed by the technical partners and are currently being evaluated by Istanbul’s team. Co-design approach is a core to UP2030 process, therefore cities and its stakeholders input for designing co-visioning process enables to develop a more specific and contextualised approach to engagement.

City is currently evaluating the feasibility of the proposal and indicating the timeline for the next steps to be taken under the co-visioning phases.

[update the process diagram once it's finalised by the city: [Guide to Co-visioning. Visioning Roadmap](#)]

As part of the preparatory activities that sets the base for the co-visioning (Milestone 1 – Validate Pilot Objectives) city is currently on validating and refined the identified key objectives. During the first year of the project, the understanding of objectives and needs has evolved and therefore the revision of objectives plays an important role for the upcoming engagement activities. With the support of the city liaisons, the activity will help to identify which aspirations are most relevant to the short-, medium- or long-term goals and to validate their relevance. [\(Full document can be found here\)](#). *(provide more detailed description on the outcome once city have completed the exercise)*

In addition, during the General Assembly meeting in Lisbon in 2023, the representatives of the city, with the support of liaison, reflected on the alignment between the identified objectives and the pilot context. This exercise helped to ensure that the objectives are linked to the pilot scale and to further specify them. For example, objective for ‘Measuring Social Benefits’ was further specified that link to pilot can be explored through sustainable energy systems, by decreasing air pollution / climate change related diseases, as well as providing a better access to the energy resources for community. Other example, of how objective for ‘promoting inclusive transport’ is linked with Kadikoy pilot district, was through promoting micro mobility options for youth and students, which also contributes to the decarbonisation goals. The objective was also linked with the thematic pillar of just transition but can contribute to the carbon neutrality goals as well. The full document, revealing how objectives are linked with pilot case, as well as UP2030 project pillars [can be found here](#).

In the coming months, the city will undergo a series of engagement activities to define the vision for a resilient, carbon neutral and just future for Kadikoy pilot and to identify concrete actions and barriers in the light of defining adaptation pathways.

Lisbon – Alvalade neighbourhood “StepUPLxALL” – City Storyline

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Context and background of the Lisbon Pilot

History

Lisbon, capital of Portugal, has a population slightly above half million inhabitants, doubled daily by commuters residing in the metropolitan region. With an area of approximately 100Km², Lisbon is divided into 24 civil parishes. Historically, Lisbon foundation goes back to the Phoenicians and Romans BCE, with remains of different cultures shaping the city. The 1755 earthquake devastated the city and the reconstruction shaped what is now Lisbon downtown.

Alvalade is one of the most recent parishes in Lisbon, following the administrative reorganization of November 8, 2012, which came into force on September 29, 2013. The new parish united the former parishes of Alvalade, Campo Grande and São João de Brito and its history inevitably goes back to the past of these three territories.

Figure 1 – Location of Alvalade civil parish

It was created as a parish in 1852, becoming part of the Municipality of Lisbon in 1885. Associated with the development of the city, it was divided in 1959, giving rise to the parishes of Campo Grande, Alvalade and São João de Brito.

Until the middle of the 20th century, Alvalade was essentially formed by fields, farms and vegetable gardens, used for the nobility's summer moments and, later, as a recreational and sports space for the population. Some of the most important events in the life of the city took place here, such as the cattle fair and the Battle of the Flowers, which took place in Campo Grande.

In the 30s of the 20th century, the parish experienced its period of greatest development, with major architectural projects integrated in the Urbanization Plan for the South Zone of Avenida Alferes Malheiro, of which we can highlight Avenida de Roma, Bairro das Estacas, Bairro of São Miguel, the Towers of Avenida dos Estados Unidos da América and, already in the 1940s, the construction of the Bairro de Alvalade.

Alvalade neighbourhood urban planning and development started in the decade of 1940 (Groer, 1948), until the 1960's. The construction of Alvalade neighbourhood was considered as one of the most important urban projects in Portugal, in the last century.

Figure 2 – Alvalade throughout the 20th century

The construction of the 230-hectare neighbourhood of Alvalade, promoted by the Federation of Pension Funds - Economic Housing, emerged with the assumption outlined in the Urbanization Plan for the South Zone of Avenida Alferes Malheiro, in the 1940s, and continues to this day with the same identity, originality and strategic importance to the city and the intention is keeping up with trends to meet the 2030 urban residence and decarbonization goals.

The original system, structured in 8 neighbourhood units (cells), remains today. It is formed by roads with different degrees of importance, blocks of buildings, meandering through public spaces, vegetable gardens, equipment, and urban furniture. Individually, each cell is organized around structuring equipment such as schools, being equipped with elements of general interest such as large open spaces, markets, church, public service facilities, schools, cinema, sports facilities to serve its population. For access to public services, each neighbourhood unit is served by a parallel network of pedestrian paths that cross the blocks, rationalizing and shortening access routes to equipment in the neighbourhood. To meet up to current requirements in terms of efficiency, reuse, communication, modernization, and response to current climate challenges, the UP2030 project intends to identify key issues in the neighbourhood, the StepUPLxALL, together with generators, facilitators, educators, experimenters of good practices, looking at replicability in other areas (www.monumentos.gov.pt/Site/APP_PagesUser/SIPA.aspx?id=30357).

Figure 3 – Urbanization Plan for the South Zone of Avenida Alferes Malheiro (1940s) (https://c4.quickcachr.fotos.sapo.pt/i/o3712df29/19998581_sPBgf.jpeg)

Figure 4 – Aerial view of Alvalade (1953) (<https://www.jf-alvalade.pt/alvalade/historia/>)

Spatial characteristics of the neighbourhood

Spatially, Alvalade is a mixed-use neighbourhood, showcasing housing, mixed housing and commercial activities, green areas, health and education facilities. The neighbourhood has been shaped by different waves of urbanisation between 1930 and 1960. The Bairro de Alvalade, middle class apartment buildings,

already integrating concepts of the Radburn theory (Clarence Stein and Henri Wright, 1920's) is based on the concept of separating automobile and pedestrian traffic to create a more efficient and safer living environment, creating the idea of a garden neighbourhood units built around a school (Martin, 2001; Salgueiro, 2002).

Figure 5 – Alvalade of today (Aerial view and Av. De Roma | Av. Da Igreja)

As per Lisbon’s Master Plan, the Alvalade neighbourhood is a consolidated urban area, despite including areas classified as Spaces for Special Use of Equipment with Associated Green Areas (*) among others.

Figure 6 – Lisbon MasterPlan | Focus on Alvalade

The entire neighbourhood integrates the current municipal ecological structure.

Figure 7 – Lisbon Ecological Structure | Focus on Alvalade

<https://www.lisboa.pt/cidade/urbanismo/planeamento-urbano/plano-diretor-municipal/antecedentes>

“StepUPLxALL” is the process to apply to Lisbon, starting in Alvalade during the project UP2030, and expanding to other boroughs. It will contribute to accelerating the city’s pathway towards sustainability, to achieve the 2030 carbon targets, with emphasis on valuing the city’s urban resilience process at the neighbourhood level. It’s expected to increase the efficiency level of the life ecosystem and reduce its carbon footprint, by decreasing the water and energy consumption implementing cross cut solutions with several co- benefits, at environmental level (water, air, noise, soil, biodiversity), climate dimension (CO₂ sinks), social level (public health and thermal comfort), economic dimension (enhancement of the territory and reduction of health costs), and others.

Figure 8 – StepUPLxALL intervention scheme

Social characteristics of the neighbourhood

The parish of Alvalade has an area of 5.34 km², representing about 6% of the city's territory. This configuration of the parish brings together in its territory the former parishes of Campo Grande, São João de Brito and Alvalade, in addition to small parcels of territory formerly belonging to the parishes of Marvila and São Domingos de Benfca.

Alvalade is one of the most populous parishes in the city of Lisbon. According to the preliminary results of the 2021 Census, the resident population is of 33,309 individuals (an increase of 4.7% compared to the 2011 Census), where 31,812 individuals were registered, of which 44,9% are men and 55,1% women. In 2021, 2489 buildings corresponding to 18,924 households were registered.

Figure 9 – Map of the resident population by parish

2021	Population (inhabitants)	Population density (N.º/ km ²)	Buildings	Households (Nr.)
Portugal	10343066	112,15	3573416	5981482
Continente	9855909	110,61	3381968	5736759
AM Lisboa	2870208	951,90	452582	1499047
Lisboa	545796	5456,32	49223	320143
Alvalade	33309	6237,64	2489	18924

Figure 10 – Census 2021 population change in percentage by parish

2021	0 - 14 years (%)	15 - 24 years (%)	25 – 64 years (%)	65 + years (%)
Portugal	12,9	10,5	53,2	23,4
Continente	12,8	10,5	53,0	23,7
A M Lisboa	14,3	10,8	53,2	21,6
Lisboa	13,0	10,1	53,5	23,4
Alvalade	13,9	10,0	51,3	24,7

In terms of age groups, the distribution in the parish of Alvalade is very similar to the city of Lisbon, with a relatively aged population with 76% over the age of 25 and 24.7% over 65, which compares to the numbers at national level.

Figure 10 – Census 2021 age distribution by sex and age group (Alvalade)

In terms of education of the employed population, Alvalade has a average high level of education.

Figure 11 – Census 2021 distribution education level of the employed population (Alvalade)

The parish has good public transportation accessibility and is quite near the city centre. The user rate of public transport (bus and metro) is high. Use of smooth means of transport, such as walking, cycling, etc, is significant. However, car traffic is still high.

População residente que vive no alojamento a maior parte do ano (N.º) por principal meio de transporte

Figure 12 – Census 2021 distribution main means of transport (Alvalade)

Challenges and opportunities

Today, Alvalade has a dynamic commerce and services sectors, receives a relevant number of commuters every day and has public and private facilities that can be improved in terms of their efficiency in the use of resources (e.g., energy, water). In the last decades, water supply utility (EPAL) has invested significantly in active leakage detection and management throughout the city, including pressure management and network rehabilitation, having installed district metering areas and more accurate monitoring of large consumers. Values for revenue-water in distribution system are around 11.3% (2021) and real-losses around 143 l/connection per day.

Regarding resources use and wastes management, Lisbon has long implemented selective waste collection, and reduction of wastes production follows the national trends and European directives.

Despite its innovative concept, challenges remain in terms of reducing carbon-based traffic, improvement of the rainwater management, separation of wastewater from rainwater, reduction of impervious areas and integration of nature-based functions as a way to rehabilitate and renovate these functions, including co-benefits as rainwater harvesting, reduce heat island effect, leisure and sport opportunities, among other issues impacting quality of life.

Four pilot facilities were selected to illustrate both measurements already implemented, needs and new actions for the future: market, research Centre - LNEC, sports facility and library.

Figure 13 – Some of Alvalade’s pilot areas preliminarily identified for the UP2030 project (market, research Centre- LNEC, sports facility and library)

Lisbon is actively working to improve the provision of high-quality multi-functional public spaces, promoting healthier lifestyles, and supporting its climate neutrality targets. As part of the EU's Net Zero Cities program, which promotes concrete actions, commitments and investments to achieve urban climate neutrality by 2030, Lisbon is due to complete its Climate City Contract (CCC) by the end of 2023. As part of this ambitious city-wide process, pilot implementation and quick scaling and replication are needed at the neighbourhood level. In this context, UP2030 is an opportunity to accelerate the climate neutrality process through the development of several climate actions in one of Lisbon's most populated neighbourhoods.

Over the last 10 years, new green infrastructure and horticultural parks were created; new playgrounds and seating areas in public spaces were created, and new trees were planted. One key challenge the city is facing is how to measure the benefits of these activities and maximise the city's value-for-money to further accelerate the introduction of new green and blue infrastructure at the neighbourhood level and remove space from cars. Overall, there is a need to create solid business-cases for the preparation of ambitious projects that can help channel significant investments in high-emissions areas such energy and water use. To support these aims, the UP2030 project will be working in close collaboration with the city's innovation agency, Lisboa E-Nova.

Furthermore, Lisbon aims to integrate intelligence in their digital decision-support platform around the level of effort and impact of its climate neutrality and adaptation actions. The approach will be tested and validated at the parish of Alvalade, an area of more than 30,000 inhabitants and characterized by significant climate vulnerabilities and social inequalities.

Current approach and actions

The city vision is anchored in a continual learning process for Lisbon and its neighbourhoods, as new challenges are faced.

Figure 14 –City Vision/Strategy on 2030

During last year’s Lisbon invested in a global strategy aligned with the climate change scenarios to prevent, mitigate, monitor, and undertake immediate action, both in normal situations and in moments of disruptive events, such as the COVID19 pandemic experienced since 2020.

Our Pilot case study aims to identify critical city locations (temporal and spatial variability component in one of the parishes -Alvalade) in terms of climate, energy and environmental risk, using GIS information, and select equipment or a set of equipment for public use (school, library, sports venue) and adapt the space in order to make it Carbon Negative.

We want to define the basic guidelines for the implementation of the pilot demonstration project, identifying existing pathologies and a set of proposed solutions (Building Envelope, Heating and Cooling System, Water consumption, Lightning, Renewables Integration, Management Systems, NBS and Green spaces, ...)

As of now, the pilot activities include:

Pilot 1: Coruchéus Library

Planned activities:

- Reinforce air conditioning (rehabilitate coverage)
- Decrease consumption
- Engage local communities
- Increase investment
- Forward books and coffee cups (“Food bank” sales per ton of paper)
- Guarantee the identity of the building (heritage)
- Promote behaviour change

- Monitor energy and water consumption continuously

Concluded activities:

PV simulation of Current Situation:

- Power: 2,18 kWp
- Production: 3 186 kWh
- Self consumption: 94,9%
- Solar fraction: 16%
- Investment: 1 744 €
- Avoided emissions: 0,6 ton CO₂/year

Pilot 2: Clube Rugby São Miguel

Planned activities:

- Reinforce air conditioning
- Decrease consumption
- Recycle water solution for synthetic field irrigation
- Assess adaptation solutions (NBS), tree plantations
- Increase engagement and investment

Concluded activities:

PV simulation of Current situation:

- Power: 10,4 kWp
- Production: 17620 kWh
- Investment: 8 320 €
- Self-consumption: 95,8%
- Solar fraction: 15,9%
- Avoided emissions: 3,2 ton CO₂/year

PV simulation of Future situation:

- Power: 16,64 kWp
- Production: 27 751 kWh
- Investment: 13 312 €

PV simulation of Full potential:

- Power: 36,4 kWp
- Production: 60 332 kWh
- Investment: 29 120 €

Pilot 3: LNEC

Planned activities:

- Reduce water losses
- Alternative sources for water uses
- Reduce energy consumption
- Refurbishment of buildings to increase energy efficiency
- Increase quality of life, reduction of urban island
- Community vegetable gardens
- Use of native plants in gardens
- Implementation of NBS (Life lungs project)
- Promote behavioural changes
- Reinforce sociocultural, recreational physical activity
- Monitoring of meteorologic and environment variables

Pilot 4: Alvalade Norte Market

Planned activities:

- Decrease consumption
- Assess water solution for reuse fish laminated ice
- Reinforce campaigns highlighting urban gardens, waste, healthy eating
- Boost the reuse of the market
- Reinforce free WIFI service
- Increase engagement and investment

Concluded activities:

Central Photovoltaic:

- 146 Modules 410W - Monocrystalline 132 cells
- Total area: ± 300 m²
- Total installed capacity of 59,860 kWp

- Production Accountant
- Web monitoring system / App

At the end of the pilot, we intend to develop a catalogue of fit-for-purpose solutions, and to encourage community involvement in the process of intervention, strengthening and transformation of the neighbourhood (local democracy) as facilitators of “voice and power” in the process (through a questionnaire/ communication/debate) with the municipality and the parish.

It is also a final objective to define solutions typified by space to intervene, which can be translated into good practices, guaranteeing the local identity and ensuring replicability in follower cities and local neighbours.

Figure 15 – Pilot Development scheme

Needs and aspirations

Our vision aims to promote, in the pilots:

- Reassessment water uses
- Improvement air quality
- Promotion of thermal comfort
- Increasing life quality
- Promoting behaviour change
- Reinforcement of sociocultural and recreational activities
- Reducing and monitoring consumptions
- Strengthening literacy
- Evaluating energy community solutions

Our overall vision is to design a path to promote solutions and strategies to highlight the importance of a net-zero neighbourhoods, in Lisbon, in order to:

- Disseminate information and urban knowledge about Lisbon
- Create synergies for an integration approach (urban planning, public space, climate resilience, water and energy efficiency, environment, culture, social rights, inclusion)
- Promote learning, reflection, participation and co-creation of solutions for a better neighbourhood
- Ensure identity and increase innovative adaptive interventions
- Publicizing the site visit in the municipal offer

People, Partners, Organisations and more

The planned interventions will be focused on the various social facilities located within the parish, such as schools, sport complexes and libraries. Lisbon wishes to assess the needs and define a set of solutions (fit for purpose NBS) to promote climate neutrality and adaptation, taking into account multiple impacts (social, economic, political, environmental, technological and heritage) at the same time. Early engagement will be planned with the local communities achieving an improved understanding of local needs to inform decisions.

Figure 16– StepUpLxALL dimensions

Figure 17– Stakeholder Engagement scheme

The Lisbon Municipality has been working closely with several key stakeholders in the pilot areas and in the wider city context (figure 18).

Figure 18– Stakeholder Map

Among the key stakeholders are:

- Lisbon Municipality Departments
- Municipal Administration
- Regional and National Administration
- Transport Sector
- Energy Sector
- NGO
- Research and Academics
- Technology suppliers
- Citizens

Activities undertaken as part of UP2030

Setting up of Learning Action Alliance

The Learning and Action Alliance (LAA) process was officially kicked off in April 2023 through an initial stakeholder mapping conducted by the City Liaison partner, Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil (LNEC). The Liaison partners also provided an initial assessment of the relevance of different members of the LAA, including a wide list of both internal and external city stakeholders relevant to the Alvalade neighborhood.

- [UP2030 Stakeholder list and matrix Lisbon_20230612.xlsx](#)
- [Stakeholder_map.pptx](#)
- [Initial Assessment of City's LAA Participants_Lisbon.docx](#)

The LAA process solidified throughout the months as Lisbon stakeholders began to engage and involve local external stakeholders in Alvalade to identify concrete pilot areas in which to implement the measures coming out of the needs analysis process. Several key local actors and areas emerged, including the Sao Miguel Rugby Club, the Corechêus Library and Elementary School, and the Alvalade Norte Market.

The aim of this engagement process was not to simply identify pilots spatially but also to actively involve the learning and action facilitators (such as teachers and sports instructors) that are key for the localization of solutions. This process of sustained local stakeholder engagement and commitment building was evident to all UP2030 stakeholders who participated in the study visit on 13 November at the General Assembly meeting, as the different pilot areas demonstrated their active involvement in the UP2030 project.

Following the General Assembly, LNEC decided to enhance internal city stakeholders' engagement, namely through the organization of 4 in-person working sessions with different departments of the municipality of Lisbon, from Environment, Climate Change & Energy, to Architecture, Transport and Water. This approach is proving key to breaking silos and identifying synergies, which is urgently needed to accelerate climate neutrality through the proposed pilots.

An extensive needs analysis process

Lisbon conducted a needs workshop involving a diverse mix of internal and external city stakeholders. The participants, representing various city departments, institutional stakeholders from different sectors, and a few local citizens, were divided into three smaller working groups. These groups focused on themes aligned with UP2030, as well as national and European policies. The objectives discussed were:

1. "Towards a carbon-neutral neighbourhood"
2. "Resilience and adaptation to face climate change effects in the neighbourhood"
3. "Inclusion: active and engaged community to promote change in the neighbourhood"

During the discussions at each table, significant attention was given to the topic of data needs. While specific data measures required for decision-making in Lisbon weren't uncovered, there was agreement that new data collection should complement historical data. This combination could predict climate risks and identify opportunities for impactful behavioural change. The suggestion was to compile and host this

data on a comprehensive platform, ensuring transparency and accessibility from a management perspective.

Management and coordination challenges in the city's work were also addressed. Bureaucracy, especially in acquiring new equipment for projects, was identified as a barrier. Another area requiring closer collaboration was communications, emphasizing the need for formal mechanisms to transmit information, particularly when interacting with residents about the costs and benefits of proposed interventions.

Regarding citizen involvement, participants highlighted a lack of incentives for intervention uptake and poor energy literacy as barriers, despite the demographic data showing a higher than average proportion of well-educated residents. The working groups identified a need for accessible and inspiring education and awareness training around energy and climate issues. They emphasized the necessity for simplified language when communicating with residents and extending communication across the entire life cycle of each project for seamless follow-up and evaluation. More insights about citizen involvement are expected from follow-up engagement activities where the city can directly interact with residents in local communities.

The workshop also touched on financing needs, noting the importance of more versatile and inclusive financing mechanisms, potentially in the form of advanced payment subsidies. Limited discussion occurred on how incentives for local businesses could promote employees' active participation in volunteering and local projects, with acknowledgment that this area requires further development.

All in all, while the workshop provided useful information, the outputs lacked specific details to gauge knowledge gaps. The broad barriers and needs identified could be due to participants' limited knowledge or time constraints during discussions.

A review of Lisbon's engagement approach also highlighted the need for more direct citizen representation. So, since the initial workshop, the Lisbon team has been reaching out and directly engaging the community. They have conducted technical visits to address the needs and barriers to specific interventions. The São Miguel Rugby Club pilot team met to discuss nature-based solutions, water use efficiency, and the requirements for a solar energy infrastructure evaluation. Meanwhile, stakeholders at the Biblioteca dos Coruchéus pilot site discussed the implementation of urban art projects.

To disseminate project information, they took part in the "Ambientes urbanos e saúde ambiental em Lisboa" conference with support from local stakeholders, including those from the research and health sectors and local residents.

As a next step, the team in Lisbon is working to create synergies between various streams of work underway in the city. They are planning to align their strategies, partly through the development of a characterization sheet for the parish and the "net-zero neighborhoods." This sheet will outline actions that are currently being implemented, planned, imported, and replicated. The team also intends to conduct interviews with neighborhood "ambassadors" to act as facilitators of change and leadership. Other planned activities involve developing a catalogue of "fit-for-purpose" solutions, and implementing specific actions where feasible. Specific initiatives such as the Mercado de Alvalade pilot and the urban art project also comprise their approach to stakeholder engagement. The Lisbon team is committed to monitoring the parish's progress and conducting communication campaigns to keep stakeholders

informed and engaged. This will occur both locally and through participation in conferences such as the "Portugal Smart Cities Summit" and the "21st European Week of Regions and Cities" reflecting their commitment to sharing insights and progress on the UP2030 project at a broader scale.

Further reading:

- [Final UP2030 - 1st workshop report Lisbon June 2023 0706.docx](#)
- [Lisbon 1st Engagement review.docx](#)

Next intended steps

- Ensure alignment between the UP2030 project and the municipal strategy (upscale)
- Promote synergies between projects and partners (continuity)
- Monitor the project performance and its impact on municipal strategy
- Create a profile sheet on "redesigning a better neighbourhood" (urban net zero guide/guidance/ recommendations)
- Increase involvement of the community throughout the intervention process (local democracy), as facilitators of "voice and power" and drivers of "attitude" change
- Promote interviews with "neighbourhood ambassadors" as facilitators of behaviour change
- Promote dissemination and engagement events: training course on "Integration of water in urban planning: nature-based solutions"
- Partnership in organizing the Eco video Lisboa Natura festival
- Create a catalogue of "fit for purpose" solutions

Working together with tools and services

As part of the UP2030 project, several tools and services are being offered to the cities by the technical partners. These tools play an important role in how the pilot project evolves and influences the final results of the city's participation in the UP2030 project and beyond. Cities were hence encouraged to reflect on the purpose of using these tools in their process and create principles to guide the pre-selection process. For Lisbon, the tools provided by the consortium are an opportunity for:

- Measurement of variables in real time and KPI calculation
- Decision support for selection of resilience improvement solutions
- Catalogue information to support decision makers.
- Reinforce warning and alert systems.
- Promote synergies between partners and citizens.
- Share data and information best practices and lessons learned.

As part of the pre-selection process led by the Implementation Taskforce, Lisbon has defined the following thematic areas for tool integration:

- Carbon-neutral neighbourhood, prioritizing renewable energy solution and public transport.
- Climate adaptation and resilience, considering multi-scale interventions and maximizing co-benefits.
- Involvement of communities in supporting the maintenance of streets and neighbourhood.

In this perspective, Lisbon has expressed interest for the Air quality monitoring and forecasting and the ecosystem service assessment tools, provided by LINKS. Moreover, thanks to the close collaboration with LNEC as liaison partner, the city of Lisbon has also the opportunity to address water-related challenges. In particular, the city has started exploring the application of tools for circularity in the urban water cycle. These include tools for measurement, water-smartness assessment, reclaimed water quality model in distribution systems and risk assessment tool for urban non-potable water reuse.

Visioning phase

The co-visioning phase is anchored on a needs assessment conducted under T2.3 and previously identified objectives. This information provided a foundation for identifying specific needs and goals for Alvalade district’s transformation. These elements were used to tailor a methodology to guide the co-design of a shared vision for the pilot. The detailed steps of the co-visioning with recommendations tailored to the context have been developed by the technical partners and are currently being evaluated by Lisbon’s team. Co-design approach is a core to UP2030 process, therefore cities and its stakeholders input for designing co-visioning process enables to develop a more specific and contextualised approach to engagement.

City is currently evaluating the feasibility of the proposal and indicating the timeline for the next steps to be taken under the co-visioning phases.

Lisbon

[update the process diagram once it’s [finalised by the city](#)]

As part of the preparatory activities, the city has started the validation and refinement of the identified key objectives. Through the first year of the project, the understanding of goals and needs have advanced, therefore revising aspirations plays an important role for the upcoming engagement activities in co-designing the vision for Alvalade.

With a support of the city’s liaisons the goal was to first validate the objectives and identify, whether the objective is most relevant to the short term, medium term, or long-term goals.

[city have not yet finalised this step, therefore more content can be added in the upcoming weeks]
[Validation of Objectives Matrix](#)

Additionally, during the General Assembly meeting in Lisbon, in 2023 city's representatives, with a support of liaison, has done the reflection on the alignment between the identified objectives and the pilot context. This exercise helped to specify goals that been identified in the first months of the project and ensure the connection with specific pilot scale and future interventions.

In the upcoming week, the city will undergo a series of engagement activities, such as spatial assessment and vision definition towards resilient, just and carbon neutral future of Alvalade.

Milano – Scalo Porta Romana – City Storyline

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Context and Background of the Milan pilot

History

The Porta Romana rail yard, “scalo” in Italian, located on the edge of Borough n° 5, was inaugurated in 1891. The rail yard has been for almost a century the beating heart of the industrial expansion of Milano towards south, providing raw materials and supplies to the many factories and workshops operating in the area, like the Tecnomasio Italiano Brown Boveri (TIBB) - a constructor of locomotives - and large-scale electrical generators, the Besozzi-Marzoli and Verga mills, the AEM powerhouse (decommissioned in 1953, today preserves the historical archives of the AEM Foundation).

It was the district of modernity, depicted in the paintings of Umberto Boccioni who had his atelier in Via Adige.

Umberto Boccioni, Officine a Porta Romana - 1908

Over the years, the Porta Romana rail yard (largely abandoned except for the passenger railroad) has taken on the role of a barrier, reinforcing the distance between northern and southern neighbourhoods and constituting an element of fracture in the design of the city, being always crossed only at its edges, to the east and west.

In 2017 the City Council of Milano ratified and the Region of Lombardy approved the Programme Agreement concerning the urban regeneration of seven decommissioned rail yards in the city of Milano. Among these is the Porta Romana rail yard. The area historically characterised by a mix of popular building, industrial and artisan systems, has been the subject of a strong urban planning in the last 10 years through the settlement of important tertiary and cultural functions such as the new buildings of Fondazione Prada, Smemoranda and Symbiosis.

The challenge for the city of Milan is to redevelop the Porta Romana district, especially in view of the 2026 Winter Olympics. Indeed, among others, the area will host the Olympic village and after the games the building will be converted into students houses and to offer different services to citizens.

Spatial characteristics of the neighbourhood

Population: 5.300 (pilot area inhabitants/users) 1.352.000 (City of Milan)

Area: 216.779 m² (pilot area); 181,8 km² (City of Milan)

Connected policies or programs: Milan Urban Masterplan "Milano 2030", Air And Climate Plan (PAC); Railyards Framework Program Agreement (Accordo di Programma Scali); Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities Mission.

The Porta Romana rail yard area has never been a residential area but in the last 10-15 years the surrounding ex industrial and artisanal areas have been at the centre of a massive urban regeneration pioneered by the building of Fondazione Prada in 2015 which partially renovated the premises of a former distillery.

The residential plot of borough n°5 present a general lack of green public spaces, therefore the Romana Park will become a valuable asset for all the people gravitating in this part of the city.

The challenge is to transform this pilot project into a hinge for the reconnection of the popular periferial neighborhoods, known under the traditional names of Gamboloita, Vigentino, Lodi-Corvetto and Tertulliano (in some cases the names have been updated for the NIL map of the city) located in the south, with the northern and more central part of Milan.

The project masterplan edited for the 2026 Olympic Games proposes a new model of integration between nature and the city.

The development, during the Olympics period, brings together residents, athletes and visitors in a community with its own specific identity, connected through the public transport network to the surrounding area. In the long run, residential and working spaces live in symbiosis with the natural landscape and outdoor activities; the integrated planning of the neighbourhood encourages pedestrian movement, creating a car-free area for soft mobility. Parco Romana is the natural heart of the project, a natural meadow free of architectural barriers that make the former railway site usable within the surrounding urban fabric, creating a new public asset rich in biodiversity.

The pedestrian and cycling paths will traverse the park in every direction especially connecting north and south.

The Masterplan includes the creation of the Olympic Village for Milan-Cortina 2026 as part of the redevelopment project, which will become a student village at the end of the Olympic Games adventure.

The east quadrant is intended for offices; the central portion in close contact with the park to the residential area; the southwest portion to the student residence (temporarily the Olympic village). Utilities are predominantly located in the southeast and northwest portions.

In addition to fulfilling and integrating every requirement of the Programme Agreement for the Porta Romana rail yard, the Environment and Ecology objectives are aligned with the protocols of the European Green Deal and the National Recovery and Resilience Plan defined at the UN SDG level, focusing on:

- decarbonisation consistent with local climate conditions;
- creation of a resilient community that promotes the health and well-being of citizens;
- circular approach that brings value in the short and long term;
- supporting biodiversity, enhancing natural capital, forestry solutions and urban agriculture.

NIL 36

Scalo Romana

Dotazione dei servizi esistenti

Social characteristics of the neighbourhood

Data and information could be found on the geoportal of the municipality of Milano <https://geoportale.comune.milano.it/portal/apps/webappviewer/index.html?id=e52d990fec5f4fe38b2a4f7d2385962a> specifically for the “Scalo Romana” neighborhood https://allegati.comune.milano.it/territorio/PGT_NIL/NIL_36.pdf

NIL 36

Scalo Romana

Dati socio-demografici

Challenges and opportunities

Through UP2030, the city will develop and apply quantitative and qualitative metrics to inform the intervention’s plan and design to ensure that it meets its objectives. These will reflect socioeconomic, demographic characteristics of beneficiaries, as well as adaptation and mitigation metrics. Milan will test for the first time at a neighbourhood scale, the multi-dimensional analysis of the City Resilience Index tool. Through this process, the city will develop a robust monitoring and evaluation system that will be replicated in all similar regeneration projects of the city.

The KPI considered: KPI1: > 20 sustainability metrics assessed; KPI2: > 1000 citizens/future users from different groups engaged from neighbouring areas; KPI3: improved soft connectivity and GHG reduction (baseline to be defined); KPI4: > 8,000 sqm of NBS with co-benefits calculated; KPI5: Circular economy in construction models achieved.

The main risk factor as seen in other regeneration processes of the city is the risk that the urban renovation is accompanied by a process of gentrification

Current approach and actions

The latest masterplan was presented in July 2021. Working on the site began in September 2022 after land reclaim. The area is currently in the excavation phase functional to the foundation.

Needs and aspirations

The City of Milan has committed to reducing its CO2 emissions by 45% by 2030 and becoming carbon neutral by 2050 (signatory of Covenant of Mayors, Global Covenant of Mayors, C40 Deadline-2020 declaration). The key challenge for Milan is now how to apply these high-level commitments at the neighbourhood scale and within the upcoming regeneration projects.

The pilot project Scalo Porta Romana represents one of the most important regeneration projects (the Winter 2026 Olympic park) ongoing in the city.

The city has committed that the regeneration shall align with the goals of the European Green Deal and the Italian Recovery and Resilience Plan in particular: (1) decarbonisation of the building stock, (2) creation of a resilient community, (3) circular economy, (4) nature-based solutions.

The project’s approved masterplan proposes a new model of integrating nature within the city, bringing together residents, athletes and visitors in a community with a strong identity.

Residential and working spaces are planned in symbiosis; the integrated planning of the neighbourhood encourages pedestrian movement, creating a car-free area for soft mobility.

The central park of the area will be the heart of the project, creating a new public asset rich in biodiversity. The Olympic Village will become a students’ village at the end of the Olympic Games to extend the life and value of the facilities.

People, Partners, Organisations and more

Stakeholder NO.	Stakeholder typology	Name	Level of influence (1 low - 10 High)	Level of interest (1 low - 10 High)	What does this stakeholder bring to the UP2030 project?
1	Municipal Administration	Municipio V - City of Milan	6	9	Public support
2	Ministry / Directorate	Città Metropolitana di Milano	7	8	Funding
3	Ministry / Directorate	Regione Lombardia	6	6	Funding
4	Ministry / Directorate	ERSAF	5	5	Knowledge and expertise
5	Ministry / Directorate	ARPA Lombardia	5	5	Knowledge and expertise
6	City council departments	city planning department - City of Milan	9	8	Collaborative partnerships
7	City council departments	Department of Urban Regeneration - City of Milan	9	8	Collaborative partnerships

8	NGOs	Osservatorio meteo Milano Duomo	3	6	Knowledge and expertise
9	NGOs	Legambiente Lombardia	4	8	Public awareness and support
10	Education	Fondazione Prada	3	5	Collaborative partnerships
11	NGOs	Osservatorio nazionale Città Clima	5	8	Public awareness and support
12	University	POLIMI	7	7	Knowledge and expertise
13	University	Università Bicocca	7	7	Knowledge and expertise
14	Education	ABCittà	5	6	Collaborative partnerships
15	Education	Fondazione CARIPLO	5	6	Funding
16	Technology Suppliers	LAND srl	5	4	Knowledge and expertise
17	Transport	MM spa	7	7	Knowledge and expertise
18	Transport	AMAT	7	7	Knowledge and expertise
19	Technology Suppliers	GEOINFOLAB	4	4	Knowledge and expertise

Activities undertaken as part of UP2030

Setting up of Learning Action Alliance

In Milan, the LAA process kicked off in April when the stakeholder mapping was developed:

- [draft_UP2030_Stakeholder_list_and_matrix_-_Milan.xlsx](#)

For the moment, the LAA has remained internal to City Hall. Milan wishes to reach out to priority external stakeholders only once the pilot project has become clearer and the specific objectives within UP2030 defined, so after the Workshop on Visions.

Even internally, there is a challenge in engaging and collaborating with other departments of the city administration. The departments which Milan involved so far and wants to collaborate with are:

Urban Resilience Department (*under the Green and Environment Department*)

Responsible for the management of "UP2030" and of the "EU Mission 100 carbon neutral and smart cities". Responsible for the coordination of adaptation measures of the PAC. It helps in adopting the integrated approach required by UP2030, thanks to its role of connector between departments.

Urban Regeneration Department

Responsible for the planning and design of urban regeneration areas (pilot areas for UP2030). They are also responsible for the urban masterplan (now under revision) and the Guidelines for the implementation and monitoring of Carbon Neutral Areas. They have a key role for the planning and design of neighbourhoods, due to their transversality and holistic approach within the Municipal departments.

Welfare and Health Department

The department is working on the co-design of Scalo Porta Romana services with different departments, using the "15 minutes city" approach. They are important for implementing one of the pillars of the project (just transition) and they have socio-demographic data.

Energy and Climate Sector

(under the Green and Environment Department)

Responsible for the management of the municipal "Air and Climate Plan" (PAC). They are searching for tools that can support in the assessment of impact of the plan (e.g. environmental, social, economic benefits of adaptation measures).

Green and Environment Department

Responsible for the design and management of green spaces, also in urban regeneration areas. They are interested in understanding how to make green spaces more resilient to climate change and how to improve the contribution of green to climate change adaptation and mitigation.

An extensive needs analysis process

In Milan, municipal stakeholders convened to delve into the needs and barriers for the design, implementation, and monitoring of carbon-neutral, resilient, and inclusive areas through urban regeneration processes. The workshop served as a platform to introduce UP2030 to various municipal departments, extracting valuable insights into ongoing activities aligning with the project. Notably, a key outcome of the workshop was the establishment of an internal working group—a collaborative entity

bridging departments to pool experiences and knowledge in the realm of local urban regeneration projects.

Amidst the workshop discussions, a pressing need surfaced—the need for an integrated approach surpassing mere data sharing. Governance structures present real challenges in Milan, with service design for urban regeneration remaining sectorial and decision-making confined within departments. The lack of control during projects' implementation phase, often outsourced to private entities, further complicates matters, with these actors operating beyond the municipality's oversight.

A transformative shift in internal working culture arose as a crucial need for Milan's municipal staff, with this change to be guided by a new standard protocol for cross-departmental collaboration. This envisioned new norm would aim to make collaborative decision-making routine, with habitual data and project outcome sharing to foster widespread awareness and alignment of concurrent and relevant projects. Recognizing the importance of upskilling staff in GIS use and data utilization, Milan also seeks to empower its workforce for more effective use of planning tools.

The evaluation of existing planning tools revealed a need for a more targeted focus on the city's needs to enhance utility. For instance, the scale at which these tools are relevant can sometimes be a limiting factor, as models and service evaluations conducted at a city scale aren't always applicable at a neighborhood scale. Additionally, department may encounter limitations due to a tool's large margins of error.

The design and management of public green spaces was also at the forefront of workshop and working groups discussions. Milan necessitates an evidence-based methodology to guide these processes. Related to this was the need for monitoring and measuring of the concrete environmental and social impacts of interventions.

A holistic approach is essential for Milan's engagement strategy. The cross-departmental working group continues to drive collaboration and integration. Simultaneously, the engagement strategy will evolve to include community groups, realtors, private entities, and NGOs, ensuring a platform for their voices. Since the initial internal workshop, Milan has engaged with the Air and Climate Office and the Urban Regeneration Department to discuss tool selection and development to support urban regeneration processes. This ongoing work compliments the continued internal realignment, particularly in defining synergies between UP2030 and the Mission for Carbon Neutral and Smart Cities (Climate City Contract).

Further reading:

- [01 UP2030_MILAN_1st Workshop Reflections and Takeways Report.pdf](#)
- [19-09-2023 Milan additional presentation.pptx](#)
- [UP2030_MILAN_Welfare and Health Department_Report.docx](#)
- [UP2030_MILAN_Air and Climate area EcosystemServices_Report.docx](#)
- [UP2030_MILAN_Green Department and Sector_Report.docx](#)
- 1st Engagemetn Review – Milan.docx

Next intended steps

- Identify the tools by the end of 2023 with the support of the technical partners (we've already started to explore some tools with the liaison partners LINKS);
- Make the definitive selection of the pilot area(s).
- Organize the workshop for the vision with internal stakeholders, in order to identify the specific objectives within UP2030;
- Start the implementation phase as soon as possible to be aligned with the ongoing activities of the municipality;
- Engage external stakeholders in the implementation of project activities and so start to share UP2030 outside the Municipality.

Working together with tools and services

As part of the UP2030 project, several tools and services are being offered to the cities by the technical partners. These tools play an important role in how the pilot project evolves and influences the results of the city's participation in the UP2030 project and beyond. Cities were hence encouraged to reflect on the purpose of using these tools in their process and create principles to guide the pre-selection process.

The UP2030 project represents an opportunity to support the municipality of Milan both in adopting new approaches in decision-making regarding green areas and in developing evaluation systems of the adaptation measures and projects implemented within the city. The tools provided by the consortium can assist the municipality in:

- Adopt new approaches that can enter into the municipal decision-making process, with the chance of replicability in different areas and in the future.
- Improve the designing and managing of urban green areas, in order to provide more ecosystems services to the city and generate benefits for the local community.
- Increase the awareness of the municipality (technicians and politicians) and citizens about the environmental, social and economic benefits of green interventions/measures adopted by the municipality within the Air and Climate Plan.
- Define an assessment and monitoring system for urban regeneration projects.

Since the beginning and the set-up of the LAA, the city emphasized the need to improve internal capacity to design green areas in urban regeneration projects, and increase awareness about environmental, social and economic impacts of adaptation and mitigation measures. For this reason, the city of Milan has expressed interest in applying the Ecosystem Service Assessment (provided by LINKS) and the City Resilience Framework and Index (from Resilient Cities Network). Milan's team is currently having conversations with the tools provider to define the achievable goals. Furthermore, the municipality has expressed interest for other tools, which could be tested in the area of Porta Romana (or other urban regeneration areas identified during the Vision workshop). These include MIRA Digital Twins Platform (by Maggioli) and the series of water management tools (provided by LNEC).

During the General Assembly in November 2023, the city had an opportunity to interact with the tool providers in order to further streamline the selection and explore which tool would be best suited to begin working with. As part of the process undertaken by the Implementation Taskforce, cities will first make a final selection of the tools, in alignment with the Visioning process, and thereafter build “implementation pathways” that map how a tool or selection of tools will be integrated in the pilot’s process in UP2030.

Co-visioning phase

The co-visioning phase is anchored on a needs assessment conducted under T2.3 and objectives previously identified within UP2030. This information provided a foundation for identifying specific needs and goals for Milan’s future transformation. These elements were used to tailor the methodology of co-designing of a shared vision for the pilot(s) (Porta Romana and/or Scalo Farini or other urban regeneration areas) that will be selected for implementation phase. The detailed steps of the co-visioning with recommendations tailored to Milano’s context have been developed by the technical partners and are currently being evaluated by the city. Co-design is an approach at the core of the UP2030 process, therefore cities and their stakeholders’ input in designing a co-visioning process enables to develop a more specific and contextualised approach to engagement.

Milan is currently evaluating the feasibility of the proposal and creating a timeline for the next steps to be taken under the co-visioning phases.

Milan

[update the process diagram once it’s finalised by the city: [Guide to Co-visioning. Visioning Roadmap](#)]

As part of the preparatory activities that sets the base for the co-visioning Milan is currently in the milestone of validating and refining the identified key objectives as well as identifying which pilot area is most suitable for next steps. During the first year of the project, the understanding of objectives and needs has evolved and therefore the revision of objectives plays an important role for the upcoming engagement activities. The challenge in the specific case of Milan is also to identify, which area of the city would benefit the most from the UP2030 project goals and scope and only then, identify linked objectives. As a part of

preparatory activity for the co-visioning, the proposal is to explore methods and ways, in supporting the city to set the pilot area which could help with further work for implementation steps as well. The full document on objectives validation process [can be found here](#).

Additionally, during the General Assembly meeting in Lisbon in 2023, the representatives of the city reflected on the alignment between the identified objectives and the pilot context. This exercise has helped to reflect on how ongoing processes in the city can be linked with UP2030. However, it is important to note, that due to the complexity of the case, objectives have to be re-defined and assessed in connection of selected pilot area for UP2030. The full document, with initial stage of revising the objectives, [can be found here](#).

In the coming weeks and months, the city will undergo a series of activities to define the scope to carry on in the next UP2030 steps. Co-visioning could be further explored on how to support city administration and co-design vision for a resilient, carbon neutral and just future for Milan's pilot and to identify concrete actions and barriers in the light of defining adaptation pathways.

Muenster – Shaping climate neutral and resilient compact neighbourhoods – City Storyline

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Context and Background of the Muenster pilot

Image: Stadt Münster Bernhard Fischer

History

Im Jahre 793 wurde auf dem Domhügel in der Nähe der Aa-Furt und der bestehenden Siedlung ein Kloster gegründet. Der sich um diese Klostergründung entwickelnde Dombezirk, die Domburg mit dem Kloster, dem Dom, dem Sitz des Bischofs- und des Domkapitels und den erforderlichen Gebäuden der Verwaltung und Versorgung ist noch deutlich im Stadtgrundriss ablesbar.

Schon in früherer Zeit siedelten sich vor der Domburg Kaufleute und Handwerker an. Das Zentrum dieser Kaufmannssiedlung ist dem Kreuzungspunkt zweier wichtiger Handelsstraßen vom Rhein in Richtung Norden (Aegidiistraße – Prinzipalmarkt – Alter Fischmarkt – Hörster Straße) und vom Osten, dem Salzgebiet am Hellweg nach Friesland (Salzstraße/Alter Steinweg – Drubbel – Roggenmarkt – Bogenstraße – Rosenstraße), welche um den Domhügel bzw. die Domimmunität herumführten, zuzuordnen. Jenseits der Aa („Überwasser“) wurde im Jahre 1040 das Frauenstift der Hl. Maria und die Pfarre Liebfrauen-Überwasser zu Münster gegründet.

In 793 a monastery was founded on the cathedral hill near the Aa ford and the existing settlement. The cathedral district that developed around this monastery foundation, the Domburg with the monastery, the cathedral, the seat of the bishop and the cathedral chapter and the necessary buildings for administration and supply can still be clearly seen in the city layout.

Already in early times, merchants and craftsmen settled in front of the cathedral castle. The center

of this merchant settlement is the intersection of two important trade routes from the Rhine to the north (the direction north (Aegidiistrasse - Prinzipalmarkt - Alter Fischmarkt - Hörster Strasse) and from the east, the salt area on the Hellweg to Friesland (Salzstraße/Alter Steinweg - Drubbel - Roggenmarkt - Bogenstraße - Rosenstraße), which led around the cathedral hill respectively the cathedral immunity. In 1040 the convent of St. Maria and the parish Liebfrauen-Überwasser were founded beyond the Aa.

Um 1200 entwickelte sich mit dem Bau einer neuen, weiträumigen Stadtbefestigung die noch heute bestehende Form des Promenadenrings. Sie umschloss ein Gebiet mit fast 100 Hektar Fläche. Noch heute sind die ehemaligen Verteidigungsanlagen und die in späterer Zeit vorgelagerten Schanzen als Grünflächen oder unbebaute Plätze erkennbar. Die Stadt wuchs stetig weiter an Bedeutung. Ab Mitte des 19. Jahrhunderts entwickelten sich aufgrund des Bevölkerungszuwachses auch Wohngebiete außerhalb des Promenadenrings, im Osten und Süden der Stadt eher Arbeiterwohnungen, im Norden auch Wohnviertel für Teile der wohlhabenderen Bevölkerung, wie Beamte und Angestellte.

Around 1200, with the construction of a new, extensive city fortification, the form of the promenade ring, which still exists today, developed. It enclosed an area of almost 100 hectares. Still the former defensive fortifications are still recognizable as green areas or undeveloped squares. The city continued to grow steadily in importance. From the middle of the 19th century, due to the increase in population, residential areas developed outside the promenade ring, in the east and south of the city more workers' housing, in the north also residential areas for parts of the wealthier population, such as civil servants and white-collar workers.

Mit dem zweiten Weltkrieg wurden etwa 91 % der Altstadt und 63 % der Gesamtstadt zerstört. Von 33.000 Wohngebäuden galten gerade 12.000 als noch bewohnbar. Zum Kriegsende lebten noch etwa 25.000 Einwohnerinnen und Einwohner in den damaligen Stadtgrenzen Münsters. Die Stadt Münster entschied sich im Wiederaufbau, anders als viele andere Städte, die überkommenen stadträumlichen Strukturen und Proportionen wiederherzustellen. Im Wiederaufbau entstanden so viele Gebäude in Anlehnung an bekannte Motive, aber auch Neubauten wie das Stadttheater mit einer neuen Formensprache. Im Jahr 1958 wurde das historische Rathaus fertiggestellt und wenige Jahre später auch der Münsteraner Dom. Mit der Neuordnung des Verkehrs nach dem zweiten Weltkrieg wurde aber in Teilen mit dem tradierten Wegesystem gebrochen. Busse ersetzen beispielsweise die Straßenbahn. (S.16) Der Promenadenring blieb weiterhin dem nichtmotorisierten Verkehr vorbehalten. (p.17)

With the Second World War, about 91% of the old town and 63% of the entire city were destroyed. Of 33,000 residential buildings, just 12,000 were considered still inhabitable. At the end of the war, about 25,000 inhabitants still lived within the city limits of Münster at that time. In contrast to many other cities, the city of Münster decided during reconstruction to restore the traditional urban structures and proportions. Thus, during the reconstruction many buildings were built in the style of well-known motifs, but also new buildings such as the municipal theatre with a new design language. In 1958, the historic city hall was completed, and a few years later, Münster Cathedral. With the reorganization of traffic after the Second World War, however, the traditional system of routes was broken in parts. Buses, for example, replaced the streetcar. (p.16 INSEK) The Promenadenring remained reserved for non-motorized traffic. (p. 17 INSEK)

Die besondere Bedeutung der Innenstadt für die Stadtentwicklung von Münster ist bereits im Leitplan Stadterneuerung (1989), im Altstadtrahmenplan (1995), in dem Integrierten Stadtentwicklungs- und Stadtmarketingkonzept (ISM) (2004) sowie in dem Integrierten Handlungskonzept „Aktive Stadt- und Ortsteilzentren“ Münster-Innenstadt (IHK Münster-Innenstadt, 2008/2016) umfänglich herausgearbeitet worden. Das im Jahr 2008 aufgestellte und 2016 bzw. 2017 in fortgeschriebener Fassung vom Rat der Stadt Münster

beschlossene IHK Münster-Innenstadt diene bis heute als planerische Grundlage für die Innenstadtentwicklung und die Städtebauförderung. Viele der dort aufgeführten Maßnahmen wurden umgesetzt oder stehen fast vor ihrer Fertigstellung, woraus sich eine hohe Entwicklungsdynamik in Münsters Innenstadt ablesen lässt. Dazu gehören Projekte wie die Gestaltung und Bebauung der Bahnhofsostseite, die Weiterentwicklung des Aa-Konzeptes (Westerholtsche Wiese), die Sanierung des Stadthauses I und des Servatiiplatzes, die Herrichtung der Dominikanerkirche als Ort der Begegnung, des Verweilens, der Kunst und Kultur oder die Etablierung des Zentrenmanagements.

Image: Betrachtungsbereich INSEK Münster-Innenstadt (2023) (Quelle: Plangrundlage Stadt Münster; Bearbeitung scheuven + wachten plus)

The special importance of the inner city for the urban development of Münster has already been comprehensively elaborated in the Urban Renewal Master Plan (1989), in the Old Town Master Plan (1995), in the Integrated Urban Development and City Marketing Concept (ISM) (2004) and in the

Integrated Action Concept "Active City and District Centers" Münster-inner city (IHK Münster-inner city, 2008/2016). The IHK Münster-inner city, which was drawn up in 2008 and adopted by the Münster City Council in 2016 and 2017 in an updated version, has served as the planning basis for inner city development and urban development funding to date. Many of the measures listed there have been implemented or are nearing completion, indicating a high development dynamic in Münster's inner city. These include projects such as the design and development of the eastern side of the train station, the further development of the Aa concept (Westerholt meadow), the redevelopment of the munci Servatiiplatz, the preparation of the Dominikaneras a place for meeting, lingering, art and culture and the establishment of center management.

Fast fünfzehn Jahre nach Aufstellung des IHK Münster-Innenstadt ist eine Überprüfung der darin beschriebenen Ziele und Maßnahmen aufgrund der sich kontinuierlich verändernden Bedürfnisse einer „Innenstadt Münster“ aber auch aufgrund neuer gesamtgesellschaftlicher Herausforderungen erforderlich. Zu nennen sind diesbezüglich beispielsweise die Transformation der Handelslandschaft mitzunehmendem Online-Handel, die Mobilitätswende, die Herausforderungen des Klimawandels, eine Wiederentdeckung der Innenstadt als Alltagsort (Wohnen, Freizeit, Bildung, Kultur, ...) und nicht zuletzt die Corona-Krise sowie die noch nicht absehbaren Auswirkungen des Ukraine-Krieges und der Energiekrise. Auch das Land Nordrhein-Westfalen fordert diese Neubearbeitung als Grundlage für die weitere Inanspruchnahme von Städtebaufördermitteln für Vorhaben im Bereich der Innenstadt. (S.7)

Almost fifteen years after the establishment of the IHK Münster-Innenstadt, a review of the goals and measures described therein is necessary due to the continuously changing needs of a "Münster city center" but also due to new challenges facing society as a whole. In this regard, for example, the transformation of the retail landscape with increasing online trade, the mobility turnaround, the challenges of climate change, a rediscovery of the city center as an everyday place (living, leisure, education, culture, ...) and last but not least the Corona crisis and the as yet unforeseeable effects of the Ukraine war and the energy crisis should be mentioned. The state of North Rhine-Westphalia also demands this new development as a basis for the further use of urban development funds for projects in the inner city area. (p.7)

Aus diesem Grund wurde das INSEK Innenstadt entwickelt und wurde im März 2023 politisch beschlossen. Aus der thematisch gegliederten Stärken-Schwächen-Analyse des INSEKS im Prozess, sowie den umfangreichen und vielfältigen Partizipationsformaten wurden die wesentlichen Zukunftsaufgaben und Zielstellungen für die Münsteraner Innenstadt abgeleitet. Insgesamt wurden sechs zentrale Handlungsfelder mit jeweils mehreren Zielstellungen identifiziert und formuliert. Die Handlungsfelder und Zielformulierungen bilden die Grundlage für die drauf folgende Ableitung, Sammlung und Erarbeitung von konkreten Einzelmaßnahmen, mit denen die jeweiligen Ziele erreicht werden können. Die Handlungsfelder mit ihren Zielen wurden vom Rat der Stadt Münster am 18. Mai 2022 als wichtiger Meilenstein der INSEK Münster-Innenstadt-Erarbeitung beschlossen.

For this reason, the INSEK (Integrated urban development concept) inner city was developed and was politically adopted in March 2023. The main future tasks and objectives for Münster's inner city were derived from the thematically structured strengths and weaknesses analysis of the INSEKS in the process,

as well as the extensive and diverse participation formats. A total of six central fields of action, each with several objectives, were identified and formulated. The fields of action and the formulation of objectives form the basis for the subsequent derivation, collection and development of concrete individual measures with which the respective objectives can be achieved. The fields of action with their objectives were adopted by the City Council of Münster on May 18, 2022 as an important milestone in the INSEK Münster inner city development.

Mehr als 1.500 Anregungen von Bürgerinnen und Bürgern sind hier eingeflossen, über 90 konkrete Maßnahmen zu sechs zentralen Handlungsfeldern sind darin enthalten. "Integriert" bedeutet, dass verschiedenste Lebens- und Themenfelder der Innenstadt betrachtet werden.

Die Handlungsfelder sind:

- 1) Grün und klimagerecht
- 2) Vernetzt und facettenreich
- 3) Vielfältig und erlebnisreich
- 4) Alltagstauglich und inklusiv
- 5) Autoarm und erreichbar
- 6) Aktiv und ko-produktiv

Ein räumlicher und programmatischer Schwerpunkt ist „Grüne/klimagerechte Gebäude und öffentliche Freiflächen“

More than 1,500 suggestions from citizens have been incorporated here, and more than 90 concrete measures for six central fields of action are included. "Integrated" means that the most diverse fields of life and topics in the inner city are considered.

The fields of action are:

- 1) Green and climate-friendly
- 2) Networked and multifaceted
- 3) Diverse and eventful
- 4) Suitable for everyday life and inclusive
- 5) Low-car and accessible
- 6) Active and co-productive

One spatial and programmatic focus is "Green/climate-appropriate buildings and public open spaces".

Image: Analysis map climate of the INSEK

Das erste Handlungsfeld „Grün und klimagerecht“ folgt der Notwendigkeit, die Themen Klimaschutz und Klimaanpassung in der Innenstadtentwicklung stärker in den Blick zu nehmen und die bisherigen grünen und blauen Strukturen zu stärken, auszubauen sowie Neue zu schaffen. Klimaanpassungsmaßnahmen stehen dabei in einem engen Zusammenhang mit der Bewahrung und Weiterentwicklung

von Grün- und Wasserflächen, mit der Stärkung einer zukunftsgerichteten Mobilitätsentwicklung und der Verringerung von CO₂-Emissionen in Bestandsgebäuden und Neubauten. Dazu zählt auch der Ausbau einer klimaneutralen und umweltgerechten Energieversorgung.

Trotz bzw. wegen ihrer historischen oftmals steinernen Stadtgestalt kann und soll auch die Innenstadt Münsters einen Beitrag zum Klimaschutz und zur Klimaanpassung leisten. Auch kommt ihr aufgrund ihrer gesamtstädtischen und regionalen Ausstrahlung eine hohe Bedeutung in diesem Themenfeld

zu. Durch die dichte Bebauung in der Altstadt lassen sich nur wenige Grünflächen finden, weshalb die Innenstadt derzeit eine große Hitzeinsel ausbildet. Daher ist es für eine klimagerechte Innenstadt wichtig, die bestehenden Grünstrukturen wie die Promenade und den Botanischen Garten zu bewahren und darüber hinaus an weiteren ausgewählten Orten im Einklang mit der historischen Struktur neue Grünstrukturen zu schaffen. Neben der Stärkung von Grün ist aber auch die Kühlung durch Wasser in den Fokus zu rücken.

Hier

nehmen die Innenstadt-Aa sowie der Aasee aber auch eine veränderte Wasserbewirtschaftung des

Regenwassers eine besondere Rolle ein. Die Aa fließt zwar mitten durch die Innenstadt Münsters,

entspricht aber nicht mehr den aktuellen Anforderungen an den Hochwasserschutz. Auch ökologische und stadtgestalterische Potenziale sollen im Zuge eines zukunftsgerechten Umbaus der Aa stärker genutzt werden.

The first field of action "Green and climate-friendly" follows the necessity to focus more on the topics of climate protection and climate adaptation in the inner-city development and to sk, to expand them and to create new ones. Climate adaptation measures are closely related to the preservation and further development of green and water areas, the strengthening of future-oriented mobility development and the reduction of CO2 emissions in existing and new buildings. This also includes the expansion of a climate-neutral and environmentally friendly energy supply. Despite or because of its historic, often stony urban form, Münster's inner city can and should also contribute to climate protection and climate adaptation. It also has a high significance in this area due to its overall urban and regional impact. Due to the dense development in the old city, there are only a few green spaces, which is why the city centre currently forms a large heat island. Therefore, it is important for a climate-friendly city centre to preserve the existing green structures such as the promenade and the botanical garden and, in addition, to create new green structures at other selected locations in harmony with the historic structure. In addition to strengthening greenery, however, cooling by water must also be brought into focus. Here, the inner-city Aa and the Aasee, but also a changed water management of rainwater, take on a special role. Although the Aa flows right through the centre of Münster, it no longer meets current flood protection requirements. Ecological and urban design potentials are also to be used more intensively during a future-oriented reconstruction of the Aa.

In der Altstadt lassen sich eine Vielzahl von Stellplatzanlagen im öffentlichen Raum finden, die derzeitig keinen Beitrag zur klimaangepassten Innenstadtentwicklung leisten. Ziel ist es, Verkehrsräume und Stellplatzflächen als Stadträume für neue Grünflächen und Aufenthaltsorte zurückzugewinnen.

Folgende Handlungsfeldbeschreibung mit dazugehörigen Entwicklungszielen wurde vom Rat der Stadt Münster zum Handlungsfeld 1 „Grün und Klimagerecht“ aus dem INSEK beschlossen:

In the old town, many parking lots can be found in public spaces, which currently do not contribute to climate-adapted inner-city development. The goal is to reclaim traffic areas and parking spaces as urban spaces for new green spaces and places to stay. The following field of action description with associated development goals was adopted by the City Council of Münster for field of action 1 "Green and Climate-Friendly" of the INSEK:

Auch in der Innenstadt Münsters sollen Beiträge zur Klimaneutralität geleistet werden, wenn gleich ihr klimagerechter Umbau und eine prägnantere Begrünung ungleich schwieriger als in den anderen Stadtteilen zu leisten sind. Denn es gilt, diesen Umbau im Einklang mit den historischen Prägungen der Stadtstruktur und der erhaltenswerten Gebäude zu vollziehen. Dass die Altstadt von dem grün-blauen Band der Aa durchzogen wird und vom Promenadenring prägnant grün gesäumt ist, kommt dem Ziel entgegen. Es gibt aber noch weitere Potenziale, denn Grün in der Innenstadt fördert die Aufenthaltsqualität und sorgt für eine Verminderung der Überhitzung.

- Erhöhung der Durchgrünung der Innenstadt im Einklang mit den historischen Prägungen sowie mit einer wassersensiblen Stadtgestaltung zur Reduzierung der innerstädtischen Hitzeinseln

- Bewahrung und Aufwertung der Promenade als integrierendes Alleinstellungsmerkmal der Stadt Münster für Grün, Klima und Erholung

- Reduzierung von Parkplatzflächen und Stellplatzanlagen zur Rückgewinnung von Raum für Grün, mehr Aufenthaltsqualität oder klimafreundliche Mobilitätsbausteine

- .

- Etablierung weiterer grün geprägter barriere- und konsumfreier Aufenthalts- und Bewegungsräume sowie ruhiger Rückzugsorte zusätzlich zum Promadenring und Aa-Raum Steigerung der Nutzbarkeit und Aufenthaltsqualität der Flächen entlang der Innenstadt-Aa
und
deren wasserwirtschaftliche, grüne und stadtgestalterische Umgestaltung
- Sicherung bestehender grüner und blauer Infrastrukturen sowie der Wasserqualität.

- Vermeidung von CO₂-Emissionen bei der Errichtung neuer Gebäude und Reduzierung durch die Sanierung des Bestands
- Erhöhung des Anteils klimaneutraler und umweltverträglicher Energie in der Erzeugung und Verteilung sowie in der Gebäudeversorgung
- g.

Diese Handlungsbeschreibung und Entwicklungsziele sind das Ergebnis eines Beteiligungsprozesses mit verschiedenen Stakeholdern wie dem Verkehrsplanungsamt, Münster Marketing, der Stabstelle Klima und anderen. Bisher besteht noch keine Priorisierung.

Spatial and social characteristics of the neighbourhood

Image: Selected neighborhood

Die Stadtgestalt in Münster besitzt historisch bedingt einen hohen Stellenwert. Besonders die in ihrem Grundriss bewahrte und in großen Teilen rekonstruierte Altstadt ist ein herausragendes Alleinstellungsmerkmal der Stadt. Die charakteristische Kleinteiligkeit der Altstadtbauten ist im Laufe der Entwicklung stellenweise durch große Baukörper ergänzt worden. Die Innenstadt hält seit jeher die Waage zwischen ihrem stadthistorischen Erbe sowie einer zeitgenössischen und zukunftsweisenden Stadtentwicklung. Zur Bewahrung eben jener Balance, zwischen alt und neu, macht sich die Stadt verschiedene Werkzeuge zu eigen, die primär zum Schutz und Erhalt besonderer Stadträume eingesetzt werden.

In dem ausgewählten Quartier finden sich diese historische Straßenführung, als auch die Kleinteiligkeit wieder. Die eher schmal ausgebildete Frauenstraße ist je nach Abschnitt unterschiedlich gestaltet. Teilweise handelt es sich um eine Einbahnstraße, die für Radfahrer in Gegenrichtung geöffnet ist. Die Höchstgeschwindigkeit beträgt 30 km/h. Insgesamt ist die Straße als Fahrradstraße ausgebildet, das bedeutet, dass sich Autofahrer den Radfahrern unterzuordnen haben. Insgesamt weist die Straße unterschiedliche Nutzungen auf. Es gibt kleinere Geschäfte wie Bücherläden, Cafés, eine Bar, ein Friesursalon und ein Reisebüro. Vor allem ist die Straße für das F24 bekannt. Das Gebäude Frauenstraße 24 (F24) in Münster war zwischen 1973 und 1981 besetzt und wird nach dem Ankauf durch die LEG NRW seit 1982 vom AStA der Uni Münster an Studierende zum Wohnen vermietet. Die Besetzung gilt als eine der längsten in der Bundesrepublik. Das Haus bietet bis heute als symbolträchtiger Ort alternativer, studentisch geprägter Kultur der 1970er und 1980er Jahre in der mittlerweile privatisierten Kneipe im Erdgeschoss des Gebäudes ein breites Kulturprogramm an. Der Kulturverein Frauenstraße 24 e.V. fördert das Kulturprogramm am Ort sowie Kunst und Bildung. Das Gebäude mit der bis heute vorhandenen

aufwändigen Fassadengestaltung wurde Anfang des 20. Jahrhunderts errichtet. Es blieb im Zweiten Weltkrieg von Bombentreffern weitgehend verschont und wurde nur in Teilen beschädigt. (vgl. <https://f24-kultur.de/>). Der Verein zeigt sich weiterhin sehr aktiv für das Gebäude, das Quartier und politische Themen. Ein Wohnheim für weibliche Studierende, die Buchhandlung mit dem Fokus auf wissenschaftliche Literatur, sowie das Café Milagro ergänzen das Angebot für Studierende. Ein wichtiger Stakeholder ist das Bischöfliches Studierendenwerk Münster, das unter anderem das Wohnheim Fürstin-von-Galitzien-Heim für 80 Studierende betreiben. Ein kleiner Abzweig in der Frauenstraße führt zur Gesamtschule Mauritz-Mitte mit einem eigenen Schulgarten. Viele historische Gebäude sind unter anderem in Form der Kirchen (Überwasser-Liebfrauen und Dom) zu finden. Räumlich prägend ist auch die Aa, die an dieser Stelle ebenfalls renaturiert werden soll, da sie auch an dieser Stelle nicht mehr aktuellen Anforderungen des Hochwasserschutzes genügt.

For historical reasons, Münster's cityscape is of great importance. In particular, the layout of the old town, which has been preserved and largely reconstructed, is an outstanding unique feature of the city. In the course of development, the characteristic small-scale nature of the old town buildings has been supplemented in places by large structures. The city centre has always maintained a balance between its historical heritage and contemporary, forward-looking urban development. In order to maintain this balance between old and new, the city has adopted various tools that are primarily used to protect and preserve special urban spaces.

In the selected quarter, this historic street layout as well as the small-scale structure can be found again. The rather narrow Frauenstraße is designed differently depending on the section. Partly it is a one-way street, which is open for cyclists in the opposite direction. The maximum speed is 30 km/h. Overall, the street is designed as a bicycle lane, which means that motorists have to subordinate themselves to cyclists. Overall, the street has different uses. There are smaller stores such as bookstores, cafes, a bar, a frieze salon and a travel agency. Above all, the street is known for the F24. The building Frauenstraße 24 (F24) in Münster was squatted between 1973 and 1981 and, after being purchased by LEG NRW, has been rented out to students for housing by the AStA of Münster University since 1982. The occupation is considered one of the longest in the Federal Republic. As a symbolic place of alternative, student-oriented culture of the 1970s and 1980s, the house still offers a broad cultural program in the now privatized pub on the first floor of the building. The KulturVerein Frauenstraße 24 e.V. promotes the cultural program at the location as well as art and education. The building, with the elaborate facade design that still exists today, was constructed at the beginning of the 20th century. It was largely spared from bomb hits during World War II and was damaged only in parts. (cf. <https://f24-kultur.de/>). The association continues to be very active on behalf of the building, the neighborhood, and political issues. A dormitory for female students, the bookstore with a focus on scientific literature, and Café Milagro complement the offerings for students. An important stakeholder is the Bischöfliches Studierendenwerk Münster, which among other things operates the Fürstin-von-Galitzien-Heim dormitory for 80 students. A small branch in Frauenstraße leads to the comprehensive school Mauritz-Mitte with its own school garden. Many historic buildings can be found, including the churches (Überwasser-Liebfrauen and Dom). Spatially formative is also the Aa, which is also to be renaturalized at this point, as it also no longer meets current flood protection requirements.

Räume, in denen sich Menschen ohne den Zwang, etwas konsumieren zu müssen, aufhalten können. Solche Bereiche, die sich vor allem Anwohnende und Alltagsnutzende der Innenstadt selbst aneignen können, sind von großer Bedeutung, jedoch zu diesem Zeitpunkt zu wenig vorhanden.

So ist unter anderem auf den großen Vorplätzen der Kirchen im Projektgebiet Raum für Aufenthaltsmöglichkeiten. Dies wurde beispielsweise auf dem Domplatz über eine temporäre Bestuhlung in der Vergangenheit gelöst. Aber auch in der Frauenstraße selbst fehlt es an attraktiven Aufenthaltsmöglichkeiten, da diese vor allem durch parkende Autos, aber auch eine Vielzahl von Fahrrädern, kaum möglich sind umzusetzen.

Spaces where people can spend time without the compulsion of having to consume something. Such areas, which can be used by residents and everyday users of the city centre, are of great importance, but too few exist at this time.

For example, the large forecourts of the churches in the project area provide space for people to stay. This was solved in the past, for example, on Domplatz by means of temporary seating. But also, in Frauenstraße itself there is a lack of attractive places to stay, as these are hardly possible to implement, mainly due to parked cars, but also many bicycles.

Insgesamt fehlt es

in der Innenstadt an einer ausreichenden Ausstattung mit (inklusive) Spiel- und Bewegungsangeboten. Bestehende Spielplätze in der Altstadt Münsters lassen sich derzeit vorwiegend innerhalb der Grünflächen im weiteren Bereich der Promenade oder auf Schulhöfen finden. Auch

wenn weitere Spielplätze geplant sind, besteht ein weiterer Bedarf, vor allem im zentralen Altstadtbereich. Insbesondere mangelt es auch an Bewegungsangeboten für ältere Kinder, Jugendliche, erwachsene Menschen und für Menschen mit Behinderungen. Weiterhin

ist die Funktion der Innenstadt als wichtiger Wohnstandort innerhalb Münsters von großer Wichtigkeit. Neben den belebten Geschäftslagen mit Gastronomiebesatz trägt die ausgeprägte Wohnfunktion maßgeblich zu der Lebendigkeit der Innenstadt bei. Auch aus diesem Grund sind die Wohnviertel der Alt- und Innenstadt ein wesentlicher Faktor für die Qualität und die Attraktivität des Münsteraner Zentrums.

Die historisch gewachsenen Teilgebiete Aegidii-, Überwasser-, Kuh-, Kiepenkerl-, Martiniviertel und Breul bilden nach wie vor die Kernbereiche des Wohnens in Münsters Altstadt. In nahezu allen Lagen der Altstadt sind darüber hinaus auch bei anderer Erdgeschossnutzung in den oberen Stockwerken Wohnfunktionen zu finden. Mit ca. 9.000 Einwohnerinnen und Einwohnern beherbergt die Altstadt insgesamt

knapp 3 % der städtischen Gesamtbevölkerung (Stand 31.12.2021: 314.332 Personen).

Das ausgewählte Quartier bietet über den Schulhof der Gesamtschule Münster-Mitte ein Bewegungsangebot, das von anderen außerhalb der Unterrichtszeiten genutzt werden kann. Weitere Bewegungsmöglichkeiten ließen sich ggf. Ebenfalls über die Kirchplätze oder temporäre Möblierung ermöglichen, diese sind aber auf eine klimagerechte Umsetzung hin zu überprüfen bzw. in Einklang zu bringen. Neben den kirchlichen Einrichtungen setzt sich die Eigentümerstruktur in der Frauenstraße aus vielen privaten Eigentümern als auch Wohnungsunternehmen zusammen. Die Gebäude in der Straße wurden von Anfang des 20. Jahrhunderts bis heute errichtet und weisen sehr unterschiedliche energetische Standards auf.

Overall, there is also a lack of sufficient provision of (inclusive) play and exercise facilities in the city centre. Existing playgrounds in Münster's old town can currently be found mainly within the green spaces in the wider area of the promenade or in schoolyards. Even though more playgrounds are planned, there is a

further need, especially in the central old town area. In particular, there is also a lack of physical activity opportunities for older children, youth, adults, and for people with disabilities. Furthermore, the function of the city centre as an important residential location within Münster is of great importance. In addition to the busy commercial areas with restaurants and cafés, the distinct residential function contributes significantly to the vibrancy of the city centre. For this reason, too, the residential areas of the old and inner city are a key factor in the quality and attractiveness of Münster's center. The historically grown sub-areas of Aegidii-, Überwasser-, Kuh-, Kiepenkerl-, Martiniviertel and Breul still form the core areas of living in Münster's old town. In almost all locations in the old town, residential functions can also be found on the upper floors with other ground-floor uses. With approximately 9,000 residents, the Altstadt is home to a total of just under 3 % of the city's total population (as of Dec. 31, 2021: 314,332 people).

The selected neighborhood offers a schoolyard of the Münster-Mitte comprehensive school that can be used by others outside of school hours. Further opportunities for movement could also be made possible via the church squares or temporary furniture, but these must be checked for climate-friendly implementation and harmonized. In addition to the church institutions, the ownership structure in Frauenstrasse is made up of many private owners as well as housing companies. The buildings in the street were constructed from the beginning of the 20th century until today and have very different energy standards.

Auffällig ist im Zusammenhang mit der ausgeprägten Wohnnutzung die geringe Anzahl an zentralen Nahversorgern im Altstadtbereich. Auch im Projektgebiet gibt es keine ausgewiesenen Nahversorger für die täglichen Bedarfe der Anwohnerinnen und Anwohnern. Im Bereich der angrenzenden Innenstadtteilversorgungslagen Hammer Straße, Wolbecker und Warendorfer Straße ist eine deutlich höhere Dichte an Einkaufsmöglichkeiten für den täglichen Bedarf vorzufinden. Hier gilt es eine Ausgewogenheit besonders im direkten Umfeld der altstädtischen Wohnbereiche herzustellen.

In connection with the pronounced residential use, the low number of central local suppliers in the old town area is striking. Also in the project area there are no designated local suppliers for the daily needs of residents. In the area of the adjacent inner-city subdistrict supply locations Hammer Strasse, Wolbecker Strasse and Warendorfer Strasse, there is a significantly higher density of shopping facilities for daily needs. Here, it is necessary to create a balance, especially in the direct vicinity of the old-town residential areas.

Neben der ausgeprägten Funktion als Wohnstandort nimmt die Innenstadt darüber hinaus eine tragende Rolle als Schul-, Bildungs- und Arbeitsstandort ein. Der Hörsaal- und die Seminargebäude der Westfälischen Wilhelms-Universität westlich des Domplatzes und im Bereich des Schlosses tragen maßgeblich zu einer hohen Frequenz an Studierenden in der Altstadt bei. Dazu zählt auch das ausgewählte Quartier. Die Verschmelzung von Studienort mit der Innenstadt ist von großer Attraktivität für Studierende und Lehrkräfte. Für die Stadt Münster und insbesondere auch die Innenstadt wiederum sind die Hochschuleinrichtungen von großer Bedeutung als wichtiger Bildungs-, Kultur- und letztendlich auch Wirtschaftsfaktor. Der fest etablierte Hochschulstandort inmitten der Stadt verleiht der Innenstadt zusätzlich ein attraktives, vielfältiges, offenes und lebendiges Flair. (S.40)

In addition to its pronounced function as a residential location, the city center also plays a supporting role as a school, education and work location. The lecture hall and seminar buildings of the Westphalian Wilhelms University west of the Domplatz and in the area of the castle contribute significantly to a high frequency of students in the old town. This also includes the selected quarter. The merging of the place of study with the city center is of great attractiveness for students and teachers. For the city of Münster and especially for the city center, the higher education institutions are of great importance as an important educational, cultural and ultimately also economic factor. The firmly established university location in the middle of the city additionally gives the city center an attractive, diverse, open, and lively flair. (S.40)

Ein wichtiges Alltagserfordernis ist die Barrierefreiheit in der Alt- und Innenstadt. Viele Orte, Wege und Angebote sind nicht barrierefrei gestaltet, zugänglich bzw. nutzbar. So stellt beispielsweise das historische Kopfsteinpflaster ein großes Hindernis für Menschen mit Behinderungen und Mobilitäts-einschränkungen dar. Viele Geschäfte und Einrichtungen sind nicht barrierefrei zu betreten. Auch fehlt es an barrierefrei gestalteten Bänken und öffentlichen Sitzmöglichkeiten, auf denen sich Menschen ausruhen und kostenlos aufhalten können. Auch im ausgewählten Quartier ist die Barrierefreiheit zu erhöhen.

An important everyday requirement is accessibility in the old and inner city. Many places, paths and offers are not designed, accessible or usable barrier-free. For example, the historic cobblestones are a major obstacle for people with disabilities and mobility impairments. Many stores and facilities are not barrier-free to enter. There is also a lack of barrier-free benches and public seating where people can rest and sit for free. Accessibility also needs to be increased in the selected neighborhood.

Begründung Pilotquartier Frauenstraße/Überwasser

- Sehr gute Verschneidungsmöglichkeit von dem, eigentlich für dieses Jahr geplantem, Reallabor Frauenstraße (das aufgrund von mehreren Baustellen auf das nächste Jahr verschoben wird) und dem in UP2030 geplanten KlimaTraining im Quartier. Das Reallabor/KlimaTraining würde dann im Sommer 2024 stattfinden.
- Sowohl die Gebäude, als auch die Ausgestaltung des Straßenraums betreffend, bietet sich viel Potential aber auch die Notwendigkeit für verschiedene Klimaanpassungs- und Klimaschutzmaßnahmen.
- Darüber lässt sich u.a. die „Umgestaltung und stadtgestalterische Verbesserung der Frauenstraße zu einem einladenden westlichen Altstadtzugang mit räumlicher Verknüpfung mit dem Schloss-Areal“ (siehe Maßnahme 2.26 INSEK-Innenstadt) weiter vorantreiben, die „Weiterentwicklung und Stärkung von privaten Quartiersgemeinschaften“ (siehe Maßnahme 6.88 INSEK-Innenstadt) umsetzen und die für UP2030 gewollte Mitnahme der Bewohner*innen, aber auch die konkrete Umsetzung von Maßnahmen vor Ort im Projektgebiet darstellen.
- In der Frauenstraße gibt es eine spannende Struktur unterschiedlicher Stakeholder (Kulturverein Frauenstraße 24, Bischöfliches Studierendenwerk, verschiedene Einzeleigentümer*innen, Ladenbesitzer*innen), die zum Teil untereinander schon sehr gut vernetzt sind und die sich u.a. sehr für das Reallabor eingesetzt haben und für die Umsetzung eigentlich schon auf dieses Jahr vertröstet wurden. Eine weitere Verschiebung könnte, neben der rein funktionalen Begründung

durch die Baustellenproblematik, gut mit der Verschneidung von UP2030 als Möglichkeit den Ansatz noch größer zu ziehen und der Wirkung auf EU-Ebene begründet werden. Über die Klima-Expo im September 2023 ließen sich bereits erste, den Raum betreffende Beteiligungswerkstätten, initiieren. Außerdem sind über UP2030 für August ein Workshop zum Thema „Vision des Klimaquartiers Frauenstraße“ sowie weitere Gespräche mit den Stakeholdern geplant. So das auch trotz Verschiebung des eigentlichen Reallabors die aktive Gemeinschaft in der Frauenstraße weiter mitgenommen werden kann.

- Die Innenstadt bietet sich als Projektgebiet gerade für ein Innovations- und Forschungsprojekt wie UP2030 sehr an. Ganz im Sinne von: „Die Innenstadt hält seit jeher die Waage zwischen ihrem stadtgeschichtlichen Erbe sowie einer zeitgenössischen und zukunftsweisenden Stadtentwicklung.“ (siehe INSEK-Innenstadt) In Abgrenzung zu dem parallel beginnenden kfw 432 Prozess (Koordination Nadine Somberg, ebenfalls Stabsstelle Klima) können noch einmal innovativere Ansätze und das Vorgehen hinsichtlich ggf. herausfordernder Ausgangsbedingungen (Denkmalschutz etc.) erprobt werden. Die Ergebnisse aus UP2030 werden in den kfw-Prozess, der noch über Jahre andauern wird, einfließen und weiterentwickelt.

Auch in den anderen Bereichen werden weitere klimarelevante Maßnahmen umgesetzt oder geplant, diese können über UP2030 mitgestaltet werden und gegenüber der EU kommuniziert werden.

Rationale for pilot neighborhood Überwasser/Frauenstraße:

- Very good opportunity to combine the Frauenstraße real laboratory, which was actually planned for this year (postponed to next year due to several construction sites), and the climate training in the neighbourhood planned in UP2030. The reallaboratory/climate training would then take place in summer 2024.
- Both the buildings and the design of the street space offer a lot of potential, but also the need for various climate adaptation and climate protection measures.
- In this way, the "redesign and urban design improvement of Frauenstraße to create an inviting western access to the old town with a spatial link to the castle area" (see measure 2.26 INSEK-Innenstadt) can be further promoted, the "further development and strengthening of private neighbourhood communities" (see measure 6.88 INSEK-Innenstadt) can be implemented, and the desired participation of residents in UP2030, as well as the concrete implementation of measures on site in the project area, can be presented.
- In Frauenstraße there is an exciting structure of different stakeholders (cultural association Frauenstraße 24, Bischöfliches Studierendenwerk, various individual owners, shop owners), some of whom are already very well networked with each other and who have, among other things, been very committed to the Reallabor and were actually postponed to this year for its implementation. A further postponement could, apart from the purely functional justification by the construction site problem, be well justified with the intersection of UP2030 as a possibility to draw the approach even larger and the effect at EU level. The Climate Expo in September 2023 could already be used to initiate the first participation workshops concerning the area. In addition, a workshop on the topic of "Vision of the Frauenstrasse Climate Quarter" and further discussions with stakeholders are planned via UP2030 for August. This will ensure that the active community in Frauenstraße can continue to be involved despite the postponement of the actual real laboratory.

- The city centre is an ideal project area for an innovation and research project like UP2030. In the spirit of: "The inner city has always kept a balance between its historical heritage and a contemporary and forward-looking urban development". (see INSEK-Innenstadt) In contrast to the kfw 432 process, which is starting in parallel (coordinated by Nadine Somberg, also from the Climate Unit), more innovative approaches and the procedure with regard to any challenging initial conditions (protection of historical monuments, etc.) can be tested once again. The results of UP2030 will be incorporated and further developed in the kfw process, which will continue for years.

Further climate-relevant measures are also implemented or planned in the other areas; these can be co-designed via UP2030 and communicated to the EU.

Challenges and opportunities

Münsters Innenstadt steht im Vergleich zu vielen anderen Innenstädten gut da. Garanten für dieses gute Zeugnis sind vor allem:

- die historisch geprägte Stadtstruktur mit ihrem pittoresken Stadtbild, mit dem Netz lebendiger Stadträume, dem stadträumlich ablesbaren Grünring und der Promenade, die für die

heutige Innenstadt ein reiches Erbe darstellt,

- die kompakte, gut bestückte Handelslage, die kaum Lücken aufweist und lediglich an ihren Rändern flüchtig ist,

- die vitale Ausstrahlung, das Stadtleben, das zusätzlich von vielen Studierenden geprägt ist und die Universitäts- und Bildungsstadt darin abfärben lässt,

- und in diesem Zusammenhang auch die Vielfalt an Kultur- und Bildungseinrichtungen,

- der vergleichsweise hohe Wohnanteil mit Schulen und Angeboten zur Kindertagesbetreuung, die mit zur Lebendigkeit und Sicherheit beitragen und der Innenstadt eine Alltagsnote geben und schließlich auch

- eine aktive und interessierte Stadtgesellschaft, die eine gute Balance von Werten bewahrenden Prinzipien und dem Neuen gegenüber offenen Einstellungen zeigt.

Münster's city center compares favorably with many other downtown areas. Guarantors for this good report card are above all:

- the historically shaped urban structure with its picturesque cityscape, with the network of lively urban spaces, the green ring that can be read in terms of urban space and the promenade, which represents a rich heritage for today's inner city,
- the compact, well-stocked retail location, which has hardly any gaps and is only volatile at its edges, - the vital charisma, the city life, which is additionally characterized by many students and allows the university and educational city to rub off on it,
- and in this context also the variety of cultural and educational institutions,
- the comparatively high residential share with schools and offers for day care, which contribute to the liveliness and security and give the city center an everyday touch and finally also
- an active and interested urban society, which shows a good balance of values preserving principles and attitudes open to the new.

Trotz der guten Ausgangslage gilt es für zukünftige Veränderungen und Herausforderungen gewappnet zu sein. So sind unausgeschöpfte Potenziale, neue gesamtgesellschaftliche Herausforderungen, das Bewahren der jetzigen Stärken und zukunftsorientierte Akzentsetzungen, welche die Notwendigkeit des Planens und Handelns auslösen.

Despite the good starting position, it is important to be prepared for future changes and challenges. So, it is unexploited potentials, new challenges for society as a whole, the preservation of current strengths and future-oriented accents that trigger the need for planning and action.

Die Themen Klimaschutz und Klimaanpassung sind zentrale Zukunftsthemen in der nachhaltigen Stadtentwicklung und wirken in sehr viele Lebensbereiche hinein. Auch bei der Innenstadtentwicklung sind ortsangepasste Lösungen zur Verbesserung des Stadtklimas als Beitrag zu Klimaschutz, -anpassung und -gerechtigkeit notwendig und zu berücksichtigen. Insbesondere in den Themenfeldern Grünräume und Wasser (s. Kap. 2.4), Mobilität (s. Kap. 2.8) und öffentlicher Raum (s. Kap 2.2) sind Maßnahmen möglich, die positive Auswirkungen auf das Stadtklima und die Klimaanpassung haben können, aber auch Bereiche wie die Energieversorgung oder das klimaneutrale Bauen und Sanieren sind wichtige Zukunftsthemen. Auch die Innenstadt Münsters kann einen gewissen Beitrag leisten, um die gesetzten Ziele zum Klimaschutz und zur Klimaanpassung zu erreichen. Hier konzentrieren sich viele städtische Aktivitäten, Herausforderungen und neue Entwicklungen, weshalb die Innenstadt eine gewisse Impulswirkung auch auf andere Stadtteile und Projekte haben kann. (s. S.36)

The topics of climate protection and climate adaptation are central issues for the future in sustainable urban development and have an impact on many areas of life. In inner-city development, too, locally appropriate solutions for improving the urban climate are necessary and must be considered as a contribution to climate protection, adaptation and justice. Measures that can have a positive impact on the urban climate and climate adaptation are possible in the subject areas of green spaces and water (see chap. 2.4 of the INSEK), mobility (see chap. 2.8 of the INSEK) and public space (see. chap. 2.2 of the INSEK), but areas such as energy supply or climate-neutral construction and renovation are also important topics for the future. Münster's city centre can also make a certain contribution to achieving the climate protection and climate adaptation goals that have been set. Many urban activities, challenges and new developments are concentrated here, which is why the city centre can have a certain impulse effect on other city districts and projects as well. (see p.36)

Münsters Altstadt ist aufgrund ihrer städtebaulichen Kompaktheit und historischen Stadtgestalt stark versiegelt und deshalb insgesamt als eine große Hitzeinsel zu bewerten.

(s. S. 36)

Due to its compact urban structure and historic urban design, Münster's old town is heavily sealed and must therefore be assessed as a large heat island overall. (see p. 36)

Die großen Grünanlagen wie die Promenade, der Schlossgarten und der Aasee mit den angrenzenden Grünflächen wirken kühlend und dienen als Freizeit- und Erholungsflächen. Ansonsten verfügt die Münsteraner Innenstadt über wenig klimaresilientes Grün. Um die bestehenden Bäume sowie zusätzliche Neupflanzungen zu sichern, ist sowohl auf die Auswahl klimaangepasster Pflanzenarten, auf eine gute Standortgestaltung als auch auf deren Versorgung mit Wasser zu achten. (S.36)

The large green spaces such as the Promenade, the Schlossgarten and the Aasee with the adjacent green areas have a cooling effect and serve as leisure and recreational areas. Otherwise, Münster's inner city has little climate-sensitive green space. In order to secure the existing trees as well as additional new plantings, attention must be paid to both the selection of climate-adapted plant species, good site design, and their supply with water. (p.36)

In Bezug auf Energienutzung und -erzeugung in der Münsteraner Innenstadt und insbesondere auch in der Altstadt gibt es eine Vielzahl an Dachflächen, die Potenziale für Gründächer und Photovoltaik bieten. Auch liegt im Gebäudebestand der Alt- und Innenstadt ein enormes, nicht ausgeschöpftes energetisches Sanierungspotenzial verborgen, das zur Erreichung einer Klimaneutralität der Stadt gehoben werden sollte. Die Wahrung der historischen Stadtgestalt und die Erfordernisse des Denkmalschutzes können dabei mit dem Klimaschutz Hand in Hand gehen. Auch das Angebot an leitungsgebundenen regenerativen Energie- und Wärmeversorgungsstrukturen ist noch ausbaufähig. (S.37)

In terms of energy use and generation in downtown Münster and especially in the old town, there are many roof areas that offer potential for green roofs and photovoltaics. The building stock in the old town and city centre also offers enormous untapped potential for energy-efficient renovation, which should be exploited to achieve climate neutrality in the city. The preservation of the historic urban form and the requirements of historic preservation can go hand in hand with climate protection. The supply of grid-based renewable energy and heat supply structures can also be expanded. (p.37)

Auf dem Weg zu mehr Vielfalt und großstädtischem Flair stellen wesentliche Zukunftsaufgaben zusätzliche Herausforderungen für die Entwicklung der Innenstadt dar: Klimagerechte, inklusive, interkulturelle, barrierefreie und offene Innenstadt, Wandel der City-Funktionen und Verkehrswende.

On the path to more diversity and metropolitan flair, key future tasks pose additional challenges for the development of the city center: Climate-friendly, inclusive, intercultural, barrier-free and open city center, change of city functions and traffic turnaround.

Mit dem politischen Beschluss der Vorlage V/0314/2023 "Energetische Stadtsanierung (KfW 432) - Zukunftsfähige, nutzungsflexible Stadtquartiere fördern – Klimaschutz, Wohnangebote, Energieversorgung, Mobilität und Nahversorgung und weitere Themen in Münster integriert betrachten" am 20.9.2023 soll die energetische Quartierssanierung systematisch weiter vorangetrieben werden.

Dieses Handeln ist aufgrund der Tatsache, dass die CO₂-Emissionen im Wärmebereich bei ca. 40% im Vergleich zu den Gesamtemissionen im Stadtgebiet von Münster (Stand 2021) liegen und dass zur Erreichung des Ziels der Klimaneutralität der CO₂-Ausstoß der bestehenden Gebäude in Münster so schnell wie möglich noch deutlicher reduziert werden muss notwendig.

With the political resolution of the submission V/0314/2023 "Energy-efficient urban redevelopment (KfW 432) - Promoting sustainable, flexible-use urban districts - integrated consideration of climate protection, housing, energy supply, mobility and local supply and other topics in Münster" on 20.9.2023, the energy-efficient urban district redevelopment is to be systematically advanced. This action is necessary due to the fact that CO₂ emissions in the heating sector are around 40% of total emissions in the city of Münster (as of 2021) and that the CO₂ emissions of existing buildings in Münster must be reduced even more significantly as quickly as possible in order to achieve the goal of climate neutrality.

Dabei bietet der Quartiersansatz im Vergleich zur Betrachtung von Einzelgebäuden die Möglichkeit, Effizienzpotenziale und Handlungsansätze nicht nur im Einzelobjekt, sondern im städtebaulichen und energetischen Zusammenhang zu identifizieren. Neben den notwendigen energetischen Sanierungsmaßnahmen und der regenerativen Energie- und Wärmeversorgung werden zusätzliche Fragestellungen zur energetischen Stadtsanierung aus funktionalen, sozialen, ökologischen sowie ökonomischen Gründen hinsichtlich eines integrierten Handlungsansatzes mitberücksichtigt.

In comparison to looking at individual buildings, the neighborhood approach offers the opportunity to identify efficiency potential and approaches not only in individual buildings, but also in an urban planning and energy context. In addition to the necessary energy-efficient refurbishment measures and the renewable energy and heat supply, additional issues relating to energy-efficient urban refurbishment are taken into account for functional, social, ecological and economic reasons with regard to an integrated approach to action.

Ein Quartierskonzept ermöglicht maßgeschneiderte Lösungen angepasst an die speziellen Anforderungen des Quartiers. Um einen größtmöglichen Nutzen der zu erarbeitenden Quartierskonzepte zu erzielen, sollen die Potenziale der „Energetischen Stadtsanierung“ in verschiedenen Stadtteilen analysiert und die Auswahl sowie die Schwerpunktsetzung der Quartierskonzepte aufeinander abgestimmt werden, so dass die durch die Quartierskonzepte entwickelten Lösungsansätze auch auf weitere Stadtteile übertragen werden können. (Immer angepasst an die individuellen örtlichen Gegebenheiten im jeweiligen Quartier.) Diese hohe Übertragbarkeit der Ergebnisse aus den zukünftigen Quartierskonzepten kann positive Erkenntnisse für die zukünftige Entwicklung des gesamten Stadtgebietes Münster liefern.

A neighborhood concept enables tailor-made solutions adapted to the specific requirements of the neighborhood. In order to achieve the greatest possible benefit from the district concepts to be developed, the potential of "energy-efficient urban refurbishment" in various districts should be analyzed and the selection and focus of the district concepts should be coordinated so that the solutions developed through the district concepts can also be transferred to other districts. (Always adapted to the individual local conditions in the respective neighborhood). This high degree of transferability of the results from the future neighborhood concepts can provide positive insights for the future development of the entire city of Münster.

Um eine quartiersübergreifende Gesamtstrategie für die Stadt zu erhalten, soll die Auswahl der Quartiere verschiedene Handlungsschwerpunkte und vorherrschende Rahmenbedingungen in den Handlungsfeldern der energetischen Stadtsanierung aufweisen.

In order to obtain an overall strategy for the city across all neighborhoods, the selection of neighborhoods should show different focal points for action and prevailing framework conditions in the fields of action of energy-efficient urban refurbishment.

Dieses Vorgehen sollte laut dem Beschluss vor allem im Rahmen des Förderprogramms "Energetische Stadtsanierung - Zuschuss (432)" (kfw-432) vorangetrieben werden. Geplant war die Erstellung von drei Sanierungskonzepten in drei unterschiedlichen Pilot-Quartieren und die Beantragung von Sanierungsmanager*innen, die die Maßnahmen aus den Konzepten in den darauf folgenden Jahren umsetzen. Die Konzepte sollten neben dem Schwerpunkt auf die Sanierung auch Maßnahmen zur Klimaanpassung beinhalten.

According to the resolution, this approach was to be driven forward primarily as part of the "Energy-efficient urban refurbishment - grant (432)" (kfw-432) funding program. The plan was to create three refurbishment concepts in three different pilot districts and apply for refurbishment managers to implement the measures from the concepts in the following years. In addition to the focus on refurbishment, the concepts should also include climate adaptation measures.

Allerdings wurde das Förderprogramm im November 2023 durch die kfw-Bank in Abstimmung mit dem Bundesministerium für Wohnen, Stadtentwicklung und Bauwesen (BMWSB) vorerst eingestellt. Bis auf Weiteres können keine Anträge mehr gestellt werden. Hintergrund ist die seit November 2023 haushaltswirtschaftliche Sperre nach § 41 BHO für Verpflichtungs-ermächtigungen im Bundeshaushalt 2023 sowie im Sonder-vermögen Klima- und Transformations-fonds (KTF).

However, the funding program was discontinued for the time being in November 2023 by kfw-Bank in coordination with the Federal Ministry of Housing, Urban Development and Building (BMWSB). No more applications can be submitted until further notice. The background to this is the budget freeze since November 2023 in accordance with Section 41 BHO for commitment appropriations in the 2023 federal budget and in the special fund Climate and Transformation Fund (KTF).

Current approach and actions

Über UP2030 besteht die Möglichkeit die Maßnahmen aus dem INSEK weiter miteinander zu verschneiden, erste Ansätze für ein Vorgehen zu entwickeln um die Herausforderungen und Chancen, die sich auch im ersten Workshop von UP2030 gezeigt haben anzugehen, und so den Weg eines Prototypens für ein Klima-Quartier in Münsters Innenstadt abzuleiten. Und dabei im Sinne des Beschlusses vom 20.9.2023 zur Vorlage V/0314/2023 (Zukunftsfähige, nutzungsflexible Stadtquartiere fördern – Klimaschutz, Wohnangebote, Energieversorgung, Mobilität und Nahversorgung und weitere Themen in Münster integriert betrachten.) zu handeln.

UP2030 offers the opportunity to further intersect the measures from the INSEK, to develop initial approaches for a procedure to tackle the challenges and opportunities that also emerged in the first UP2030 workshop, and thus to derive the path of a prototype for a climate quarter in Münster's city center. And to act in accordance with the resolution of 20.9.2023 on submission V/0314/2023 (Promoting sustainable, flexible-use urban districts - integrated consideration of climate protection, housing offers, energy supply, mobility and local supply and other topics in Münster).

Der räumliche Fokus der Betrachtung wird bei UP2030 auf dem Quartier Frauenstraße/Gesamtschule Münster-Mitte/Überwasserkirchplatz/Überwasserstraße liegen. Das Projektgebiet stimmt annähernd mit den Grenzen der Stadtzelle Überwasser überein, eine von 174 Stadtzellen in die Münster unterteilt ist. In dem ausgewählten Quartier sind viele der oben beschriebenen Beiträge und Ziele in Ansätzen darstellbar.

The spatial focus of the UP2030 study will be on the Frauenstraße/Gesamtschule Münster-Mitte/Überwasserkirchplatz/Überwasserstraße district. The project area roughly coincides with the boundaries of the Überwasser city cell, one of 174 city cells into which Münster is divided. Many of the contributions and objectives described above can be realized to some extent in the selected district.

Geplant ist, dass über das Projekt UP2030 konzeptionelle Grundlagen erarbeitet, werden bzw. in einem Leitfaden zusammengefasst werden, die darstellen welche Planungsvorgaben/ -instrumente, kurz-, mittel- und langfristige Maßnahmen, Datengrundlagen, Fördermöglichkeiten, Beteiligungsansätze etc. grundsätzlich in Bestandsquartieren beachtet werden sollten oder können. Diese ermöglichen dann eine schnellere Erstellung von Konzepten bzw. einer ersten Einschätzung und die Umsetzung von Maßnahmen

in vergleichbaren Quartieren. UP2030 wird dabei besonders auf die Synergien zwischen Klimaanpassungs- und Klimaschutzmaßnahmen sowie auf Beteiligungsansätze, die über Beratungs- und Informationsangebote hinausgehen, fokussieren und sich dabei an der Climate Proofing Methode von Büro Happold (einem Projektpartner aus dem UP2030 Konsortium) orientieren.

Bei dem Workshop im Mai wurden die fehlenden Umsetzungsmöglichkeiten von Projekten der Anwohnenden, sowie fehlende Akzeptanz und Verständnis von klimagerechten Maßnahmen als eine Herausforderung identifiziert.

It is planned that the UP2030 project will be used to develop conceptual principles or summarize them in a guideline that shows which planning specifications/instruments, short, medium and long-term measures, data bases, funding opportunities, participation approaches, etc. should or can be taken into account in existing districts. These then enable concepts to be drawn up more quickly or an initial assessment to be made and measures to be implemented in comparable neighborhoods. UP2030 will focus in particular on the synergies between climate adaptation and climate protection measures as well as on participation approaches that go beyond consulting and information offers and will be based on the climate proofing method of Büro Happold (a project partner from the UP2030 consortium).

At the workshop in May, the lack of opportunities for residents to implement projects and the lack of acceptance and understanding of climate-friendly measures were identified as a challenge.

Über UP2030 soll daher der stadtweit etablierte Ansatz des KlimaTrainings auf Quartiersebene weiterentwickelt werden und so ein mögliches systematisches Vorgehen, welches die Umsetzung von Maßnahmen durch Stakeholder im Quartier sowie die Akzeptanz von diesen fördert, erarbeitet werden.

Ein wichtiger Aspekt für die Umsetzung ist darüber hinaus die finanzielle, aber auch ideelle Förderung von Projekten Dritter. Dabei soll der Ansatz der Etablierung eines Klimafonds in Münster auch auf die Stakeholder (sowohl Bürger*innen, als auch Einzelhändler*innen, Unternehmen, Initiativen etc.) ausgearbeitet werden.

Die Ergebnisse aus UP2030, die auf die Beförderung von Klimastadt-Quartieren einzahlen, richten sich primär an Verwaltungsakteure und soll sie bei der Umsetzung von Klimastadt-Quartieren unterstützen und das vorhandene Wissen bündeln.

UP2030 therefore aims to further develop the established city-wide approach of climate training at neighborhood level and thus develop a possible systematic approach that promotes the implementation of measures by stakeholders in the neighborhood and their acceptance.

Another important aspect of implementation is the financial and non-material support of third-party projects. The approach of establishing a climate fund in Münster will also be developed for stakeholders (citizens, retailers, companies, initiatives, etc.).

The results from UP2030, which contribute to the promotion of urban climate districts, are primarily aimed at administrative actors and support them in the implementation of urban climate districts and pool existing knowledge.

Ende Oktober hat die Stabsstelle Klima die Zusage für das Projekt Future BEEing Projekt erhalten. Dabei handelt es sich um ein Interreg VI C Projekt, das gemeinsam mit der Gemeinde Enschede, energieland2050, Gemeinde Hengelo, Buro de Haan, Küsters.Grün.Stadt.Klima, FH Münster und der Saxion Hochschule.

At the end of October, the Climate Unit received approval for the Future BEEing project. This is an Interreg VI C project that is being carried out jointly with the municipality of Enschede, energieland2050, the municipality of Hengelo, Buro de Haan, Küsters.Grün.Stadt.Klima, Münster University of Applied Sciences and Saxion University of Applied Sciences.

Den Teil, den die Stadt Münster in dem Projekt erarbeitet, wird die Erstellung eines Lastenhefts zur Entwicklung eines digitalen Werkzeugs sein, das einen integrierten Überblick über alle Maßnahmen und unterschiedliche Szenarien darstellt, die die Zukunftsfähigkeit eines Quartiers fördern können. Es ist ein u.a. ein wichtiges Instrument zur Beantwortung von Planungsfragen im Zusammenhang mit Sanierungen und Umstrukturierung bestehender Quartiere in Verbindung mit ihren Kostenpunkten. Die Planungsfragen beziehen sich auf energetische Effizienz, Wetterbeständigkeit und Standards für nachhaltige Quartiersentwicklung. Das Tool wird dann darauffolgend von dem weiteren Partner*innen entwickelt und hat als Zielgruppe Einzeleigentümer*innen, Genossenschaften, Eigentümergemeinschaften und Investoren.

Die Ergebnisse sowohl aus UP2030 als auch aus Future BEEing sollen in den weiteren Prozess der energetischen Quartierssanierung aufgenommen, genutzt und weiterentwickelt werden.

Further aspects and actions, which are relevant to the UP2030 process

- The concept of the successful implemented approach of Climate Trainings in Münster and furthermore the approach of a concept and implementation of a KlimaTraining on the neighborhood scale. This should enable the participant, who live in neighborhood not only to change their lifestyle in the context of their everyday behaviour. Additionally, it should motivate the participants to do something for their neighborhood itself in the form of the creation of more green spaces on the streets, rainwater management, urban gardening, green facades, the colour of facades and the use of renewable energy and refurbishment. As in the original concept of the KlimaTraining there will be companies, organisations and experts who share knowledge and offer a wide range of different try out possibilities.
- The drafting of the 5th Charta of the European Union on equality between men and women. There will be some workshops with different stakeholders during the year 2023. The results could be helpful for the up2030 Pilot in Münster.
- The Climate City Contract. In the context of the City-Mission Münster will organise different formats of workshops and event to enable different stakeholders to develop the Climate City Contract. That will be a workshop with stakeholders of bigger companies with a high emission footprint, the City Forum an event with different workshops and stakeholders. In October the Climate City Week will take place in the whole city. The idea is to discuss the approach of the up2030-neighborhood during the City Forum and the Climate City Week as well.
- The different projects we already had in the context of up2030 like the Mulitklima project.
- The communication approach of the Climate Office.

- The informal/ formal planning instruments like the climate-friendly urban land use planning.
- The development for a climate fund
- And as well the following instruments and concepts:
 - Climate Protection Plan, Strategy & Action Program 2030
 - Concept on Climate Adaptation & Action Program 2030
 - Sustainability Strategy Münster 2030
 - EU 100 Climate Neutral and Smart Cities
 - Annual municipal balance on energy & GHG Emissions
 - Green Spaces Ordinance - defines the green system
 - Green potential roof register
 - Solar potential roof register
 - Wastewater and rainwater management concept
 - Climate-friendly urban land use planning
 - Future Beeing Tool
 - Energienutzungsplanung (kommunale Wärmeplanung) wird erarbeitet
 - Digitale Zwilling der Stadtwerke

Needs and aspirations

Folgenden Maßnahmen aus dem Handlungsfeld „Grün und klimagerecht“ aus dem INSEK könnten über UP2030 weiterverfolgt werden:

1.1 Maßnahmen zur qualitätsvollen energetischen und klimagerechten Objektsanierung, Sanierungsmanagement und Aufklärungs- und Informationsmaßnahmen

1.2 Aufstellung einer Priorisierung von Maßnahmen zur Klimaanpassung für die Innenstadt

1.3 Programm „Grüne und solare Dächer und Fassaden in der Innenstadt“

1.5 Programm „Zukunftsbäume“

1.7 Weiterentwicklung und Umsetzung des Aa-Konzeptes für die Innenstadt-Aa

1.8 Intensivierung einer gezielten Bewirtschaftung von Regenwasser

1.9 Klima- und artenschutzgerechte Anpassung und Umsetzung „Masterplan Licht“

1.10 Konzept zur Weiterentwicklung und Ausbau von leitungsgebundenen Energie- und Wärmeversorgungsstrukturen im gesamten Innenstadtbereich

The following measures from the field of action "Green and climate-friendly" from the INSEK could be pursued further via UP2030:

- 1.1 Measures for high-quality energetic and climate-friendly refurbishment of buildings, refurbishment management and education and information measures.
- 1.2 Prioritisation of climate adaptation measures for the city centre
- 1.3 "Green and solar roofs and facades in the inner city" programme
- 1.5 Programme "Trees of the Future"
- 1.7 Further development and implementation of the Aa concept for the inner city Aa
- 1.8 Intensification of targeted rainwater management
- 1.9 Adaptation and implementation of the "Light Master Plan" to protect the climate and species
- 1.10 Concept for the further development and expansion of grid-based energy and heat supply structures in the entire inner-city area.

Abb. 72: Zukunftsszenario Frauenstraße (Darstellung: WILLNER VISUALISIERUNG)

Abb. 73: Frauenstraße, 2022 (Foto: Stadt Münster)

People, Partners, Organisations and more

The stakeholder list shows the relevant people so far.

Relevant in the process are the people of the city council – from different departments

There we identified:

There have already been some meetings and interviews with some of the people about the approach and their role. In the stakeholder list are some notes about the current state of the involvement so far. Further exchange appointments are already terminated for April.

The first workshop was on the 24th of May. It is a kind of intern kick-off with the aim to analyse further what is needed for a climate-friendly neighborhood in Münster.

Guiding questions are: What is a climate-friendly neighbourhood in Münster? Which instruments for planning and implementation do we already have? Which ones do we still need? Who needs to be involved? How can residents be involved? Analysis of strengths and weaknesses in this fields.

Activities undertaken as part of UP2030

Setting up of Learning Action Alliance

In Münster, the Learning and Action Alliances (LAA) process is restricted to internal City Hall stakeholders. In the beginning, the Climate Office (which is coordinating the UP2030 project for Münster) wanted to cooperate with the Mobility and Civil Engineering departments,

- [230323 UP2030 Stakeholder list Muenster EXTERN-without_contact_details.xlsx](#)

After the needs workshop, Munster conducted interviews with local stakeholders in the Fraunstrasse district to further map needs. Some of the initial ideas that came out of this engagement process point to the implementation of an Urban Living Lab through car exclusion, temporary green structures and long-term measures such as asphalt unsealing. For the latter measure, Munster is engaging with a local master's student who is specializing in this field.

Next steps of Munster LAA's process include a site visit with the Diocese of Munster (a major building owner in the city) and additional meetings regarding the unsealing of surfaces.

An extensive needs analysis process

Die Stadt Münster führte einen Bedarfsworkshop mit ihren internen kommunalen Akteuren durch. Der Workshop zeigte zwei Hauptthemen auf: die Notwendigkeit einer internen Zusammenarbeit der Abteilungen, um Siloarbeit zu vermeiden, und die Möglichkeiten zur Anpassung und Integration des Klima-Trainings.

Muenster implemented its needs workshop with its internal municipal stakeholders. The workshop revealed two primary themes: the need for internal department collaboration to eliminate silo working and the opportunities to adapt and integrate the Klima Training.

Es wurden Kommunikationslücken zwischen den städtischen Abteilungen aufgezeigt, insbesondere in Bezug auf Projektplanung, Zeitplanung und Strategie. Dies unterstreicht die Notwendigkeit eines umfassenden digitalen Planungsinstruments, das allen Abteilungen zugänglich ist, um das isolierte Arbeiten zu überwinden. Die vorgeschlagene Plattform sollte Daten integrieren, insbesondere bei der Kartierung räumlicher Elemente wie Gebäudebestand und Grünstrukturen. Denn es gibt ein Missverhältnis zwischen Daten und Instrumenten zur Bewertung des Gebäudebestands im Vergleich zu neuen

Baugebieten, die von neuen Leitlinien für eine klimafreundliche städtische Flächennutzung profitieren. Die Fokussierung und Angleichung der Planungsbemühungen ist daher ein Aspekt, den UP2030 angehen könnte. Die ressortübergreifende Zusammenarbeit wird als wesentlich erachtet, und obwohl die erste Diskussion mit den Akteuren von Vorteil war, muss sie weiter vertieft werden.

Communication gaps between city departments were highlighted, specifically related to project planning, timing and strategy. This emphasised the need for a comprehensive digital planning instrument accessible to all departments to address siloed working. The proposed platform should integrate data, particularly in mapping spatial elements like building stock and green structures. This is because there is a disparity in data and instruments for evaluating existing building stock compared to new building areas; which benefit from new guidelines for climate-friendly urban land use. Focusing and aligning planning efforts, therefore, is one aspect that UP2030 could address. Interdepartmental cooperation is deemed essential, and while the initial discussion with stakeholders was beneficial, it requires further exploration.

Die Workshop-Teilnehmer waren sich einig, dass die Einbindung der Bevölkerung für den Erfolg und die Nachhaltigkeit der Maßnahmen entscheidend ist. Münster ist sehr daran interessiert, den bestehenden KlimaTraining-Ansatz als Methode zur Einbindung der Gemeinde zu nutzen. Dieser Ansatz sieht vor, dass bereits engagierte Gemeindemitglieder (KlimaTrainer) auf bestehenden Beziehungen zu ihren Nachbarn und anderen Einwohnern aufbauen, um Informationen darüber zu vermitteln, wie sie vom Klimabewusstsein profitieren können.

Workshop participants agreed that community involvement is vital for the success and sustainability of measures. Muenster is keen to leverage the existing KlimaTraining approach as a method for community engagement. This approach will see already engaged members of the community (KlimaTrainers) build upon existing relationships with their neighbours and other residents to deliver information on how climate awareness can benefit them.

Münster steht vor einigen Schwierigkeiten bei der Einbindung der Bevölkerung, da eine gewisse Konsultationsmüdigkeit aufgrund früherer Klimaprojektkonsultationen, die noch nicht in die Umsetzungsphase übergegangen sind, befürchtet wird. Aus diesem Grund konzentriert sich der kurz- und mittelfristige Ansatz der Stadt Münster darauf, schnelle Erfolge zu erzielen, d. h. kostengünstige Maßnahmen, die die Stadt schnell umsetzen kann, um die Einwohner wieder einzubinden, Vertrauen aufzubauen und die Effektivität und das Engagement der Stadt zu beweisen.

Muenster faces some difficulty with community engagement as there are fears of consultation fatigue from previous climate project consultations that have not yet progressed into the implementation phase. Because of this, Muenster's short and medium-term engagement approach going forward prioritises identifying quick wins, i.e., lower-cost interventions that the city can implement quickly to reengage residents, build trust and prove the city's effectiveness and commitment.

Die Stadt Münster beabsichtigt außerdem, die bestehenden KlimaTraining-Formate anzupassen, um eine Veranstaltung in kleinerem Rahmen in der Gemeinde durchzuführen, bei der die Einwohner mit Klimapädagogen, Mitarbeitern der Stadtverwaltung und Unternehmen zusammengebracht werden, die

den Besuchern Ratschläge und Ausrüstung für Maßnahmen zur Verbesserung der Effizienz und zur Verringerung der Emissionen in ihren Haushalten anbieten können.

Muenster also aims to adapt existing KlimaTraining formats to replicate a smaller scale community event bringing together residents with climate educators, municipality staff, and businesses who may offer visitors advice and equipment for actionable steps to take within their households to improve efficiency and reduce emissions.

Der Workshop und die sich daraus ergebenden Diskussionen zeigten, dass in Münster über die traditionellen Ansätze hinaus gedacht werden muss. Das KlimaTraining-Projekt wird als wertvoll angesehen, aber es muss darauf geachtet werden, dass keine Teile der Gemeinschaft ausgeschlossen werden. Darüber hinaus ist es trotz der wahrgenommenen Konsultationsmüdigkeit wichtig, dass die Stadt in der Lage ist, direkt mit der Bevölkerung in Kontakt zu treten, um gezieltere Erkenntnisse in Bezug auf die UP2030-Mission zu gewinnen und UP2030 im Bewusstsein der Öffentlichkeit von anderen klimabezogenen Projekten in der Stadt zu unterscheiden.

The workshop and resulting discussions revealed the need for thinking beyond traditional approaches in Muenster. The KlimaTraining project is seen as valuable, but consideration is needed to avoid excluding any segments of the community. Additionally, despite the perceived consultation fatigue, it is important that the city is able to engage directly with the community to extract more focused insights related to the UP2030 mission and distinguish UP2030 in the public's awareness from other climate-related projects in the city.

In den nächsten Schritten sollten die Ziele und der Umfang des Integrierten Stadtentwicklungskonzepts (INSEK), des Programms "100 klimaneutrale Städte" und von UP2030 untersucht werden, um zu verstehen, wie sie sich gegenseitig ergänzen. Insbesondere müssen die bestehenden, laufenden und geplanten Projekte und Programme untersucht werden, um eine umfassende und ganzheitliche Vision zu schaffen, die kontextspezifisch ist.

Looking more broadly at alignment, in the next steps, the goals and scope of the Integrated City Development Concept (INSEK), the 100 Climate Neutral Cities program, and UP2030 should be examined to understand how they complement each other. Especially, there is a need to explore the existing, ongoing, and planned projects and programs to create a comprehensive and holistic vision that is context-specific.

Unter anderem die Arbeit an UP2030 und dem Climate City Contract fördert mehr und mehr den Punkt heraus, dass gerade um die Zivilgesellschaft in der Umsetzung von Projekten zu bestärken und zu unterstützen finanzielle bzw. Freie Mittel fehlen. Zudem benötigt die Transformation innovative Idee auf unterschiedlichen Ebenen. Die Stadt Münster hat wenig Möglichkeiten Projekte finanziell zu unterstützen, weil die Mittel, die im Haushalt eingestellt sind, fast ausschließlich zur Umsetzung eigener Projekte genutzt werden können. Dieser Umstand stößt mehr und mehr auf Unmut in der Bevölkerung und hemmt die so dringend notwendige Umsetzung von Projekten auf verschiedenen Ebenen.

The work on UP2030 and the Climate City Contract, among other things, is increasingly highlighting the fact that there is a lack of financial and free resources, especially to encourage and support civil society in the implementation of projects. In addition, the transformation requires innovative ideas at different levels. The City of Münster has few opportunities to support projects financially because the funds allocated in the budget can be used almost exclusively to implement its own projects. This situation is increasingly meeting with resentment among the population and is hampering the urgently needed implementation of projects at various levels.

Über eine unkomplizierte Möglichkeit Projekte finanziell zu unterstützen, könnte das Umfeld für klimafreundliches Entscheiden, das sich aus Nachfrage, aber auch aus dem zur Verfügung stehenden Angebot bedingt, (siehe Strategie für klimafreundliches Entscheiden) verstärkt werden. Zu prüfen ist wie ein Klimafond aufgebaut sein kann, welche Projekte darüber unterstützt werden, wie darüber auch die Förderung von Start-ups und innovativen Ideen von Unternehmen vorangetrieben werden können. Auch die Förderung von Quartiersansätzen über den Klimafonds – der wie oben beschrieben sehr zielführend ist- sollte überprüft werden. Am 21.11.2023 fand die Informationsveranstaltung der Agentur für kommunalen Klimaschutz am Deutschen Institut für Urbanistik (Difu) zu dem Thema “Werkzeuge für die treibhausgasneutrale Kommune: Klimafonds” statt. Ausgehend von diesem Wissen und den Erfahrungen aus dem bereits etablierten Zentrenfonds, der Projekte fördert, die zur Stärkung der Zentren dienen, findet am 9.1. eine Visionswerkstatt zu dem Thema statt. Beteiligt sind daran auch Münster Marketing und das Stadtplanungsamt. Dabei sollen verschiedene erste Varianten eines Klima Fonds entwickelt werden und Ziele, mögliche Finanzierungsmöglichkeiten für diesen Fond festgelegt werden.

Die Ergebnisse sollen am 25.1. der Politik vorgestellt werden und wenn möglich weiter diskutiert werden. The results are to be presented to politicians on January 25 and discussed further if possible. Münster wird im Februar die erste Version des Klimastadt-Vertrages einreichen. Diese Version wird auch den weiteren Weg hin zur Klimaneutralität skizzieren und auf das Thema Klimafond eingehen. Das heißt die Ergebnisse können auch gut für den Prozess genutzt werden.

An uncomplicated way of providing financial support for projects could strengthen the environment for climate-friendly decision-making, which is based on demand but also on the available supply (see strategy for climate-friendly decision-making). It is necessary to examine how a climate fund can be structured, which projects can be supported through it and how it can also be used to promote start-ups and innovative ideas from companies. The promotion of neighborhood approaches via the climate fund - which is very effective as described above - should also be reviewed. On 21.11.2023, the Agency for Municipal Climate Protection held an information event at the German Institute of Urban Affairs (Difu) on the topic of "Tools for greenhouse gas-neutral municipalities: climate funds". Based on this knowledge and the experience from the already established Center Fund, which promotes projects that serve to strengthen the centers, a vision workshop on the topic will take place on January 9. Münster Marketing and the city planning office are also involved. Various initial versions of a climate fund will be developed and objectives and possible financing options for this fund will be defined. The results are to be presented to politicians on January 25 and discussed further if possible. Münster will submit the first version of the Climate City Contract in February. This version will also outline the further path towards climate neutrality and address the issue of the climate fund. This means that the results can also be put to good use in the process.

The results of the Climate Week and the documentation of the whole process for the Climate City Contract are available under: <https://www.stadt-muenster.de/klimastadt/startseite>

Aspekt Suffizienz im Rahmen des KlimaTrainings

Further reading:

- [Final UP2030 - 1st workshop reporting Muenster 19June2023.docx](#)
- [Needs Workshop Submission Documents](#)
- <https://www.stadt-muenster.de/klimastadt/rueckblick-klimastadt-woche>
- [Fotoprotokoll KlimaBarCamp.pdf](#)

Expected next steps:

- Side visits in cooperation with the Diocese of Münster, the initiative green-instead-of-grey and a master student (thesis about the potential of unsealing of surfaces)
- Core group meetings: City of Münster, Liaison and Tool Provider (Buro Happold)
- Planning and realization of a vision workshop ◇ Creating a Vision of the Roadmap
 - Internal organizational units of the City of Münster
 - Buro Happold
 - Key stakeholders (e.g. Diocese of Münster as building owners)
 - Klima Trainers
- Focussing on key themes in the roadmap in form of smaller vision workshops for example about the Climate fund to push climate projects in the city and the neighborhood and the approach of a climate training in the neighborhood
- One bigger vision workshop about the expected content for the roadmap

Working together with tools and services

As part of the UP2030 project, several tools and services are being offered to the cities by the technical partners. These tools play an important role in how the pilot project evolves and influences the final results of the city's participation in the UP2030 project and beyond. Cities were hence encouraged to reflect on the purpose of using these tools in their process and create principles to guide the pre-selection process.

For Muenster, the tools provided by the consortium partners are an opportunity to:

- develop a systemic method to integrate synergies between mitigation and adaptation measures in urban development processes.
- promote replication in other neighbourhoods.
- enable the involvement of citizens in such processes (fulfilling their wish to establish the format of Klima Training at neighbourhood level).
- raise the acceptance of the implementation of measures among residents.

As part of the pre-selection process led by the Implementation Taskforce, Muenster has expressed interest for tools focusing on green and climate-friendly neighborhoods, targeting the issue of lack of spaces in the city centre (and therefore the needs to maximize resources, impacts and trade-offs in land-use). In addition, the city is interested in co-design roadmap and receive support in planning temporary interventions at the neighborhood level.

Following the logic above, the city has expressed interest in digital tools for planning instruments, roadmap and scenario tools, decision support system tools, as well as participatory design methods. To date, the city has started collaborating with consortium partner Buro Happold on the use of the Climate Proofing Tool. The city of Muenster aims to carry out a quick assessment of urban development projects and their impacts and potentials on both climate mitigation and adaptation, and provide high-level recommendation for decision-making. The idea is to develop further this approach and ensure public participation and acceptance in the process.

During the General Assembly in November 2023, the city & liaison had an opportunity to interact with the tool providers in order to further streamline the selection and explore which tool would be best suited to begin working with. As part of the process undertaken by the Implementation Taskforce, cities will first make a final selection of the tools, in alignment with the Visioning process, and thereafter build "implementation pathways" that map how a tool or selection of tools will be integrated in the pilot's process in UP2030.

Co-visioning phase

The co-visioning phase is anchored on a needs assessment conducted under T2.3 and previously identified objectives. This information provided a foundation for identifying specific needs and goals for Frauenstraße as a pilot area within UP2030 transformation. These elements were used to tailor the methodology to guide the co-design of a shared vision for the pilot. The detailed steps of the co-visioning with recommendations tailored to the context have been developed by the technical partners and are currently being evaluated by Münster's team. Co-design approach is a core to UP2030 process, therefore

cities and its stakeholders input for designing co-visioning process enables to develop a more specific and contextualised approach to engagement.

City is currently evaluating the feasibility of the proposal and indicating the timeline for the next steps to be taken under the co-visioning phases.

Vision workshops on three levels – Small compact rounds with lots of output

Münster

[update the process diagram once it's finalised by the city: [Guide to Co-visioning. Visioning Roadmap](#)]

As part of the preparatory activities that sets the base for the co-visioning (Milestone 1 – Validate Pilot Objectives) city is currently on validating and refined the identified key objectives. During the first year of the project, the understanding of objectives and needs has evolved and therefore the revision of objectives plays an important role for the upcoming engagement activities. With the support of the city liaisons, the activity will help to identify which aspirations are most relevant to the short-, medium- or long-term goals and to validate their relevance. [\(Full document can be found here\)](#). (provide more detailed description on the outcome once city have completed the exercise)

Additionally, the representatives of the city, with the support of liaison, will reflect on the alignment between the identified objectives and the pilot context. This exercise will help to ensure that the objectives are linked to the pilot scale and to further specify them. The full document, revealing how objectives will be linked with pilot case, as well as UP2030 project pillars [can be found here](#). *[updates will be provided after city have undergone the exercise]*

In the coming months, the city will undergo a series of engagement activities to define the vision for a resilient, carbon neutral and just future for Münster's pilot and to identify concrete actions and barriers in the light of defining adaptation pathways.

Kurzversion/ strategische Einordnung (Short Version/ Overall vision)

Klimastadt-Quartiere

1.) Einordnung

Münster hat sich früh auf den Weg gemacht, eine klimafreundliche und klimaangepasste Stadt zu werden: Unternehmen setzten früh auf Energieeffizienz und investierten in Erneuerbare Energien und Stadtverwaltung und Politik starteten vor fast 30 Jahren mit der kommunalen Klimaarbeit. Die Stadtgesellschaft zeichnet sich seit Jahrzehnten durch zahlreiche Initiativen zum Schutz des Klimas und der Umwelt aus. Auch Münster erlebt mit der Fridays for Future Bewegung seit 2019 eine starke Aufbruchsstimmung. Der Rat in Münster hat sich 2019 das ambitionierte Ziel gesetzt, bereits bis 2030 klimaneutral zu werden. Daraufhin hat die Verwaltung eine Studie beauftragt, um zu analysieren, was für die Erreichung dieses Ziels notwendig ist. Diese hat zwei Herausforderungen in den Fokus gerückt:

Die Zielerreichung gelingt nur, wenn die gesamte Stadtgesellschaft mitarbeitet

Münster kann die Erreichung des Ziels nur bis zu maximal 50 Prozent beeinflussen. Der Rest muss durch Land, Bund und EU gestaltet werden.

Münster set out early on to become a climate-friendly and climate-adapted city: Companies focused on energy efficiency early on and invested in renewable energies, and the city administration and politicians started municipal climate work almost 30 years ago. For decades, urban society has been characterized by numerous initiatives to protect the climate and the environment. Münster has also been experiencing a strong spirit of optimism since 2019 with the Fridays for Future movement. In 2019, Münster council set itself the ambitious goal of becoming climate-neutral by 2030. As a result, the administration commissioned a study to analyze what is needed to achieve this goal. This brought two challenges into focus: The target can only be achieved if the entire city society works together

Münster can only influence the achievement of the target up to a maximum of 50 percent. The rest must be shaped by the state, federal government and EU.

Münster muss jetzt der Schulterschluss gelingen – innerhalb der eigenen Stadtgesellschaft, aber auch mit Land, Bund und EU. Es reicht nicht aus, wenn nur einzelne Unternehmen, Initiativen, Privatpersonen oder die Verwaltung sich dafür einsetzen. Mit der Botschaft „Münster wird Klimastadt“ startete die Stadtverwaltung Anfang 2023 einen Prozess, der alle Akteure der Stadtgesellschaft zusammenbringt.

Münster hat dabei ihre Rolle als eine der Vorreiterinnen genutzt, um sich bei dem EU-Projekt „100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030“ zu bewerben und wurde von der EU als eine von neun Städten in Deutschland ausgewählt, die durch die EU gefördert und begleitet werden. Zudem konnte sich die Stadt erfolgreich auch weitere EU-Projekte bewerben, über die strategisch relevante Ansätze weiterentwickelt werden, wie beispielsweise die Umsetzung von Klimastadt-Quartieren.

Münster must now join forces - within its own city society, but also with the state, federal government and EU. It is not enough for individual companies, initiatives, private individuals or the administration to get involved. With the message "Münster becomes a climate city", the city administration launched a process at the beginning of 2023 that brings together all stakeholders in urban society.

Münster used its role as one of the pioneers to apply for the EU project "100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030" and was selected by the EU as one of nine cities in Germany to receive EU funding and support. The city was also successful in its application for other EU projects, which are used to further develop strategically relevant approaches, such as the implementation of climate city districts.

Klimastadt-Quartiere

Aufgrund der Tatsache, dass die CO₂-Emissionen im Wärmebereich bei ca. 40 % im Vergleich zu den Gesamtemissionen im Stadtgebiet von Münster (Stand 2021) liegen und dass zur Erreichung des Ziels der Klimaneutralität der CO₂-Ausstoß der bestehenden Gebäude in Münster so schnell wie möglich noch deutlicher reduziert werden muss, kommt den Quartieren in Münster eine besondere Bedeutung zu.

Der Quartiersansatz stellt im Vergleich zur Betrachtung von Einzelgebäuden die Möglichkeit, Effizienzpotenziale und Handlungsansätze nicht nur im Einzelobjekt, sondern im städtebaulichen und energetischen Zusammenhang zu identifizieren. Neben den notwendigen energetischen Sanierungsmaßnahmen und der regenerativen Energie- und Wärmeversorgung werden zusätzliche Fragestellungen zur energetischen Stadtsanierung aus funktionalen, sozialen, ökologischen sowie ökonomischen Gründen hinsichtlich eines integrierten Handlungsansatzes mitberücksichtigt.

Climate city districts

Due to the fact that CO₂ emissions in the heating sector are around 40% of the total emissions in the city of Münster (as of 2021) and that the CO₂ emissions of existing buildings in Münster must be reduced even more significantly as quickly as possible in order to achieve the goal of climate neutrality, the districts in Münster are of particular importance.

Compared to looking at individual buildings, the neighborhood approach makes it possible to identify efficiency potential and approaches for action not only in individual buildings, but also in an urban planning and energy context. In addition to the necessary energy-efficient refurbishment measures and the renewable energy and heat supply, additional issues relating to energy-efficient urban refurbishment are taken into account for functional, social, ecological and economic reasons with regard to an integrated approach to action.

So ermöglicht ein Quartierskonzept maßgeschneiderte Lösungen angepasst an die speziellen Anforderungen des Quartiers. Um einen größtmöglichen Nutzen der zu erarbeitenden Quartierskonzepte zu erzielen, sollen die Potenziale der „Energetischen Stadtsanierung“ in verschiedenen Stadtteilen analysiert und die Auswahl sowie die Schwerpunktsetzung der Quartierskonzepte aufeinander abgestimmt werden, so dass die durch die Quartierskonzepte entwickelten Lösungsansätze auch auf weitere Stadtteile übertragen werden können. (Immer angepasst an die individuellen örtlichen Gegebenheiten im jeweiligen Quartier.) Diese hohe Übertragbarkeit der Ergebnisse aus den zukünftigen Quartierskonzepten kann positive Erkenntnisse für die zukünftige Entwicklung des gesamten Stadtgebietes Münster liefern.

In this way, a neighborhood concept enables tailor-made solutions adapted to the specific requirements of the neighborhood. In order to achieve the greatest possible benefit from the district concepts to be developed, the potential of "energy-efficient urban refurbishment" in various districts is to be analyzed and the selection and focus of the district concepts coordinated so that the solutions developed through the district concepts can also be transferred to other districts. (Always adapted to the individual local

conditions in the respective neighborhood). This high degree of transferability of the results from the future neighborhood concepts can provide positive insights for the future development of the entire city of Münster.

Um eine quartiersübergreifende Gesamtstrategie für die Stadt zu erhalten, soll die Auswahl der Quartiere verschiedene Handlungsschwerpunkte und vorherrschende Rahmenbedingungen in den Handlungsfeldern der energetischen Stadtsanierung aufweisen.

Mit dem politischen Beschluss der Vorlage V/0314/2023 "Energetische Stadtsanierung (KfW 432) - Zukunftsfähige, nutzungsflexible Stadtquartiere fördern – Klimaschutz, Wohnangebote, Energieversorgung, Mobilität und Nahversorgung und weitere Themen in Münster integriert betrachten" am 20.9.2023 soll die energetische Quartierssanierung systematisch weiter vorangetrieben werden.

In order to obtain an overall strategy for the city across all districts, the selection of districts should show different focal points for action and prevailing framework conditions in the fields of action of energy-efficient urban redevelopment.

With the political resolution of the submission V/0314/2023 "Energy-efficient urban redevelopment (KfW 432) - Promoting sustainable, flexible-use urban districts - integrated consideration of climate protection, housing, energy supply, mobility and local supply and other topics in Münster" on 20.9.2023, the energy-efficient urban district redevelopment is to be systematically advanced.

Dieses Vorgehen sollte laut dem Beschluss vor allem im Rahmen des Förderprogramms "Energetische Stadtsanierung - Zuschuss (432)" (kfw-432) vorangetrieben werden. Geplant war die Erstellung von drei Sanierungskonzepten in drei unterschiedlichen Pilot-Quartieren und die Beantragung von Sanierungsmanager*innen, die die Maßnahmen aus den Konzepten in den darauffolgenden Jahren umsetzen. Die Konzepte sollten neben dem Schwerpunkt auf die Sanierung auch Maßnahmen zur Klimaanpassung beinhalten.

Allerdings wurde das Förderprogramm im November 2023 durch die kfw-Bank in Abstimmung mit dem Bundesministerium für Wohnen, Stadtentwicklung und Bauwesen (BMWSB) vorerst eingestellt. Bis auf Weiteres können keine Anträge mehr gestellt werden. Hintergrund ist die seit November 2023 haushaltswirtschaftliche Sperre nach § 41 BHO für Verpflichtungsermächtigungen im Bundeshaushalt 2023 sowie im Sondervermögen Klima- und Transformationsfonds (KTF).

Aber auch unabhängig von der Förderung soll das Ziel verfolgt werden.

According to the resolution, this approach was to be driven forward primarily as part of the "Energy-efficient urban refurbishment - grant (432)" (kfw-432) funding program. The plan was to create three refurbishment concepts in three different pilot districts and apply for refurbishment managers to implement the measures from the concepts in the following years. In addition to the focus on refurbishment, the concepts were also to include climate adaptation measures.

However, the funding program was discontinued for the time being in November 2023 by kfw-Bank in coordination with the Federal Ministry of Housing, Urban Development and Building (BMWSB). Applications can no longer be submitted until further notice. The background to this is the budget freeze since November 2023 in accordance with Section 41 of the Federal Budget Code (BHO) for commitment appropriations in the 2023 federal budget and in the Special Climate and Transformation Fund (KTF).

However, the goal should also be pursued independently of the funding.

So werden im Rahmen des EU-Projektes UP2030 „urban planning and design ready for 2030“ wichtige Bausteine für diesen Ansatz erarbeitet und an Hand eines Quartiers in der Innenstadt verdeutlicht und hinsichtlich deren Übertragbarkeit auf weitere Quartiere überprüft.

As part of the EU project UP2030 "urban planning and design ready for 2030", important building blocks for this approach are being developed and illustrated using a district in the city center and examined with regard to their transferability to other districts.

Bezug zum INSEK Innenstadt

In dem Anfang 2023 beschlossenen Integrierte Stadtentwicklungskonzept für die Innenstadt (INSEK Innenstadt) werden die Themen Klimaschutz und Klimaanpassung als zentrale Zukunftsthemen in der nachhaltigen Stadtentwicklung, die in sehr viele Lebensbereiche hineinwirken dargestellt.

So sind auch bei der Innenstadtentwicklung ortsangepasste Lösungen zur Verbesserung des Stadtklimas als Beitrag zu Klimaschutz, -anpassung und -gerechtigkeit notwendig und zu berücksichtigen.

Reference to the INSEK city center

In the integrated urban development concept for the city center (INSEK Innenstadt) adopted at the beginning of 2023, the topics of climate protection and climate adaptation are presented as central future topics in sustainable urban development, which have an impact on many areas of life.

This means that solutions adapted to the location to improve the urban climate are also necessary and must be taken into account in inner city development as a contribution to climate protection, adaptation and justice.

Münsters Innenstadt kann einen gewissen Beitrag leisten, um die gesetzten Ziele zum Klimaschutz und zur Klimaanpassung zu erreichen. Hier konzentrieren sich viele städtische Aktivitäten, Herausforderungen und neue Entwicklungen, weshalb die Innenstadt eine gewisse Impulswirkung auch auf andere Stadtteile und Projekte haben kann.

Münsters Altstadt ist aufgrund ihrer städtebaulichen Kompaktheit und historischen Stadtgestalt stark versiegelt und deshalb insgesamt als eine große Hitzeinsel zu bewerten.

Die großen Grünanlagen wie die Promenade, der Schlossgarten und der Aasee mit den angrenzenden Grünflächen wirken kühlend und dienen als Freizeit- und Erholungsflächen. Ansonsten verfügt die Münsteraner Innenstadt über wenig klimaresilientes Grün. Um die bestehenden Bäume sowie zusätzliche Neupflanzungen zu sichern, ist sowohl auf die Auswahl klimaangepasster Pflanzenarten, auf eine gute Standortgestaltung als auch auf deren Versorgung mit Wasser zu achten.

Münster's city center can make a certain contribution to achieving the goals set for climate protection and climate adaptation. Many urban activities, challenges and new developments are concentrated here, which is why the city center can also have a certain stimulating effect on other districts and projects.

Münster's old town is heavily sealed due to its urban compactness and historic urban form and is therefore considered a large heat island overall.

The large green spaces such as the promenade, the palace gardens and the Aasee lake with its adjacent green areas have a cooling effect and serve as leisure and recreational areas. Otherwise, Münster's city center has little climate-resilient green space. In order to safeguard the existing trees as well as additional new plantings, attention must be paid to the selection of climate-adapted plant species, good site design and their water supply.

In Bezug auf Energienutzung und -erzeugung in der Münsteraner Innenstadt und insbesondere auch in der Altstadt gibt es eine Vielzahl an Dachflächen, die Potenziale für Gründächer und Photovoltaik bieten. Auch liegt im Gebäudebestand der Alt- und Innenstadt ein enormes, nicht ausgeschöpftes energetisches Sanierungspotenzial verborgen, das zur Erreichung einer Klimaneutralität der Stadt gehoben werden sollte. Die Wahrung der historischen Stadtgestalt und die Erfordernisse des Denkmalschutzes können dabei mit dem Klimaschutz Hand in Hand gehen. Auch das Angebot an leitungsgebundenen regenerativen Energie- und Wärmeversorgungsstrukturen ist noch ausbaufähig. (s. S. 36 f INSEK Innenstadt).

Als Maßnahmen sind im Handlungsfeld 1 „Grün und klimagerecht“ unter anderem folgende Maßnahmen identifiziert worden:

1.1. Maßnahmen zur qualitätsvollen energetischen und klimagerechten Objektsanierung, Sanierungsmanagement und Aufklärungs- und Informationsmaßnahmen

1.2 Aufstellung einer Priorisierung von Maßnahmen zur Klimaanpassung für die Innenstadt

In terms of energy use and generation in Münster's city center and especially in the old town, there are a large number of roof areas that offer potential for green roofs and photovoltaics. There is also an enormous, untapped potential for energy-efficient refurbishment hidden in the building stock of the old and inner city, which should be exploited to achieve climate neutrality in the city. The preservation of the historic cityscape and the requirements of monument protection can go hand in hand with climate protection. The range of grid-based renewable energy and heat supply structures can also be expanded. (see p. 36 f INSEK city center).

The following measures, among others, have been identified in field of action 1 "Green and climate-friendly":

1.1 Measures for high-quality energy and climate-friendly property refurbishment, refurbishment management and education and information measures

1.2 Prioritization of climate adaptation measures for the city centre

2.) UP2030 zur Förderung von Klimastadt-Quartieren

Über UP2030 besteht die Möglichkeit die Maßnahmen aus dem INSEK (wie 1.1. und 1.2)

weiter miteinander zu verschneiden, erste Ansätze für ein Vorgehen zu entwickeln um die Herausforderungen und Chancen, die sich auch im ersten Workshop im Mai 2023 von UP2030 gezeigt

haben anzugehen, und so den Weg für einen Prototypen für ein Klimastadt-Quartier in Münsters Innenstadt abzuleiten.

Dieses Vorgehen zählt ebenfalls auf Beschlusses vom 20.9.2023 zur Vorlage V/0314/2023 (Zukunftsfähige, nutzungsflexible Stadtquartiere fördern – Klimaschutz, Wohnangebote, Energieversorgung, Mobilität und Nahversorgung und weitere Themen in Münster integriert betrachten.) ein.

Der räumliche Fokus der Betrachtung wird bei UP2030 auf dem Quartier Frauenstraße/Gesamtschule Münster-Mitte/Überwasserkirchplatz/Überwasserstraße liegen. Das Projektgebiet stimmt annähernd mit den Grenzen der Stadtzelle Überwasser überein, eine von 174 Stadtzellen in die Münster unterteilt ist. In dem ausgewählten Quartier sind viele der oben beschriebenen Beiträge und Ziele in Ansätzen darstellbar. Zudem wird der Raum im INSEK Innenstadt mehrfach als Potentialraum für die attraktive Verbindung zwischen Schlossplatz und Innenstadt bewertet und unter dem Handlungsfeld 2: „Vernetzt und facettenreichen“ unter der Maßnahme 2.26 „Umgestaltung und stadtgestalterische Verbesserung der Frauenstraße zu einem einladenden westlichen Altstadtzugang mit räumlicher Verknüpfung mit dem Schloss-Areal“ (s. S. 86) mit in den Maßnahmenkatalog übernommen.

2) UP2030 for the promotion of climate city districts

UP2030 provides the opportunity to further interlink the measures from the INSEK (such as 1.1. and 1.2) to further intersect with each other, to develop initial approaches for a procedure to tackle the challenges and opportunities that also emerged in the first workshop of UP2030 in May 2023, and thus to derive the path for a prototype for a climate city district in Münster's city center.

This approach also contributes to the resolution of 20.9.2023 on submission V/0314/2023 (Promoting sustainable, flexible-use urban districts - integrated consideration of climate protection, housing offers, energy supply, mobility and local supply and other topics in Münster).

The spatial focus of UP2030 will be on the Frauenstraße/Gesamtschule Münster-Mitte/Überwasserkirchplatz/Überwasserstraße district. The project area roughly coincides with the boundaries of the Überwasser city cell, one of 174 city cells into which Münster is divided. In the selected district, many of the contributions and objectives described above can be realized to some extent. In the INSEK Innenstadt, the area is also assessed several times as a potential space for the attractive connection between Schlossplatz and the city center and is included in the catalog of measures under field of action 2: "Networked and multi-faceted" under measure 2.26 "Redesign and urban design improvement of Frauenstraße to create an inviting western access to the old town with a spatial link to the castle area" (see p. 86).

Geplant ist, dass über das Projekt UP2030 konzeptionelle Grundlagen erarbeitet, werden bzw. in einem Leitfaden zusammengefasst werden, die darstellen welche Planungsvorgaben/ -instrumente, kurz-, mittel- und langfristige Maßnahmen, Datengrundlagen, Fördermöglichkeiten, Beteiligungsansätze etc. grundsätzlich in Bestandsquartieren beachtet werden sollten oder können.

Diese ermöglichen dann eine schnellere Erstellung von Konzepten bzw. einer ersten Einschätzung und die Umsetzung von Maßnahmen in vergleichbaren Quartieren. UP2030 wird dabei besonders auf die Synergien zwischen Klimaanpassungs- und Klimaschutzmaßnahmen sowie auf Beteiligungsansätze, die über Beratungs- und Informationsangebote hinausgehen, fokussieren und sich dabei an der Climate Proofing Methode von Büro Happold (einem Projektpartner aus dem UP2030 Konsortium) orientieren.

It is planned that the UP2030 project will be used to develop conceptual principles or summarize them in a guideline that shows which planning specifications/instruments, short, medium and long-term measures, data bases, funding opportunities, participation approaches, etc. should or can be taken into account in existing districts.

These then enable concepts to be drawn up more quickly or an initial assessment to be made and measures to be implemented in comparable neighborhoods. UP2030 will focus in particular on the synergies between climate adaptation and climate protection measures as well as on participation approaches that go beyond consulting and information offers and will be based on the climate proofing method of Büro Happold (a project partner from the UP2030 consortium).

Bei dem Workshop im Mai wurden die fehlenden Umsetzungsmöglichkeiten von Projekten der Anwohnenden, sowie fehlende Akzeptanz und Verständnis von klimagerechten Maßnahmen als eine Herausforderung identifiziert.

Über UP2030 soll daher der stadtweit etablierte Ansatz des KlimaTrainings auf Quartiersebene weiterentwickelt werden und so ein mögliches systematisches Vorgehen, welches die Umsetzung von Maßnahmen durch Stakeholder im Quartier sowie die Akzeptanz von diesen fördert, erarbeitet werden.

Ein wichtiger Aspekt für die Umsetzung ist darüber hinaus die finanzielle, aber auch ideelle Förderung von Projekten Dritter. Dabei soll der Ansatz der Etablierung eines Klimafonds in Münster auch auf die Stakeholder (sowohl Bürger*innen, als auch Einzelhändler*innen, Unternehmen, Initiativen etc.) ausgearbeitet werden.

Die Ergebnisse aus UP2030, die auf die Beförderung von Klimastadt-Quartieren einzahlen, richten sich primär an Verwaltungsakteure und soll sie bei der Umsetzung von Klimastadt-Quartieren unterstützen und das vorhandene Wissen bündeln.

At the workshop in May, the lack of opportunities for residents to implement projects and the lack of acceptance and understanding of climate-friendly measures were identified as a challenge.

UP2030 therefore aims to further develop the established city-wide approach of climate training at neighborhood level and thus develop a possible systematic approach that promotes the implementation of measures by stakeholders in the neighborhood and their acceptance.

Another important aspect of implementation is the financial and non-material support of third-party projects. The approach of establishing a climate fund in Münster will also be developed for stakeholders (citizens, retailers, companies, initiatives, etc.).

The results from UP2030, which contribute to the promotion of climate city districts, are primarily aimed at administrative actors and are intended to support them in the implementation of climate city districts and to bundle existing knowledge.

3.1. Future Beeing

Ende Oktober hat die Stabsstelle Klima die Zusage für das Projekt Future BEEing Projekt erhalten. Dabei handelt es sich um ein Interreg VI C Projekt, das gemeinsam mit der Gemeinde Enschede, energieland2050, Gemeinde Hengelo, Buro de Haan, Küsters.Grün.Stadt.Klima, FH Münster und der Saxion Hochschule.

Den Teil, den die Stadt Münster in dem Projekt erarbeitet, wird die Erstellung eines Lastenhefts zur Entwicklung eines digitalen Werkzeugs sein, das einen integrierten Überblick über alle Maßnahmen und unterschiedliche Szenarien darstellt, die die Zukunftsfähigkeit eines Quartiers fördern können. Es ist ein u.a. ein wichtiges Instrument zur Beantwortung von Planungsfragen im Zusammenhang mit Sanierungen und Umstrukturierung bestehender Quartiere in Verbindung mit ihren Kostenpunkten. Die Planungsfragen beziehen sich auf energetische Effizienz, Wetterbeständigkeit und Standards für nachhaltige Quartiersentwicklung. Das Tool wird dann darauffolgend von dem weiteren Partner*innen entwickelt und hat als Zielgruppe Einzeleigentümer*innen, Genossenschaften, Eigentümergemeinschaften und Investoren.

Die Ergebnisse sowohl aus UP2030 als auch aus Future BEEing sollen in den weiteren Prozess der energetischen Quartierssanierung aufgenommen, genutzt und weiterentwickelt werden.

3.1 Future Beeing

At the end of October, the Climate Unit received approval for the Future BEEing project. This is an Interreg VI C project that is being carried out jointly with the municipality of Enschede, energieland2050, the municipality of Hengelo, Buro de Haan, Küsters.Grün.Stadt.Klima, Münster University of Applied Sciences and Saxion University.

The part that the city of Münster is working on in the project will be the creation of a specification sheet for the development of a digital tool that provides an integrated overview of all measures and different scenarios that can promote the sustainability of a neighborhood. Among other things, it is an important instrument for answering planning questions in connection with the refurbishment and restructuring of existing neighborhoods in conjunction with their cost points. The planning questions relate to energy efficiency, weather resistance and standards for sustainable neighborhood development. The tool will then be developed by the other partners and is aimed at individual owners, cooperatives, owners' associations and investors.

The results from both UP2030 and Future BEEing are to be incorporated, used and further developed in the ongoing process of energy-efficient district refurbishment.

3.2. Betrachtung von Prototypen-Gebäuden für energetische/klimagerechte Sanierung

Siehe auch Maßnahme 1.1 des INSEKS

3.2 Consideration of prototype buildings for energy/climate-friendly refurbishment

See also measure 1.1 of the INSEKS

4.) Vorgehen

Der Ansatz der Beförderung von Klimastadt-Quartieren soll bis Mai durch eine Reihe von Workshops konkretisiert werden, deren Ergebnisse dann im Weiteren umgesetzt werden.

Folgende Workshops sind angedacht:

Workshop Strategie Klimastadt-Quartiere

Teilnehmende: Vertreter*innen der Stabsstelle Klima und Team Münsters Mitte Machen

Ziel: Übergeordnete Vision für das strategische Vorgehen für die Förderung von Klimastadt-Quartieren erarbeiten. Ausgehend von dem oben beschriebenen Ansatz sollen Bausteine ergänzt, und konkretisiert sowie die jeweiligen Ergebnisse hinsichtlich ihrer Wirkung eingeordnet werden und Zuständigkeiten verteilt werden.

Workshop Road Map

Workshop KlimaTraining im Quartier

Ziel: Vision wie ein KlimaTraining im Quartier ablaufen kann, welche Aspekte zu berücksichtigen sind

Workshop Klima Fond

4) Procedure

The approach of promoting climate city districts is to be concretized by May through a series of workshops, the results of which will then be implemented.

The following workshops are planned:

- Workshop Climate City Neighborhoods Strategy

Participants: Representatives of the Climate Unit and Team Münsters Mitte Machen

Aim: To develop an overarching vision for the strategic approach to promoting climate city districts. Based on the approach described above, building blocks are to be supplemented and concretized, the respective results are to be classified in terms of their impact and responsibilities are to be distributed.

- Workshop Road Map
- Workshop on climate training in the neighborhood

Objective: Vision of how climate training can take place in the neighborhood, which aspects need to be considered

- Climate fund workshop

Rotterdam – BoTu (Bospolder Tussendijken) – City Storyline

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Context and Background of the Rotterdam pilot

History

BoTu has always been improving itself in every aspect of social and living quality. Bombed in the second world War, one of the most popular parks “Park 1943” in BoTu still stands today as a symbol of rebuilding and resilience. The two neighbourhoods have undergone significant transformation and urban renewal since the 1970s and are continuing to set an example for the rest of Rotterdam as one among 5 of the natural gas free districts* in the city. This objective originates from the Coalition Agreement 2018-2022 (June, [2018](#)), introducing the so-called Rotterdam Energy and Climate Agreement. One of the action points was concerned with the development of an integral and sustainable neighbourhood approach. Each district started off with an analysis of the area and technical research. Based on the former, a communication- and participation plan was formulated, as well as an “area business case” ([Municipal Executive, 2019](#)).

The district also has the goal of becoming the first resilient district of Rotterdam by 2028. The [Resilient BoTu 2028](#) programme lays out the way that the two neighbourhoods (Bospolder & Tussendijken) are going to achieve this goal. Following an unconventional yet holistic approach, the focus of the programme is laid on using physical challenges such as the energy transition and climate adaptation as a lever to strengthen social resilience. BoTu invests in its people as its primary asset, improving their life and capacities. This approach serves to create room for new forms of collaboration between municipalities and partners and between the partners themselves. There is also plenty of room for experimentation.

**In the Dutch context, 'aardgasvrij' is often the manner of describing the energy transition to renewable energy sources.*

Policy context

The path towards Resilient BoTu

Year	Title	Type	Focus/remark	Enabling factor
2014-2018	Coalitieakkoord	Coalition agreement	City	Guiding principles
2014-2018	#Kendoe	Coalition programme	Safe neighbourhoods; Integral approach district-safety; Citizen jury, right to challenge	Programme & budget

2014-2018	Focus district	1. Focus on West; 2. Implementation Programme: Onwijze wijk (2016) 3. Focus-approach: Safety	Budget was made available through the aforementioned programmes; the steppingstones for Resilient BoTu were laid	Mandate, collaboration, role of "Stadsmarinier"
2018	Mayor* visits New York (Brownsville)	Inspiration for a new four-year programme	Direct impulse for formation Resilient BoTu 2028; Focus on social resilience. *Visit together with CRO, MO, Stadsmarinier	Mayor, Roles of MO, CRO, Rebelgroup
2019	Resilient BoTu 2028	Policy Programme	Opportunities for implementation were found parallel - overlap with other policy programmes	Mandate, formalisation, budget for the first 5 years

Table 1. Enabling policy context Resilient BoTu 2028

The path towards the establishment of the programme Resilient BoTu 2028 was paved with the introduction of the **2014 “#Kendoe” Coalition Programme** (Coalition 2014-2018). The focus neighbourhoods of this approach were determined based on the five neighbourhoods with the lowest score on the 2014 “neighbourhood profile”. One of these neighbourhoods was Tussendijken.

The starting point for this “focus approach” was concerned with **social and safety issues** (behind closed doors) in the area. The #Kendoe programme employed a **mixed method approach**, seeking close collaboration with the corporation “Havensteder”*. Next to social and safety issues, investments were made to tackle the “decay and vacancy of the shopping street” at de Schiedamseweg; youth-nuisance; high unemployment. At the same time, this programme paid attention to the development of integral approaches for district-safety; citizen juries; “Right to Challenge” (I.e., new forms of local democratic participation). An important enabling factor generated by the aforementioned programme would be the creation of a budget. The enabling context established by the focus district (2014-2018) approach can be divided into three streams (See table 1).

Building further on the work carried out during the first years of the focus approach, the implementation programme “Onwijze Wijk” (2017-2018) was developed- a collaboration between the Stadsmarinier*, Delfshaven Coöperatie, Havensteder and Delfshaven area. With this, the foundation was laid for what is known today as the programme Resilient BoTu2028. Later, these stakeholders then came to be part of the BoTu-council.

Furthermore, parallel developments took place concerning the establishment of Rotterdam's Resilience Office, launching its first strategy in 2016. Being part of an international network, the team was able to facilitate knowledge exchange and a field trip to learn from the experiences of Brownsville, New York. This visit gave the direct boost for the development of the programme Resilient BoTu 2028. It is important to mention that, regarding the implementation of the programme, there is significant overlap with city-wide policy programmes that focused on themes as “Aardgasvrij” in BoTu. Consequently, this created the need to collaborate across different policy themes.

(Will add some background info from BoTu monitor about the role of stadsmarinier in 2016, the initial “team” created and how they came to be the core team of resilient BoTu)

[Social Impact by Design in Bospolder-Tussendijken - Platform Overheid](#)

System visualisation

The BoTu-monitor is divided into four parts:

Monitor	Part 1	Part 2	Part 3	Part 4
2020	Index+	Netwerken	Hefboom	Governance
2021	Netwerken	Index+	SlbD	Governance

Programmes

Table

Opportunities

Table

>>>>

[Spatial characteristics of the neighbourhood](#)

BoTu has a special characteristic as an urban island flanked by primary transport corridors and natural corridors. Along the northern and eastern edge of the neighbourhood lies the Schie river, along the southern edge is the Dakpark (an elevated continuous green roof public park) and to the west is transport corridor of Mathenesseweg. In the inner streets of BoTu are the Park 1943, market square Visserijplein, Bospolderplein and the shopping street of Schiedamseweg as important landmarks.

The districts of Bospolder and Tussendijken are around one square kilometre in size. Together they account for 7,000 households with more than 14,000 residents. Both districts have a high population density, and there is a high degree of diversity among the residents.

This high density is a significant indicator towards available public space per person in the neighbourhood. Since public spaces and green areas tend to be centralized within specific areas of the neighbourhood, this implies challenges in access to these areas as well*.

The concepts of compact city and connected city are especially relevant here. The neighbourhood in general may be walkable given that it has a small footprint of 1 sq. km. However, the non-uniform distribution of green areas and public spaces negatively impacts quality of life. Additionally, because it is an urban island, this poses questions on the degree of connectivity with the rest of the city.

More than 60% of the housing stock consists of social rental housing in the lowest segment. These homes are often aged and suffering from overdue maintenance. On average, the household sizes (number of

people per household) are bigger while the size of the homes are smaller than the rest of Rotterdam. This puts further stress on the space to person ratio on a household level.

Questions to explore further

Is the neighbourhood connected to the rest of the city? Why do people move around? What kinds of movement do you see? What would you say are the most important places and public spaces/ parks in your neighbourhood?

Social characteristics of the neighbourhood

Approximately 80% of the population is made up of ‘new Dutch’ and nearly 70% of residents have a non-Western background. In addition, the population is relatively young. There are more 0 to 14-year-olds than the Rotterdam average, while the percentage of older residents (65+) is lower than average.

Many households in BoTu are battling severe debts, and the average unemployment rate is high. Almost three-fourths of households are in the ‘low income’ bracket. On the list of the 20 poorest postal codes in the Netherlands, Tussendijken and Bospolder are in second and fifth place, respectively.

Questions to explore further

What are the neighbourhood’s strengths? What motivates participation?

Turning challenges into opportunities

The BoTu approach is all about empowering its local communities as champions. Social resilience is increased by strengthening local communities and their networks through [Asset-Based Community Development](#). Physical challenges - such as the energy transition and climate adaptation - serve as leverage to strengthen Social Resilience and foster Social Improvement.

BoTu has an above-average number of residents who do not have a diploma or do not have the right diploma, who feel lonely and unhealthy, depend on welfare and/ or are battling serious debt. The residents of Tussendijken rate their quality of life lower than anywhere else in Rotterdam.

There is also good news. Bospolder and Tussendijken both score well when it comes to connectedness. Residents feel connected with their neighbourhood, are involved and want to invest in the district. The turnover rate is relatively low. The district’s location and accessibility, its many facilities, numerous community networks and small-scale initiatives all play a part in this. It is precisely this positive energy and the many cooperative ventures in the district that offer opportunities for continuing the upward trend in the social index in BoTu seen over the past four years.

The district’s relatively small size and developments in the vicinity also offer good starting points for making BoTu a resilient district, in this way enabling the jump to the urban average. The political and administrative will to press ahead in BoTu is made clear in the ‘New Energy for Rotterdam 2018-2022’ coalition agreement of the mayor and aldermen, in which BoTu is mentioned several times and in relation to a number of areas.

Current approach and actions

BoTu ongoing activities are structured through a 3x3x3 approach. On a spatial level (the where), the activities focus on the areas of Schans-Watergeus (along the river), heart of BoTu and on schools and public squares in the neighbourhood. In terms of key thematic pillars (the what), the programme focuses on building capacity for work, language and debt, activities aimed at healthcare, youth and parents and regeneration/ renovation interventions in the areas of energy, housing and outdoor space. The binding element is the implementation approach (the how) which focuses on creating a Call for Action by inviting co-creation and co-ideation, identification of community assets and building up community cohesion, and creating Professional within the community as key champions who lead and implement various activities.

Taking BoTu to the next level – Needs and aspirations

Since 2019, the programme has implemented several activities that were outlined in the strategy. Based on the lessons learned and looking ahead into the next few years of programme implementation, 2 key needs have been identified.

These needs at this stage are framed from the perspective of scaling up ongoing activities. At a later stage, needs through the standpoint of barriers to scaling up will be framed.

Need 1

- Building a framework or blueprint to replicate BoTu's district-first approach to other neighbourhoods within Rotterdam and the Netherlands. Some ideas on what this blueprint may consist of:
 - Documenting initiatives and harvesting the results
 - Analysing the initiatives and methodologies used
 - Creating policy recommendations that can be replicable to other neighbourhoods
 - Indicators, energy efficiency opportunities
 - Neighbourhood Screening process

- Measures for climate adaptation and climate resilience through the focus on social resilience
- The LAA can be in the form of working groups consisting of community groups, policymakers, external stakeholder etc with the purpose of critically analysing the program and building this blueprint together
- This need builds upon what the city is already doing in the form of:
 - Booklet on lessons learned in the last 4 years (collection of evidence; chapters on mitigation and adaptation / with a different focus, how these measures lead into social resilience etc)
 - Conference on BoTu (June 2023) which will have community/social resilience workshops
 - Creating an implementation model for upscaling which will work hand in hand with the creation of the blueprint
 - District council (Wijkraad) – The new regulation on district councils (2022), and the new district approach which is being implemented in the city

Need 2

- Expanding the program activities further within BoTu. Through the documentation and analysis process, areas for further interventions will be identified. These interventions will in turn unlock the broader KPIs that the city has defined, such as
 - Creating additional job opportunities related to the energy transition in BoTu and adjacent neighbourhoods.
 - Encouraging and facilitating innovative, local initiatives to reduce CO2 output in BoTu by increasing awareness and social resilience.

People, Partners, Organisations and more

For the abovementioned needs, a series of working groups will be identified. In principle, the methodology of the blueprint creation will define the set of stakeholders who will co-create at each stage. Additionally, the LAA which will steer the entire Blueprint process will also be identified.

For instance, for collection evidence and documentation, all organizations, like Veldacademie, who can support and participate will be mapped.

In other cases, a working group for critically analysing past initiatives and defining the success and shortcomings of the same will also be mapped.

BoTu has a rich diversity of active residents, initiatives and network activities that are involved all across the neighbourhoods. Activities range from social support to greening initiatives. There have been previous studies that mapped all these initiatives in a detailed manner and the Resilient BoTu programme through the neighbourhood's team continues to engage, monitor and expand its outreach. Key stakeholders from these initiatives who can support in the co-creation of this blueprint will also be mapped. Some examples are:

1. Rotterdam Environment Center: training of local energy coaches and energy ambassadors;
2. Wijkenergie Werkt: employment opportunities in the energy transition;

3. Delfshaven Energy Cooperation: collective solar rooftops to make solar energy available to all residents of BoTu;
4. BoTu network: residents, initiatives and communities within the neighborhood.

Questions to explore further

Who are the people we need to engage no matter what? Who might not be as important now but maybe at a later stage?

Activities undertaken as part of UP2030

Setting up of Learning Action Alliance

The objective of Rotterdam under UP2030 is to create a framework of the Resilient BoTu 2028 approach, that can be used by other districts¹. By comparing the innovative approaches of Resilient BoTu 2028 with the normalised structures and standards of the city, potential entry points for the learnings can be found. In this way, the process of developing the framework strives to ensure the applicability of the content of the framework. One of the common risks in developing policy (frameworks) can be found in cases where a framework is developed in a vacuum, where the anticipation on the reality and day-to-day activities of the end-users is failed to be taken into consideration. Therefore, the ambition of Rotterdam is to develop a framework in co-creation, to ensure its applicability and usability, by anticipating on the needs and the language spoken in the day-to-day activities of potential end-users.

In Rotterdam, the Learning and Action Alliances (LAA) process was officially kicked off in April 2023. The process began with a stakeholder mapping, focused on two key groups: city programs and other districts and local stakeholders in the chosen pilot neighbourhood, BoTu. The tasks for this preliminary engagement process were divided between the programme managers of Resilient BoTu 2028 (districts & BoTu) and Resilient Rotterdam (city programmes).

- [UP2030 Stakeholder list and matrix Rotterdam BoTu.xlsx](#)

Following the two workshops on Needs, Rotterdam continued to engage with key stakeholders to better frame their objectives for the UP2030 project, including through the organization of a reflection workshop in June 2023. In the following months, Rotterdam has been continuing to meet with local actors, often through 1-1 meetings to build an alliance of involved stakeholders, in line with the city's strategy around Asset Based Community Development (ABCD).

Process of identifying actors for the LAA:

Analysing the Policy context

The Learning Action Alliance was not set up in a vacuum- prior to inviting different stakeholders to participate in the first workshop, a policy analysis was carried out to determine relevant city programmes, and to understand the context and pathways that led to the emergence of the programme Resilient BoTu 2028. Relevant policy programmes would be Aardgasvrije wijken (Natural-gas-free districts or energy transition program), Rotterdams Weerwoord ('Rotterdam Weatherwise' - Climate Adaptation program), Resilient Rotterdam, and representatives from the cluster of societal development. For the scope of the first workshop, representatives from the first three programmes were invited.

New trends of district governance. Next, the new trends of district governance were analysed to build an understanding towards the formal structure of governance. As the newly introduced "Wijk aan Zet" (model on district governance, 2022) guides the structured development and governance of districts, it is important to identify potential overlap between the ambitions of this model, and the work carried out under Resilient BoTu 2028. In doing so, entry points for knowledge sharing and city-wide (up)scaling can be identified, by making the experience accessible in a language that is to be spoken² by all those working at the district level. Therefore, representatives from the implementation and development of this model will be engaged and invited for co-creation as well.

Underlying structures. Moreover, the underlying structures of the interventions carried out under the umbrella of Resilient BoTu 2028 were identified, with a similar logic of reasoning as laid out in the previous paragraph. An example of such a structure would be the working standards and protocols of urban planning of the city, which is called the ‘RSPW’ (Rotterdam standard for project working). This underlying structure can be found in the example of the redevelopment of a square, such as Driehoeksplein³. However, the difference is that the urban planning process of Driehoeksplein was designed in a way so that it would deviate from the standards, to enable innovation in integrated work, public-private partnerships, and participation. In a similar fashion as the 3x3 approach (as mentioned in Chapter 1), in UP2030, Rotterdam’s efforts to develop a framework, take place on different levels.

District managers and policy programmes. Parallel to anticipating on underlying structures and new trends in district governance, district managers have been engaged to find a match between their priorities and needs, with the experience and lessons learned in elements and interventions carried out under Resilient BoTu 2028. In this way, a user-focused approach is taken in co-creation, to ensure that the structure and content of the framework is designed in such a way that it adds value to the existing work of the user and is easy to use. Next, representatives from three city programmes have been engaged to enable mutual learning throughout the co-creation process, determine overlap in similar ambitions and efforts, and align these efforts wherever it has the potential to generate added value and contribute to policy innovation. While different elements from the Resilient BoTu 2028 approach have the potential to be upscaled to other districts, through district managers as a first entry point, it is worth to consider the potential of scaling the approach at a programme level, and a process level.

[An extensive needs analysis process](#)

Workshop 1 – May 2023

In the Rotterdam pilot, the city organized a workshop for each identified target group. The initial workshop involved internal city and district administration stakeholders engaged in comparable projects. The main objective of the first workshop was to kick-off the co-creation process of the blueprint (framework) and gain a comprehensive understanding of the current state of affairs within the participating policy programmes and districts.

Integrated work. The workshop underscored the need for integration across departments to address multiple climate challenges simultaneously. The aspiration is to embed implementation strategies into wider local development, rather than limiting them to standalone climate projects. However, questions were raised about executing this cost-effectively and incentivizing multiple stakeholder types to adopt this integrated approach. A common challenge mentioned by all participants was concerned with the internal institutional obstacles related to integrated work. While the city seeks to stimulate integrated work in urban planning, the discussion of the participants demonstrated that the internal structures have not been designed to facilitate integrated work.

¹ District managers have been identified as a first group of potential end-users. Therefore, the preliminary focus in co-creating the framework and making the lessons from BoTu scalable, starts with the focus on district managers. However, the process carries the great potential to be scaled across the municipal organisation by anticipating on different structures and trends, e.g., district governance and urban planning.

² to be spoken, as this is a newly introduced model ‘Wijk aan Zet’, and the process of implementation started in 2023, i.e., it became a model by Regulation, but the process of adapting the ‘mutual language’ and implementing corresponding structures is ongoing.

³ Driehoeksplein is one of the public squares being redeveloped under the Resilient BoTu 2028 program. The square was co-designed together with the residents and focuses on improving the climate adaptation & co-benefits within the neighbourhood.

Multi-level strategy and the social aspect. There was consensus that local strategies should primarily align with social needs and challenges, giving secondary consideration to the physical and technical aspects of the local landscape. To achieve integration, a cohesive long-term multi-level strategy is required to align climate-related projects. This strategy should also encompass financing, as the lack of integrated budgeting currently limits the joined-up approach. The programme of Rotterdams Weerwoord currently undertakes efforts to combine social and physical data in climate adaptation in their strategy ‘district approach’.

Community engagement. Participants discussed community engagement, emphasizing the need for more inclusive, transparent, and effective participatory processes. The consensus was that a broader pool of residents could be reached to garner support and ownership for local programs. While there is a strong will to engage in this manner, Rotterdam faces challenges in establishing rapport with some diverse sections of the community and must work towards addressing their specific needs. This type of community engagement should be well-designed and considered earlier in project timelines, moving away from the current reactive approach.

From blueprint to framework. Reflecting on Rotterdam's aim to create a "blueprint" for the Resilient BoTu 2028 approach, the question arises: What would this blueprint look like? Due to time and scope of the workshop, the discussion on the content of the blueprint was not an explicit part this session. The workshop discussions focused on a general understanding and implementation level. Based on this scope, different categories of potential elements that could be included in the blueprint need consideration. In addition, feedback was given by the participants on the use of the term ‘blueprint’, as it indicates that district-specific interventions can be copy-pasted from one district to the other. Therefore, the decision was made to select a more accessible term, which is ‘framework’.

Moreover, the first workshop also delved into understanding how governance operates at different scales, such as district vs. city. Given the diverse contexts of each district, efforts should be directed toward identifying commonalities that can be integrated into a framework. Therefore, in the following months, 1-on-1 discussions were initiated to establish the further development of the co-creation process.

1-on-1 engagement

In the following months after the first workshop, different meetings were initiated with the participants of the first workshop, as well as the engagement of internal structures. The process of needs analysis could be understood as a continuous one. During the first workshop, general needs related to integrated work, district priorities and city programmes efforts, were discussed. In the bilateral follow-up meetings with the participants, the focus was laid on the context and priorities of the districts to determine potential areas of collaboration and experimentation in the co-creation process. Simultaneously, follow-up meetings were initiated with the city programmes to enable a process of mutual learning and to align efforts in common areas of interest. The goal of these follow-up meetings has been to allow for ‘coalition-building’ with the stakeholders, identify testing pilots for upscaling actions/knowledge, and most importantly, to create ownership, i.e., the participation of the stakeholders in the co-creation process is interest-driven, depends on the motivation of those engaged. The efforts taken in the co-creation process should built upon existing priorities and opportunities from the districts and city programmes. The first follow-up meetings have resulted in the identification of focus areas for co-creation through collaborative decision-making. These meetings have been mapped in Rotterdam’s Engagement Roadmap.

Parallel efforts at the BoTu-level

Through the process of UP2030, two lines of activities have been identified, one focusing on the city level and district level, to enable the formation of a framework and facilitate the direct and indirect upscaling of Resilient BoTu 2028, in the district itself and in other districts or structures. The first line has been

discussed in the previous paragraphs. The second line is focused on the existing network groups and stakeholders involved in Resilient BoTu 2028 itself.

On the BoTu-level, different activities were organized, varying from a conference, to trainings, a reflection session, and more. It is important to underline that the activities to be carried out under UP2030 and the co-creation process towards the development of a framework, closely anticipate on ongoing initiatives and interventions in Resilient BoTu 2028.

The first milestone before summer, was the organization of the conference ‘Working on resilience at district level’, organized by Resilient BoTu, Resilient Rotterdam, Veldacademie, Resilient Delta Initiative. The goal of the conference was to share the experience obtained in BoTu with a broad range of stakeholders from diverse sectors, inside and outside the city of Rotterdam. The residents were engaged to host workshop sessions on different best practice examples of BoTu, varying from local meeting places and community resilience, to measuring social resilience, physical interventions as a lever for social challenges, the energy transition in BoTu, community-building, to participatory budgeting. One of the lessons learned during this conference, is the need to further focus on sharing the experience from BoTu with the municipal structure internally. While there is a lot of attention from the outside world, there seems to be a lack of engagement of the internal structure. Therefore, the focus on ‘how to bring this knowledge back into the organization’ became a key priority for the following phase.

Next, a significant development in BoTu, has been the change in district managers; BoTu got a new district manager. In line with the efforts under UP2030, a reflection session was organized to discuss the first phase of Resilient BoTu and start the discussion on the needs for the time to come. The second group of stakeholders engaged in a workshop comprised district-level community and service delivery stakeholders. Reflecting on the past five years of the ongoing Resilient BoTu program, they identified priority areas for the next phase. About 30 people participated in this session, from the police, housing cooperation, local initiatives, active residents, civil society representatives, and civil servants. In general, the discussion was mainly concerned with the ‘root system’ in BoTu, the underlying network of local residents, connections, initiatives, and community-building. The coming time, a period of deeper reflection with different groups in the BoTu-network will be carried out, led by the new district manager.

Moreover, ABCD (Asset-based Community Development) forms the foundation of Resilient BoTu, as ‘working principles’. The trainings on ABCD are provided by a local cooperative ‘Delfshaven Coöperatie’, who also introduced this way of working long before the start of ‘Resilient BoTu 2028’. After summer 2023, a three-day ABCD course was provided to professionals and local residents in the district, to enable the participants to put community-building to practice in their day-to-day work. Simultaneously, a refresher course has been organized for the local project leaders of Resilient BoTu, as well as efforts to address the need to ‘bring this knowledge back into the municipal organization’.

Another milestone of Resilient BoTu is concerned with the start of the new Open Call, where participatory democracy and participatory budgeting is put into practice. The foundation for the development of BoTu’s Open Call was laid by the programme’s element called “Social Impact by Design” (SibD). One of the pillars in the first phase of Resilient BoTu 2028, was designed by the Rebel Group, the ‘Call to Action’ (‘Social Impact by Design’). The underlying goals of this process sought to stimulate creative interventions, innovative strategies, private investments. This process symbolized a new way of working, that is inclusive, open and integrated, people-focused, social challenges as a starting point. The foundation for the programme Resilient BoTu 2028 was laid by the pathways that led to its creation, both from the government and the community, from policy programmes to bottom-up initiatives. The combination of the pre-existing efforts and local context with political leadership and attention, called for the need for a new approach. Therefore, to understand the current ‘Open Call’ of BoTu, that is funded by the subsidy ‘Community-led local development’ (through Kansen voor West), it is necessary to further unpack the

foundation that was laid by its predecessor, with a focus on, e.g., participatory democracy and participatory budgeting. As the city had a Coalition change, the priorities of the city's leadership changed as well. One of the outcomes has been to not continue the funding of Resilient BoTu 2028 as a programme. While the efforts taken through Resilient BoTu 2028 are likely to continue, one of the key questions became; how to fund elements such as BoTu's *Open Call*, where the district manager delegated her budget to the local residents. [Last year](#), the representatives from the local resident decision-making body of BoTu's Open Call, applied and successfully obtained the CLLD-subsidy, which is now being used to continue the Open Call.

Resilient BoTu 2028 serves as an umbrella and brings together different initiatives, ambitions, and city programmes. As elaborated on in the first chapter, the programme has been structured around the 3x3 approach, in which interventions are carried out on different scales. One of the programmes that falls under the umbrella of Resilient BoTu 2028 is called 'Aardgasvrij BoTu'⁴. At this moment in time, an evaluation of the five pilot areas of 'Aardgasvrij' is being conducted by the department of sustainability, under the so-called 'how-track'⁵. The objective of this evaluation is to determine the lessons learned in the five pilots. After the evaluation has been completed, next steps of the learning trajectory will be determined. This is expected to take place in the first part of 2024.

Another example of a project under Resilient BoTu 2028 is Driehoeksplein (Resilient schools and public squares, as part of the 3x where). After several years of preparation and stimulating innovative approaches in the urban planning process of Driehoeksplein, the first steps of redevelopment were taken in summer 2023. As previously mentioned, (p. 11), the urban planning process of Driehoeksplein was designed to stimulate innovation in integrated work, public-private partnerships, and participation, with a focus on resilience. As Driehoeksplein has entered the phase of implementation, the time has come to collect the lessons learned at the process level of preparation and to determine how value can be added to the internal structures in doing so.

Further reading:

- [Rotterdam 1st Workshop report Resilient BoTu.docx](#)
- [1st Engagement Review - Rotterdam.docx](#)
- Add other reports from the workshops & 1-to-1s (I don't have this in a report, I will try to make an overview in English of the most important results of the follow-up meetings/1-on-1s)

⁴ Aardgasvrij BoTu is a programme from the department of sustainability of the city of Rotterdam. It translates as 'natural-gas-free BoTu'. This programme has been initiated as part of the city-wide efforts related to the energy transition. The ambition for natural-gas-free districts originates from the Coalition Agreement 2018-2022 and was stimulated by the national ambition of the Dutch government to change to sustainable energy resources, 'moving away from natural-gas' by 2050.

⁵ A process of learning led by the department of sustainability, the 'how-track' (het hoe-spoor) is concerned with 'how does Aardgasvrij land in the district' and 'integrated work'.

Working together with tools and services

As part of the UP2030 project, several tools and services are being offered to the cities by the technical partners. These tools play an important role in how the pilot project evolves and influences the final results of the city's participation in the UP2030 project and beyond. Cities were hence encouraged to reflect on the purpose of using these tools in their process and create principles to guide the pre-selection process.

Within UP2030, Rotterdam aims to focus on co-creation process, participation and engagement, as well as future replication and upscaling. In this perspective, the team has defined the following thematic areas for tools integration:

- Co-creation process for the framework
- Focus on social inclusion, and continuation of engagement process (social resilience together with climate resilience)
- Interest in replication and upscaling

The pre-selection of tools and Rotterdam's co-creation process

In the process of pre-selecting the tools, a list of potentially interesting tools for Rotterdam was established by the city project manager and liaison partner. Next, the list of pre-selected tools as well as the complete tool overview in Excel were shared with the team. In further discussing the tools, a session was organised with the liaison partner and the Rotterdam team. Due to the absence of the district manager, it was not possible to define a final list of pre-selected tools. Therefore, the discussion on the tools was taken to the regular team meetings, where the space was created for extensive discussion by the representatives of Resilient Rotterdam and Resilient BoTu. The approaches taken in Rotterdam are known for their innovative character, the same goes for Resilient BoTu 2028, as it was designed with a key focus on experimentation and innovation, which is why, the question arose; what is the added value of the pre-selected tools of UP2030, and what innovation can it bring to what is already being done within the scope of Rotterdam's ambitions under UP2030? The team continued and offered a colour-coded selection including elaboration on the level of interest in a specific tool. Another question raised was concerned with the introduction of potentially 'new environments', and the implications it bears for further fragmentation of information and ways of working at the city of Rotterdam.

Moreover, it may be the case that some tools could become useful at a later stage, but it is more difficult to define this, as Rotterdam focuses on a co-creation process. This discussion and the issues raised during the pre-selection phase were discussed during UP2030's General Assembly in Lisbon. The city representatives spoke to different partners and elaborated on their perspective regarding the tool selection process. These discussions contributed to obtaining a better understanding of how the tools can be approached by Rotterdam in a way that the utilization of a tool goes beyond the selection and 'plugging' it wherever it may fit, by working with tailored support based on the current phase of the city under UP2030.

The city has been setting up a co-creation process, where each next step is decided upon in format of collaborative decision-making and learning, relating to, e.g., the steps in co-creation and content of the framework. Currently, the coordination of this process is carried out by the city's project manager, with the support of the liaison partner. In this process, there is a great potential to innovate and upscale actions, as the city's efforts are concerned with different layers in the municipal organisation. However, in this process, there is a need to establish a monitoring group that can facilitate bringing together all these efforts in a structured way and offer a space for reflection and discussion. The city and liaison envision to

take this further as a next step in tool selection, where the focus is laid on the city's need and the question of how partners as TU Delft, Mapping for Change and Resilient Cities Network, could facilitate the needs of the city with tailored advice and support.

Therefore, the next steps in the tool selection process, is user-focused (city perspective) and expertise-focused, as well as the potential of partners to offer tailored support, rather than tool-focused. This is in line with the tools Working Groups that are steering the process of tool implementation. At this phase of the process, the needs of the city require more in-depth discussions with relevant partners to allow for innovative support to be offered. Furthermore, the city project manager and liaison partner established a timeline to bring together the steps and approaches taken so far, and to identify the needs for support from UP2030 partners. There is striven to have a draft of the framework process, potential elements, and next steps by the end of 2023. Subsequently, relevant partners will be approached to start the discussion on tailored support.

Moreover, through Rotterdam's efforts under UP2030, there is envisioned that the co-creation process of the framework, based on Resilient BoTu, allows for the emergence of the context in which the approach could be upscaled⁶. To maximize the impact of UP2030, it is important to clearly distinguish between the 'tools' that can be offered from Resilient BoTu to other districts and structures in the city, and cities in the UP2030 consortium, vs. the utilization of tools offered by UP2030 partners. Therefore, at this stage, the focus is laid on sharing the experience from Resilient BoTu 2028 with the internal municipal organisation and addressing the issue of 'how to bring this knowledge back into the municipal organisation'.

In sum, the main aims and expected outcomes of the city in relation to the tools offered through UP2030 is to work towards tailored support for the co-creation process and framework development as a first step.

Co-Visioning Phase

The co-visioning phase for BoTu district's transformation is based on a needs assessment conducted in Task 2.3 and objectives set in the UP2030 initiative. This phase uses the gathered information to pinpoint specific needs and goals tailored to BoTu's unique context. Therefore, the methodology for co-designing a shared vision is customized for BoTu, drawing on this foundational information.

The technical partners have developed a detailed co-visioning process, incorporating recommendations specifically for Rotterdam. This process is now under evaluation by the city. Co-design, a central approach in UP2030, involves cities and stakeholders in crafting the co-visioning process and this collaboration ensures a more targeted and context-sensitive approach to engagement.

Currently, Rotterdam is assessing the feasibility of this proposal. The city is also working on establishing a timeline for the upcoming steps in the co-visioning phases.

⁶ There are different types of upscaling innovation and experimentation in political governance and public policy. The willingness of actors to participate in the co-creation process can be motivated by different levels of interest in applying the knowledge; these interests can be reactive and facilitative, or pro-active and anticipatory. The content and elements that could be upscaled, as well as the appropriate format and type of upscaling are defined in this collaborative process.

Rotterdam

[update the process diagram once it's finalised by the city: [Guide to Co-visioning. Visioning Roadmap](#)]

As part of the preparatory activities that sets the base for the co-visioning (Milestone 1 – Validate Pilot Objectives), Rotterdam is currently in the milestone of validating and refining the identified key objectives. Over the first year of the project, our understanding of these objectives and needs has evolved, making it crucial to revise them. This step is vital for the success of future engagement activities. City liaisons are assisting in this process, helping to discern which objectives align best with the short-, medium-, or long-term goals and provide more detail elaboration of objectives and their scope. For instance, objective to ‘Improve quality of life for residents’ was further detailed that Resilient BoTu 2028 program, under UP2030, aims to foster holistic social development and community resilience by facilitating access to information and creating collaborative spaces for future action planning. The full document detailing objectives and the timeline can be found [here](#).

Additionally, at the General Assembly meeting in Lisbon in 2023, city representatives and liaisons further reviewed how these objectives fit within the pilot's context and how they align with UP2030 pillars (resilience, carbon neutrality, just transition). The goal of this review was to ensure that the objectives are targeting for the pilot scale and to further refine them. The updated document, which includes these revised objectives and their alignment with the pilot and the UP2030 project pillars, will be accessible [here](#).

In the upcoming weeks and months, Rotterdam will engage its key stakeholders in various activities to shape a vision that aligns with key aspirations for BoTu as well as UP2030 goals for a resilient, carbon-neutral, and just future. These activities will be centred around defining the pilot's vision and pinpointing actionable steps and potential barriers aimed at crafting adaptive pathways.

Thessaloniki Dioikitirion Urban District – City Storyline

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Context and Background of Thessaloniki’s pilot case

History

Location and key historic events that influenced the pilot neighbourhood’s development

The Thessaloniki pilot will focus on the Urban District of “Dioikitirio”, a district located at the western end of Thessaloniki’s historic centre. It is an area that brings together many elements that shaped the modern image of Thessaloniki's city centre.

On October 27, 1912, during the first Balkan War, the Greek army liberated the city. Equally important key historic events that shaped the city’s new profile, were the compulsory exchange of the populations after the Asia Minor disaster of 1922 and the big fire of 1917. Starting from a house at the beginning of "Agiou Dimitriou" street, the fire devastated, almost thirty-two hours, with the help of “Vardaris” (a strong north wind of the area), 120 ha of the city centre was completely burned, leaving 72.000 homeless, two-thirds of whom were Jews.

Just after the city's liberation from the Ottomans, the first Greek administration of Thessaloniki immediately occupied itself with the restructuring of the city's planning. In early 1913, and without losing any time, the official representation of the Greek government, formed a committee for the preparation of a new city plan. Among the Embellishment Committee's recommendations was the widening of "Egnatia" Street to a total width of 24 meters, with 5-meter sidewalks planted with trees, and the widening of "Venizelou" Street, a road extending down to the sea which also connected the port with the "Dioikitirio (the government building).

After the fire, the Greek government, led by Eleftherios Venizelos, decided to lead a major reconstruction process embracing the very latest ideas and methods of modern town planning ignoring any pre-existing land ownership, and land uses. An International Planning committee was immediately formed, composed of the French architect-archaeologist Ernest Hébrard, the English landscape architect Thomas Mawson, the French military engineer Joseph Pleyber, the architects Aristotelis Zachos and Konstantinos Kitsikis, the port expert Angelos Ginis, and the city's Mayor, Konstantinos Angelakis.

The plan of the Committee guided by Ernest Hébrard, constitutes an interesting transfer of that era's leading views concerning design to geographically local and historically particular circumstances. It introduced Thessaloniki to classical divisions (with axes, diagonals, monuments-focal points), a hierarchical street network, the concentration of public services, and the creation of a "civic" centre for the city, the rational organization and zoning of spaces for production and consumption, the selective highlighting of monuments, and preservation of a number of "picturesque" residential precincts. The traditional image of Thessaloniki faded away and was replaced by a "modern" homogeneous space, without its previous defining features.

Image 01: Location of the pilot area within Thessaloniki’s city centre.

The boundaries of the pilot area (image 02) are of a high historic and spatial importance, including:

- “Egnatia” street
- The western ruins of Thessaloniki’s Walls
- “Olympiados” Street
- “Aristotelous” Civic Axis

Image 02: The boundaries of the pilot area

Image 03: Monuments and archaeological traces remaining in the contemporary urban tissue

Turning points in the way this pilot neighbourhood was shaped

As mentioned earlier, Hebrard's plan was one of the turning points that changed the entire image of the city, replacing its traditional image with a "modern" one.

Throughout the interwar period, the shape of Thessaloniki changed rapidly. Between 1922 and 1924, around 100,000 refugees arrived from Asia Minor, while the centre began to be rebuilt.

Based on this construction fever, the city of Thessaloniki managed to maintain its vitality despite generally unfavourable conditions, including the financial crisis of the 1930s and the wider political instability prevailing in Greece. With the outbreak of the B' Word War all planning and construction activity in the city ceased, and it was not until the end of the decade and the end of the Civil War that further changes were seen in the urban space.

In an effort to revitalize the local economy and reduce the housing problem, after World War II, the Greek government decided to mobilize private capital. With the change in the building coefficients and the

notorious degrees of 1956 and 1960, which permitted a much denser exploitation of building projects in Thessaloniki than in other Greek cities, there was feverish building throughout the sixties and seventies. At the same time, the great wave of internal migration increased both the population and the extent of the city.

Also, during the sixties and seventies, a parallel policy of major public works also helped shape the modern image of the city, such as the modernization and expansion of the city's port, the construction of the new waterfront (Nea Paralia), the construction of the University Campus and the International Fair Site. In 1962, digging in preparation for the construction of the new Courts on the Axis of Aristotle (following Hebrard's Plan) revealed the ancient market.

Located in the western part of the historic city center, the pilot area was for years a thriving commercial and residential part of the city. The recent financial crisis of 2010 has caused dramatic changes in the study area. Many economic activities closed, especially the underground retail shops, leaving behind empty buildings and an overall sense of destruction and desolation.

The area today is at a turning point. In recent years, two parallel events affect and define the character of the pilot area: (a) the extensive renovations carried out by the municipality of Thessaloniki, which reversed, to a large extent, the area's deterioration image. (b) real estate and recreation investments in the vacant building stock and their conversion to short-term dwelling for tourist exploitation

Key policy documents which have shaped actions, projects and approaches in the pilot neighbourhood

According to the Greek Constitution, the State is primarily responsible for strategic spatial planning, including the building policy which is practically used as a strategy for the spatial organization. At the national level, the Ministry of Environment, Energy, and Climate Change elaborates, applies, and monitors the general guidelines for spatial development; conducting urban master plans, providing housing, and ensuring environmental protection lie under its authority. The official peripheral and local authorities undertake the next two levels of regional and urban planning with quite a freedom of act although they remain always accountable to the central government.

Greek legislation on Spatial Planning is a three-level, strongly hierarchical structure constituted by National and Peripheral plans, Regional and Local (Regulatory and General Land-Use plans addressed to the expanded region of a major or middle-sized town), and locally specialized plans concerning specific areas in the city or Zones of Development Control.

In practice, spatial planning is concentrated in the Strategic Programmes seeing general directions and policies to be further defined locally and the General Land-Use Plans followed by various Urban Studies on individual urban projects, detailed town plans, and implementation acts.

Planning law favors the involvement and dominance of the central state bodies at every level from the national government represented by the minister to planning departments, municipalities, and other state institutions while excluding the civic society. This centralized system is able to cover restricted regional planning but finds it ever more difficult to compete with the dynamic transformations of the city and the necessity for through-scale strategic spatial planning.

- The Integrated Sustainable Urban Development Strategy of the Thessaloniki Metropolitan Area
- The Thessaloniki Resilience Strategy 2030

Spatial characteristics of the neighbourhood

Location and connections

The “Dioikitirion” Urban District is named after the historic Ottoman-era building called “Dioikitirio” (Government House) which is located in the area. Originally built in 1891 as the residence (konak) of the governor-general (vali) of the Ottoman Salonica Vilayet as a seat of the Ottoman authorities. Today it hosts the services of the Greek Ministry of Interiors – Department of Macedonia and Thrace.

The urban district is well-connected to other parts of the city by public transportation, as the main public transport axis, “Egnatia” Street, passes through the area. Also, along “Egnatia” Street, the under construction main line of the Metro runs.

Urban profile of the area (size, density, land uses, public spaces, nature and build environment etc)

The characteristics of the urban area are varied and with great contradictions. The entire area includes:

(a) areas with intense traffic, congested by the city's major traffic axes (such as Egnatia Street, Agios Dimitriou Street, Karaoli and Dimitriou Street, etc.) but also quiet neighborhoods with a sense of human scale.

(b) areas where the building stock has the architectural characteristics of the era of massive modern reconstruction but also areas that gather historical traces and monuments.

(c) lively areas with lively recreational activities and upgraded public space but also degraded and "dead" areas.

The whole area is very dense with a low percentage of green spaces.

Image 04: Today images of the pilot area

Area Profile (based on the revised General Urban Plan of Municipality of Thessaloniki - not yet officially approved):

- **Urban District code:** Σ4 – Dioikitirio
- **Section:** Central – western
- **Other divisions:** includes 3 urban sub-districts
- **Area:** 0,06 Ha
- **Population (2001):** 21.735 residents (2011): (2021):.....
- **Main Land Use:** residential area
- **Landmarks:** It is an area with important historical landmarks such as the “Dioikitirio” building, Western Walls, the Byzantine church of 12 Apostles, “Aristotelous” Civic Axis (were it’s located: the Church of Prophet Elijah, Roman Forum, Byzantine Church of Panagia Chalkeon, Bey Haman Ottoman Baths).
- **Statutory land uses** of the pilot area include mainly Central Business District land uses and Residential zones (general type). Other land uses include primary and secondary education, cultural and religious infrastructures, green open spaces, and archaeological places including archaeological parks (see image 05).
- After the crisis, the area entered into a phase of transition becoming an area of more complex land uses.

Image 05: Statutory land uses

Energy efficiency and carbon emissions

Carbon dioxide annual emissions in the Municipality of Thessaloniki are estimated at 2,494,215 tons while the and the energy consumption per year is estimated at 5,461 GWh (reference year: 2011).

Greenhouse gas emissions

Energy consumption per carrier

Social characteristics of the neighbourhood

Thessaloniki is the second largest municipality of Greece, with a Resident Population of 317.778, of which 145.087 male (45,6 %) and 172.691 female (54,4%) [2021 census].

According to data derived from the Population Census conducted by ELSTAT, over the past three decades the population of the Metropolitan Area of Thessaloniki has been redistributed along the lines of two basic trends: **the shrinking of the densely populated core of the urban fabric and suburbanization and urban sprawl**. Despite the population increase of Thessaloniki Conurbation, its share in the overall population of the Metropolitan Area is declining, mainly due to a population decrease in the Central Municipality. The latter's share in the total population of the Metropolitan Area decreased from half in 1991 to less than a third by 2011.

Evolution of the population of the Municipality of Thessaloniki

Municipality	1991	2001	2011	2021
Thessaloniki	395.789	375.276	322.240	317.778

The Following Tables present the latest demographic data base on the 2011 census

Municipality	Total	Economically active					Economically inactive			
		Total	Employed	Unemployed			Total	Students	Retired	Other
				Total	Formerly Employed	"Youth"				
Thessaloniki	325.182	134.572	103.243	31.329	22.694	8.635	190.610	64.752	71.571	54.287
Male	148.470	72.353	55.417	16.936	12.680	4.256	76.117	30.920	34.696	10.501
Female	176.712	62.219	47.826	14.393	10.014	4.379	114.493	33.832	36.875	43.786

Description / Residential density (m2 per inhabitant)	Total	Ownership type	
		Owned	Rented/ Cooperatively owned / Other type of ownership
Municipality of Thessaloniki	147.376	92.380	54.996
Under 15 m2 per inhabitant	3.712	2.045	1.667
15 - 29 m2 per inhabitant	40.888	27.265	13.623
30 - 44 m2 per inhabitant	40.202	25.316	14.886
45 + m2 per inhabitant	62.574	37.754	24.820

Municipality	Total	Apartments' Surface (m ²)									
		under 40	40 - 49	50 - 59	60 - 69	70 - 79	80 - 89	90 - 99	100 - 109	110 - 119	120+
Thessaloniki	205.398	13.896	18.031	26.818	30.590	34.141	28.869	18.447	13.142	7.492	13.972

Challenges and opportunities

The overall key challenges at social and spatial level of the pilot area can be summarised as follow:

- Urban shrinkage regarding residence and economic activities
- Porosity of the urban fabric - vacant apartments and entire buildings
- Decline of economic activity, especially at building basements (effect to the liveability of the Greek street plinth)
- A trend to the monofunctional (leisure – tourism – short term rentals)
- Gentrification processes, loss of the neighbourhood cohesion

Current approach and actions

During the last years, lots of areas have been regenerated such as

- Mavili Square regeneration [before](#) and [after](#)
- [12 Apostoli church area/square](#)
- [Syggrou street](#)

In addition, some asphalt paving projects have taken place in Agiou Dimitriou, one of the main axes of Thessaloniki that crosses along the Pilot Area.

The current strategies under implementation are:

- [Resilient Thessaloniki: A Strategy for 2030](#)
- ROOF Action Plan (URBACT)

Other planned projects or initiatives include:

- The installation of Electric Vehicle Charging Points

- The development of Micro mobility hubs
- Urban regeneration and commercial revitalization

Needs and aspirations

Dealing with the urban shrinkage phenomenon

- Dealing with the phenomenon of population loss and economic activities
- Reverse the image of decline at the street level
- Keep the multifunctionality and multicultural character of the area
- Policy strategies and tools

Neutral, circular, and eco-district for all

- Pilot demonstration of a neutral, circular and eco-district for all
- Energy improvement of the building stock
- Participatory policy tools – the district as a Living Lab

Access to Affordable Social Housing

- Analysis and recording of vacant building stock
- Comprehensive analysis of the district trends regarding residential issues
- Social Rental Agency Thessaloniki as key policy initiator
- Propose efficient and applicable policy tools

Key elements to be defined include:

- A comprehensive trends’ analysis of the shrinking phenomenon of the pilot area
- The development of a neutral district model based on local and micro-local characteristics
- The development of affordable housing policies as key tools to reverse shrinkage without gentrification effects

Key needs of the pilot area relating to capacity & planning include:

Needs in terms of the challenges of Climate change

- The adoption of modern data collection methods and systems that will support the making of valid and timely decisions.
- Strengthening the infrastructure and equipment to deal with emergency situations and phenomena related to climate change
- The strengthening of urban greenery
- The increase of green and unstructured surfaces.
- The utilisation of abandoned lands and undeveloped spaces.
- The implementation of programs to develop integrated systems of smart cities (smart cities).
- The preservation of the remaining free streams and the elimination of the risk of flooding.

People, Partners, Organisations and more

Stakeholders - Neutral, circular, and eco-district	
Municipality of Thessaloniki	Department of Construction of Municipal Buildings & Renovations of Common Areas

	Resilience Observatory Thessaloniki
The Centre for Research & Technology, Hellas - CERTH	Information Technologies Institute
Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	Civil Engineering Department
Hellenic Electricity Distribution Network Operator S.A- HEDNO	Directorate of the Region of Macedonia - Thrace
Thessaloniki Water Supply and Sewerage Organisation– EYATH S.A.	Research and development chemist
Gas Distribution Company- EDA THESSALONIKI - THESSALIA S.A	Corporate Affairs and Internal Audit 7 Growth and Market Strategy
Centre for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving- CRES	CRES representative & National Coordinator of the Covenant of Mayors

Stakeholders - Affordable Social Housing	
Municipality of Thessaloniki	Department of Construction of Municipal Buildings & Renovations of Common Areas
Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs	
International Organization of Migration	Project Helios
Heinrich Böll Stiftung	Thessaloniki Office
Major Development Agency SA	Social Rental Agency
Association of Real Estate Owners of Thessaloniki	

Stakeholders -Dealing with the urban shrinkage phenomenon	
Municipality of Thessaloniki	Department of Construction of Municipal Buildings & Renovations of Common Areas
Creativity Platform	A non-profit, collective scheme, seeking to function as an interdisciplinary platform of exchanging ideas, actions, research and appliances related to the “creative capital” and the “creative economy” in the city of Thessaloniki.
InCommOn Innovative Communities Onwards	Civil non-profit company that promotes sustainable and participatory urban development to tackle the problems that Greek cities are facing

Activities undertaken as part of UP2030

Setting up of Learning Action Alliance

In April 2023, the Learning and Action Alliances (LAA) process was kicked off through an initial stakeholder mapping conducted by the City Liaison partner, Major Development Agency Thessaloniki (MDAT). In addition, MDAT and Thessaloniki held 5 internal meetings to further map the stakeholders of the Diokiterion pilot area and identify the core groups that need to be engaged.

- [UP2030 Stakeholder list and matrix template Thessaloniki.xlsx](#)

The LAA process solidified following Workshop 1, which took place in May. Indeed, Thessaloniki and MDAT wished to devise additional in-person stakeholder engagement in months 9 and 10. After a series of internal meetings between the City Liaison and the Municipality, three priority groups for additional stakeholder engagement emerged:

- Elderly
- Parents
- Experts

The rationale is that people over 60-65 years old represent 10% of the overall population of the Diokiterion area. Parents also represent a large share of the population and Thessaloniki is committed to revitalising Diokiterion making it a child-friendly area.

To help guide this additional round of engagement, Thessaloniki decided to show a map of the pilot area to let the priority groups highlight the characteristics of the neighbourhood and its needs and barriers, as well as a canvas template.

On 17 October, Thessaloniki held a workshop with the elderly people from the Diokiterion neighbourhood. 17 people attended the workshop in-person. The workshop demonstrated the high levels of pro-activity of the engaged groups, who contributed to needs identification and showed the extent to which they feel part of the "Action" part of Thessaloniki's LAA.

Between 19 and 25 October, Thessaloniki interviewed 4 selected experts who are also residents of Diokiterion. They also run volunteering activities in the area and organize seminars and awareness-raising activities to engage locals. Among the greatest ideas that came out of these meetings is the creation of a neighbourhood committee that could help build stronger community engagement and contribute to the implementation of local initiatives. Some of the proposed initiatives include:

- Adoption of local plants & trees by the residents
- Training residents to reuse materials. More than 40+ different materials that can be reused in households.
- Creation of green spaces between buildings, on roofs and in courtyards.

In November/December, Thessaloniki is planning to engage the schools in the area and find ways to engage parents.

An extensive needs analysis process

Thessaloniki implemented a workshop on needs engaging a combination of internal and external stakeholders. As a follow-up, a working group was also established. The participants mainly addressed the urgent need to tackle the phenomenon of urban shrinkage in the center of Thessaloniki. The pilot area (Diokiterion neighbourhood) holds significant potential for reversing this effect given its current transitional stage of development.

Several overarching needs emerged from the workshop, with a particular focus on developing a robust social policy framework, strengthening Thessaloniki's Social Rental Housing Agency, and improving wider social service structures to encourage families to repopulate the area. Challenges to this include the absence of affordable housing strategies, inaccessible pedestrian infrastructure, and the lack of a common vision at the city level. Nevertheless, opportunities were found in current community initiatives such as an ongoing tree planting project in schools and existing plans like the Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan and Circular Economy activities.

Some high-level needs were identified in Thessaloniki, including a better internal understanding of the city's development frameworks and enhanced participatory approaches. These actions have some governance limitations, however, for example lack of decision-making power at a district level and the absence of a common vision and coordinated strategy in areas such as affordable housing.

In response to the identified needs and barriers, workshop participants proposed a range of potential solutions. To address financing gaps, they suggested collaborating with regional authorities and the government to unlock new funding sources. They also recommended the creation of a communication strategy to encourage broader awareness and validation of climate interventions. On a local scale, there is hope that community involvement can be mobilised through educational activities focused on participatory approaches and the introduction of concrete incentives whose visibility will encourage public involvement in climate projects. The overarching theme is a call for realistic and applicable solutions, considering the relatively short timeframe until 2030 and the availability of resources.

The initial review of Thessaloniki's engagement approach brought attention to some specific gaps in knowledge. The city should delve deeper to address data needs. There is a need for specific climate indicators, comprehensive data on emissions and sources, vacant building stock, green space, public perceptions of net zero, and demographic change.

There is now an opportunity to delve deeper into the relationships between targets and their impacts. For instance, exploring the correlation between the need for increasing green spaces in the city and its potential to contribute to reducing CO2 emissions or creating more liveable environments. Understanding these interconnections can inform strategic decision-making and foster synergies between different sustainability goals.

The city is now actively engaged in identifying and prioritizing stakeholder groups, coupled with plans for in-person engagement activities aimed at extracting more specific needs.

Further reading:

- [Final UP2030 - 1st workshop reporting template June 2023 Thessaloniki.docx](#)
- [1st Engagement Review - Thessaloniki.docx](#)

Intended next steps:

The next step for Thessaloniki's team is the creation and development of a District Climate Action Plan.

Working together with tools and services

As part of the UP2030 project, several tools and services are being offered to the cities by the technical partners. These tools play an important role in how the pilot project evolves and influences the final results of the city's participation in the UP2030 project and beyond. Cities were hence encouraged to reflect on the purpose of using these tools in their process and create principles to guide the pre-selection process.

For Thessaloniki, the key consideration for integrating tools in the process is, ***how can the city adapt the tools that were selected into the district?*** as it consists of neighborhoods with many different and specific socio-cultural characteristics. The city sees the tools provided by the consortium as an opportunity to:

- Activate the residents
- Map the area
- Digitalize spatial data

As part of the pre-selection process led by the Implementation Taskforce, Thessaloniki has defined the following thematic areas for tool integration:

- Focus on housing and energy renovation (old buildings and affordable housing)
- Renovation of green public areas and improve pedestrian infrastructure (i.e., pocket garden)
- Interest in participatory approach (communication strategy, easy vocabulary, volunteers, district as a living lab)

Moreover, the municipality is also interested in strengthening its capabilities in participatory approaches and stakeholder engagement (such as communication strategy, easy vocabulary, volunteers, living lab).

Following the logic above, at this stage Thessaloniki has pre-selected three typologies of tools. Thessaloniki wants to strengthen its climate action related data management capabilities (in collaboration with the Smart Cities Working Group), model energy efficiency (METU) and assess heat risk (UCCRN) in the pilot area. The analysis will be carried out through a lens of spatial justice (TUD).

Co-visioning phase

The co-visioning phase for Diokiterion district's transformation is based on a needs assessment conducted in Task 2.3 and objectives set in the UP2030 initiative. This phase uses the gathered information to

pinpoint specific needs and goals tailored to Diokiterion’s unique context. The methodology for co-designing a shared vision was customized to the districts, drawing on this foundational information.

The technical partners have developed a detailed co-visioning process, incorporating recommendations specifically for Thessaloniki. This process is now under evaluation by the city. Co-design, a central approach in UP2030, involves cities and stakeholders in crafting the co-visioning process. This collaboration ensures a more targeted and context-sensitive approach to engagement.

Currently, Thessaloniki is assessing the feasibility of this proposal. The city is also working on establishing a timeline for the upcoming steps in the co-visioning phases.

Thessaloniki

[update the process diagram once it’s finalised by the city: [Guide to Co-visioning. Visioning Roadmap](#)]

As part of the preparatory activities that sets the base for the co-visioning (Milestone 1 – Validate Pilot Objectives), Thessaloniki is currently in the milestone of validating and refining the identified key objectives. During the first year of the project, the understanding of objectives and needs has evolved and therefore the revision of objectives plays an important role for the upcoming engagement activities. With the support of the city liaisons, the activity will help to identify which aspirations are most relevant to the short-, medium- or long-term goals and to validate their relevance. [\(Full document can be found here\)](#). *(provide more detailed description on the outcome once city have completed the exercise)*

Additionally, during the General Assembly meeting in Lisbon in 2023, the representatives of the city, with the support of liaison, reflected on the alignment between the identified objectives and the pilot context. This exercise has helped to ensure that the objectives are linked to the pilot scale and to further specify them. For example, objective “tackling urban shrinkage” was further elaborated, revealing its link to the pilot area, as ‘creating inclusive and attractive neighbourhood, providing affordable housing properties and more green spaces.’ Furthermore, identified objectives were assessed against three thematic pillars of resilience, carbon neutrality and just transition. For instance, an ‘Affordable green housing policy development’ objective was linked to just transition, as a key priority, while carbon neutrality was identified and a secondary priority. The full document, with revised objectives linked with the pilot case and UP2030 project pillars, [can be found here](#).

In the coming weeks and months, the city will undergo a series of engagement activities to define the vision for a resilient, carbon neutral and just future for Thessaloniki’s pilot and to identify concrete actions and barriers in the light of defining adaptation pathways.

City of Zagreb - Modular indoor growing farm – City Storyline

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Context and background of Zagreb's pilot case

History

Povijest

Historic events that influenced the pilot neighbourhood's development

Before the inclusion of the City of Zagreb in the UP2030 project, the City, in the status of local coordinator, was involved in the project **proGReg: Productive green infrastructure for post-industrial urban regeneration**, the implementation of which is still ongoing. The goal of that project was to develop productive green infrastructure for the urban regeneration of former industrial areas, and in this case, it is the targeted area of the former Sljeme factory in Sesvete.

City of Zagreb, EU project proGReg: Image of the elaborated site in Sesvete district

As part of the project, criteria for sustainable urban development with the implementation of green and smart technologies were defined, through a list of activities to be implemented in accordance with the City's development strategy and the principles of implementation of nature-based solutions. As part of locally led activities, the **proGReg** project dealt with three basic activities: the implementation of productive green infrastructure, the co-creation of an urban renewal project, and the development of self-sustaining business model solutions based on green technologies.

Regarding that, the project has produced the following results so far: arranging and equipping the Info Centre in Sesvete as a contact point for communication with citizens; modernization of the existing urban garden in Sesvete with innovative technologies; performance of the Therapeutic Garden; **the implementation of a modular urban farm that includes solar solutions, green walls and roofs as well as aquaponics elements**; creation of guidelines to adjust the planning regulations in order to easily facilitate the implementation of the NBS in the future.

All these activities were actually a „following step“ to study "Green and Blue Sesvete", which was formerly prepared by the Faculty of Architecture of the University of Zagreb, with the support of a local non-governmental organization, and whose goal was to define the real spatial potential and needs, i.e. to review and remodel the existing planning documentation that foresees the production and business zone in the centre of the settlement, with a minimal percentage of other uses.

All these successfully implemented activities, both with acquired knowledge and experience, led to an interest in further progress - improving the development of the location, as well as improving activities that will contribute to efforts related to climate neutrality and sustainable urban development. Success of the implementation and visibility of **proGIreg** project was a perfect inspiration to stay determined to continue the development of NBS solutions and promotion of green technologies through other future activities and projects.

City of Zagreb, EU project proGIreg: Citizen engaged in CO-DESIGN process

Instead of a conclusion, we consider it important to mention that in the earliest phase of preparing the project idea, the goal was to focus on the location in Sesvete, and to further spread the idea throughout the neighborhood and the city district. However, after making basic analyzes and collected data in the first 6 months of project implementation, it is concluded that it is advisable to include another city location in the same theme, in order to ensure a more far-reaching echo of the project. Today, we are developing the project at 2 locations in parallel: a school in the city district of Sesvete and a zoo in the city district of Maksimir. Although the spatial, social and economic context of these 2 locations is significantly different, what they have in common is a strong common interest in the development of this project idea and mutual cooperation that can undoubtedly bring the project progress!

Povijesni događaji koji su utjecali na razvoj pilot projekta u gradskim četvrtima

Prije uključivanja Grada Zagreba u projekt UP2030, Grad je u statusu lokalnog koordinatora bio uključen u projekt proGReg: Produktivna zelena infrastruktura za postindustrijsku urbanu regeneraciju, čija je provedba još uvijek u tijeku. Cilj tog projekta bio je razviti proizvodnu zelenu infrastrukturu za urbanu regeneraciju bivših industrijskih područja, a u ovom slučaju to je ciljano područje bivše tvornice Sljeme u Sesvetama. U sklopu projekta definirani su kriteriji održivog urbanog razvoja uz primjenu zelenih i pametnih tehnologija, kroz popis aktivnosti koje će se provoditi u skladu sa strategijom razvoja Grada i načelima provedbe rješenja temeljenih na prirodi. U sklopu lokalno vođenih aktivnosti, projekt proGReg bavio se trima osnovnim aktivnostima: implementacijom produktivne zelene infrastrukture, kreiranjem projekta urbane obnove i razvojem rješenja samoodrživog poslovnog modela temeljenog na zelenim tehnologijama. S tim u vezi, projekt je do sada polučio sljedeće rezultate: uređenje i opremanje Info centra u Sesvetama kao kontaktne točke za komunikaciju s građanima; modernizacija postojećeg urbanog vrta u Sesvetama inovativnim tehnologijama; izvedba Terapijskog vrta; implementacija modularne urbane farme koja uključuje solarna rješenja, zelene zidove i krovove te elemente akvaponike; izrada smjernica za prilagodbu planske regulative kako bi se u budućnosti lakše implementirala rješenja temeljena na prirodi (NBS).

Sve ove aktivnosti bile su nadogradnja na studiju „Zelene i plave Sesvete“, koju je svojedobno izradio Arhitektonski fakultet Sveučilišta u Zagrebu, uz potporu lokalne nevladine organizacije, a čiji je cilj bio definirati stvarne prostorne potencijale i potrebe, odnosno revidirati i preurediti postojeću plansku dokumentaciju koja predviđa proizvodno-poslovnju zonu u središtu naselja, s minimalnim postotkom ostalih namjena.

Sve te uspješno provedene aktivnosti, kako stečenim znanjem tako i iskustvom, dovele su do interesa za daljnjim napretkom – unapređenjem razvoja lokacije, kao i unapređenjem aktivnosti koje će doprinijeti naporima vezanim uz klimatsku neutralnost i održivi urbani razvoj.

Uspjeh implementacije i vidljivost proGReg projekta bila je savršena inspiracija da ostanemo odlučni da nastavimo razvoj NBS rješenja i promicanje zelenih tehnologija kroz druge buduće aktivnosti i projekte.

Umjesto zaključka,

smatramo važnim napomenuti da je u najranijoj fazi pripreme projektne ideje cilj bio fokusirati se na lokaciju u Sesvetama, te ideju dalje širiti po susjedstvu i gradskoj četvrti. Međutim, nakon izrade osnovnih analiza i prikupljenih podataka u prvih 6 mjeseci provedbe projekta zaključuje se da je preporučljivo uključiti još jednu gradsku lokaciju u istoj temi, kako bi se osigurao dalekosežniji odjek projekta. Danas, projekt razvijamo na 2 lokacije paralelno: škola u gradskoj četvrti Sesvete i Zoološki vrt u gradskoj četvrti Maksimir. Iako se prostorni, društveni i ekonomski kontekst ove 2 lokacije značajno razlikuje, ono što im je zajedničko jest čvrsti zajednički interes u razvoju ove projektne ideje te međusobna suradnja koja nedvojbeno može donijeti samo napredak!

Key policy documents which have shaped actions, projects and approaches in the pilot neighbourhood

The Spatial Plan of the City of Zagreb and the General Urban Plan of Sesvete, are planning numerous new traffic corridors, new roads in Sesvete villages, new roads in the economic zone of Sesvete North - which will undoubtedly generate the development of new and accompanying facilities. Also, a significant expansion of one of the most important and largest city cemeteries, Markovo polje, is planned.

Significant development potential in Sesvete also is represented by abandoned brownfield areas (former factory Badel Sesvete, former Ciglana Sesvete, former military warehouse Duboki Jarak, former factory Sljeme Sesvete).

All mentioned existing planning documents testify to the desire and need - both local authorities and the local population - for the implementation of sustainable solutions and the implementation of green policies.

Besides all the given data (which testify to the development potential of the location), the selection of the pilot project was also influenced by the valuable experience of the City of Zagreb in the implementation of similar policies and programs:

- „productive Green Infrastructure for post-industrial urban regeneration”/proGReg (GA 776528) / Ongoing/ ProGReg project, (<http://progireg.eu/the-project/>)
- The Urban Gardens project /Ongoing, financed entirely by the City of Zagreb

City of Zagreb: Urban gardens

Ključne politike koje su oblikovale aktivnosti, projekte i pristupe u pilot projektu

Prostornim planom Grada Zagreba i Generalnim urbanističkim planom Sesveta planirani su brojni novi prometni koridori, nove prometnice u Sesevskim selima, nove prometnice u gospodarskoj zoni Sesvete sjever – što će nedvojbeno generirati razvoj novih i popratnih sadržaja. Također, planirano je značajno proširenje jednog od najznačajnijih i najvećih gradskih groblja Markovo polje.

Značajan razvojni potencijal u Sesvetama također predstavljaju napuštena brownfield područja (bivša tvornica Badel Sesvete, bivša Ciglana Sesvete, bivše vojno skladište Duboki Jarak, bivša tvornica Sljeme Sesvete).

Svi navedeni postojeći planski dokumenti svjedoče o želji i potrebi - kako lokalnih vlasti tako i lokalnog stanovništva - za implementacijom održivih rješenja i provedbom zelene politike.

Uz sve navedene podatke (koji svjedoče o razvojnem potencijalu lokacije), na odabir pilot projekta utjecalo je i dragocjeno iskustvo Grada Zagreba u provedbi sličnih politika i programa:

- „Produktivna zelena infrastruktura za postindustrijsku urbanu regeneraciju”/proGReg (GA 776528) / U tijeku/ ProGReg projekt, (<http://progireg.eu/the-project/>)
- Projekt Urbani vrtovi /U tijeku, u potpunosti financira Grad Zagreb

Turning points in shaping pilot neighbourhood(s)

Based on the experiences gained in previously implemented projects (related to the creation of an urban farm model, and the desire to its further development, as well as improvement and implementation of the same model in a wider area, and to use the existing scientifically based, integrated urban and architectural solutions to guide socio-technical requirements related to the efforts of cities to fulfil their goals in ensuring climate neutrality by 2030), there was an interest in designing a new pilot project in this particular area.

As the UP2030 project seeks to improve existing solutions, Zagreb - in the first place - wanted to continue developing a modular urban farm system, but this time in one elementary school in Sesvete district. Idea was to reduce the cost of delivery to schools, reduce CO2 emissions, and include children to participation in growing food at all stages, whereas the grown food can be used in the school kitchen.

Nevertheless, as idea of UP2030 project continues to develop furtherly, Zagreb has learned that the elementary school - besides all its huge benefits to promote the project ideas - also has certain limitations in processing the planned project measures, whereas additional project partner, Zagreb ZOO, was introduced to be sure we can overcome the same restrictions. From this point City of Zagreb continues the project development in two locations (meaning, two districts) in parallel!

It is important to note here that the idea of the project does not change at all, and that the scope of implementation remains the same as originally planned, except that it will be spatially spread over two areas.

This activity opens the possibility of expanding the scope of target groups, better dissemination and increased visibility of the project. The changes in question are not recognized here only as "pure changes" but also as "improvements" of the basic idea.

Therefore, main "turning point" in project development can be described as engagement of two equally important partners in the project instead of one: elementary school in Sesvete district, as well as Zagreb Zoo in Maksimir district. Even though those two "neighbourhood(s)" have totally different physical and social description and different levels of development and business activities, as well as different access to the public and the market, they beyond any doubt share many mutual interests and totally same approach in process of introducing NBS solutions and green technology innovations.

That is exactly why we consider them as two ideal partners, to help each other in execution of planned project activities, to learn from each other and to complement each other in a common goal!

Nevertheless, even though it would be logical to expect that two different location points will activate two different neighbourhoods within the project – our expectation is that activation of Sesvete School will activate Sesvete district indeed, but activation of Zagreb Zoo will both activate its own district Maksimir as well as raise interest of all city area and wider.

Prekretnice u oblikovanju pilot projekta

Na temelju iskustava stečenih u dosadašnjim realiziranim projektima (vezanim za izradu modela urbane farme, te želje za njegovim daljnjim razvojem, kao i unapređenjem i implementacijom istog modela na širem području, te korištenjem postojećih znanstveno utemeljenih projekata i integriranih urbanističkih i arhitektonskih rješenja za usmjeravanje socio-tehničkih zahtjeva povezanih s naporima gradova da ispune svoje ciljeve u osiguravanju klimatske neutralnosti do 2030. godine), postojao je interes za osmišljavanje novog pilot projekta na ovom području.

Kako projekt UP2030 nastoji unaprijediti postojeća rješenja, Zagreb je, prije svega, želio nastaviti s razvojem modularnog sustava urbanih farmi, ali ovoga puta u jednoj osnovnoj školi u Sesvetama. Ideja je bila smanjiti troškove dostave u škole, smanjiti emisiju CO2, uključiti djecu u sudjelovanje u uzgoju hrane u svim fazama, a uzgojenu hranu koristiti u školskoj kuhinji.

Ipak, kako se ideja projekta UP2030 dalje razvija, Zagreb je saznao da osnovna škola, uz sve svoje velike benefite za promociju projektnih ideja, ima i određena ograničenja u provedbi planiranih projektnih mjera, slijedom čega je uveden dodatni projektni partner, zagrebački ZOO vrt, kako bismo bili sigurni da možemo prevladati potencijala ograničenja. Od tog trenutka Grad Zagreb paralelno nastavlja razvoj projekta na dvije lokacije (unutar dvije odvojene gradske četvrti)!

Ovdje je bitno napomenuti da se ideja projekta nimalo ne mijenja, te da obujam realizacije ostaje isti kao što je i planirano, osim što će se prostorno prostirati na dva područja.

Ova aktivnost otvara mogućnost proširenja opsega ciljanih skupina, bolje diseminacije i veće vidljivosti projekta. Promjene o kojima je riječ ovdje nisu prepoznate samo kao "promjene" već i kao "poboljšanja" osnovne ideje.

Dakle, glavna "prekretnica" u razvoju projekta može se opisati kao angažman dvaju jednako važnih partnera u projektu umjesto jednog: osnovne škole u Sesvetama, kao i zagrebačkog Zoološkog vrta u Maksimiru. Iako ta dva "susjedstva" imaju potpuno različit fizički i društveni opis te različite razine razvoja i poslovnih aktivnosti, kao i različit pristup javnosti i tržištu, oni van svake sumnje dijele mnoge zajedničke interese i potpuno isti pristup u procesu uvođenja NBS rješenja i zelenih tehnoloških inovacija.

Upravo zato ih smatramo dvama idealnim partnerima, da jedni drugima pomažu u realizaciji planiranih projektnih aktivnosti, da uče jedni od drugih i da se nadopunjuju u zajedničkom cilju!

Štoviše, iako bi bilo logično očekivati da će dvije različite lokacijske točke aktivirati dva različita kvarta unutar projekta – naše je očekivanje da će se aktiviranjem škole Sesvete aktivirati doista gradska četvrt Sesvete, ali aktiviranjem zagrebačkog Zoološkog vrta aktivirat će se ne samo gradska četvrt Maksimir nego će se pobuditi interes cijelog gradskog područja pa i šire.

Spatial characteristics of the neighbourhood(s)

Prostorne karakteristike lokacija u projektu

General note:

Since UP2030 Zagreb Pilot decided to include two different neighbourhoods among the same subject - Spatial and Social characteristics of the neighbourhood(s), will be given separately for both neighbourhoods in the following elaboration.

Opća napomena:

Budući da je UP2030 Zagreb Pilot odlučio uključiti dva različita susjedstva u istu temu - Prostorne i društvene karakteristike susjedstva(a), bit će dane odvojeno za oba susjedstva u sljedećoj razradi.

Land use characteristics

Karakteristike korištenja prostora

Neighbourhood I: Sesevete District

Sesevete district is the part of the City of Zagreb since 1981 and today it is the easternmost district of the city, characterized by settlements on the slopes of Mount Medvednica and the southern area in the plains within housing and an economic zone.

It is the largest city district with the largest number of inhabitants.

The city district of Sesevete occupies 25.8% of the total area of the City of Zagreb (165.25 km² out of a total of 641 km²).

Lokacija I: Gradska četvrt Sesevete

Gradska četvrt Sesevete u sastavu je Grada Zagreba od 1981. godine i danas je najistočnija gradska četvrt koju karakteriziraju naselja na obroncima Medvednice i južni ravničarski prostor unutar stambeno-gospodarske zone.

Najveća je gradska četvrt s najvećim brojem stanovnika.

Gradska četvrt Sesevete zauzima 25,8% ukupne površine Grada Zagreba (165,25 km² od ukupno 641 km²).

Neighbourhood II: Maksimir District

The Maksimir district is a characteristic city district with a large proportion of green areas consisting of forests, parks and meadows along streams and residential areas that are well covered by accompanying amenities.

The quarter occupies 2.3% of the area of the City of Zagreb, which is 3.02 km².

As part of the Masimir district, there is also the Maksimir Park, which was created at the end of the 18th and the beginning of the 19th century on the outskirts of the city at that time. It was the first public park in Southeastern Europe, but also one of the first in the world. Since 1964, it has been protected as a monument of park architecture, and it is also protected as a cultural asset.

Today's Zoo is also located within the Maksimir Park area.

*City of Zagreb: Illustration of Statistics on Sesevete District
(Sesevete District occupies an area of 165 km², which is 25.8% of the area of the City of Zagreb)*

*In this area there are protected areas of park architecture, natural areas recommended for protection and parts of nature that are protected by the measures of spatial plans. Also, in this district there are archaeological areas and individual localities, a historical architectural complex and an ethnological area.

Lokacija II: Gradska četvrt Maksimir

Četvrt Maksimir karakteristična je gradska četvrt s velikim udjelom zelenih površina koju čine šume, parkovi i livade uz potoke te stambena naselja dobro pokrivena popratnim sadržajima. Četvrt zauzima 2,3% površine Grada Zagreba, što iznosi 3,02 km².

U sklopu gradske četvrti Maksimir nalazi se i park Maksimir koji je nastao krajem 18. i početkom 19. stoljeća na periferiji tadašnjeg grada. Bio je to prvi javni park u jugoistočnoj Europi, ali i jedan od prvih u svijetu. Od 1964. godine zaštićena je kao spomenik parkovne arhitekture, a zaštićena je i kao kulturno dobro. Današnji Zoološki vrt također se nalazi na području parka Maksimir.

*Na području četvrti nalaze se zaštićena područja parkovne arhitekture, prirodna područja preporučena za zaštitu i dijelovi prirode koji se štite mjerama prostornih planova. Također, u ovoj se četvrti nalaze arheološka područja i pojedinačni lokaliteti, povijesna graditeljska cjelina te etnološko područje.

*City of Zagreb: illustration of Statistics on Maksimir District
(Maksimir District occupies an area of 3,02 km², which is 2,3% of the area of the City of Zagreb)*

Natural, public space and built environment land marks

Znamenitosti prirodnog i javnog prostora te izgrađenog okoliša

Neighbourhood I: Sesvete District

The northern part of the district includes the hills below Medvednica, and the southern plain in the contact zone of the Sava River. At the junction of the hills and the plain, the Sesvete settlement is situated. Half of the area of the district (50%) consists of agricultural and undeveloped areas, which is the highest percentage, in this kind of land use, of all city districts. Significant areas are planned for economic use in the future.

In relation to the total area of the City of Zagreb, the share of public green areas is 0.1%, and the share of sports and recreational areas is 0.4%.

*City of Zagreb: illustration of Statistics on Sesevete district
(0,4% is the share of sports and recreation areas; 0,1% is the share of public green areas)*

Lokacija I: Gradska četvrt Sesevete

Sjeverni dio četvrti obuhvaća pobrđe ispod Medvednice, a južni nizinski dio u kontaktnoj zoni rijeke Save. Na spoju brda i ravnice smjestilo se naselje Sesevete.

Polovicu površine četvrti (50%) čine poljoprivredne i neizgrađene površine, što je u postotku najviše u ovakvoj namjeni zemljišta od svih gradskih četvrti. Značajne površine planirane su za gospodarsko korištenje u budućnosti.

U odnosu na ukupnu površinu Grada Zagreba, udio javnih zelenih površina je 0,1%, a udio sportsko-rekreacijskih površina 0,4%.

Neighbourhood II: Maksimir District

The Maksimir district has the largest city park (Park Maksimir), and the share of public green areas in the total area of the district is the highest of all city districts and is 12.8%.

This district is also the 1st sports district that houses the Maksimir City Stadium, the Svetice Sports Recreation Center, the Svetice Swimming Pool Complex, the Maksimir Tennis Center, and numerous accompanying facilities, and the share of sports and recreation areas in the total area of the district is 2.9%.

*City of Zagreb: illustration of Statistics on Maksimir district
(2,9% is the share of sports and recreation areas; 12,8% is the share of public green areas)*

Lokacija II: Gradska četvrt Maksimir

Četvrt Maksimir ima najveći gradski park (park Maksimir), a udio javnih zelenih površina u ukupnoj površini četvrti najveći je od svih gradskih četvrti i iznosi 12,8%.

Ova četvrt je ujedno i prva po važnosti sportska četvrt u kojoj se nalaze Gradski stadion Maksimir, Športsko rekreacijski centar Svetice, Bazenski kompleks Svetice, Teniski centar Maksimir i brojni popratni sadržaji, a udio sportsko-rekreacijskih površina u ukupnoj površini okruga je 2,9%.

City of Zagreb: Illustration on Sesvete and Maksimir statistical data; (Sesvete District takes 25,8% of the City's total surface area; Maksimir District takes 2,3% of the City's total surface area)

Characteristics on size, walkability, density

Karakteristike veličine/ prohodnosti/ gustoće četvrti

Neighbourhood I: Sesvete District

The city district of Sesvete is the largest city district, with the largest number of inhabitants compared to other city districts, but with almost the lowest population density, which is only 424 inhabitants / km², which is three times less than the population density of the entire city (1,232 inhabitants / km²). In an administrative context, the city district consists of 46 local committees.

The spatial distribution of residents is not uniform, as the density is much higher in the central urban part of the city quarter (in the Sesvete settlement) and the density is much lower in other settlements with family housing.

This area is crossed by many major roads that connect Zagreb with the east of Croatia.

Pedestrian zones are concentrated in the centre of the settlement, and bicycle traffic mode is developing and increasing due to the expressed interest of the population.

Lokacija I: Gradska četvrt Sesvete

Gradska četvrt Sesvete najveća je gradska četvrt, s najvećim brojem stanovnika u odnosu na ostale gradske četvrti, ali s gotovo najmanjom gustoćom naseljenosti koja iznosi svega 424 st./km², što je tri puta manje od gustoće naseljenosti cijelog grada (1.232 st./km²). Administrativno Gradska četvrt sastoji se od 46 mjesnih odbora.

Prostorni raspored stanovnika nije ujednačen, jer je gustoća znatno veća u središnjem urbanom dijelu gradske četvrti (u naselju Sesvete), a znatno manja u ostalim naseljima obiteljskog stanovanja.

Ovim područjem prolaze mnoge glavne prometnice koje povezuju Zagreb s istokom Hrvatske. Pješačke zone su koncentrirane u središtu naselja, a biciklistički način prometa se razvija i povećava zbog izraženog interesa stanovništva.

Zagreb Touristic Board: Maksimir Park image; City of Zagreb: Sesvete district image

Neighbourhood II: Maksimir District

The Maksimir district is a medium-sized district. Although far back in history it was created on the outer eastern edge of the city, today, after the expansion and development of the city, it is positioned in its center.

The southern part of the district is predominantly low-lying, highly urbanized and connected by important city roads that connect the city and suburban areas with the very center of the city.

Although the district is highly urbanized by its character, a large proportion of green and park areas make it interesting for walks, bike rides, the use of ecological modes of movement and all kinds of recreation.

Lokacija II: Gradska četvrt Maksimir

Četvrt Maksimir je četvrt srednje veličine. Iako je davno u povijesti nastala na vanjskom istočnom rubu grada, danas se, nakon širenja i razvoja grada, smjestila u njegovo središte.

Južni dio četvrti pretežno je nizinski, izrazito urbaniziran i povezan važnim gradskim prometnicama koje povezuju grad i prigradska područja sa samim središtem grada.

Iako je četvrt po svom karakteru izrazito urbanizirana, veliki udio zelenih i parkovnih površina čini je zanimljivom za šetnje, vožnju biciklom, korištenje ekoloških načina kretanja i sve vrste rekreacije.

City of Zagreb: Panoramic aerial photography of Sesvete district

Connections to the UP2030 urban planning concepts

Veze s konceptima urbanog planiranja UP2030

Neighbourhood I: Sesvete District

As Sesvete district historically grew, in the past decades, it never achieved to develop a clear and articulated urban form and identity.

But recently, through the activities of a local non-governmental organization and with the help of experts from the Faculty of Architecture, it has developed an urban self-awareness that, among other things, requires a greater quantity and better quality of public spaces, green urban areas, new main square, better public amenities, an efficient road network, bicycle tracks, a safe railway crossing, a new space for a music school, a hub with spaces for small spin-off companies, "fab-labs" and producer culture. And above all, what is being sought is a new urban identity and dignity.

Lokacija I: Gradska četvrt Sesvete

Kako su Sesvete povijesno rasle, u proteklim desetljećima, nikada nisu uspjele razviti jasnu i artikuliranu urbanu formu i identitet.

No, u posljednje vrijeme, kroz djelovanje lokalne nevladine organizacije i uz pomoć stručnjaka s Arhitektonskog fakulteta, razvila je urbanu samosvijest koja, između ostalog, zahtijeva veću količinu i kvalitetu javnih površina, zelene urbane površine, novi glavni trg, bolju javnu opremljenost, učinkovitu cestovnu mrežu, biciklističke staze, siguran željeznički prijelaz, novi prostor za glazbenu školu, hub s prostorima za male spin-off tvrtke, "fab-labs" i kulturu proizvođača. A povrh svega, traži se novi urbani identitet i dignitet.

Neighbourhood II: Maksimir District

Given that the Maksimir district can already be described as a "green district", all the conceptual determinants of the UP2030 project can be applied here! Both the Maksimir Park and the Zoo, which is an integral part of it, have long been involved in the implementation of green policies and the application of all modern green technologies, and already have enviable references in the field of green renovations and the application of NBS solutions. In addition to all the new knowledge and experiences that this district

wants to embrace through the UP2030 project, it is also an excellent example and showcase of implementations from which others can learn, and that is exactly what their role will be in the Zagreb pilot project.

As a conclusion, this is a district with a strong historical and natural identity, which will be here used as a positive circumstance to spread the idea of the project more successfully and widely.

Lokacija II: Gradska četvrt Maksimir

S obzirom da se četvrt Maksimir već sada može opisati kao „zelena četvrt“, ovdje se mogu primijeniti sve konceptualne odrednice projekta UP2030! I Park Maksimir i Zoološki vrt, koji je njegov sastavni dio, odavno su uključeni u provedbu zelenih politika i primjenu svih suvremenih zelenih tehnologija, te već imaju zavidne reference u području zelenih obnova i primjene NBS rješenja. Uz sva nova znanja i iskustva koja ova gradska četvrt želi prihvatiti kroz projekt UP2030, ona je i izvrstan primjer i “izlog” implementacija iz kojih drugi mogu učiti, a upravo će to i biti njihova uloga u ovom zagrebačkom pilot projektu.

Zaključno, radi se o četvrti sa snažnim povijesnim i prirodnim identitetom, što će se ovdje iskoristiti kao pozitivna okolnost za uspješnije širenje ideje projekta.

Energy efficiency, travel behaviour, energy consumptions, availability of green space / the neighbourhood's carbon emissions

Energetska učinkovitost, modeli putovanja, potrošnja energije, dostupnost zelenih površina / lokalne emisije ugljike

LARGEST CITY DISTRICT

Sesvete 165.22 km²
9.2% of the total population of the City of Zagreb lives on an area of 25.8% of the City's total surface area.

- 7 special nature reserves of forest vegetation within Medvednica Nature Park
773.12 ha
- Maksimir Park
356.21 ha

City of Zagreb: Interesting statistical facts about the city districts of Sesvete and Maksimir

Neighbourhood I: Sesvete District

The awareness of the local population and local government is in dialogue with contemporary sustainable and green policies. In accordance with its possibilities, the local community has already implemented some green solutions, and the rest are planned when favourable economic conditions are created for it.

The City of Zagreb carried out the energy renovation of one school, with the aim of reducing energy consumption in educational institutions, and the trend of energy renovation in educational institutions is planned to be continued.

The local government is working on the improvement of bicycle traffic and the construction of new bicycle paths, due to existing level of citizen awareness about the need and desire for more sustainable modes of transportation in the settlement.

The local government has also already supported private investments in the processes of transformation of old brownfield sites: on the site of the former Badel Sesvete factory, the construction of a new multi-apartment settlement with plenty of social and public facilities is planned, which is supposed to be carried out in accordance with the laws and regulations of the EU (European Green Deal).

Lokacija I: Gradska četvrt Sesvete

Svijest lokalnog stanovništva i lokalne samouprave u dijalogu je sa suvremenom održivom i zelenom politikom. Lokalna zajednica je u skladu sa svojim mogućnostima već realizirala dio zelenih rješenja, a ostala se planiraju kada se za to stvore povoljni gospodarski uvjeti.

Grad Zagreb proveo je energetske obnovu jedne škole, s ciljem smanjenja potrošnje energije u obrazovnim ustanovama, a planira se nastaviti trend energetske obnove obrazovnih ustanova.

Lokalna uprava radi na poboljšanju biciklističkog prometa i izgradnji novih biciklističkih staza, zahvaljujući postojećoj razini svijesti građana o potrebi i želji za održivijim načinima prijevoza u naselju.

Lokalna samouprava također je već poduprla privatna ulaganja u procese transformacije starih "brownfield" lokacija: na prostoru bivše tvornice Badel Sesvete planira se gradnja novog višestambenog naselja s obiljem društvenih i javnih sadržaja, koji će se provoditi u skladu sa zakonima i propisima EU (European Green Deal).

Neighbourhood II: Maksimir District

As already stated in the previous elaborations, this is a district that we can with every right call a "green district". In addition to that, the Maksimir Park, which is the main spatial determinant of this district, also houses the Zoo, which uses the term "Green heart of the city" as its basic slogan.

Consequently, as is to be expected, this district can be considered a good example of importance to protect and develop city parks in urban areas.

The relatively wide and undeveloped lowland area that stretches from the north of the city from the slopes of Mount Medvednica all the way to the center of the city and Maksimir Park, allows a constant and unhindered flow of fresh mountain air into the densely populated part of the city, which is a great benefit for all the inhabitants.

Parts of the district are partly covered by well-managed forest and partly by remnants of an old, once impenetrable dense forest.

Although the public transport network in this district is well developed, there is a burden on car transport due to the central spatial position in the city and the economic activities within the district. Bicycle traffic is also represented thanks to the existing sports and recreational facilities.

City of Zagreb: Panoramic aerial photograph of Maksimir district

Lokacija II: Gradska četvrt Maksimir

Kao što je već navedeno u prethodnim elaboracijama, radi se o četvrti koju s punim pravom možemo nazvati "zelenom četvrti". Osim toga, u parku Maksimir, koji je glavna prostorna odrednica ove četvrti, nalazi se i Zoološki vrt, čiji je temeljni slogan "Zeleno srce grada".

Stoga se, kao što je i za očekivati, ova četvrt može smatrati dobrim primjerom važnosti zaštite i razvoja gradskih parkova u urbanim sredinama.

Relativno široko i neizgrađeno nizinsko područje koje se proteže od sjevernog dijela grada (od obronaka Medvednice pa sve do središta grada i parka Maksimir), omogućuje stalan i nesmetan dotok svježeg planinskog zraka u gusto naseljeni dio grada, što predstavlja veliki benefit za lokalno stanovništvo. Dijelovi gradske četvrti dijelom su prekriveni dobro održavanom šumom, a dijelom ostacima stare, nekoć neprohodne guste šume.

Iako je mreža javnog gradskog prijevoza u ovoj četvrti dobro razvijena, postoji opterećenje automobilskim prijevozom zahvaljujući centralnoj prostornoj poziciji u gradu te ekonomskim aktivnostima unutar četvrti. Biciklistički promet također je zastupljen zahvaljujući postojećim sportsko – rekreacijskim sadržajima.

City connection to neighbourhood

Povezanost četvrti sa gradom

Neighbourhood I: Sesvete District

Sesvete area will be developed and renovated in the future in parallel and in interdependence with the balanced and qualitative development of the City of Zagreb, while trying to preserve and develop its own identity and individuality.

The spatial connection with the rest of the City of Zagreb is solid, but - due to the area intersected by many major roads, an insufficiently efficient road network and an unsafe railroad crossing - it leaves a lot of room for improvement.

Lokacija I: Gradska četvrt Sesvete

Područje Sesveta će se u budućnosti razvijati i obnavljati usporedno i u međuovisnosti s ravnomjernim i kvalitetnim razvojem Grada Zagreba, nastojeći pritom očuvati i razvijati vlastiti identitet i individualnost. Prostorna povezanost s ostatkom Grada Zagreba je solidna, ali - zbog područja ispresijecanog velikim brojem prometnica, nedovoljno učinkovite cestovne mreže i nesigurnog željezničkog prijelaza - ostavlja dosta prostora za poboljšanje.

Neighbourhood II: Maksimir District

The spatial connection of this district with the rest of the City of Zagreb is excellent due to its position in the central part of city urban area. The city's road network is well developed, and all major highways, railways, buses and trams are here accessible.

Lokacija II: Gradska četvrt Maksimir

Prostorna povezanost ove četvrti s ostatkom Grada Zagreba odlična je zbog položaja u središnjem dijelu gradskog urbanog područja. Razvijena je gradska cestovna mreža, te su dostupni svi važniji autoputovi, željeznice, autobusi i tramvaji.

Social characteristics of the neighbourhood

Socijalne kategorije karakteristika gradskih četvrti

Demographic characteristics / households / groups of people

Demografske karakteristike / kućanstva / demografske skupine

Neighbourhood I: Sesvete District

In the city district of Sesvete lives 8.9% of the population (70,009 out of a total of 790,017 inhabitants of the City of Zagreb).

In the period between the 2001 and 2011 population censuses, there was a significant change in the number of inhabitants in some local councils, and the number of inhabitants increased by 18.2%.

With the construction of the Novi Jelkovec housing estate in 2009, a local committee of the same name was formed. The number of inhabitants increased significantly in 7 local committees, while only 2 local committees recorded a slight decrease in the number of inhabitants, while the other unmentioned local committees recorded only minor changes in relation to the number of inhabitants.

The average age of the population is 37.8 years, which is lower than the average age of the City of Zagreb, which is 41.6 years. Households are almost equally represented as two-member, three-member and four-member households, and there are slightly fewer one-member households, while the share of five-member / six-member households / and more is much higher compared to all other city districts. In conclusion, the average number of household members is 3.18 (2011).

The total number of apartments in the city quarter is 30,155, and the average area of the apartment is 84.32 m² (2011).

The share of highly educated population is 13.8%. The number of employees in legal entities is 11,617 (2018). The number of unemployed persons is decreasing.

The district recorded the largest increase in population due to immigration and natural population growth. On average, it is the youngest community in Zagreb. As a community, it is quite traditional, very closely related to the entrepreneurial way of thinking and living.

Lokacija I: Gradska četvrt Sesvete

U gradskoj četvrti Sesvete živi 8,9% stanovništva grada (70.009 od ukupno 790.017 stanovnika Grada Zagreba).

U razdoblju između popisa stanovništva 2001. i 2011. godine u pojedinim mjesnim odborima došlo je do značajne promjene u broju stanovnika, te je broj stanovnika porastao za 18,2%.

Izgradnjom stambenog naselja Novi Jelkovec 2009. godine formiran je istoimeni mjesni odbor. Broj stanovnika značajno je porastao u 7 mjesnih odbora, dok samo 2 mjesna odbora bilježe blagi pad broja stanovnika, dok ostali nespomenuti mjesni odbori bilježe tek manje promjene u odnosu na broj stanovnika.

Prosječna starost stanovništva je 37,8 godina, što je niže od prosječne starosti Grada Zagreba koja iznosi 41,6 godina. Domaćinstva su gotovo podjednako zastupljena kao dvočlana, tročlana i četveročlana, a jednočlanih je nešto manje, dok je udio petočlanih /šestočlanih/ i više domaćinstava znatno veći u odnosu na sve druge gradske četvrti. Zaključno, prosječan broj članova kućanstva je 3,18 (2011.).

Ukupan broj stanova u gradskoj četvrti je 30.155, a prosječna površina stana je 84,32 m² (2011.).

Udio visokoobrazovanog stanovništva je 13,8%. Broj zaposlenih u pravnim osobama je 11.617 (2018.). Broj nezaposlenih se smanjuje.

Četvrt bilježi najveći porast stanovništva zahvaljujući doseljavanju i prirodnom priraštaju stanovništva. U prosjeku je to najmlađa zajednica u Zagrebu. Kao zajednica dosta je tradicionalna, vrlo blisko vezana uz poduzetnički način razmišljanja i življenja.

Neighbourhood II: Maksimir District

6.2% of the population of the City of Zagreb lives in the Maksimir district (48,902 out of a total of 790,017 inhabitants of the City of Zagreb).

In the period between the population census of 2001 and 2011, there was an increase in some local councils and a decrease in some, but overall without significant changes.

The city district consists of 11 local committees.

The average age of the population is 43.5 years, which is higher than the average for the City of Zagreb (41.6). The majority of households are one-member and two-member households (57.0%), while three-member and four-member households are represented by a share of 34.4%.

The largest share is three-room apartments.

The share of highly educated population is 39.3%. The number of unemployed persons is decreasing.

Lokacija II: Gradska četvrt Maksimir

U gradskoj četvrti Maksimir živi 6,2% stanovništva Grada Zagreba (48.902 od ukupno 790.017 stanovnika Grada Zagreba).

U razdoblju između popisa stanovništva 2001. i 2011. godine u pojedinim mjesnim odborima bilježi se porast a u nekima pad broja stanovnika, ali sveukupno bez značajnijih promjena.

Gradsku četvrt čini 11 mjesnih odbora.

Prosječna starost stanovništva je 43,5 godina I veća je od prosjeka Grada Zagreba (41,6). Kućanstva su najvećim dijelom jednočlana I dvočlana (57,0%), dok su tročlana I četvrtveročlana zastupljena udjelom od 34,4%.

Najveći je udio trosobnih stanova.

Udio visokoobrazovanog stanovništva je 39,3%. Broj nezaposlenih osoba je u padu.

Challenges and strengths

Izazovi i prednosti

Neighbourhood I: Sesvete District

Sesvete area has the largest number of primary schools, 18 of them (of which 16 regular and 2 art schools), 29 preschool education facilities (of which 21 are city kindergartens and 8 private), as well as the largest number of social protection institutions (24) of all city districts.

Furtherly, in the city district of Sesvete, it is necessary to build 5 new kindergartens with a total capacity of 1250 children.

According to data from the *Public Health Service Network*, there is a lack of medical teams for general medicine, dental medicine, and women's health care, as well as the construction of new health centre facilities is needed.

*City of Zagreb: Illustration on Sesvete statistical data
(28 locations of preschool education; 18 locations of primary school education)*

Lokacija I: Gradska četvrt Sesvete

Na području Sesveta nalazi se najveći broj osnovnih škola, njih 18 (od toga 16 redovnih i 2 umjetničke škole), 29 ustanova predškolskog odgoja (od toga 21 gradski vrtić i 8 privatnih), kao i najveći broj ustanova socijalne zaštite (24) od svih gradskih četvrti.

Nadalje, u gradskoj četvrti Sesvete postoji potreba za izgradnjom 5 novih dječjih vrtića ukupnog kapaciteta 1250 djece.

Prema podacima iz Mreže javnih zdravstvenih službi, nedostaje liječničkih timova opće medicine, dentalne medicine i zdravstvene zaštite žena, a potrebna je i izgradnja novih objekata domova zdravlja.

Neighbourhood II: Maksimir District

Maksimir is a district with many health institutions (15), of which 9 are health centers and 6 hospitals (Clinical Hospital Center Zagreb, Merkur Clinical Hospital, Srebrnjak Children's Hospital).

In the eastern part of the district, there is a complex of higher education institutions, a High Police School, the Faculty of Agriculture and the Faculty of Forestry of the University of Zagreb.

There are 5 high schools around the city district (3 city high schools, 2 private schools and one female dormitory).

For the improvement of existing facilities in the future, reconstruction of the Sports Recreation Center of Svetice and the City Stadium Maksimir is planned, as well as the construction of new smaller district schools with the extension and improvement of the existing ones.

*City of Zagreb: Illustration on Maksimir statistical data
(16 locations of preschool education; 12 locations of primary school education)*

Lokacija II: Gradska četvrt Maksimir

Maksimir je četvrt s mnogo zdravstvenih ustanova (15), od kojih je 9 domova zdravlja i 6 bolnica (KBC Zagreb, Klinička bolnica Merkur, Dječja bolnica Srebrnjak).

U istočnom dijelu nalazi se kompleks visokoškolskih ustanova, Visoka policijska škola, Agronomski i Šumarski fakultet Sveučilišta u Zagrebu.

U gradskoj četvrti nalazi se 5 srednjih škola (3 gradske srednje škole, 2 privatne škole i jedan ženski đački dom).

Za unaprjeđenje postojećih objekata u budućnosti je planirana rekonstrukcija Športsko rekreacijskog centra Svetice i Gradskog stadiona Maksimir, te izgradnja novih manjih područnih škola uz dogradnju i poboljšanje postojećih.

Participation motivation

Motivacija za participaciju

Neighbourhood I: Sesvete District

Citizens' interest (which was also evident through other previously implemented projects!) in improving the identity image of the settlement, increasing the quality of life and supplementing better / more modern / more sustainable contents in the settlement, are the basic motive for participation in the implementation of projects related to sustainable urban development.

Lokacija I: Gradska četvrt Sesvete

Interes građana (koji je bio vidljiv i kroz druge dosad provedene projekte!) za poboljšanjem identitetske slike naselja, povećanjem kvalitete života i upotunjavanjem kvalitetnijim/modernijim/održivijim sadržajima u naselju, osnovni su motiv sudjelovanja u provedba projekata vezanih uz održivi urbani razvoj.

City of Zagreb, EU project proGReg: Citizen involved in green politics implementation

Neighbourhood II: Maksimir District

Zoo Zagreb, with its popularity among citizens and its local and international activities, certainly represents one of the city's most significant landmarks, and thus also a landmark of the Maksimir District itself. For many years, the institution has been successfully involved in the implementation of EU projects (such as: the project "Modernization of the Vocational Education and Training System" which was co-financed by the European Social Fund and is the result of work on the Erasmus+ program project "European Professional Zookeeper Qualification Framework"; Modernization of the Zoo Zagreb Phase I; City windows to nature - Improvement of urban biodiversity and development of green infrastructure (Modernization II); Modernization of the Zoo Zagreb Phase III - Wildlife Sanctuary) which have recently significantly contributed to the quality of work and general attendance, as a result of which Zoo Zagreb itself, as well as its visitors and citizens within the city district have a strong motivation to continue developing and improving public facilities and educational programs at that location.

Lokacija II: Gradska četvrt Maksimir

Ustanova Zoološki vrt Grada Zagreba sa svojom popularnošću među građanima i svojim lokalnim i međunarodnim djelovanjem, zasigurno predstavlja jedan od najznačajnijih gradskih landmarka, pa tako i landmarka same četvrti Maksimir. Ustanova je već dugi niz godina uspješno uključena u provedbu EU projekata (kao što su: Projekt “Modernizacija sustava strukovnog obrazovanja i osposobljavanja” sufinanciran je iz Europskog socijalnog fonda a rezultat je rada na projektu Erasmus+ programa, pod nazivom “Europski okvir kvalifikacija profesionalnih čuvara zooloških vrtova”; Modernizacija zoološkog vrta u Zagrebu I faza; Gradski prozori u prirodu – unaprjeđenje urbane bioraznolikosti i razvoj zelene infrastrukture (Modernizacija II); Modernizacija Zoološkog vrta grada Zagreba III faza - Oporavilište za divlje životinje) koji su svojedobno značajno doprinijeli kvaliteti rada i općoj posjećenosti, slijedom čega i sami Zoo Zagreb, i njegovi posjetitelji ali i građani unutar gradske četvrti imaju snažnu motivaciju nastaviti razvijati i unaprjeđivati javne sadržaje i edukativne programe na toj lokaciji.

*City of Zagreb, EU project proGleg:
Citizen with special needs engaged in activities of Therapeutic garden*

Challenges and opportunities

Izazovi I prilike

Key approaches/ concepts; Level of success in implementing actions; Other linked projects and opportunities

Main opportunities are projects and actions which are already implemented before, and to be used as a background for further projects and improvement.

In Sesvete district:

The main benefit of modular urban farm in school is targeting specific target groups, mainly children and teenagers, who exactly are the most important group of citizens in process of introducing green politics and life quality improvements. Children are also an excellent mediator in intergenerational communication and influencing awareness raising.

Existing element to be used and furtherly developed in new projects are:

- combined modular urban farm from the H2020 proGireg project in Sesvete, Zagreb - already implemented
- therapeutic garden to target disabled users in the neighbourhood of Sesvete, Zagreb - already implemented

In Maksimir district (ZooZagreb):

The main benefit of modular urban farm in Zoo is possibility to target very wide range of different target groups. Since it is a public content that is equally attractive, entertaining and educational, it can indeed attract the most diverse groups of users.

Existing element to be used and furtherly developed in new projects are:

- the project "Modernization of the Vocational Education and Training System" which was co-financed by the European Social Fund and is the result of work on the Erasmus+ program project "European Professional Zookeeper Qualification Framework"
- Modernization of the Zoo Zagreb Phase I
- City windows to nature - Improvement of urban biodiversity and development of green infrastructure (Modernization II)
- Modernization of the Zoo Zagreb Phase III - Wildlife Sanctuary

Photo ZooZagreb: "Red panda High five :)" / Education in ZooZagreb

Ključni pristupi/koncepti; Razina uspješnosti u provedbi aktivnosti; Ostali povezani projekti i mogućnosti

Glavne prilike su projekti i akcije koji su već provedeni i koji će se koristiti kao pozadina za daljnje projekte i poboljšanja.

U gradskoj četvrti Sesvete:

Glavna prednost modularne urbane farme u školi je ciljanje na specifične ciljne skupine, uglavnom djecu i tinejdžere, koji su upravo najvažnija skupina građana u procesu uvođenja zelenih politika i poboljšanja kvalitete života. Djeca su također odličan posrednik u međugeneracijskoj komunikaciji i utječu na podizanje razine svijesti.

Postojeći elementi koji će se koristiti i dalje razvijati u novim projektima su:

- kombinirana modularna urbana farma iz projekta H2020 proGireg u Sesvetama, Zagreb - već implementirano
- terapijski vrt za korisnike s invaliditetom u naselju Sesvete, Zagreb - već implementirano

U četvrti Maksimir (Zoološki vrt Zagreb):

Glavna prednost modularne urbane farme u zoološkom vrtu je mogućnost ciljanja vrlo širokog raspona različitih ciljnih skupina. Budući da se radi o javnom sadržaju koji je podjednako atraktivan, zabavan i edukativan, doista se može privući najrazličitije skupine korisnika.

Postojeći elementi koji će se koristiti i dalje razvijati u novim projektima su:

- projekt „Modernizacija sustava strukovnog obrazovanja i osposobljavanja“ koji je sufinanciran iz Europskog socijalnog fonda i rezultat je rada na projektu Erasmus+ programa „European Professional Zookeeper Qualification Framework“
- Modernizacija Zoološkog vrta Zagreb I. faza
- Gradski prozori u prirodu - Unapređenje urbane bioraznolikosti i razvoj zelene infrastrukture (Modernizacija II)
- Modernizacija Zoološkog vrta Zagreb Faza III - Utočište za divlje životinje

Questions to explore further:

Key challenges faced in pilot neighbourhood? Risk factors in pilot neighbourhood?

*The main challenge we face in the city district of Sesvete is the reduced possibility of maintaining plants inside the urban farm when the school is not working, and the reduced visibility of the project implementation due to the obligation of controlled entrance to the school. **(Proposed solution:** plant maintenance will be simplified by using vegetation that does not require high maintenance and does not require a lot of care; visibility and openness to the public will be solved by introducing another partner - the Zoo - which is open to the public).*

*The main challenge we face in the Maksimir district is that the Zoo is in a heritage protection zone, so the challenge is the architectural design of a modular urban farm that will meet the constructive, aesthetic and functional criteria strictly determined in such areas. **(Proposed solution:** an architectural design office that has experience in working in protected areas, but also experience in designing facilities for accommodation and protection of animals, will be engaged, which will work on the creation of the necessary documentation and coordination of performance).*

Pitanja za dodatno istraživanje:

Ključni izazovi s kojima se suočava pilot projekt na odabranim lokacijama? Čimbenici rizika u provedbi pilot projekta?

Glavni izazov sa kojim se susrećemo u gradskoj četvrti Sesvete jest smanjena mogućnost održavanja biljaka unutar urbane farme u vrijeme kada škola ne radi, te smanjena vidljivost projektne implementacije radi obaveze kontroliralog ulaza u školu. **(Prijedlog rješenja:** održavanje biljaka će se pojednostavniti uporabom vegetacije koja nije zahtjevna za održavanje i ne zahtijeva veliku brigu; vidljivost i otvorenost prema javnosti riješiti će se uvođenjem drugog partnera – Zoo vrta – koji je otvoren prema svojoj općoj javnosti).

Glavni izazov sa kojim se susrećemo u gradskoj četvrti Maksimir jest to da se Zoo vrt nalazi u zoni zaštite baštine, slijedom čega izazov predstava dizajn i arhitektonsko oblikovanje modularne urbane farme koja će zadovoljiti konstruktivne, estetske i funkcionalne kriterije striktno određene u takvim područjima. **(Prijedlog rješenja:** angažirati će se arhitektonsko projektni ured koji ima iskustvo u radu u zaštićenim cjelinama ali i iskustvo u projektiranju objekata za smještaj i zaštitu životinja, koji će raditi na izradi potrebne dokumentacije ali i koordinaciji izvedbe).

Current approach and actions

Aktualni pristupi projektnim aktivnostima

Ongoing activities; Current strategies

Current approach in process of planning new activities are:

- to improve existing green infrastructure network in the city (to improve existing model of modular urban farm in Sesvete district as well as to fulfil existing green network in Maksimir district)
- to leverage existing knowledge from recent projects to extend application of modular urban farms to school communities as well as to raise awareness on importance of healthy food both for humans and animals in urban areas

Tekuće aktivnosti; Trenutne strategije

Sadašnji pristupi u procesu planiranja novih aktivnosti su:

- *poboljšati postojeću zelenu infrastrukturnu mrežu u gradu (poboljšati postojeći model modularne urbane farme u četvrti Sesvete kao i dodatno unaprijediti postojeću zelenu mrežu u četvrti Maksimir)*
- *iskoristiti postojeće znanje iz nedavnih projekata za proširenje primjene modularnih urbanih farmi na školske zajednice kao i za podizanje svijesti o važnosti zdrave hrane za ljude i životinje u urbanim područjima*

Among **Current approach and actions**, there are projects or initiatives to be furtherly explored;

As the main goal is to upgrade existing projects to move closer to climate mitigation and data collection in area of food production improvement (regarding food in urban system), the main idea of overall project is to establish a model which will be firstly proven in small scale in chosen location and controlled environment, and lately to be replicated in wider context and in larger use.

First step, therefore, is to DRILL-DOWN most relevant data and partners, whereas **last step** will be to SCALE-UP all gathered data and gained knowledge.

According to everything mentioned, **1st year** is to be used to organize “Analyses Workshops” on scientific background (where step#1 will focus on “needs”, step#2 will focus on “tools” and step#3 will focus on “solutions”). In addition, **2nd year** is to be used for implementation of container farm model “in-situ” including accompanying education of students and related interested parties. Finally, **3rd year** is to carry out SCALE-UP OF KNOWLEDGE and set up a concept for a thematic DATA CATALOG.

UPDATE /OCTOBER/2023:

The **First step** has already been successfully completed within the first 6 months, whereas the analysis of the collected data has already had a positive impact on the modeling of project activities! Minor changes compared to the original plan were successfully introduced (referring to introduction of new project stakeholder!), however these changes should have a major impact on the more successful realization of the basic unchanged project idea!

Aktivnosti I projekti koje bi trebalo dodatno istražiti u okviru aktualnog pristupa projektu

Budući da je glavni cilj nadogradnja postojećih projekata kako bi se približili ublažavanju klime i prikupljanju podataka u području poboljšanja proizvodnje hrane (u vezi s hranom u urbanom sustavu), glavna ideja cjelokupnog projekta je uspostaviti model koji će se prvo dokazati u "malom mjerilu" na odabranoj lokaciji i kontroliranom okruženju, a kasnije replicirati u većem kontekstu i u široj upotrebi.

*Prvi korak je, dakle, "istražiti" najrelevantnije podatke i partnere, dok će posljednji korak biti "proširenje" svih prikupljenih podataka i stečenog znanja. Prema svemu navedenom, **prva godina** će se koristiti za organiziranje "Radionica analize" na znanstvenoj pozadini (gdje će se korak #1 fokusirati na "potrebe", korak #2 će se fokusirati na "alate", a korak #3 će se fokusirati na "rješenja"). Osim toga, **2. godina** će se koristiti za implementaciju modela kontejnerske farme "in-situ" uključujući popratnu edukaciju studenata i drugih zainteresiranih strana. Konačno, **treća godina** je provedba SCALE-UP-a znanja i postavljanje koncepta za tematski KATALOG PODATAKA.*

AŽURIRANJE/LISTOPAD/2023:

Prvi korak je već uspješno odrađen unutar prvih 6 mjeseci, gdje je analiza prikupljenih podataka već sad pozitivno utjecala na modeliranje projektnih aktivnosti! uspješno su uvedene manje promjene u odnosu na prvobitni plan (uvođenje novog ključnog dionika u projekt!), međutim upravo bi te promjene trebale imati veliki utjecaj na uspješniju realizaciju osnovne nepromijenjene projektne ideje!

Needs and aspirations

Potrebe I nastojanja

Visions and goals

Vision 1: To capitalize on strong agricultural history as well as apply and improve existing models;

Vision 2: To continue the efforts of city to mitigate climate risks by expanding the green infrastructure networks and introducing NBS as well as to contribute to zero emission efforts by producing food that needs no transport;

Vision 3: To redefine urban agriculture by creating and closing the loop from „School Farming to Food Production to Food Consumption to Food Waste to Composting, and back to School Farming”;

(*the same model is intended to be used in Zoo, whereas Zoo will be the showcase of food production loop both for humans and animals and proof of their inextricable link in the ecosystem!)

Vizije I ciljevi

Vizija 1: Iskoristiti snažnu poljoprivrednu povijest kao i primijeniti i poboljšati postojeće modele;

Vizija 2: Nastaviti s naporima grada da ublaži klimatske rizike širenjem mreža zelene infrastrukture i uvođenjem NBS-a, kao i pridonijeti naporima za nulte emisije proizvodnjom hrane kojoj nije potreban prijevoz;

Vizija 3: Redefinirati urbanu poljoprivredu stvaranjem i zatvaranjem kruga od „školskog uzgoja do proizvodnje hrane do potrošnje hrane do rasipanja hrane do sastavljanja i natrag do školskog uzgoja“;

(*isti model se namjerava koristiti u zoološkom vrtu, dok će zoološki vrt biti ogledni primjer proizvodnje hrane i za ljude i životinje istovremeno te dokaz njihove neraskidive veze u ekosustavu!)

Needs and aspirations

Understanding of climate issues on Food Pilot

Climate change generates specific climate risks which impact daily life.

We note unexpected changes in weather conditions or more extreme behavior of those expected, which is why some vegetation and some crops that are traditionally produced and used locally do not succeed or even begin to be absent from production.

Contextualisation of Zagreb Needs: Self-sustainability of plant cultivation and resilience of green food

It is our NEED to make citizens aware of these processes and the hint of potential even more drastic processes, and to guide them in the possibility of replacing one culture with another or growing displaced cultures in conditions protected from external influences and drastic weather changes.

In order to achieve this, it is necessary to maintain the education of citizens, but also what is even more important: to present them with an example of good practice. Just such an example is a modular urban farm, where vegetation used for human and animal nutrition would be grown as well as seedlings of plants and trees for a additional greening of urban areas where needed.

Meeting this NEED is expected to result in other equally valuable benefits, such as the production of part of the food in the location (which makes the location more resistant to external changes!), a reduction in transportation costs, a positive impact on biodiversity, and other complementary benefits.

Food resilience strategy has a wide range of positive outcomes, such as: Health and well-being; Self-reliant communities; Lifelong learning; Thriving local food economy; Resilient and sustainable food system; Improvement of public spaces and garden city heritage; and many others.

LOCATION	NEED	ACTIVITY	BENEFIT
SCHOOL	need to formulate very concrete interventions/ need to make a showcase of food resilience possibilities	FOOD PRODUCTION: VEGATALES	Food resilience/ reducing transport
		FOOD PRODUCTION: FRUITS	Healthy food/ positive impact do biodiversity
		FLOWER PRODUCTION	Urban greening/ biodiversity/ reducing CO2
ZOO	need to formulate very concrete interventions/ need to make a showcase of food resilience possibilities	FOODPRODUCTION FOR HUMANS AND ANIMALS	Food resilience/ ecosystem support
		PRODUCTION OF SMALL PLANTS	Urban greening/ biodiversity/ reducing CO2

Illustration on project activities on Needs

Need 1: To formulate very concrete interventions!

Actions

- To expand existing modular urban farm model (developed in the H2020/proGReg project) by introducing small modular indoor growing farms adjacent to elementary and high schools)
- To engage and include local schools (**via Sestete location!**) as well as other city schools (**via Maksimir / Zoo location!**) to adjust modular urban farm to school needs; to apply „co-design process” in all modular urban farm activities

Need 2: To make a showcase of food resilience possibilities!

Action:

- To implement both activities and infrastructure to provide part of the **school/Zoo** meals at indoor urban farm
- Shape healthy diet choices; offer climate education and opportunities; increase food resilience; reduce transport related CO2

GLOBAL NEEDS	CITY NEEDS	LOCAL COMMUNITY NEEDS	PROJECT NEEDS	PROJECT ACTION ON NEEDS	
need to be prepared for climate change	need to make scientific knowledge to be used at local levels	need to use local experiences as feedback to policymakers (to higher up or share with other jurisdictions)	need to formulate very concrete interventions	To expand existing modular urban farm model; To engage and include local school and Zoo	<i>„A local food production and distribution system based on ecological sustainability, able to withstand natural and man-made shocks is a vital part of food resilience “</i>
need to support decision-makers at the local and regional levels in increasing their capacity: to absorb knowledge solutions/ to anticipate risks/ to adapt/ to change	need to level-up climate finance contributions	need to integrate NBS into adaptation planning processes	need to make a showcase of food resilience possibilities	To provide part of the school/Zoo meals at indoor urban farm; To Shape healthy diet choices/ offer climate education/ increase food resilience/ reduce transport related CO2	<i>(based on a World Health Organisation, 1996 World Food Summit definition of food security)</i>

Illustration on ranking the levels of need

Potrebe i nastojanja

Razumijevanje klimatskih pitanja na pilot projektu vezanom uz uzgoj hrane

Klimatske promjene stvaraju specifične klimatske rizike koji utječu na svakodnevni život.

Bilježimo neočekivane promjene vremenskih uvjeta ili ekstremnije ponašanje onih očekivanih, radi čega neka vegetacija i neke kulture koje se uvriježeno lokalno proizvode i koriste slabije uspijevaju ili čak počinju izostajati iz proizvodnje.

Kontekstualizacija Potreba za Zagreb: Samoodrživost uzgoja biljaka i otpornost zelene hrane

Naša je POTREBA osvijestiti građane o ovim procesima i nagovještaju potencijalnih još drastičnijih procesa, te ih uputiti u mogućnosti zamjene jednih kultura drugima ili uzgoj potrebnih kultura u uvjetima zaštićenih od vanjskih utjecaja i drastičnih vremenskih promjena.

Da bi se to postiglo potrebno je održati edukaciju građana, ali i ono što je još važnije: prezentirati im primjer dobre prakse. Upravo takav primjer jest modularna urbana farma, u kojoj bi se uzgajala istovremeno i vegetacija koja se koristi za ishranu ljudi i životinja, ali i sadnice ukrasnog bilja i drveća koji bi se koristili za dodatno ozelenjavanje urbanih površina gdje postoji takva potreba.

Iz zadovoljavanja ove POTREBE očekuje se da će posljedično proizaći i druge jednako vrijedne koristi, kao što su proizvodnja dijela hrane na lokaciji (što lokaciju čini otpornijom na vanjske promjene!), smanjenje troškova transporta, pozitivan utjecaj na bilokošku raznolikost i druge komplementarne dobrobiti.

Strategija otpornosti hrane ima širok raspon pozitivnih ishoda, kao što su: zdravlje i opća dobrobit; jačanje samostalne zajednice; cjeloživotno učenje; razvoj lokalne prehrambene ekonomije; otporan i održiv prehrambeni sustav; unapređenje javnih prostora i gradske baštine vrtova; i mnogi drugi.

LOKACIJA	POTREBA	AKTIVNOST	DOBROBIT
ŠKOLA	potreba za formuliranjem vrlo konkretnih intervencija/ potreba za oglednim primjerom mogućnosti otpornosti hrane	PROIZVODNJA HRANE: POVRĆE	Otpornost hrane/smanjenje transporta
		PROIZVODNJA HRANE: VOĆE	Zdrava hrana/ pozitivan utjecaj na biološku raznolikost
		PROIZVODNJA CVIJEĆA I UKRASNOG BILJA	Urbano ozelenjavanje/ bioraznolikost/ smanjenje CO2
ZOO	potreba za formuliranjem vrlo konkretnih intervencija/ potreba za oglednim primjerom mogućnosti otpornosti hrane	PROIZVODNJA HRANE ZA LJUDE I ŽIVOTINJE	Otpornost hrane/podrška ekosustavu
		PROIZVODNJA SADNICA	Urbano ozelenjavanje/ bioraznolikost/ smanjenje CO2

Ilustracija o projektnim aktivnostima – Potrebe

Potreba 1: Formulirati vrlo konkretne intervencije!

Aktivnost

- Proširiti postojeći model urbane farme (razvijen u projektu H2020/proGInreg) uvođenjem malih modularnih farmi za uzgoj u zatvorenom prostoru u blizini osnovnih i srednjih škola)
- Angažirati i uključiti lokalne škole (**preko lokacije Sesevete!**) kao i druge gradske škole (**preko lokacije Maksimir / Zoološki vrt!**) kako bi se prilagodila modularna urbana farma potrebama škole; primijeniti „proces zajedničkog dizajna“ u svim aktivnostima modularnog urbanog gospodarstva

Potreba 2: Napraviti “ogledni primjer” mogućnosti otpornosti hrane!

Aktivnost

- Provesti i aktivnosti i infrastrukturu kako bi se proizveo dio obroka u školi/zoološkom vrtu na lokalnoj zatvorenoj urbanoj farmi
- Oblikovati izbor zdrave prehrane; ponuditi obrazovanje o mogućnostima zaštite klime; povećati otpornost hrane na vanjske utjecaje; smanjiti CO2 povezan s prometom

POTREBE NA GLOBALNOJ RAZINI	POTREBE NA GRADSKOJ RAZINI	POTREBE LOKALNE ZAJEDNICE	POTREBE PROJEKTA	PROJEKTNE AKTIVNOSTI VEZANE UZ POTREBE	
<i>Potreba za spremnost na klimatske promjene</i>	<i>potreba za stvaranjem korištenjem znanstvenih podloga za praktičnu lokalnu primjenu</i>	<i>potreba za korištenjem lokalnih iskustava kao povratne informacije kreatorima politika (za podizanje važnosti na višu razinu ili potvrđivanje zakonodavnih okvira)</i>	<i>Potreba za formuliranjem vrlo konkretnih intervencija</i>	<i>Potreba za proširenjem postojećeg modela urbane farme; Potreba za uključivanjem škole i zoološkog vrta</i>	<i>„Lokalni sustav proizvodnje i distribucije hrane temeljen na ekološkoj održivosti, sposoban izdržati prirodne i umjetno izazvane šokove vitalni je dio otpornosti hrane“</i>
<i>potreba za podrškom donositeljima odluka na lokalnoj i regionalnoj razini u povećanju njihove sposobnosti: apsorbiranja rješenja znanja/ predviđanja rizika/ prilagodbe/ promjena</i>	<i>potreba za povećanjem doprinosa za financiranje klimatskih promjena</i>	<i>potreba za integracijom NBS-a u procese planiranja prilagodbe</i>	<i>Potreba za stvaranjem oglednog primjera otpornosti hrane</i>	<i>Potreba za proizvodnjom dijela obroka u školi/ zoološkom vrtu unutar modulane farme; Potreba za oblikovanjem zdravih izbora hrane/ za edukacijom o klimatskim promjenama/ za povećanjem otpornosti hrane/ za smanjenje CO2 vezanim uz transport</i>	<i>(na temelju definicije sigurnosti hrane Svjetske zdravstvene organizacije iz 1996. Svjetskog sastanka na vrhu o hrani)</i>

Ilustracija o rangiranju razina potreba

Among Needs and aspirations, there is a subject posed to be further explored:

According to recent initiative and recommendation to reconsider possibility of installing a green roof instead of an ordinary flat roof in reconstruction or new development of any given building, it is a challenge to try to implement innovation in form of -so called- "Edible Landscape" which will be a sub-goal in this project to be furtherly explored.

*Tema koju je potrebno dodatno istražiti u području **Potreba i nastojanja**:*

Prema nedavnoj inicijativi i preporuci da se ponovno razmotri mogućnost ugradnje zelenog krova umjesto običnog ravnog krova u rekonstrukciji ili novom razvoju bilo koje građevine, izazov je pokušati implementirati inovaciju u obliku tzv. "Jestivog krajolika" što će biti podcilj u ovom projektu koji će se dalje istraživati.

People, Partners, Organisations and more

Pojedinci, partneri, organizacije I ostalo

Already engaged stakeholders; People needed to be engaged

List of main actors engaged to reach the approach and outputs:

1. Elementary school Luka, Sesvete, Zagreb
2. Public institution ZooZagreb, Zagreb

List of other actors needed to be engaged:

1. architectural office (private company) with knowledge and experience in the field of cultural and nature protection / exact business entity, TBD
2. organizations and individuals who will present the practical application of the idea of climate and environmental protection as well as sustainable healthy food production system (for participation in seminars and workshops that are part of project activities) / exact business entity, TBD

Već uključeni dionici; Subjekti koje je potrebno dodatno angažirati

Popis glavnih aktera angažiranih za postizanje pristupa i rezultata:

1. Osnovna škola Luka, Sesvete, Zagreb
2. Javna ustanova Zoološki vrtZagreb, Zagreb

Popis ostalih aktera koje je potrebno angažirati:

1. arhitektonski ured (privatna tvrtka) sa znanjem i iskustvom u području zaštite kulture i prirode / točan poslovni subjekt, odredit će se naknadno
2. organizacije i pojedinci koji će prezentirati praktičnu primjenu ideje zaštite klime i okoliša kao i održivog sustava proizvodnje zdrave hrane (za sudjelovanje na seminarima i radionicama koje su dio projektnih aktivnosti) / točan poslovni subjekt, odredit će se naknadno

City of Zagreb: Illustration of City of Zagreb organisation at official website

*Among **People, Partners, Organisations and more** there are elements that are yet to be defined to reach the goal;*

*Stakeholder prioritization will direct more attention to those who can offer **data** and/or **co-working** in area of urban food-production-system and climate effect to food production. The importance of a multidisciplinary approach in the "logical matrix" of identification of potential stakeholders was considered to achieve inclusion of all sectors that can contribute to the realization of the topic.*

The process of „stakeholder identification“, „stakeholder selection“ and finally „stakeholder cooperation“ will be accompanied by seminars, focus group interviews, surveys and demonstrations.

Finally, stakeholder engagement can be broken down as follows: public sector and partners to (CO)DECIDE; educational sector to COPRODUCE; academic sector to ADVICE; public institute to CONSULT; general public and NGOs to INFORM.

Među pojedincima, partnerima, organizacijama i ostalima, postoje elementi koji se tek trebaju definirati da bi se postigao cilj;

Određivanje prioriteta dionika više će se bazirati na onima koji mogu ponuditi podatke i/ili suradnju u području urbanog sustava proizvodnje hrane i klimatskih učinaka na proizvodnju hrane.

Razmotrena je važnost multidisciplinarnog pristupa u „logičkoj matrici“ identifikacije potencijalnih dionika kako bi se postiglo uključivanje svih sektora koji mogu pridonijeti realizaciji teme.

Proces „identifikacije dionika“, „odabira dionika“ i na kraju „suradnje dionika“ bit će popraćen seminarima, intervjuima fokus grupa, anketama i demonstracijama.

Konačno, angažman dionika može se raščlaniti na sljedeći način:

javni sektor i partneri biti će pozvani da (SU)ODLUČUJU; obrazovni sektor biti će pozvan na KOPRODUKCIJU; akademski sektor biti će pozvan za SAVJETOVANJE; javni zavod biti će pozvan za KONZALTING; javnost i nevladine organizacije biti će pozvani za INFORMIRANJE.

Setting up of Learning Action Alliance

The LAA process was kicked off in April 2023 with a stakeholder mapping conducted by City Liaison partner Vesela Motika. In this early phase, Zagreb proposed the Luka Sesvete elementary school as the key pilot area and local stakeholder, later realizing that implementing solutions (such as a modular urban farm) in this school implied several safety and technical limitations. For this reason, a key new stakeholder of the project is the local ZOO, which is already an important actor for children in Zagreb and Croatia as a whole.

- [Initial Assessment of City's LAA Participants Zagreb.docx](#)
- [UP2030 Stakeholder list and matrix template 17_05_2023.xlsx](#)

In addition to the Needs workshop, Zagreb has engaged around 30 stakeholders for interviews. One key take away of this process is that the level of interest across stakeholders has been high, though Zagreb reached out to make this process formal, the response was poor. In the context of an economic downturn, many potential LAA stakeholders perceived their participation as being directly linked to some kind of resource commitment to which they do not want to tie themselves to. A second key result of this process is that Zagreb would like to further prioritize the needs of women, in addition to the ones of children.

An extensive needs analysis process

Zagreb's stakeholder engagement process began by inviting internal city stakeholders to a workshop. The purpose was to identify and address high-level needs related to policy and strategy, setting the stage for the successful implementation of their pilot project.

During this workshop, several needs came to light, falling under two overarching themes. The first theme revolved around the lack of technology and literature. Participants expressed that there is not sufficient funding to support research and there is a need for co-ordinating local strategies in key areas such as education. As a result, some of the foundational elements that would support the pilot implementation are missing and this fragmentation was exacerbated by the lack of communication between public and private sector actors.

Zagreb recognised the need to bridge this gap and address data scarcity to support evidence-based decision-making. For example, improved data collection to complement the development of a digital participation platform, a tool for a more engaged and empowered community. This platform would encompass data sharing mechanisms that improve transparency, data and reporting compatibility, and facilitate auditing and reporting on all processes related to urban food systems.

The second theme highlighted the importance of increasing citizens' awareness about climate issues. To achieve this, the city acknowledged the necessity of producing educational materials. These materials would serve a dual purpose: supporting their pilot project's community strategy and educating the public about urban farming. The aim is to make citizens more aware of the potential impact of the pilot efforts on their community, fostering a sense of shared responsibility.

To add further qualitative information to that gathered in the workshop, Zagreb conducted several interviews with key stakeholders and also held meetings at the local farmers' market to broaden the range of perspectives. Details on the findings are still to be shared with the engagement taskforce but will hopefully be available for the visioning phase.

Following the initial workshop, further assessment was needed to assess how the project vision aligns with existing local strategies, such as the Action Plan for Energy Sustainable Development and Climate Change Adaptation of the City of Zagreb, 2019. The city aims to address climate adaptation goals by

incorporating behaviour change initiatives within urban design strategies. As a next step, the city and liaison will explore how future engagement activities can delve deeper into this point in future follow up activities.

The road ahead for Zagreb is planned to widen engagement; a review of their overall approach directed the city to undertake a more extensive stakeholder mapping exercise. This allows them to better identify and target interest groups who could provide a more representative range of insights.

The city plans to expand its reach and involve more members of the community. This inclusive approach includes a collaboration with teaching staff to develop a school curriculum that integrates knowledge about urban farming and climate change with the wider educational curriculum. By doing so, they hope to empower the next generation with essential knowledge and a deeper sense of environmental responsibility.

Additionally, Zagreb is actively working on designing events to enhance local education and awareness about the impact of food consumption on climate change. These events will further solidify the city's commitment to creating an engaged and informed community.

Further reading:

- [Final UP2030 - 1st workshop report Zagreb June 2023.docx](#)
- [UP2030-1st workshop- surveys EN.xlsx](#)
- [1st Engagement Review - Zagreb .docx](#)

Working together with tools and services

As part of the UP2030 project, several tools and services are being offered to the cities by the technical partners. These tools play an important role in how the pilot project evolves and influences the final results of the city's participation in the UP2030 project and beyond. Cities were hence encouraged to reflect on the purpose of using these tools in their process and create principles to guide the pre-selection process.

For Zagreb, the tools provided by the consortium represent an opportunity to:

- Bring the topic closer to the general public
- Increase creative solutions and better implementation in the future
- Give citizens insight about the importance of the topic starting from the youngest age

As part of the pre-selection process led by the Implementation Taskforce, Zagreb has defined sustainable food-chains and food education in schools as key thematic areas for tool integration. In this perspective, the city has selected measuring and assessment tools (such as carbon budgeting, air quality monitoring, resilience assessment framework), as well as tools to support capacity building within the municipality. However, Zagreb will continue to refine the scope of tools selection, will deepen the collaboration with tools providers and work in parallel with the visioning roadmap roadmap (including the second UP2030 workshop on visioning).

Visioning phase

The co-visioning phase is anchored on a needs assessment conducted under T2.3 and previously identified objectives. This information provided a foundation for identifying specific needs and goals for Sesevete Primary School and the Zoo as pilots for UP2030 transformation. These elements were analysed to tailor a methodology to guide the co-design of a shared vision for the pilot. The detailed steps of the co-visioning with recommendations tailored to the context have been developed by the technical partners and are currently being evaluated by Zagreb’s team. Co-design approach is a core to UP2030 process, therefore cities and its stakeholders input for designing co-visioning process enables to develop a more specific and contextualised approach to engagement.

Zagreb

[update the process diagram once it’s finalised by the city: [Source](#)]

As part of the preparatory activities, the city has validated and refined the identified key objectives. During the first year of the project, the understanding of objectives and needs has evolved and therefore the revision of objectives plays an important role for the upcoming engagement activities in co-designing the vision for selected pilot areas. With the support of the city liaisons, the activity helped to identify which aspirations are most relevant to the short, medium or long term goals and to validate their relevance. Moreover, the document provided more insight into why certain objectives were identified and their relevance to the pilot. As well as how certain objectives could be translated into actions and support the definition of adaptive pathways to achieve the defined vision (e.g. Objective: Provide school meals from local urban farms. Explanation: ‘...open the communication channel with some of the already identified farms in the Sesevete district’ and ‘work on establishing communication channels and logistic processes including food safety and public procurement’). [The full document can be found here.](#)

In addition, during the General Assembly meeting in Lisbon in 2023, the representatives of the city, with the support of liaison, reflected on the alignment between the identified objectives and the pilot context. This exercise has helped to ensure that the objectives are linked to the scale of the pilots and to further specify the objectives.

In the coming weeks and months, the city will undergo a series of engagement activities to define the vision for a resilient, equitable and carbon neutral future for Zagreb's pilots and to identify concrete actions and barriers in the light of defining adaptation pathways.